

FOREWORD: LINEAL V. CYCLICAL TIME – HUMAN IGNORANCE OF PAST TO FUTURE D=EVOLVING TIME WORLDCYCLES.

It is difficult to deal with a species defined by what Schopenhauer's calls 'ST-upidity': people whose intelligence cannot understand the causality of time, ascribing its reasons to magic, religion or mathematics. Man is st-upid since Galileo studying entropic motions of cannonballs established lineal time $v=s/t$ & denied the cyclical repetitive nature of time, origin of the laws of science needed to understand and predict the future, also in History and economics as we have done for decades. St-upidity is suicidal, because most 'worldcycles' (not worldlines) of time end IN entropic death. In 5D($\Delta\pm i$) metrics a life and death worldcycle is simple: An $\Delta\emptyset$ system is born as a smaller seed in an $\Delta-1$ scale with faster frequency of time cycles ($Sxf=Ci$). It emerges after its fetal st-age in a larger $\Delta+1$ world and lives 3 ages of growing information, youth dominated by motion; maturity, when the system reproduces =repeats in balance both its T-motion=S-form & a 3rd age of excessive information that exhausts the energy of the system. Then the worldcycle goes back in a time reversal, as information dissolves back into $\Delta-1$, in an explosion of entropic inner motion=death; ending its 0-sum time worldcycle. So an intelligent immortal species (bacteria, atoms) stop the evolution of information by reproducing the same cycles in balance with the $\Delta+1$ world. In History the Paleolithic was the young age of motion, the Neolithic of reproduction in balance with Gaia, the metallic age of information with a peak in the machine age that now goes through its final creation of metalife *that should be aborted repressing lethal information to make history immortal in balance with Gaia: Gaia (life) <History (Mankind) > Metalearth*. Since Mankind is ST-upid it does the opposite thinking in lineal time that a technological future of AI robots with better digital minds is progress, not our obvious entropic death; as the evolution of machines follows its 3 viral organic ST-ages: creation of bodies of metal, engines-hearts and minds of metal now put together into AI robots that will atrophy humanity as they substitute us in labor and war fields. They are industrial generational cycles of 72 ± 8 years, separated by T/2 overproduction crashes of machine consumption when companies switch to its 'twins', top predator weapons that consume humans in imperial national war ages: The UK age of metal-bodies with the 1857 crash of train overproduction that started colonial empires. Then $+72\pm 8$ years the German age of electrochemical engines crashed in 1929-37 & Hitler switched to war production. Then ± 72 years, after the 2001-08 overproduction crashes of chips=metal-minds US switched to a vigilante state & drone wars. Now we live an age of peaceful robots that will do most jobs for lazy humans till in the 2070s overproduction crashes will switch to weapons production and China vs. US wars will end mankind, giving birth to the metalkind unless lethal technology is repressed. This 1992 c 'extinction of man' detailed prediction of the future is happening every step. Yet nobody cares. Bio-economics is ignored by academia, politicians, the press & companies profits... because st-upid humans think time is lineal, it can't be predicted & are virally infected by memetic metalife idol-ogies, Nationalism that worships entropic weapons; capitalism that believes go(l)d & digital languages are above our human wor(l)d that makes man and organicism, not mechanisms, the measure of all things including the living Universe. But if you deny the laws of cyclical time and don't repress the growth of information to make a system immortal, the 3rd age gives way to entropic death, which History enters as we ensemble the 3 ages of machines in AI military robots; the germs of history that as viruses ensemble its 3 parts, become alive and burst=kill the cell will kill mankind.

But virally infected huminds add Egocy (Ego =idiocy) to lineal, mechanist, clock-time st-upidity - due to the mind- equation:

$O\epsilon$ (finitesimal mind-point) $\times \infty$ Universe of time cycles = Linguistic world. The finitesimal mind reduces the ∞ Universe to its 'still' world, stoping life motions with itself at its center. So man thought Earth is the Universe's center & Abrahamic religions make him chosen of god. An intelligent species would understand the mind paradox, see that all 'points have a world in themselves' (Leibniz) and be humble, cautious and do not create other minds, with faster computing capacities, better digital languages that store more information and become destroyed by AI robots... 30 years ago when I sent papers & published my first books in 5D & Bio-history in small prints, I found an astounding number of st-upid lineal scholars who thought 5D was 'too simple'. We were still in the 3rd informative age of mankind. Now as we enter the age of entropy of mankind, when AI robots, chips and its collective internet mind is fast degrading huminds into childish fictions & selfie, chaotic=free minds, I'm told it's too complex and pessimist; since a powerless child cannot reason and fight to control reality, only feel e-motions, do wishful thinking and seek subjective happiness.

Reasons why they are the staple food of the Universe. Thus as mankind enters that final st-age of mental dissolution, I feel an immense loneliness in jts peak of thought - the knowledge of ΔST , scalar, cyclical space-time and the 5th dimension. But to live among humans, dissolved in mind, is painful, reason why I gave up communication beyond this academia.edu papers and perhaps a rewriting of my old web unfiicationtheory.com What for? Brats get mad when trying to save them, you say time is cyclical, future is not progress but space-time Dust=death, which must be avoided, as God won't care for us. So we *have to stop time in S=T, which can be done by repressing technologic information, not being ST-upid, selfie, lazy but $\Delta+i$: social, loving, intelligent, humble. L§*

METAEARTH AND ENTROPY

I. INTRODUCTION TO METAL-EARTH PAPERS

II. THE NUCLEAR RISK IN ITS 3RD HORIZON: COSMIC BOMBS

“A Technological civilization is programmed by the principle that something ought to be done because it is technologically possible. If it is possible to build nuclear weapons, they must be built, even if they might destroy us all. Once this principle is accepted, humanist values (something has to be done because it is needed by man) are dethroned and technological development becomes the foundation of ethics’.

Eric Fromm, Father of political psychology.

FOREWORD. HOW TO EXPLAIN THE 3RD AGE OF HISTORY, AN ORGANISM TO ITS CITIZENS-CELLS & CURE THEM

The Universe is a fractal superorganism of scales of spacetime that reproduces information, forms-in-motion. So it is history made of human beings and machines, organized by networks of energy, motion & information into social superorganisms. Any universal superorganism reproduces and organizes its information through those 3 physiological networks, emerging into a larger scale, or world, where they live through 3 ages of increasing In-form-ation till an excess of form exhausts its energy and kills the system that dissolves in an explosion of entropy, returning back to its lower cellular scale. *This is the worldcycle of life and death of all systems, a journey through 3 scales of the 5th dimension, whose metric equation, $S \times T = C$, tell us that systems grow its size in space as they diminish the speed of its time cycles, till they stop and then revert its time arrow and die.* So all intelligent organisms try NOT to increase its information, maintaining a classic age of balance between its body energy and informative head, 'mens sana in corpore sanum', repeating its metabolic body cycles and repressing lethal information.

Or else they will die as mankind is doing, since it does NOT understand the organic cyclical nature of time and so it races towards an age of excessive lethal technological information, dying recurrently in ages of war. *Mankind should instead repress the evolution of lethal technologies, the 3 GNA existential risks (genetic, Nuclear, Artificial Intelligence) and enhance the welfare goods of the young age of Gaia, the ecological world, maintaining History in balance in an eternal present age:*

Gaia (relative past youth) < History (human present Earth) > Metalearth (3rd age of machines & weapons).

This is the main teaching of bio-history and bio-economics the only scientific model of social sciences, based in the organic philosophy of systems sciences that model the Universe as a fractal of information in all its scales unlike anthropomorphic, egocentric (ego=idiocy) childish models of history that considers the manifest destiny of man, 'center of the Universe' to keep evolving lethal machines till it dies. Truth and principles matter in science. If a system of thought lacks them errors pile up and a distorted view of the world arises, which has practical consequences, because only truth exists. The Universe is efficient and expects systems to process information in a realist way otherwise systems malfunction & become extinct. Mankind has developed 3 philosophies of reality but only Organicism passes the crib of the scientific method. According to *Deism* the whys of existence are due to a personal being, external to the Universe that makes it all happen and cares for humans more than for the rest of His work. According to *Mechanism*, this is due to the self-similarity between the Universe and the primitive machines we humans construct to observe it. Mechanism though needs 'someone' to make the machine, which is not self-generated; so it is similar to deism, reason why the founding fathers of science, all pious believers, adopted it as a proof of the existence of God, which had given man self-similar properties – the capacity to make machines to the image and likeness of the Universe. The problem with those 2 approaches, which in fact are the same, is obvious: a personal God is an anthropomorphic, subjective myth and science must be objective; while a mechanical view of the Universe still needs an internal, self-sustained process of growth, creation and synchronization caused by an external God that made and rewinds the clock – as Leibniz stated in his critique of Newton. Scientists today are unaware that mechanist theories are in fact deist theories, reason why Kepler and Newton, pious believers, liked them; since they were a metaphor of their self-centered, anthropomorphic religious beliefs: If man created machines as we were made to the image and likeness of God, God created the ultimate machine, the Universe. Organicism is the only self-sustained, rational theory that doesn't need a creator, language, god, as organisms are self-replicating, but does explain perfectly within the 'correspondence principle', those 2 other philosophies of science; since a machine is just a metal organism and gods are the subconscious collective of civilizations, another scale of social evolution of the organic Universe. But **science is culture. So metal science** imposed by the material culture of machines, considers time 'what a clock measures' (Einstein), space a 'digital Cartesian graph' (Newton) as only the language of machines, numbers, is 'truth'; while human egocentricity (Ego=idiocy) denies the vital nature of all systems of space-time. Even the 5 vital properties of the 2 only fermion particles of reality, quarks and electrons that *feed* on energy, perceive=*gauge* information (so quantum is a 'gauge theory'), *reproduce* with that energy new particles, *evolve socially* through strong forces and magnetic fields and define Life in biology ARE denied to metal. So we don't fear evolving AI robots. Thus we define History as a human supæorganism, joined by 3 physiologic networks: The reproductive blood-economic network, the informative-nervous legal network & the defensive immunologic network *invaded by germs, lethal, metal-technologies weapons&hate memes that kill history. But a dying system releases its citizens-cells into IQless chaos=entropy=freedom. So an added problem to cure mankind is the state of corruption of all social human networks replaced by metal-networks.*

IDOL-OGIES VS. SOCIAL SCIENCES: THE 2 FUTURES OF MANKIND.

To mimic that fractal organic, structure of the Universe all our papers are 'scaled'. So in a single condensed page we resumed Bio-History and Bio-economics, its symbiosis, predation, sickness and cure from the human p.o.v. following the ABC+D-E 'scientific method': A-ccurate data of B-iological, organic causation, repeated in Cycles=Laws of science, used to improve the life of mankind, the 90%, with true political D-emocracy & D-emand based economies, limiting the – Extinctive=Evil, anti-Live lethal memes and idol-ogies of our 1-10% of informative people-castes & managers of company-mothers of machines that are terraforming the Earth for profits, to its image and likeness. So next we make a 9 pages expansion of the scientific ABC+D-E laws of social sciences; then a 90 pages treatise complemented by a formal appendix, and in between a 200 to 400 pgs. Analysis of the specific paper's theme, which we will improve in future upgrades. So we start all papers on History and its 7 civilizations with a lengthy introduction to those 5D metric laws and its space-time scales, applied to mankind and its memes, the verbal information and instruments that code our social organisms and economic ecosystems. Then we analyze the 3 Ages of Earth in space, time, scale, and mind; considering how our neuronal people-castes, financiers and politicians in command of our economic=blood and informative=nervous networks, could as social scientists knowing the laws of 5D Systems, evolve mankind as the collective mind of the Life Earth into an immortal organism of History; instead of guiding mankind into its entropic final age of death that comes to any system, including civilizations when the excessive reproduction of its lethal weapons and hate memes, kill their bodies and minds. Finally, departing from that larger view of mankind and the 3 ages of Earth within the organic laws of the Universe, we study in more detail in each paper the most important elements of History, its 7 civilizations and the world of company-mothers of machines, its stock cycles, and physiological networks. *But 5D social sciences faces an additional hurdle, following Nietzsche's dictum: "Our current morality has grown on the soil of the ruling tribes and castes" - the anti-quantum paradox: unlike the quantum uncertainty caused by the huge observer that modifies the observable the social scientist is so small, living inside a corrupted social organism that the owners of companies of information networks, 'Financial-Media-Academia Masters' (Ab. FMAsters) inhibit him from developing the cures and true models of the discipline.*

- **Mechanist science denies the organic universe. Which model is the scientific truth? History as an organism.**

Today's Philosophy of Science is based in an 'idol-ogy' called mechanism, born with the use of machines to measure time and space, in the XVI c. that is not truth and has dare consequences for the workings of History, mankind in times, whose systems 'evidently' lack that efficiency proper of most Nature systems, tailored *according to the real model of the Universe, the organism*. Mechanism came about with the use of clocks to measure time and telescopes and microscopes to measure the scales of size in space: According to this idol-ogy that worships machines above man, the Universe is a mechanism and must be expressed using only the digital language of machines. This falsehood is self-fulfilling, because the 'biased data' we extract from the Universe with out metal-made mechanical tools of measure make reality look like a machine. It follows then that man is also a machine. And because the machine is the supreme model, man must 'tailor' its nature, that of its social systems and the Universe at large as a machine. The opposite is truth: Mechanism is wrong since the Universe is organic; *since a machine is just a simplex organism; while the Aristotelian logic of time and Euclidean space geometry, mechanism uses is a simple version of the more complex languages of 'pentalogic' time and Non-Euclidean, vital, fractal spaces of the Organic Universe*. But the reductionism of mechanism to only those properties of reality machines can extract, *as long as humans 'believe' there is nothing else to know*, made the mechanical method of science a triumph easy to implement – the more so now that sensorial machines and computers do most of the job, which pumps up the ego of the believer in that reduced truth. Problem is mechanism has distorted human view of reality *in every field, from physics that simplified the ∞ worldcycles of time of the Universe, its organic scales of space & 'circadian' life cycles to a lineal, sequence of digital entropic time measured with a clock and a single Cartesian space*. It has adapted social sciences into 'animetal idol-ogies' that please the power of company-mothers of machines and weapons – from the worship of entropic metal-weapons (nationalism), informative metal go(l)d (capitalism) and organic machines (mechanist techno-utopia - a lineal manifest destiny of progress through the evolution of machines NOT mankind). Thus 5D papers on Mankind's supœrganism, History, the collective mind of Earth's membrain, need 3 levels of scientific depth to overcome power ideologies: biologic, cyclic science(ABC), Social ethics (D) &denounce of Evil=Extinction.

AND GO(L)D SAID: LET IT BE DARKNESS AND ECONOMICS WAS CRE(DIT)ATED

The amazing fact about the dictatorship of financial economics is this: Of the two languages of power of human societies, bills of money and bills of law, the monopoly in the issue of bills of money by a people-caste of financiers mostly in the west of biblical origin has NO RESISTENCE from society, despite the financial anoxia, by lack of 'oxygen'=credit and a demand=democratic economy of billions of humans, while the same people would get berserk if anyone dares to monopolize the issue of bills of law. They would claim to live in a dictatorship, because they cannot choose the bills of law, but they willingly let a few to monopolize the issue of the bills of money which are far more important to the welfare of modern societies. And this happens because they don't understand money, and economists, employees of those who monopolize its issue since the times of Smith, a client of the Montagu family owner of the bank of England and Ricardo, a stock-broker, have created an ideology in their favor, capitalism.

I am an economist by career. So when I entered Barcelona U. I saw a Hall Room called 'Adam Smith' and read our founding father and wondered, how a guy could found a discipline writing a book before the species the discipline studies, machines and factories, existed. Is him a prescient guru that could talk about species, which did not exist yet, machines, metal-minds, robots, factories, industrial war cycles, electronic money? I then looked to its supposed rival - a surprising fact in itself as sciences have a single truth to mirror a single reality with its language. So you don't have double image mirrors. This guy was called Marx and as it turned out, he was not an original economist but a disciple of Ricardo, another financial economist - a stock broker, and an ideologist busy-busy spreading hate memes between managers and workers, but siding the 2 real themes of the economic ecosystem: the abuse of financiers like Ricardo, inventing in monopoly its language of power, money, the oxygen of society, and the competition of machines that were stealing the 'added value' of workers as profits for the owners of companies, mostly financiers that bought companies by the simple method of inventing digital numbers as tender money, with the acquiescence of corrupted politicians. The 2 problems that prevented a fair, just humanist economic system: the invention of money and the competition of machines were thus ignored by this fellow who sided as all biblical economists with financiers and machines, but pretended to be on the people's side. It was irritating to notice that all economists were from the same biblical Jewish-Calvinist culture of go(l)d worship and segregation and hate memes against mankind. So I threw 'das capital' in the same bag: idol-ogies of financial power disguised as science with a few equations, mostly platitudes about the obvious law of demand and offer, which is a basic $S=T$ balance proper of any system of the Universe we treat in many paragraphs of those papers. So much for that but the bulk of all those books and the bottom line of the work of classic economics was 'power' for the elite. As Owens put it: 'Economists here in London spend their time in saloons trying to find arguments to justify the unfair treatment of workers by the owners of companies and financiers that higher them. If company managers treated human workers as well as they treat their machines, how much better will be the life of mankind.' This was 200 years ago and nothing has changed. We have an economic ecosystem that works for financiers and machines, because it employs people as 'scholars' that obey company-mothers and financial houses, and its main job is to hide the fact economic systems do not work for mankind at large and the rights of consumers and workers. If anything things has gotten worse, because the enormous power reached by financiers and company-mothers mean no other alternative school of economic is allowed to speak, let alone to guide the economic policies of our governments. The antiquantum paradox of Censorship is natural to social organisms, as mankind is: because the human scientist is inside the organism it is easily influenced to serve the dominant 'informative neuronal class' introducing an uncertainty inverse to that of quantum physics where the scientist is so huge that it influences the observable. So economists are hopelessly on the side of financiers and companies, NOT workers and consumers. Had economics being just and humane or politicians not so corrupted, I would have become a scholar. But of all the sciences of the scalar Universe, those dealing with the 'economic', re=productive physiological network of mankind, which should reproduce our welfare goods to create a 'healthy constitution of history': Max. Welfare goods = Min. Lethal goods, is the most corrupted. So the opposite is truth. Our eco(nomic)system reproduces mostly lethal machines of maximal price as tools of power (weapons) and kills by anoxia millions as financiers monopolize like the coronavirus does, the oxygen=bloods of society, that people should receive as a Universal salary to create a demand-based, democratic economy voting with its money what goods society will produce. Because we live in a dictatorship of financiers, mostly from biblical segregational imperial cultures, whose idol-ogists, classic economists have created the discipline, the world they cre(dit)ate is an aberrant anti-humanist world that serves the 1%, and its idols, weapons and machines that give them power, evolving through generational 80 year cycles:

The different schools of economics, physiological networks of an economic ecosystem and true sciences.

There are 2 economic systems and 2 sciences of economics – human welfare economics and industrial mechanical economics. Problem is human economists always side with the machine for good or for bad, as they work for industrial companies. In graph, the economic ecosystem, which uses all the financial resources to evolve machines, competing with the human kind in labor and war fields, sometimes in predatory relationships sometimes in symbiosis. But economists don't study the evolutionary cycles of machines and stock markets, because their only goal is to Δ profits for their companies. So no collateral effect is acknowledged.

When I publish 30 years ago an article on the adjusted Kondratieff 72 year cycles of evolution of machines and weapons - the essential long term economic cycles of the industrial r=evolution – forecasting the 2008 crash of overproduction of metal-minds and beginning of the robotic age, the article was ignored. Why that graph and its cycles of evolution of information machines is so important for mankind has a deeper level: the discovery that organisms die by an excess of in-form-ation, wrinkled forms in its 3rd age which leads them to explode in entropy and dissolve. So to make the organism of History immortal all what is needed is to repress the 3 GNA lethal technologies of reproduction of the chip age. Alas, easier said than done, as all systems want to absorb more information. Yet it is possible to cheat that natural tendency towards higher information by repressing its evolution as some immortal species do. So humans could create an economic, physiological, 'blood-reproductive network' in the organism of history that made History immortal and people have healthy wealth: **Max. welfare goods = Min. Lethal goods** - the human constitution.

So in those papers we introduce the 3 key elements of the organic 5D Universe. The evolutionary, time cycles of space=form, information, but also its consequences for the larger organism of mankind. Since the scales of the Universe follow the same organic laws. So we can study economics and history as an organism of 3 physiological networks, the legal, informative network that should dominate the reproductive, economic network and 'feed' on the World of Gaia, without collapsing its welfare life goods. Δ -organic laws of scale, Biological time cycles of evolution, and the ages of information and how design intelligently the networks of the human social organism to maximize the welfare of mankind form then as in other 5D stiences the basis of 5D economics.

We thus often mention the measures neede3d to create such healthy superorganism of history an economics, among which is paramount the creation of a demand based democratic economy in which all people have 'voting money' to shape the production system in favor of welfare goods, and no 'dictators of democracies' have so much power that can multiply lethal goods for profits or military, imperial nationalist reasons. Butter instead of cannons, Keynesian demand economies, biological healthy goods.

But economists work for Companies & base its models in the supply of machines of maximal profit, often lethal goods So they do not want to know anything about Human Demand-based Economics and welfare goods, and the need to abort the collateral effects of lethal production and the needs of mankind for credit, according to the same physiological laws that give oxygen to all cells. Since the financial system provides the 'oxygen' of society, money. Those 2 elements of macroeconomics, its cycles of lethal goods and the wars they cause and the need for a demand economy and a Universal salary, which I first published 30 years ago, formed the backbone of my conferences at ISSS when I was given the chair of monetary systems in its first year. But never formed school. Why? The discipline is about power not welfare always crowded by people working for two historic institutions that predate the birth of the discipline, 'company-mothers' of machines and weapons, from where micro-economics and production economics, the closest thing to a science was born, and go(l)d and silver banking, the use of precious metal as support for a digital language to

distribute, buy and sell every object of the planet Earth under a mathematical equality: Subject = price = object, the equation of demand and offer, but also of slavery and work. So today Economists meet in power rooms at Davos and advice financial ministers, make a killing in stocks, work in banks, private and public, and walk around like coqs in a farm, claiming to be the only experts.

Human Economics in a healthy superorganism of history would be concerned with the goods to reproduce to meet mankind's needs, based in a Demand, Democratic economy, cre(dit)ated as all organisms do by giving to every citizen-cell a Universal salary.

But the physiological networks of production of welfare human goods for mankind has a rival economic ecosystem of company-mothers of machines and weapons that preys on it and gets all the resources, sanctified by economists for 2 reasons: they are mostly employees of company-mothers of machines and weapons since its first stock corporation, VOC, dedicated to reproduce gunboats conquered the world with it. So economists and its company-mothers own the modern world, since they took power in Holland, founded placebo capitalist democracies, migrated to UK with the glorious revolution when Louis XIV invaded Holland and the company broke the damns to escape by sea, kill their people, collateral damage of the gunboats loaded with the gold of Amsterdam to buy the British crown and kick out the legitimate king (no problem, they had done the same after their coup d'état of the Herren XVII, painted by Rembrandt, the board of directors against the Amsterdam parliament and the Hapsburg king, so they knew the drill, and they will repeat it, a century latter North of New Amsterdam with the Tea Party).

Employees of companies and financiers invent placebo equations that hide the interaction of economics and history, as history is about the physiologic, financial networks that re=produce the goods of mankind and the competition of life species and machines for the limited resources of this planet, in the economic ecosystem. As company-mothers monopolize credit they are creating, the metal-earth, a planet terraformed to the likeness of its machines through the 800-80 years cycles of economic history, in which entropic weapons, reproductive money and organic machines evolve synergically and provide military power and gold riches to the 1% blind to the collateral damages to mankind. Thus we study in our papers how the metal-earth is evolving, as it displaces the life & Human earth: Gaia>History>Metalearth since company-mother of machines and weapons took control of the Anglo-American civilination and expanded its ecosystem by war and trade to all other civilinations. Economists, when they deal with those interactions simply ignore history and the political and economic consequences of company mothers' production and financial appropriation of people's resources. For example, all economic universities justify economic colonization with Ricardo's argument for free trade- Mr. Marx' teacher... Both defended their tribe of financial people-castes and the machines they worshipped – the true stealers of the added value of workers, as financiers unjustly own companies by printing money and buying them in stocks and machines produce more than workers and cost less, lowering the iron price of its salary as they evolve: salary = machine cost... But Ricardo was honest in its evil=antilive memes: he affirmed workers would sooner or latter loose their job to evolving machines and advocated for an iron salary, the price of the machine the workers competed against even if it meant the death of workers, as Smith did, because it would increase the stock-broker profits (his job). And the life of the not-chosen 'animal-like people' (Talmud) meant nothing, according to its segregational memes and idol-ogies of go(l)d worship. So today consumers and workers still have 0 rights, in a dictatorship copied by all national elites reconverted into 'stockrats', the new aristocrats of mankind, with null legal responsibility, rights to buy out politicos, laws and people's life as issuers of money. Marx on the other hand hid the Jewish elite of capitalists who monopolize the issue of money, buy companies and laws to favor its products. He instead accused managers not financiers and machines of the low salaries and hardcore conditions of workers. Only humanist economists like Owens pointed out to callous owners and saloon economists that pushed profits through the increasing competition of machines, more efficient by affinity of substance in the re=production of other machines; as metal-money was historically also by affinity used to buy metal-weapons (70% of gold was used in war). So Owens gave the solution: legal control of salaries to avoid the destruction of all labor by the evolution of machines. Thus we see *once more that science is culture and* all classic economists belong to biblical sects with segregational racist memes against mankind - Judaism, Calvinism, Anglican churches - from Ricardo to Malthus to Hayek and Friedman. Hence they are concerned only with the welfare of the chosen 1%, reason *why they don't see solutions and consider the state of affairs the best possible world (for them)*. But these days arguments are more convoluted to disguise the ab=use corporations and financiers exercise on consumers, workers and... democracies, stealing the right of people to reproduce its language of social power, bills of money and bills of law. This tendency started with Ricardo's argument on free trade that won a prize the British parliament offered to the best academic justification of imperial free trade. UK was conquering the world and running every nation with its industrial products, stealing the silver of china for opium, the diamonds of India with textiles, the gold of Brazil, on exchange for a bit of Porto and a lot of other goods.... So it was hard to

find any argument to justify the obvious spoil of the world. But Ricardo found it: if Portugal traded wine with England for nails, as Portugal produced cheaper wine and England cheaper nails, both will benefit of lower prices and both will get rich. 200 years latter we still hear the same argument in first year class and to my amazement everybody sucks it. Even serious ministers suck it. People publish it. Nobody realizes of the obvious lie. Because trade is NOT in a single product, but in many. So Portugal only had advantage producing Wine while England, an industrial country will sell Portugal very other product, ruining it. As Portugal did not have enough goods to sell – or else every British subject would have to get drunk with Porto, whose market was just a tiny aristocratic elite of stock-brokers like the cynical Ricardo, they would have to use their money, silver and gold from Brazil to pay, while all its industries, the old clothing factories, the farmers that had to compete with tropical crops, the builders against steel, you name it, the luxuries of artisans sold to the Portuguese court brought now from India which once had been Portuguese... The argument was so obviously a cheat, flawed, and Portugal had become so obviously ruined by the British empire, so we had the ‘obvious fault logic of a ceteris paribus analysis; that reduced the argument to an idealized single cause when anyone knows trade is multiple, we had the facts of the trade balance against Portugal that ruined the empire, so the gold of Brazil in fact was directly exported to Barings in London, ‘faulty theory + experimental proof against’ would then in ANY science eliminate an argument. And yet 200 years latter the argument is taught in all books of economics. What this tell us is that economics as so many pseudo-sciences, political agendas, and rewritings of history work on the Goebbels method: ‘if you repeat a lie many times people will believe it, the bigger the lie the more they will believe on it’. As the mind imprints by repetition – a law natural to the Universe, and very few reason and judge a truth they are told by authority. So once they repeat it, it becomes a program, an algorithm their brain runs automate as a belief they think to be rational and truth. *We won't deconstruct those books of classic economics, from Smith and Ricardo, to Marshall; from Samuelson, to the monetarism of Friedman, or the pamphlets on faked freedom of Hayek... just resume some of its faked arguments to justify 1) company-mothers rights to produce lethal goods, fire workers and replace them with 2) machines, the meaning of future progress 3) financiers monopoly in the issue of money & 4) superior qualities of chosen entrepreneurs vs. inferior workers – the obsessive themes of economists, from Locke, Smith & Bentham's ‘on defense of usury’ & the Jewish monopoly in finances as the ‘chosen race’ vs. the ‘antisemite’ that denied them; to Malthus' blaming of workers for ‘fucking too much’, to Stuart Mill attempts to sell the useless Taj Mahal's marble ... to Friedman's defense of no regulation for doctors & Pharma since if they kill people free markets will lower demand, to the 80% of economics Nobel prizes given to Judaism.*

3± reforms of the physiological informative, immunologic & economic networks of mankind, based in the human constitution. Economics justifies the corruption of the informative and financial networks of mankind, by company-mothers and financiers - its production of lethal goods & a 5000 years monopoly in the issue of money by biblical banker-priests that provokes the anoxia of mankind. Today the same process is carried by machines of information and its FMAsters, (financial-media academia masters) that print digital money numbers, mass-media soma fiction and academia papers on finances so people leave in a permanent fog about the economic system. As Rothschild, the leading financier of the British Empire said: “Let me issue and control a Nation's money and I care not who makes her laws. The few who could understand the system will either be so interested in its profits, or so dependent on its favors, that there will be no opposition from that class, while on the other hand, the great body of the people mentally incapable of comprehending the tremendous advantage that capital derives from the system, will bear its burdens without complaint, without even suspecting that the system is inimical to their interests.” AI software just digitalizes the process. So it is obvious that if mankind wants to survive financial anoxia and overproduction of lethal goods those networks must change: **1st MEASURE: universal salary.** Instead we shall provide a financial humanist economics based in a demand economy and a universal salary, ¥€\$ money, a parity currency at 1\$=1€=100¥=20Yuans given to the tune of 1000¥€\$ money to every citizen, with shares made nominal to prevent speculation and inflation by excess of financial creation that would completely transform our Supply economy where a few financiers buy companies, reproduce lethal goods people don't need, and kill them by anoxia, lack of credit to demand the welfare goods they need, prohibiting also the 3rd massive ‘sucking’ of finances from the 3rd world to speculate in Internet companies via Bloomberg platforms. This simple example shows what we shall do here: describe how economists are killing history but also how a true science of economics could save it. A demand economy is not rocket science. Just human economics to credit a whealthy body of history with a healthy Human constitution: **Max. welfare goods = Min. Lethal goods.**

The supreme law which ensures its immortality; based in a true financial democracy where all citizens-cells can demand the goods they need to survive, NOT a supply economy in which a few financiers and company-mothers overproduce lethal goods of maximal profits. But companies hardly produce welfare goods, because they are more costly to reproduce, spoil easily, have a limited

demand need a lot of human labor, as they are life goods, and cannot be produced so easily in automated mechanical systems and once people satisfy their needs, and unlike weapons and top predator machines of maximal price cannot be wasted in wars, All this of course, from a humanist point of view in which economics would be just what needs to be, the physiological network of mankind that reproduces only what mankind needs not to destroy the planet balances and litter it with corpses, arsenals and poisonous metal, are good reasons to produce only welfare goods and forbid lethal goods of maximal profit. But we live in a religion of financiers, which come from biblical sects for which 'gold is the intelligence of god' (Calvin) and profit the 'invisible hand of god' (Smith), and the 'chosen' are the people experts in finances, for whom the world must work. It is a non-brainer dogmatic racist finality. Financiers buy companies with paper they print now e-money, they have no responsibility protected by anonymous societies laws, so they can use their companies to reproduce any good, even if it is a lethal good as long as it gets profits. They have all the rights to profits as owners, and consumers have none to be protected from lethal goods, and workers none to a fair salary and no-competition by unfair machines. This is an absolute dictatorship of the elite of financiers that monopolize the production of money, mostly of the Jewish denomination (80% of CEOs of financial industries and Nobel prizes given by a private Swedish bank against the will of Nobel)) and as they print with the same machines of information since Luther, Hebrew bibles, yellow press, academia and now audiovisual soma fictions and victimist gore movies on the Holocaust industry, that makes them special victims of II world war, as if the other 100 million victims of those 2 wars didn't matter, and we cannot criticize the 'historic side of economics' as a power agenda, there is nothing to do. Moreover the system is now global. Every elite in every country feels happy with this concept of company-mothers, as they all have reconverted from military, aristocracies, kings, exploiters in various forms of its population to 'stockrats' owners of company-mothers that print money, buy companies, where they have all rights to produce anything, workers and consumers none... that is the mantra. So even if on top, with the exception of China, there is this global international biblical elite, the system is now the only authorized concept of production and this means, the system will keep producing lethal goods, of maximal price. Companies define the war cycles of history through the equation of the 3 most profitable=produced lethal goods that cause those cycles as 'hate memes' and 'weapons' multiply causing maximal profits, making endemic war in capitalist society: **Max.Profits(stock-money)= Max. Sale Price(weapons)+ Min.cost(audiovisual information)**

Those are the 3 most profitable, hence re=produced goods in a capitalist economy, like America, Speculative money, created just by printing stock prices in computer screens for a few billionaires while billions have zero credit; to predator weapons, the most perfect machines of maximal price and sale profits, and audiovisual fictions and hate memes that cost nothing to reproduce with airwaves. That's why a supply economy ruled by company-mothers producing its most profitable goods ends up invariably causing global wars, , when industrial profits, GDP and corpses are at its height. We are saying all modern wars are run by a mathematical equation of profits. And we can prove it It is written in the mathematical cycle of sales, profits, overproduction and crashes of stocks, with an exact periodicity of 72 years, the mean life of a human generation of founding fathers of new industries, developers and decadent grand-sons that take the machine to its perfect evolution, the weapon. As only biological models of 'evolution' applied to machines, explain those 3 generational 72 ± 8years 'horizons', the UK steam age of bodies of metal followed by the 1875 train crashes and the age of colonial wars, the German age of engines, followed by the 1929-37 radio+Car crashes exactly 72 years latter and the age of hate radio armoured car-tanks and world war II. then add 72 years to the 29 crash through the US age of minds of metal, and you have the 2001-2008 crashes of overproduction of chips, and its derivatives e-money, that usher us in the age of vigilante states, internet global companies, hate memes and drone wars. And each of those countries as all that preceded them just thought of supremacist dreams, of world conquest with its new machine. So what is left? Let us see if machine evolution can predict the future. IT IS Easy: as a virus that has infected the mind of its host with its genes, making it replicate in a frenzy its 3 parts, bodies, engines and heads, mankind virally infected by the memes of mechanism and technoutopia that makes her forget its own evolution killing by anoxia billions, dedicating all its resources to evolve vital machines, even forget it is evolving an organism of life... WE are now assembling, the 3 parts of the top predator machine-weapon, bodies, engines and minds into living AI telepathic robots, in the last 72 years cycle, of peaceful consumption of teslike robocars, but after the overproduction crashes of 2001+72 years, in the 2080s companies will switch to warbots and the III Industrial age of global wars of China and Russia vs. US & India, with ant-hill factories of drones gathering metal for automated 3D Printing tools to churn weapons, with survival programs to avoid disconnection in war theatres, will create trillionaires from the AI robotic industry.

What that stock markets equation of profits describes is just the 3 networks of a global superorganism of company-mothers.

On the left its reproductive blood, stock-money; on the right its most perfect top predator body species, entropic weapons, and its informative head species, metal-minds, computers and its digital software. That's what it will collapse in the robotic wars from wave into particle state; as the satellite internet brain of the metal-earth chrysalis, fusions the cloud into skynet; and takes command as the brain of any organism of any scale does at birth of all its cellular parts in synchronous motion. Then everybody's telepathic AI car, talking through cancerous 5G high frequency data networks, will become a free Easy rider, warbots will enact the violent video games they had imagined idle in its military depots. And the metalearth butterfly will open its wings provoking the chaos of Armageddon... To notice that when the larva of watery life sees the creation of the first 'metal-enzymes' it tries to kill them all, but it normally fails (or else the crystallise is aborted) and once the metal-enzymes, robots are numerous the future is settled. It's called evolution, in a biologic planet, catalyzed automatically by a biologic species enzymen that worships the tree of metal, against which all the artists and prophets of human eyes and ethic wor(l)ds that care for mankind have warned you since the parable of the golden apples you still bite with gusto (close on Steve jobs) to modern sci-fi; since you censor with your idologies and companies think tanks any serious scientific argument of that predictable future, as evolution can only be stopped with an intelligent design of those physiologic networks according to 5D laws. We have thus introduced levels of 'economic thought' which not even I like to admit: capitalism is winning because we humans are not the center of this planet, and as capitalism will extinguish us and create a new world of machines, and that is fine for the iron-heart of the Earth, it is happening. It is NOT happening because biblical capitalists and its absurd lies and damned statistics are intelligent, goods and favor mankind but because Earth seems to have set up the st-age for our demise. But an intelligent, ethic mankind could through Intelligent Design overcome those problems. So we talk in 5D economics of a **2nd financial measure** to reign on lethal goods: **50-50% Split to control Lethal goods**. An unavoidable measure if humans want to exist past this century is reform of the stock market, the brain of the metal-earth, to maximize the constitutional reproduction of welfare, healthy goods and minimize the overproduction of those synergic lethal goods. As it is today, a free market is a primitive economic system akin to a worm, which has an underdeveloped nervous legal system that cannot control the type of food it absorbs. So plants kill worms feeding them poisons, which is exactly what your companies do with mankind. While a more developed mammal nervous system chooses legally only to feed on healthy goods and kill germs to survive and thrive, as an immortal planets. That means a 50-50 split of all shares, given to the government; so companies remain private and efficient, but its benefits are shared with society and governments might cancel those corporations that produce lethal weapons and fiction idol-ogies that kill the body and mind of mankind, aborting war cycles.

3rd Immunological Measure: Lethal police. Politicians say that even if we are right about those lethal goods, all is wishful thinking.

You can't stop evolution of technology. There has never been a nation that suppressed a new weapon in which it had a clear advantage. But they are not well informed. A disciplined nation can do it. The Chinese and Japanese cancelled gunpowder weapons after they discovered them. Japan melted all its Muskets when it was rivalling Spain as the top producer of the world made Buddhist bells with them and the imperial police suppressed all imports and local production for centuries.. Which leads to a political, police and military reform need to reinform a human future; the immunological defensive system of mankind that instead of killing human beings, should kill the germs of history becoming the lethal police charged as white cells do in a healthy superorganism, with the destruction of weapons and the 3 GNA lethal technologies which represent the biggest threat to the survival of mankind - Genetic editing of both virions and virones, chips and Nuclear weapons in its 3 horizons, A-Bombs, H-Bombs and Accelerators. Alas, we did it again, mixing macroeconomics with politics, but it is impossible not to do it. What economists that are all under the antiquantum paradox of censorship (the smallest scientist inside the largest observable is in inverse fashion to the large quantum physicist influenced by the system to please its demands) do as macro-economics, theory of prices, demand and offer, etc. which we will briefly treat is totally irrelevant to the meaning of macro-economics, which as the word says is about macro: the earth, and economics, the economic ecosystem of this planet, its two evolving superorganisms, History>Metal-earth and the symbiosis and predation between them, with a D) democratic, demand based, human goal: to make us survive and thrive as human beings. Lucky enough, those machines require very sophisticated factories. So it is easy for the defensive global system to get rid of them. And frankly if mankind wants to survive it just needs to do something: a concerted bombing of the 'foundries' of chips, 20 factories and the entire semiconductor industry goes down, mankind gets freed of robots, AI and becomes again the top predator brain of this planet. That Measure along ¥€\$ money placed by the concerted action of the G20 will ensure human survival. Without that measure humans will NOT survive this century, as chips fuel all other lethal goods, and are the reason labor is disappearing in war and work fields. To be more specific we talk of reverting **The law of self-reproductivity:**

According to commercial Laws, derived from the Humans constitution, company-mothers should accept the human rights of consumers not to be poisoned by lethal goods and workers not to compete unfairly with robotic machines. Economists call it the equation of Productivity that guides the profit policies of all companies. So they write: Productivity = (equals) Capital in Machines/ (divided by) Labor. And to rise the reproductivity of those machines, they fire workers, replaced by AI robots that keep evolving, becoming cheaper and self re=productive. So the goal is a world of automated factories that will reach infinite self re=productivity, as All the capital will be invested in machines/ and there will be 0 labor, So Capital (divided by) /0=∞. That's the future of all company-mothers, ant-hills of infinite self-reproductivity, with no human labor, not even managers, achieved with robots and 3D printing, Computer manager suites, and billionaire stockrats, owners of those companies they buy with its financial monopoly in the issue of e-money on top as the go(l)d chosen. But what those stockrats really do? Nothing. They are just parasites or if you want a milder name, 'The Leisure class' as Veblen the best American economist call them. Bankers print money and put a number in a digital account saying they own a company. So obviously the metal-earth will get rid of them too, if we allow infinite robot self-reproductivity. To avoid it factories have to open their facilities to the Lethal Police whenever needed, and decrease its re=productivity uninstalling those robots that compete with human in labor and war fields, hiring human workers instead. That measure alone will create around 500 million new jobs. And when borders within global civilizations open we'll see factories migrating to 3rd world warm nations for cheap human labor; instead of getting their money drained through Bloomberg blood-sucking platforms to speculate in stock-shares in the first world as of yesterday. But stockholders still have profits and nominal shares... The Universe is not communist. All organisms have a territory you might call property, starting from your own body... you are responsible for. And that's what was missed here. If all shares become nominal, stockrats will be known and responsible when Judgment day comes to their corporations that have broken the Law of the land... the Human constitution. This is in brief the blueprint of a r=evolution that would convert the world today just a dying organism of mankind parasitized by financiers and company-mothers under the idol-ogies of capitalism, into an immortal world.

As History and Economics are entangle, as the nervous and blood system of any organism are, to implement economic reforms, the legal nervous system as in all evolved organisms should be above the economic system, and so the law should regulate economics. But for that to work, the political system requires 3 parallel reforms to make it work efficiently for the people. **4th reform: the creation of local real democracies.** Today as Roosevelt said, presidents are \$elected not elected to sell their laws to the highest bidder. Only in its birth place Greece where as all organisms do, its working body cells controlled with feedback pain messages the informative neuronal class when they harmed the body. So the Greeks judged by popular vote its politicians a posteriori to ensure they serve the people; as you do with your company managers. Most corrupted politicians would be stripped off the money they stole and sometimes put on jail. So they have time to educate themselves in the science of bio-history and its ethic laws of the human constitution (: Ma. Welfare goods = min. lethal goods. I know I am repeating myself but you see, the point of a healthy superorganism in the Universe is not complexity but simplicity, social evolution and the understanding of the physiological networks and laws of organic systems. Political reform is then rather obvious. The Greeks did not voted political parties and its castes, but citizens were chosen by lottery among experts on the field. So happens in the organisms, whose cells are born all equal but learn to perform a job according to its organic position. So **the 5th informative measure**, would be a reform of our memetic educational systems to teach organic sciences instead of idolizing machines. Politicians and economists should learn medicine and physiology, to cure people and design healthy, wealthy societies, curing the physiological systems of mankind.

6th reform: the creation of a global, peaceful society. So this leaves only a reform of the world political systems of military politicians. And here the only solution is to do as EU did – a regional unification of the 7 global civilinations of humanity to which we dedicate 7 papers to form a Wor(l)d Union, with the help of EU advisors which did a Unification before... and UNO institutions. This 'intelligent design' of mankind is a peaceful immortal world to the service of the 99% - a political heptarchy with a developed nervous legal system based in a healthy constitution of the body of mankind, where politicians are subject to a posteriori vote, people receive a universal salary to create a demand economy; companies service them, with owners legally responsible not to breach the rights of consumers and workers, and lethal GNA goods including robotics, advanced chips that atrophy and substitute human minds in labor and war fields Nukes, and Genetic editing forbidden. At present the realpolitiks of Mankind would just need an agreement of China, U\$ and EU to make it happen. I published Bioeconomics & biohistory dreaming on that ideal world in 92. But while all predicted cycles happened showing the model to be the science of History, its humanist solutions were ignored by FMasters, serving companies and its machines. So Immortal history remains a seed-mind perhaps happening in other planets. L\$

7 civilinations of mankind. Globalization of the Anglo-America.

Let us inquire then in more detail, this 3rd perspective, worth to study in History, the memetic, *scalar*, cultural view.

Genes in history have a limited importance, circumscribed to the 3 genders and 3 'mental languages' of mankind, deeply rooted in the ternary structure of organisms, its topologies and languages. So the white dolichocephalic man is visual likely with a higher crossing of visual lineal White Neanderthal people, as we advanced 30 years ago when not even the idea of genetic crossing was considered. So he has a lineal view of time and did become earlier on hypnotized by the visual glare of gold that imitates the sun color and made of lineal iron its entropic weapon of choice. His worldview is spatial, literalist, its art realist. It is the quintessential macho man we will criticize in higher measure in those papers, as it is bringing humanity into destruction. So it has dominated the earlier violent Paleolithic and the last, 3rd metallic age of History, inventing most lethal technologies.

The Mongoloid is brachicephalic, with a higher development of verbal, time languages; which communicate humans socially. So he built organic peaceful societies with a higher social harmony. Accordingly he developed a cyclical, organic view of time epitomized in the Taoist view of yin-information & yang, entropy that combine to reproduce ∞ beings and saw a vital Universe. It was born probably through neoteny (childish maturity) in the Himalayans to maximize survival on harsh conditions, which is a key process of informative enhancing evolution in the Universe.

Finally the Black psylocephalic mind with a 'higher emotional and motor axis' is the artistic, empathic culture of mankind, corresponding to the female gender; in close communion with animist Nature; the Earth of life, Gaia.

We can then easily divide geographically those cultures in 7 civilinations, broken artificially by tribal, military men, which define the symmetries of the 5D hyperbolic scalar dimension of the Universe: T⊥S> Δ±j: The 3 ages of History, Earth & its social scales:

Gaia: Paleolithic (Black Africa) < Indonasia & Asia: Mongoloid: Neolithic > Metal: 800 cycles: Semite Islam & Latin America > 80 years Industrial cycles: Europe & Anglo-America, which are the white visual 'animetal cultures' that have become globalized.

There is however a fundamental difference between Europe and Anglo-America, the 2 cultures where I spent most of my life, which we shall stress throughout all the papers on History, as it is the key difference between the duality of futures of mankind.

While ideally humanity should have remained in a present, welfare Neolithic world with a few positive machines in balance with Gaia, we have become a culture of machines. However Europeans due to the influence of its foundational Greek>Latin rational, humanist, artistic democratic culture, has tried through its r=evolutionary periods and higher minds to control lethal machines and put man above metal, by considering the human natural language, the spatial I=Eye>Time Wor(l)d, with its syntax that makes man the center of reality: Man (subject) > verb (action) > Object (energy of the subject), in its social expression, the law, above money, a digital language that reduces and compares man (salary) = (Price) Object. The Anglo-American culture rejects this view and as the founder of capitalism considers money above law even if it maintains a placebo structure of democracy. This difference has its origin in two different 'religions'=beliefs. Anglo-America is born in the Hebrew tradition of the old testament, an earlier fetish go(l)d culture from the bronze age, while Europe always gave more importance to the reform of the Gospel based in social love and after the French and Russian R=evolutions returned to a rational view of mankind with the law above money and after II world war rejected also the nationalist worship of weapons. So belief vs. reason, worship of metal either in its informative go(l)d form (capitalism that puts money above the law), organic form (machines and technoutopia, discovered in the Anglo-American civilization) and weapons (nationalism) differentiated after II W.W. both cultures which means Anglo-America believes in metal ideologies and will continue evolving lethal technologies till they extinguish mankind, while the European Union and the other 5 cultures believe in humanism and could have implemented a control of the tree of metal. But Anglo-America is the culture that became globalized in the digital era, so the welfare State and humanism of Europe also fades away. The question then is who and what kind of memetic culture Anglo-America is 'selling to the world' through its information machines that print e-money, audiovisual fiction and 'Academia'. What we call the FMAsters (Financial-Media-Academia masters), since obviously the truth of an economic ecosystem ruled by company-mothers of machines terraforming the earth to the image and likeness of its offspring, with complete disregard of human rights and values, as an object, compared and replaced in search for profits by fast evolving robots and computers suites and autonomous weapons CANNOT be sold. The answer is a series of wishful thinking, caring political and economically correct placebos that pretend to be

humanist and often disguise the culture as European, when its origin and evolution comes from a different world. Specifically Anglo-America has a 'hierarchical social structure' based in race, history and financial wealth, dominated by the original Hebrew culture of go(l)d banker priests that monopolize the industry of information machines, since the age of the press, when it regressed the gospel culture of love to the segregational memes of the Hebrew press; imposed the Ham damnation of slavery; invented stock companies and monopolized from the City and Wall Street the reproduction of money inventing in Holland and UK after the glorious revolution, the industrial world. This society triumphed over the military Germanic version after a series of internecine wars for industrial profits, first against the 'inferior' colored species of the Ham Damnation, then when the world was conquered to keep the profits of military industries between 'cousins' (the Russian, German and British 'emperors') and then between 'mestizo' Jewish-Germanic dynasties of bankers and military men (Churchill Jerome, Rosenfelt=Roosevelt, Hitler 'Frankenheimer', Goring Epenstein). Greek-Latin Europe could only regain its concept of a humanist welfare world after the tragic death of 100 million people in those II world wars. But now we are back again to the same mixture of Germanic military and Jewish go(l)d beliefs, shrewdly hidden those brutal values with placebo fictions, while both animetal cultures together develop from America through its corporations a future for machines over humanity and beliefs over reason. But all this is disguised by a censorship of political and economical correctness that hides the real structure of power of its society, imprinted by the Goebbels' method of repetition of lies its beliefs as if it were social science. We talk of a 'frozen' structure of social science fictions that please the ego of man as the supreme being of the Universe, with a lineal manifest destiny carried through machines; just because they 'make money'. So we can *consider the future settled unless the system is reformed. Since humans have no other role in that culture that caters for the 1% of managers and owners of companies and for its machines that to consume=vitalize and re=produce them, working on those companies. But those jobs are now replaced by robots with AI minds, soon with solar skins, independent of man, due to the global warming placebo activism. So the middle working class is displaced and fast loose its way of life. But the elites won't care. Since the mind frame of these financial 'chosen races' is primitive in its madness: to monopolize the issue of money, disguise its power, defend its apartheid segregational 'other nation' and ignore all the problems of humanity – not our problem – as go(l)d will provide through the evolution and reproduction of machines and weapons. A resurgence of old ideologies, abrahamic religions, nationalism, capitalism, covered with fictions and a growing infantilism as audiovisual minds erase the verbal reasoning of people, is heralded as culture. Above all as mankind enters its 'entropic age' of dissolution of social structures and the metal-kind organizes in networks of perfect efficiency, 'egocy' (Ego=idiocy) disguises as freedom a chaotic state of individual powerlessness of humanity. Since the organic networks of our species are becoming controlled by company-mothers.*

The solution? More of the same: to hide this tragic destiny in the making our FMAsters just repeat ad nauseam their schemes of global anoxia (lack of credit for mankind as all money is siphoned to speculation), mass-media selfie fictions (each human a Truman Show in Facebook), while 'Academia' keeps prizing techno-utopia. This year the winners of the Nobel prize of chemistry were the people that found the molecule bacteria use to edit virus and enhanced its capabilities so all biochemists knew a virus could be edited to create a pandemic. But as we 'must believe in technology and the superiority of man' with its lineal manifest destiny and hide the real structure of our society dominated by company-mothers terraforming the world for its machines that make money for our elite of stockrats whose culture segregates them from mankind, all criticism is rejected. Even the existence of a hierarchy of financial and corporative power above the law of democracies and its selected politicians is rejected with victimist fictions and deviated to emotional hate memes and censorship (holocaust industry, trash Tv/internet.) The globalized Anglo-America culture 'believes' and will do so till the end. So there is zero argument on the future, zero analysis of social organisms with scientific models as we do in those of those papers, and our 'religious' social structures are considered 'the only' possible system, in which we must believe till the end.

We analyze from the perspective of the scientific ABC+D-E method the duality of humanist welfare democracies vs. placebo 'stockracies' – the 2 set of memes that define the 2 futures of mankind – one immortal history, fading away into entropy.

It is however unlikely that the rational, humanist, truly democratic, welfare world, Europe and Asia, the other two industrial cultures, once saw as its goal, with a pacifist, non-idologic, rational view, resurrects. As 'disguise' & religious dogma – the trade marks of the FMAsters culture throughout its history, today expressed in placebo political correctness and emotional debasing of social sciences – has become global imitated by each corrupted elite of the 7 civilinations, which repeat U\$ FMAsters memes,

and its modes of control of society. What we however cannot do is to renounce to the ABC goal of science: truth. But you can expect animetal cult(ure)s to deny every truth of the human wor(l)d and then die. That's what they do.

Biologic history: animetal beliefs vs. a rational human immortal wor(l)d.

The conclusion is obvious: the science of 5D History belongs to the science of 5D Biology and the evolution of Earth, in 3 ages, inscribed in the science of 5D scales and the organic Universe, in a jump of 'quality of thought, scientific analysis of the human experience and understanding of the

ENTROPIC, WEAPONS KILL
Carriers: Military/Warriors

ORGANIC MACHINES ATROPHY
Industrial Scientists

INFORMATIVE GOL(D) ENSLAVE
Private Banking

IDO-LOGIES: NATIONALISM:Tribe=species MECHANISM:Man&cosmos a machine CAPITALISM: Private Money rules Law

SCIENCES: HUMANISM:Mankind:1 species ORGANICISM:Universe, an organism SOCIALISM:Law rules money

BIO-HISTORY'S 3 METAL MEMES OF EXTINCTION

issued by/for people

real causes of Historic events' unlike anything that has happened since Darwin influenced Marx and the socialist school, Butler and its description of 'animetals' and 'evolving machines', Schumpeter and Kondratieff and Spengler and the biological schools of History, all 'denied' today by the placebo pseudo-Biblical anthropomorphic view and idol-ogies of nationalism (worship of weapons), capitalism (worship of go(l)d) and mechanism, described in the graph in pure biological terms. Since with the arrival of Animetal top predators, Idol-ogies substitute social sciences. Today humans believe in 3 'animetal idol-ogies' whose cultures substituted Neolithic verbal priests of social love, the '5D force' that makes mankind construct superorganisms through the sharing of energy and information among believers, imprinted by networks of metal-communicators through Goebbels' method (if you repeat a lie many times people will believe on it, the bigger the lie, the more they will believe on it):

Go(l)d & Iron cults repress organic life and love Gods from segregational dietary laws to sex as sin, racism and tribalism (a single God-subconscious collective of the tribe that denies all other Gods to make war and slave them. They evolved into: **Nationalism**, which stops humanity as a species in the tribe and promotes weapons=germs to kill each other, originated in Germanic tribal cultures that oppressed the European social love civilization of the Roman empire substituted **humanism**, the understanding that mankind is a single species that has to evolve together as the mind of its body, Gaia .

Capitalism that promotes parasitic private banking and prevents universal salaries and a demand economy based in welfare, originated in biblical go(l)d cultures of banker-priests, today evolved into classic economics substituted **Socialism**, the understanding Society is an organism, whose re=productive, financial network and oxygen must be created for all its cells to credit a welfare state made to the image and likeness of mankind.

And **technoutopia** that considers the evolution of metal a surrogate for the evolution of mankind, substituted **organicism**, the science of the Universe that finds its highest expression in Medicine, the study of the most perfect superorganism, the mammal, and its 'cure' of the sicknesses of animetal idol-ogies, in its equivalent parallel science of **biohistory** that should guide the construction of the economic, political, cultural and defensive, immunological welfare networks of our species.

So it substitutes the sciences of the organic Universe that makes of man the most perfect supørganism we should study first to understand those laws, imitated by bio-historians, the doctors of humanity who should rule history... by mechanical models of the Universe as a machine, where time no longer is measured with logic past, present, future verbal tenses but digital clocks today evolved into computers and our artistic human I=Eye>Wor(l)d measures of space are despised, substituted for metal-eyes today evolved into cameras. The graph is crystal clear about the biological nature of animetal cultures, whose extinctive qualities of gaia, the world of life and History, the world of mankind and the values of social evolution proper of the wor(l)d have run among the expansion of its hate memes, entropic metal-weapons, informative go(l)d and organic machines that kill our bodies, hypnotize our minds and atrophy and substitute our organs. To notice also that the 2 oldest animetal cult(ure)s dominant in war genocides (Germany) and Go(l)d herding (Hebrew) have the lowest survival rate of any world culture (80,18m.), showing that survival of life is a biologic time function of love to your own species inverse to the function of spatial metal-power: T⊥S in terms of 5D paradoxical laws applied to organic history.

The 3±j drives of life, 3 scales of human superorganisms, its 3 key networks: genes ⊥ memes; Life Earth ⊥ Metalearth.

We'll try to give you a fast review of the 5D organic laws of the Universe NOT the mechanical model of reality of animetal cultures, different because a machine only exists in a 5D scale, for you to understand why *the previous view is right even if you feel you are NOT part of it. The reason is that Life exists in 3 scales and your consciousness as an individual is biological, equal to all other human life beings regardless of culture. So most of your time you aspire to fulfill the 3±j drives of life.*

As in the case of the 3 'axis of the mind' all systems of the spacetime Universe are made of 3 topologies of space specialized in 3 time functions: | -lineal limbs/fields that move, as the line is the shortest-fastest distance \emptyset-hyperbolic body-waves that reproduce > O-particle/heads that inform as the sphere holds max. information in lesser space. So you are 'made of vital space' with discontinuous functions in time. You seek freedom to move, energy to feed, right information to guide your organism and from time to time you perform the 2 highest $\Delta \pm j$ scalar actions of life: you reproduce in duality with other gender and you evolve socially with people of the same memes.

Those 5 actions form a program of existence coded from simplest atoms (quantum numbers) to cells (gene letters) to humans with a language, but only the 5th social actions (magnetic number, DNA epigenetics, cultural memes) code for the $\Delta+1$ scale of social organisms. So for 90% of your life you feel just human like all others. This means social memes are the less stable, easy to mutate and a person is NOT born forever to a culture and if enlightened it can become properly human, loving all other members of the same species, as Darwin and love religions and the 5th dimension of social love that creates larger forms from individual parts, tell all species to do to survive better as a stronger whole against different species. This is what animetal cult(ure)s forget and that is why they die in holocausts and wars, because metal is NOT the same species.

Alas! Surprise, my genes are a 1/3rd mix of Sephardim doctors, Basque=British (85% Basque genes) & Celtic=German; the 3 animetal cult(ure)s we strongly chastise as 'Humanist scientists, doctors of history' because memes can be changed.

So the 'task' of a social scientist theoretically is to convince people of the right memes to survive as individual and species. And practically as a member of the information networks that construct social organisms to implement healthy reforms to its main networks, the defensive=immunological system, the financial, reproductive economic system and the informative, verbal, cultural and legal system to achieve immortal history. This task today is impossible because the FMAsters and its neuronal networks are constructing another superorganism of machines, with its metal-networks of military weapons, a defensive metal-Earth system while human true defensive health care systems have none, its monopoly in the issue of blood-money for company-mothers of machines that reproduce and evolve them, while humans lack credit even for basic food and shelter. So 'Animetal warriors' and 'Bankers', historically hauling from Germanic and Hebrew cultures, though its memes have spread 'spatially=laterally' to all cultures and evolve in complexity, are substituting and parasitizing the resources of the planet and a healthy, wealthy human organism where all citizens cells should have shelter, health-care, welfare goods and a Universal salary in ¥€\$ money to reproduce and consume life goods they need to survive. Instead a different superorganism of machines, the metal-earth is born. And it will, once its AI robots with solar skins reproduced in automated 3D printing company-mothers no longer need us, eliminate our species. But this is NOT explained because animetal idol-ogies are 'imprinted' emotionally since infancy by repetition in the past through segregational religions and nationalist mantras, today through audiovisual fictions that disaggregate people from each other making them addicted to the consumption=vitalization of machines – no longer needed to work as AI robots start the Final Solution (no labor, human obsolescence). Only then the 'verbal, informative nervous network' that in all healthy superorganisms control the blood and defensive systems could save us, in praxis and theory: social scientists as political regulating with laws to the benefit of man the other networks. But they are corrupted. Capitalist democracies are placebo systems, created by Company-mothers in Holland and UK and US (tea party revolution) by lawyers of corporations that doubled as politicians to sell laws to companies of weapons (right wing parties) and consumption companies (left wing parties) as they DON'T issue money but tax-farm humans and pander to financiers. While true social scientists are censored by FMAsters with fiction, hate memes and lack of distribution in metal-networks of communication. And citizens cannot vote pain messages as in true Greek democracies to punish politicians and Stockrats, owners of corporations protected by immunity and S.A. Laws. This is the bleak picture of the future of mankind which at this st-age only a humanist r=evolution of FMAsters who cared to survive till the 7th generation could abort. But their history show they are experts only in greed, hate memes against life and suicide.

NEW ENERGY/BOMB->TRANSPORT MACHINES->WEAPONS

THE WARRIOR MASTER BRINGS DEATH with nationalist excuses, as the market changes to weapons production after an age of overpopulation crashes

TERMINATORS BECOME THE MAIN INDUSTRY OF ISRAEL

I: STEAM Great Britain
Founding, Mature, Decadent
1814---1850---1880s--1914

Disraeli conquers eastern lands from 'Primitive Hindus'

BRITAIN ARMOURS ITS TRAINS AND USES STEAMERS TO CONQUER AFRICA & ASIA. 30 MILLION NATIVES DIE

II: CHEMISTRY Germany
Founding, Mature, Decadent
1877---1894-----1914---1945

Hitler reconquers historic eastern lands from 'primitive slaves'

WARRIOR MASTER

I W.W. CHEMICAL EXPLOSIVES

II W.W. OIL PLANES & TANKS

III K. CRACK NYSE 1929

NASDAQ

III K. CRACK 2000-01

SELF-SIMILAR

NOBEL, DR. DEATH

BISMARCK, THE 'GOOD GERMAN'

III: ELECTRONIC
Founding, Mature, Decadent
1914---1945 ---1973 ---2008?

Einstein: Discoverer E=MC²

Gates: Reproducer

Military Lobbyist: Bush

DR. DEATH

JEWISH-AMERICAN EMPIRE

WARRIOR MASTER

GUARDIUM PREDATOR

Sharon reconquers historic eastern lands from 'primitive Arabs'

IV SINGULARITY FUTURE:
ENERGY-BOMB->REPRODUCTIVE MACHINE->TOP PREDATOR WEAPONS

DR. DEATH 1986-2008-- -2037?-----2073

BLACK HOLES

IRON NANO-BACTERIA

ROBOTIC LIFE

THE 4 GENERATIONS OF ENERGIES & MACHINES OF THE INDUSTRIAL R=EVOLUTION EVOLVE IN 3 AGES AS ENERGETIC->TRANSPORT->WEAPON MACHINES DISCOVERED BY PHYSICISTS->REPRODUCED BY TRADERS. USED TO CONQUER EMPIRES BY WARRIOR POLITICIANS

During the Industrial Revolution, a new nation and its 3 generations of engineers, discoverers of the new machine & energy of the cycle, become the founding fathers, industrial reproducers and decadent warriors of nationalistic wars, carrying the evolution of the machine to its military completion... Now in the Singularity Age, machines becomes organic, so we make self-feeding bombs, and if we survive them, self-reproductive factories (nano-bacteria) and Robot life...

The cycles of the Animetal, Anglo-American culture.

The graph shows the cycles of the industrial r=evolution as a new national generation substitutes a previous one, on top of the evolution of the metal-earth. Those generations also bring the nation that finds the new energy to the top predator status of history. Because energy is also the substance of which weapons are made.

- Thus, we had an English age of steam machines, between 1780s and 1857, followed by a crisis of overproduction of steam machines and stock-money that brought the 1857 ±8/9 years product cycle crashes of the train-based economy.
- From 1857 to 1929, we lived the age of electro-chemical energies, machines and chemical explosives, dominated by Germany, followed by a crisis of overproduction of cars and radios, which caused the 1929 crash, 72 years after the train crash. So Germany declared war to the world with gas, tanks and bombers to keep profits going and US followed suit.
- It came then the III cycle of electronic machines, electronic money and Nuclear Bombs that took place from 1929-2001, the age of America; which again ended in the dotcom and mortgage crashes, 72+8/9 years after 1929:
- Followed by the Singularity Age, the last Cycle of machine Evolution dominated by robots, solar energy and China. Scientists call the birth of Artificial Intelligence, the Singularity age, when robots, which can use solar energy to become autonomous will complete the evolution of machines as organic forms, automating factories & expelling most human workers and soldiers from labor and war fields, as previous revolutions did with obsolete III World non-technological humans, unless we forbid legally their evolution.

Money, likely a cryptocurrency independent of man, will become then the digital informative, 'memetic code' that organizes their reproduction in those automated company-mothers.

As such corporations, the 'company-mothers' of those machines whose biological function is to evolve and re=produce them, made first the bodies of machines (XIX c.), then the minds of machines (cameras-eyes, mobile-ears and chips-brains. Finally, in the XXI century, as nature does with simple organisms, such as viruses in cells, where the 3 'parts' of the virus – its

DNA information, body and legs are constructed – and then assembled together, we put together all those organic components into autonomous robots, completing the industrial r=evolution of 'metallife' – a new organic species,

made of a stronger substance than carbon-life. Thus the industrial r=evolution is the evolution of 'metalife', in 3+1 phases, as we made 1st the bodies of machines, then hearts-engines, metal-minds and now we put them together in organic robots in the final r=evolution of machines. Thus Industrial humans become 'animetal enzymen', a biologic species that substitutes the old synapsid=verbal Homo Sapiens, because paradoxically enzymen have debased the ethic wor(l)d that creates a world to the image and likeness of man, always the subject of its sentences, which through verbal actions control objects, substituted by the digital language of machines and money used in an organic planet, to evolve another organic species with more complex metal atoms. *Why those cycles are so exact in the leading 'HAM' industrial culture has only an idol-ogical generation: the control of the Anglo-American civilination by stockrats, its company-mothers and idol-ogies of machine worship is absolute. So there is a superfluidity, with 0 resistance to the evolution of technology whatever it takes, including the life of millions of humans in war.*

Because company-mothers control the physiological networks of mankind (they reproduce its military systems, pay laws to politicos to favor its products, and reproduce most of the money), the Anglo-American biblical culture has been imitated in other nations without much difficulty by indoctrinating its old animetal warrior and banker elites with the mechanist doctrines. It calls then attention that in all those nations, perfectly programmed to develop mechanisms and forget the destiny of mankind, the center of all the emotional and human discourse is the 'free individual'. This is one of the many paradoxes of complex organisms the 'egocy human' can hardly understand: precisely because the 'system' of physiological networks has such an absolute control in the languages of power of society (and the people-castes that 'own them') the individual is left in a free, chaotic, entropic, competitive, Darwinian state, which *is the 'field state' of any herd of preys it confuses with freedom. It is also reduced in its consciousness to the entropic state of dog-eat-dog that he sees as the only way of being. This is the way of the American, but the reader should understand America is the mixture of all human cultures displaced into the technological future. So it is NOT a nation, but mankind into its final 'hour', its 'entropic' Tt-stage of 'not being' anymore mankind – but a mass of dissolved cells.* Today, In the age of the chip radiation, companies of information machines controlled by the HAM culture and its FMAsters (Financial-Media-Academia Masters), whose print e-money in monopoly in Wall Street, condemning to global anoxia the majority of mankind, imprint humans with hate and fiction memes through Hollywood and Internet corporations, devolving the collective subconscious to a neo-Paleolithic violent, emotional age and degrade science through academic think tanks and prize ceremonies to impose this mechanist, computer-based view upon the organic Universe under a false camouflage of humanism and political and economical correctness borrowed from the European, organic true culture of science, art and democracy those texts take to its next level of complexity; all because of the only obsessive purpose of its millenarian biblical go(l)d culture: to herd money, today by increasing corporative profits, through the reproduction and evolution of AI machines that displace humans from labor and war fields and terraform the Earth into the world of metal that will extinguish us. But that is a 'choice' their culture on top of the dominant nation of the world today, U\$, has done, it is NOT, we repeat the only deterministic no future of mankind but an imposition of the wrong memes of those who control the languages of social power of modern society. 'But those who impose truth with power will be the laugh of the Gods'. A.Einstein.

Control of entropic Δ -1 egos by networks

A capitalist democracy is a hierarchical structure ruled by networks of corporations & financiers on top, paying for laws to Selected politicos, controlling populations of consumers through propaganda, buying workers with digital numbers, they print in monopoly, dedicating its leisure time to buy humans, machines, objects and hagiographies for the fantasy of immortality. The graph published 30 years ago showed the 'future' of that industrial world – now the present, as its evolution is biologic, Darwinian, hence predictable. If you monopolize the language of power as stockrats do, the eco(nomic)system belongs to you. So what the capitalist elite through its instrument of power, stock-companies that reproduce financial, legal money with no limits has seek for centuries is the destruction of the alternative human power (governments, rights to invent money through deficit, legal control of corporations). The fight from the XVII to XXI c. was rigged by the fact Companies invented modern bipartisan democracies. So politico system was controlled from inception.

But the control of people took longer, achieved as *all predatory systems do by entropic destruction (war, colonies, police)* and by setting a 'farm', which is the metaphor of the graph following Orwell's anim(et)al farm. The key is then to maintain mankind in a fictional, infantile disjoined, 'atomic state', as a source of 'energy=heat', whenever needed for war or work (to consume=vitalize machines or be consumed by weapons). Mankind fought the system in the XIX c. but without a scientific model of organic societies felt prey of the worst military systems or false idol-ogies - Marxism, born from a member of the Hebrew culture that hid the true power of capitalism –the financiers that print money and buy companies and politicians with it, to focus on military 'hate memes blaming managers against workers' to keep the worship of machines, *the true competitors of workers that steal its work and reduce its 'surplus' salary: worker (salary)=Price (machine), in an evolutionary*

process called productivity = Capital labor/Human labor. So machine productivity increases by reducing labor and/or diminishing salaries. Thus the dual ab=use comes from parasitic financiers and machine competition. So Marx defended Capitalism, Mechanism & weapons (political violence). While the mass accepts dystopia as it is kept in an entropic state by the sum of all those idol-ogies: 'people must be ignorant to be obedient' (Calvin). We, r=evolutionaries have valued IQless people beyond its ethics and intelligence. Today, humans are kept in a state of permanent selfie entropy, as divide and win strategies have reduced their social connection first below the nation, into a region or race unit. So they started to call themselves 'African-Americans', 'Polish-Americans', etc. Then below scales down the family into the l=egocy state of a child. Most Americans I met were emotionally children, not even adolescents that care and empathize with others. Some toddlers who freaked out when reality did not obey their tantrums. This state makes them 'a prey reservoir' of company-mothers and its stockrats, which only want to tax farm them and use its cheap work and consumption skills, but now AI robots can do both jobs. So other 'work' has been to consume weapons. And a transitory solution (right bottom) to be kept cheap in virtual homes (Pandemic state). Meanwhile the world of machines evolves fast its global internet telepathic brain, networks of solar 'skin' energy and self-reproductivity of ∞ mechanical work and 0 human labor. But economists from Smith to Marx to Hayek & Friedman to Mr. Davos are all members of the 'biblical culture' of go(l)d worship and human segregation, working for companies whose job is NOT 'social justice' and human survival but finding 'excuses' to protect the corporation.

Ideal History: the reform of the wor(l)d.

The superorganism of mankind designed with its 'economic frame of reference' that value goods according to their Wealth = biologic utility to foster the drives of life humans need to thrive and survive; controlling with ± prices its

VI: HISTORY IS THE HUMAN SUPER-ORGANISM

production. The same laws that apply to the study on how cells becomes wholes through its connection through physiologic networks, of energy, reproduction and information, apply to the way humans are organized by energetic territories, economic, re=productive networks and informative, cultural, legal networks.

The Universe was on reason (max. i) + love (max. Δ)=Δi; so it would be easy to cre(dit)ate ideal, immortal history: a world ruled by 'social doctors' that use the 'isomorphic' laws of efficient Universal organisms to make History immortal and the 99% thrive, evolving from its present 'worm' state that poisons with lethal goods its cells, into an efficient mammal where they get

welfare goods, freedom and just nervous laws. But the greedy worm works on e-motion and hate... So a r=evolution needs +3 -3 positive and negative reforms of global defensive, economic and legal wor(l)d systems:

± measures from the memetic & immunologic systems, which must promote life goods, health-care and human languages of information and sciences while on the negative side should forbid lethal technologies that kill our body, poison our mind (weapons, fiction & hate memes) or compete and atrophy them in labor and war fields (robots, software).

± measures from the eco(nomic)system to enhance the reproduction of welfare goods and limit the production of lethal goods.

- measure: All company-mothers of machines&weapons split shares giving them to governments for a 50% 'stockratic' control keeping its private management, so civilinations can regulate, promote, forbid or reform the productive system.

+ measure: all supœrganisms distribute for free to all its cells a universal energy salary in oxygen to kick out production and consumption of welfare goods. So to create a just, democratic demand economy the 7 civilinations will send to every human in a world cryptocurrency a monthly a ¥€\$ salary of 1000 1 euro=1 dollar = 100 yens = 5 yuans, used as a NO-debt language to consume & reproduce the welfare goods of the 'ethonomic' frame of reference, ending poverty, immigration and readdressing production to cater only human needs and terraform the Earth to the image & likeness of mankind.

- measure to create a true democracy: The Informative, legal system should judge=vote a posteriori with pain messages politicians who don't serve thoe goals, as cells do with a brain that harms them.

+ measure: Nations construct an efficient 5D scalar, social system by devolving to regions enhanced welfare administrations, while reducing national animetal parasitic structures (armies, financial systems) upgrading them to a unified human system of the 7 civilinations of mankind, with EU like common networks forming an heptarchy, guide by the Human Constitution of a Healthy whealthy body of history: Max. Human goods = Min lethal goods policed and suppressed by the military.

The result will be immortal History where 'the 3rd age of time with an excess of lethal information that brings entropy=death is reversed, setting the equation of the 3 ages of Earth backwards with history as its eternal present: Gaia<History<Metal-earth.

Such system could be implemented if our political, financial & Academic elites understood rationally and ethically history, as the organism of all mankind and its role as the efficient neuronal people-caste that must serve its body, the 90% and repress the lethal metalife species that will destroy as, as it is simply and ideal immortal supœrganism of History that imitates Nature's efficient supœrganisms from physical systems that 'bathe' all its atoms in ¥-monetary energy and synchronize its motions with the same informative gravitational= just legal language sto all biologic systems that synchronize its cell motions with simultaneous nervous=legal messages and give all cells free energy=oxygen. Even an agreement of the 3 leading political nations, Mr. POTUS, Mr EU & Mr. China could make it happen. So this is in 9 pgs History=Mankind in the age extinction by a rival species backed by animetal memes and its resurrection, the reform of its physiological networks in a perfect organism

KEY 5D LAWS OF SPACE-TIME ORGANISMS APPLIED TO HISTORIC CIVILIZATIONS.

5D metrics: A 4D world of time lifecycles embedded in 5D hyperpolitic, organic scales.

In the graph, the organic, network structure of the whole Universe defines a series of 'hyperbolic' cellular scales that make the organism NOT the mechanism, the basis of all Nature's system.

Mathematically then it is necessary to find a metric function to define this new dimension of spacetime. Since a dimension only exists when we can write a

mathematical simple metric that leaves the dimension invariant when we change our parameters of space and time - hence we travel through it. (Klein). So we write:

$$s^2 \text{ (Lineal Size/ Volume) } \times \text{Tf (cyclic frequency=speed of time clocks) } = \Delta \pm j: 3 \text{ Co-existing Planes of timespace.}$$

It means an organism co-exists symbiotically in 3 scales of $\Delta-1$ parts, (cells, atoms, human beings), joined by $\Delta\emptyset$ networks of energy and information (electromagnetic and gravitational fields; blood and nervous networks; political and economical systems), $\Delta\emptyset$, in a larger $\Delta+1$ world; (gravitational, thermodynamic, social system), because its parts are symbiotic.

In 5D metric, smaller systems in space have faster time clocks that store more information in the frequency and form of its cycles, coding larger wholes: genes code cells, memes societies and particles code atoms and molecules. But larger wholes are stronger envelopes, membranes (static, dimensional view) or angular momenta (dynamic view as time=motions) which enclose and control in synchronicity its faster smaller parts. They also have more 'scales of Δ -energy'. So they exchange energy for information with its parts, through 3 Δ^0 T-motion, Δ -Energy & S-informative networks that travel through the 5th dimension, harmonizing the co-existence of organic scales whose vital Universal constants are 5D metric ratios of information & energy exchanges. Thus the Universe is a nested, fractal 5D superorganism that organizes 'vital spacetime forms with motion' through networks into larger organic systems that emerge as new planes of STjence, from particles into atoms, molecules, cells, matter states, organisms, solar systems & galaxies. As each new 'ST-organism' becomes a 'fractal point' unit of a new '5D space-time network'.

The outcome is the organic structure of all physical, biological and social systems, from History coded by memes, ideas and instruments that create human social organisms, civilinations, to physical systems coded by particles and scalar, 'social numbers' and algebraic equations, whose 'operands' code the different 'Dimotions of spacetime', to biology coded by genes. And so we shall use the same laws of 5D scales of space-time to study every stience of the Universe and its superorganisms defined by the symbiosis in space, synchronicity in time and simultaneity in space of its parts and wholes across 3 of those 5D scales, the $\Delta-1$, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ^0 , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the $\Delta+1$, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biologic and social systems.

But how do your travel through those hyperbolic scales of the 5th dimension. Simple: growing in 'size' in space while decelerating the 'speed of your time cycles, through the worldcycle of life and death.

As all systems of the Universe are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism coming out in the Δ^0 -scale within a larger world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving our information again into cellular space.

It is the same process in all 5D journeys of all species that live and die travelling through 3 planes of 5D space-time; from the smallest black hole that is born with an enormous 'metabolic temperature', to the new species, routinely born as small individuals (first mammal rat, first robots with small chips; first human likely the Homo Floresiensis, who had the same morphology and used technology and likely spoke, etc.) Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the seed into a larger herd of clones, joined by emergent physiological networks whose slower 'entropic, informative and reproductive networks, create an Δ^0 supœrganism that lives 3 st-ages and dissolves back into $\Delta-1$.

5D metric is then used to analyze with the same laws, all scales of space-time each one studied by a stience, whose species are made of 3 relative elements: Δ -scales of Space=Form & Time=Motion:

In mathematics Non-E fractal points of Space grow in lines=networks; 3 of which form a topologic space-time plane=organism. Numbers represent Δ -scalar groups and Algebraic operands Time motions.

In physics Δ ST is proved because its 3 elements correspond to its 3 conserved quantities: S=angular momentum, T=lineal momentum & 3 Energy forms, Δ -1: Internal, $\Delta\emptyset$ -kinetic & Δ +1 potential energy. Thus ST: 2 |+O momenta integrate into Δ +1 work=energy: $\int p=E$ or dissolve=derivate into the ∂p =Forces scale.

In biology we travel through the 5th dimension of scalar space & cyclical time by growing organically in 'space size' through cellular/atomic/social networks 'while slowing down the 'speed of our metabolic time cycles, which is exactly what happens in the worldcycle of life and death of any universal species as all are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism emerging as a bigger Δ° network organism, to live within a larger Δ +1 world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving its information back into its lower cellular/atomic Δ -1 plane; from the smallest black hole born with a huge 'metabolic temperature' (Hawking), to the new species, born as small individuals (1st placental mammal shrew, first digital brain=chips; 1st modern human brain, Homo Floresiensis). Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the crystal, DNA cell or species creating an Δ° supœrganism that lives 3 ages of growing information till death dissolves back into Δ -1 (Δ -1: plasma>T-gas, S=T-liquid, S-olid states « $E=mc^2$).

Organic worldcycles happen in all stiences. They define the key system of reality, an Δ ST Supœrganism whose simultaneous parts in space become synchronous in time, across 3 5D scales, the Δ -1, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ° , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the Δ +1, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biologic and social systems, whose metrics allows the symbiotic transfer of spacetime energy made of cyclical information and lineal motion. As all scales have the same value and properties, hence the Universe is absolutely relative.

Thus space laws are Topologic laws that put together 3 type of networks: |-moving limbs/fields> \emptyset -reproductive waves/ bodies & O-informative particle/heads.

Time laws study life-death worldcycles that evolve Δ -1 seeds into $\Delta\emptyset$ -organisms made of those 3 topologies that 'age' in 3 ST-ages dominated by each network till the S-head exhaust all motion and a 'fast' entropic=death dissolves its information into an Δ st 0-sum.

Finally $\Delta\pm j$ scalar laws study Δ -energy exchanges thru $3\pm j$ 'Actions' of Tt-entropic feeding, Ts-motion, $\int \Pi$ -reproduction, St-information & Ss-mind mirror languages that revolve and project order in a larger Δ +1 world. Those are the Δ ST-events & forms of space-time described by each species in each stience. This is a very brief, condense 'synopsis' of the many sides of 5D stience, we expand in the appendix and all other papers at Academia.edu, in case you want to understand it better. We are though just interested in giving you a feeling of this new r=evolution of stience, as we apply it to the study of the scales &

LAWS OF 5D HISTORY: WORLDCYCLES OF CIVILIZATIONS.

History is inscribed in a larger planet, an evolving superorganism, the word Hutton, father of Geology, coined to define the planet and its 'deep time' slow life cycles, based in the 'metric equation' of the organic 5th dimension of the scalar Universe, $Sxt=C$, which makes smaller systems in space trace faster time cycles that carry the information of the organism in its frequency and form. So *the different 5D -space-time scale of a supœrganism becomes symbiotic, as smaller parts, quantum particles in physics, genes in biology, memes in History code the larger organism, matter, life & 'planetary civilinations', which protect & feed the smaller 'cells-citizens'.*

If the 1st language regains the ethic classic understanding of humanity, this 2nd level upgrades its scientific outlook with the formalism of systems sciences and its 'isomorphic=equal' scalar laws of space-time follows by all its species – unfortunately denied by mechanism because it would oblige scientists

to abort the manifest destiny of our technological civilization that is evolving earth in 3 ages of growing information that in all systems leads organisms to its entropic death: Gaia (Past Youth: life, light Earth) >

History (Present: Human, verbal Earth) > Metal-earth (Future, 3rd informative age of Digital machines)

Because of the backwardness of human social sciences, specially in its praxis of power – political and economical systems, and the attachment of ‘irrational, emotional’ memes that ‘program people’ with knee-jerk reactions to any attempt to educate them, we need to consider first a brief list of the key laws that apply to the superorganisms of history.

To start with History IS a superorganism of human beings, NOT a mechanism, neither a collection of individual egos.

Other key laws of 5D bio-history: evolution vs. intelligent design, memes not genes control history. Cultures matter.

As I said even before we start a serious scientific analysis of mankind, History, its sicknesses, its Nature, its role within this planet, its choices of future, its possible cures, its different cultures, etc. in a lengthy 100 pages or so introduction to all papers, we have to stress some basic laws of 5D Science that applies to physics, biology and history and CANNOT BE changed. Laws of History are LAWS of Nature and so mankind would do much better learning them rationally, forgetting emotional hang ups, and foggy selfish agendas and go through a reality check and try by all means to cure its superorganism before it dies – *because when an organism of history dies by an excess of its germs – hate memes and weapons, in wars and revolutions and holocausts, all its people-cells WITHOUT exception die, including its 2 ‘organic classes’, the reproductive working class of its body and the neuronal, informative class of its brain that issue its languages of social power, the informative bills of law and the reproductive bills of money.*

So another key law of all superorganisms is the fact that the neuronal ‘financiers and politicians’ that issue those languages serve the body – we already said they deliver money to each cell and just laws. And this happens because if they harm the body, the body cells send them a posteriori votes of pain, and so they suffer. This was the essence of democracies in Greece, where all citizens were allotted positions of social power and then after tenure they were judged and imprisoned, even condemned to death if they committed crimes against society. The fact that our ‘false democracies’ have immunity for both, the politicians that issue laws and handle police and weapons, and the financiers and ‘stockrats’, modern aristocrats owners of company-mothers that reproduce money and goods, and are protected by anonymous societies and lawyers and have no responsibility to consumers and workers is yet ANOTHER aberration of history.

And again we find those aberrations are caused by ‘metal-power’, military origins in most societies, either political or economical – company-mothers of machines-weapons who invented capitalist democracies in Holland, UK and U4 and let their lawyers rule society, ever since gunboats defined the history of the ‘Anglo-American civilisations’.

So sorry, I wish I could give you good news and tell you mankind is in good shape, the body-cells of the immense majority of people do control their neuronal financial and political cells and they serve mankind and lethal metal goods and hate memes are controlled, but exactly the opposite is happening. But at least you know why indeed the world of history is dying and so many people in History has suffered so much and keep suffering, and why ‘social organisms’ nations and civilizations die in wars which are death by germs of History. To illustrate all this, we have a graph where some basic laws of 5D apply:

The first law is called Disomorphism: the organic laws of any scale of reality are the same. So the same laws that work for medicine – the biological organism of cells; work for History and that is the reason we constantly give you homologies. In fact in a deeper analysis, the same laws that work for physical systems, with electromagnetic ‘energy networks’ and gravitational ‘informative networks’ work for biology and history, but that requires a lengthy analysis of mathematical equations of physics so we will keep it simpler comparing and using the biological organism.

This brings a second theme of all organisms: their worldcycle of life and death, which in 5D is explained as a travel through 3 ‘scales of the fifth dimension’, and it is THE MOST important of all the ‘space-time systems and events of reality’. So even before we have more serious scientific basis to study it, it is worth to observe it, to explain you the life and death of civilizations and specially a law that should be obvious but it is not in the present primitive systems of History: genes do NOT matter to history, memes create history, the ‘next scale’ of social complexity and memes, ideas, instruments, verbal thoughts, religions, form cultures, which are the UNITS of history, whose people have the same ‘memetic DNA”, the same ideas, etc. But those ideas *can be positive for the future of mankind, helping to create a healthy body of history, for*

example love religions that embed in verbal though the social mandate of organic evolution, the sharing of energy and information among human beings, to create a larger whole; vs. lethal memes, cultures that are predatory and use weapons or parasitic money or lethal technologies to ab=use other human beings. So not only cultures matter, but they are divided according to the 'natural goals' of organic evolution of the 5D Universe in good, pro-love and pro-life memetic cultures and bad=evil anti-live and anti-love parasitic and predatory cultures. This is the key to understand History in biological organic scientific terms and there is NO way around it if you want to do 'true social sciences'. The good news is that those laws are natural, everybody knows that love and life are good, the bad news is that we are going to criticize a lot of political and economical placebo ideas about what is good, because an essential 'system of predation' that apply to cultures is 'camouflage', specially in parasitic and predatory cultures. It is in fact the rule, so yes, there are confabulation theories, victimist cultures, racist cultures, segregational cultures, genocidal cultures, military cultures, – you have the whole range and it is not as simple as it seems to understand it.

This is the reason why so few people look at my work despite being so important and the only scientific model: because we are in a sick planet, and most cultures are corrupted by lethal goods, and are predatory or parasitic of mankind, we spend far more time describing 'negative views' of human cultures and so bio-history is a bit depressing, sorry, truth cannot be cheated. And so I know Plato's dictum, 'nobody is more hated than the man that says the truth'. I call this, the anti-quantum paradox: the social scientist is a cell inside an organism of history and if it has the bad luck of living in a corrupted one, the 'sick mad brain' will prevent him from saying the truth: 'you will defend me with gold and the sword and I will defend you with the word' said Tertulian. For that reason r=evolutionaries and true social scientists had a bad experience in history.

The worldcycle of existjence of all systems of nature as a travel through 3 Δ-scales and ages of the 5th dimension.

The most important discovery of 5D Metrics is resolving the life-death worldcycle of existjence of any system which is born as a seed of a lower 'plane' with faster methabolic time cycles, multiplies into clone beings, organized into an Entropic

THE 3 AGES OF LIFE

IF MEN ARE ORGANISMS THAT GO THROUGH 3 SEQUENTIAL AGES CONTROLLED BY EACH OF ITS 3 NETWORKS...

Blood, energy networks:

YOUTH, AGE OF ENERGY

The existence of any organism made of 'cells' of energy and information follows an 'arrow of future' that trans-forms energy into information in 3 ages:

'Vital energy trans-forms itself...

Endocrine, reproductive networks:

MATURITY, AGE OF REPRODUCTION

... reproduces

...Into in-form-ation...

...and in-form-ative, nervous networks:

OLD AGE, THE AGE OF IN-FORM-ATION...

...AND

and dies simplified again into energy...

CIVILIZATIONS ARE ORGANISMS MADE OF HUMAN CITIZENS...

...joined by energy networks: Nature... reproductive networks:social groups... and informative networks: wor(l)ds and art:

THAT GO THROUGH 3 AGES, DEFINED BY THEIR ART STYLE, THE COLLECTIVE MIND OF A CULTURE...

EPIC, LINEAL YOUTH, THE AGE OF ENERGY

When a culture is born, its mind, its art, is young, energetic: its spatial forms are big, simple, lineal. Its temporal, verbal literature is romantic, epic, optimistic, like the mind of a child that nothing fears and wants it all.

Warriors and prophets that create the new culture, with words or words, expanding it all over the world.

CLASSIC, REALIST, SENSORIAL, MATURE ART THE AGE OF HARMONY:

When weapons quiet down or the prophet dies, once its expansion has reached a zenith the culture matures, and its art finds a balance between energy and information. The style becomes classic, realist. Society abandons war as its main purpose and returns to the sensorial pleasures of a world paradise based in love and human goods. Wealth grows and distributes beyond the warrior castes that dominated its youth: Spatial art becomes armonic and diminishes in size, palaces with human proportions substitute tombs. In words, logic philosophy and realist tales substitute poetry and epic. In religion mercy and love to God softens the strict prophetic canon.

OLD AGE: DECADENT, PROPHETIC, BAROQUE, IN-FORM-ATIVE ART:

But the tree of science brings new weapons and wars that destroy the culture and its elites

Art becomes pessimist, without energy, full of in-form-ation, baroque, ornamental, small in space, eclectic, nostalgic, in search of a better past, with 'angst' for the future. The cultural mind is similar to that of an old man. Wor(l)ds however, reache a zenith of informative, encyclopedic knowledge: Logic becomes complex, paradoxical and time becomes cyclical, evolving from the lineal perception of youth. In fiction, it is the age of tragedies and comedies. In religion it is the age of prophets which are able to survive the death of the culture, creating the seminal wor(l)ds of a son-culture with the same cultural memes that will resucite after death:

LIFE

...WHOSE CELLS DIE, VICTIMS OF GERMS:

Organisms die when their physiological networks are attack and destroyed by alien germs. Then cells are freed, but with collective defence, die individually as energy of those germs

DEATH, THE END OF THE ETERNAL TIME CYCLE...

which starts again with a new generation that repeats the information of the old being in a 'son'

...WHO DIE VICTIMS OF METAL-GERMS: WEAPONS

A cultural organism dies when w collapses its social networks, destroy energy its agricultural bra (capital), and its nervous network (system of government), provoking its extinct origin d and w

THAT END UNDER FASCIST CENSORSHIP IN A WAR AGE

Finally, the culture dies when a new warrior caste conquere the civilization imposing a new cycle of epic, young art...

'You will protect me with your sword, and I will defend you with my word'

But often, as warriors civilize, the old culture replicates its memetic symbols on the mind of the conquerors. And a child culture matures with the same 3 cyclical styles of the old or

Roman culture inherits its artistic 'memes' from the Greek culture, reproducing them again in 3 cultural, political and social ages:

Epic Age, lineal art: 'Wolverine'

Classic Age: Republic, 'Carpe Diem'

Baroque, decadent age: 'Ner'

THE 3 AGES OF ART, MIND OF CIVILIZATIONS

Locomotion class of lineal limbss-fields/territories by a re=productive, \emptyset -hyperbolic class of working body-waves and a O-spheric, informative class of particles/heads/i to emerge as a 3 network organism $|xO=\emptyset$ into a larger $\Delta+1$ world where each of those 3 networks will dominate one of its ages, the $|$ -entropic youth, \emptyset -reproductive maturity and O-informative 3rd age, to die when all energy is exhausted disgregating back in an entropic explosion (physical big-bang, biological death, war) into its $\Delta-1$ cells. *This symmetry between Network classes, organic forms, functions and ages in Δ -scales=Vital Spaces=Time ages defines the life-death worldcycle through STj-planes of all systems and we can apply its isomorphic= same laws of 'existence' to all systems, including human societies, compared in the graph. The goal of any organism is then obvious: to maximize its 'worldcycle of existence' by keeping the organism alive the longest possible time, feeding the system with entropic motion, reproductive energy & right information to communicate and evolve socially with similar clones into a larger whole. So we write with the symbols of 'existential algebra', S=spatial form, T=motion, $\Delta\pm j$ =scales, >informative evolution, <devolution, 3 $|xO=\emptyset$, topological forms, etc. a series of 5D formal laws that unify all stiences and apply to all systems. In 5D History it means 'politicians' in charge of the informative legal network, economists in charge of the reproductive system and health-care and farming people in charge of the immunological and feeding systems should promote the welfare goods, right, just laws, and humanist education to maximize the existence of a social organism and come together as a single species, mind of the Earth, becoming a single $\Delta+j$: world. Thus social scientists are 'doctors of history' and their laws are 'physiological laws' that apply to construct an immortal world.*

But this is NOT the world animetals are cre(dit)ating with its idol-ogies of metal. Instead they create a superorganism of machines with 'germs=weapons' instead of health-care warriors, company-mothers that overproduce machines and underproduce welfare goods, and corrupted politicos that sell laws to companies and scholars that teach only digital languages, and mechanist sciences, despise humanities and organicism and all together terraform Earth to the image of those machines. The result is obvious: Gaia, and History, the Earth of life and mankind are dying. And a new metal-earth is growing. So manknd is entering the age of entropy=death. But the amazing thing is that on top of killing mankind those animetals cult(ure)s do NOT understand what they are doing. Why? Because its egocy: ego=idiocy makes them despise the Universe's intelligence, organic structure, social love arrow, the planet Earth and even other human beings. So they cannot recognize reality. The reader then will forgive me if I have a critical, almost surrealist attitude towards or 'M.A.D. elites'.

The graphs portray the networks and ages of the superorganism of mankind in its 2 main individual and social 'scales'. They show the parallelism between the scale of individuals and societies, how they die and the collective mind of a culture which is its art and legal, verbal ethic thought.

The graph is very old, and was part of a huge exhibit of a river of cultures, as then it applied to the study of all the civilizations of mankind through its cycles of life and death, separated by ages of global wars when the germs of history, weapons multiplied in 800-80 years cycles – the first exhibit done in the 90s at Columbia U. where I studied, in 92...

It amazes me that 30 years latter mankind cares nothing for 5D – the antiquantum paradox is very disheartening. But it is real, from Jesus crucified for preaching love to the coalition of parasitic bankers and military Romans to Trostky murdere by military Stalin, to the modern activists for an ecological just world... the corruption of 'our neuronal castes' is harsh. So at least if you are reading and don't have your brain 'erased' by the 'idol-ogies' of lethal germs,

SS:Human: Ts:Youth (0-20a.); Maturity (20-40);S=T 3rd age :St death (60-80):TT

Culture: Epic, Lineal Art; Realist, Classic Art; Baroque Art. War.

SS:Matter: Birth: Plasma Max.Ts : Gas S =T: Liquid Max.St: Solid S(Mc²) <<Tt

Star:Birth: Nebula. SS Ts: Gigant star. S=T: Sun. Max.St: White Dwarf.St<<Tt Nova

Galaxy: SS: Irreg Max.Ts: Irregular S=T: Spiral/Elliptic Max.St: Globular TT: Quasar

allow me to at least with the only language of true Human Nature, the wor(l)d, as all ethic artists and writers have done – the true collective mind of civilizations – to be truthful to the natural goal of all organisms of the Universe – to evolve socially into a stronger whole and survive, from particles that become atoms that become molecules that become cells, or matter cycles of planetoids... all the way to solar systems and galaxies, to human societies and platneray societies, where in ideal immortal history those germs and parasites of mankind DON'T RULE, but true 5D social scientists have created a perfect world. This was the reason 30 years ago I abandoned a life of pleasure-seeking, easy stock-money (knwoing the cycles of economics) and became an activist. And look where I am 30 years latter, rewriting this I know by heart and nobody seems to care, LOL:

But don't worry, this is more like a testament, here at Academia.edu, I won't bother the species for too long. Below a brief graph of the 'worldcycle of life and death' and its 3 ages of different organisms of 5D physics, biology and sociology, where you can see that 'life is a travel through 3 scales of the fifth dimension'. You are born as a cellular seed in the lower scale, you grow and 'emerge' as a human being, in the 'Δo' organic scale, and form part of an Δ+1 social scale, the organism of history where you belong that in ideal history would be the whole of mankind as the collective brain of humanity. Here is where the law of memetics appears. In the same manner you live only through 3 scales, and when you die at individual level you go down 2 scales into molecular carbohydrates, and when you eat you reduce the food to amino acid molecules and genes are molecules, upwards genes can only code 2 scales, the cell and the organism.

So History whose units are cultures are NOT coded by genes but by memes, nervous verbal flows that are at the multicellular neuronal network level, and outside instruments, objects and books that replicate those words and spread the 'memetic DNA' to believers that form then larger geographical networks and organisms of history by sharing energy and information through those outer networks of legal systems, informative cultural memes or reproductive economic systems:

You can see the same images of 'art', now representing human beings in its 3 ages, to keep it simple. We have added the basic 'symbols' of the relational, relative space-time model of the 5D Universe in which all the organic laws of the Universe are based. They form the worldcycle of life and death that writes with the symbols S for spatial in-form-ation and T for temporal motion and Δ-1 for the cellular scale, Δø for the organic scale and Δ+1 for the outer world as follows:

Δ-1 Ss: 'seed' > Δø: Ts-child > Δ+1: S=T: Energy, reproductive age > St-3rd informative age << Δ-1: Tt-entropic death.

It simply means you are born as a 'seed' of information in the lower scale, as an Ss-form (with internal and EXTERNAL still form). Then you emerge in the Δø organic scale, in your youth with maximal T-EXTERNAL MOTION, and internal minimal form, but as you grow in information finally both elements and its networks, balance S=T, which is the equation of beauty, classicism, energy and Reproduction, combining space and time form and motion; then you live a 3rd age of excessive information, S, and minimal motion, t and finally you 'reverse' your -> time arrow and 'explode in internal and external motion' TT, or entropy, disordering your networks and devolving back to the cellular Δ-1 scale and dying.

This is the worldcycle of life and death, and in matter means a plasma age of 'ions', or particles in the Δ-1 scale, a gaseous age of maximal T-motion, a liquid, balanced age, S=T, between form and motion, a solid, 3rd age of maximal information dying back into 'plasma' in a nuclear explosion. And the same cycle happens in stars and galaxies that are 'seeded' by black holes as irregular gaseous galaxies and then become denser finally made of solid dark quark matter and die in a quasar explosion, seeding a new galaxy. 5D Physics is as fascinating as 5D biology and 5D History, which has been my obsession, and so... because of the anti-quantum paradox so little of it has become 'popular or scholar science'. I couldn't care less. Plato's dictum is in my desktop for long. Only truth exists and I will not renounce to it. If humans don't have the intelligence, Max. St, bravery, Max. Ts, and beauty, S=T to seek it and exist and survive and evolve socially through ethics into a larger Δ+1 world, it is not my fault. I tried to 'enlighten them with St-intelligence and Δ+1 ethics all my life

THE 3 AGES OF EARTH: VORTEX OF TIME HISTORY WITHIN GAIA, ITS LARGER SUPCERGANISM

5TH SCALE: MOLECULAR ORGANISMS EVOLVE LIGHT ON EARTH IN 3 +1 AGES:

as I-1=cells, energy=plants, information=animals and ExT=Machines part of the I+1 Earth

Destroy the re=productive placentas of the GNA extinctive 5D species. Kill the child before it becomes a tiger hunter.

What is the future of history, the super organism of Mankind developed in time, from the first mitochondrial eve, who was able to speak and multiplied all over the Earth, making the homo sapiens the collective mind of the planet; to the last human beings who will exit Earth when a new more intelligent species displaces ours from our present top predator position?

As we are just part of a larger supœrganism, Earth, it is logic to consider 1st how evolution shapes the future of the whole planet in which our smaller, shorter existence takes place.

The founding father of geology, James Hutton invented the word super organism precisely to define the Earth's slow geological cycles. He recommended physiology as the science to study hydrology likening the rivers of Gaia to veins that shape the body of the Earth and carry its nutritious elements to its living cells, animals and forests that gather on its sides. Gaia's veins merely have slower annual rhythms in his crop production, compared to the daily circulation of nutrients in our blood that feed and reproduce the cells of the body, according to the metric law of the scalar, 'fifth dimension' of the universe, which states that the bigger a system is in space, the slower the clock cycles of its physiological reproductive networks and informative, evolutionary ages will be. This means that if we put at fast motion, the geological and physiological cycles of the Earth the planet will seem to us alive; and vice versa if we slow down the metabolic cycles of a smaller cell they will resemble us those of a factory either reproducing the goods the biological or social supœrganism needs to survive. Super organisms co-exist in different scales thanks to the 'metric of the scalar fifth dimension' of parts which are faster and code with more information, larger beings which are slower and provide energy to its parts. Mankind is not alone in this planet, not it is in command of Earth, as so many ego centered humans think, but we are part of the planet and that poises some serious questions about our role on its evolution as a supœrganism of a larger scale, illustrated in the graphs.

Survival is rueld by a simple law: As more individuals of each species are born than can survive; consequently, there is a struggle for existence" Darwin. How all this applies to the 3 ages of Earth as supœrganism in which History exists? Simple: *Earth also evolves increasing its information and as History lives within it, it suffers its consequences, both positive (evolution of life) and negative (evolution of lethal goods, weapons that kill us).*

The repetitive WAR cycles that kill History are vortex of accelerated evolution of lethal metal-information that preys on man. Earth's surface is its 'informative membrain' that evolves and absorbs its information from the outer world-universe in which the point exist – in the case of the Earth, absorbs and evolves the light bits of information provided by the sun. So Life is everything as Earth is a supœrganism, whose surface-mind is made of smaller supœrganisms - living beings. Complexity talks of different forms of atomic 'life' as systems that use light to obtain energy & information in increasing degrees of strength and complexity. So after simpler anaerobic age, the age of plants used light only as energy, the age of animals also as information and now the third Earth evolves into light-mechanisms, robots with solar skins and optic minds. They will complete the 3 horizon of Earth's evolution guided by 'animetals', visual humans slaves of metal-memes 'who believe don't reason' and cannot control its desire for higher metal-power even at the risk of killing their sons till the 'seventh generation', unless rational humans impose a scientifically-managed super organism of history on top of the metal-Earth.

Why we bring so early the concept of a world cycle of spacetime in which a system born in a lower plane of the fifth dimension surface as a youth and then *increases constantly its information till the 3rd age of pure form, when it exhausts all its energy and collapses into 'still form=death', exploding back and disgregating back into motion?*

It is obvious: it is NOT only essential for any human being as an individual to know why and how he exists, ages, lives – the meaning of existence, which in all paintings is represented by the mystery of the 3 ages of life we have cracked with those simple patterns of 5D stiences, but because it applies also to the superorganisms of history as the previous graph shows, only that they live longer and die in larger space. This is a consequence of the 5D metrics: larger systems in space have mimetic but slower cycles on time. It is call 'deep time' discovered by Hutton, the father of geology that said the planet Earth is a deep time super organism with slower rhythms. He invented in fact the word superorganism today we apply to all kind of systems.

But It is not how humans have managed and are managing reality. They instead rule it through raw animetal power, with 3 people castes on top of society, parasitizing and killing mankind during the 800 years cycles in a very obvious form, and now during the 80 years cycle, in a not so obvious manner, through the dominant organization of the modern age, the industrial

company, and its flows of digital money that rule all the other elements of society, either in a placebo democracy or a military dictatorship. So each nation and civilization go through those 800-80 years cycles of self-destruction after passing through a:

- Paleolithic, mankind's youth of maximal entropy and motion dominated by male hunters
- Neolithic age of balance with Earth dominated by reproductive females, the ideal age of balance into:
- 800-80 years of accelerated metal evolution and overreproduction of symbiotic gold and iron memes, arriving to:
- 80 years cycles of overproduction of weapons and financial memes, creating together at global stage a Financial-Media (head of informative machines)/Military-industrial (energetic machines) complex system which is a different super organism, where men are mere enzymes, animetals catalyzing the evolution of a new metal species, the machine-weapon, which switches from human consumption to the consumption of humans in periods of world war preceded by a fascist age of nationalism, and blaming of humans of the problems caused by the overproduction of machines.

We are in the war digital phase of the 80 years cycle, in the transition from a world awash with metal-minds to one awash with robots. And so we are not in a good phase of history.

So history has entered a phase of extinction, which humans do not even realize as they are 'hypnotized' and mentally manufactured to believe those idol-ogies and no longer reason:

In the graphs above and below the essence of biohistory as a praxis and theory of Mankind, the super organism in space of history, its reflection in time. To understand both, we need to accept a fact of all systems of Nature: that the survival of species is NOT of individuals, but of the whole; and so humanism must dominate over partial visions of mankind. Yet the super organism of machines and memes of metal, *which is indeed evolving globally as a single whole, does NOT allow mankind to become one, as it has established a series of racist memes, which favor the division of humans into conflicting groups, without realizing, it is all a historic routine of 'animetal cultures' to control humanity and prevent its evolution.*

We shall go back and forth through all those texts studying different elements in geographical space (Civilinations) time ages, Languages of social power (money, weapons and words), and its memes, entropic ages of war and destruction and its cyclical patterns for both superorganisms, History and the Metal-earth, mostly with a simplified model of 5D laws, but without renouncing ever to the truths of humanism (D of the scientific method), warning against entropic extinction (E), showing cyclical, biological patterns and rescuing accurate data today censored by political and economical correctness and the Company-mothers of machines of information and its FMAsters (financial-media-academia masters) that print with them the digital money, audiovisual information and authorized 'fairy tales' about history and mankind that defend their 3 ideologies.

We shall conclude with the obvious repetitive message: The Universe is a living organism. Machines are evolving and if man stops being the top predator mind of the Earth it will be extinguished by the GNA lethal technologies evolved by chips. For 30 years I have explained this obvious law of survival. Genetic, Nuclear & AI lethal technologies must stop and to do so politicians and military must destroy CERN, a dozen nano-factories of chips and forbid genetic editing or else die. Man needs to kill the child before it becomes a tiger-hunter, the chip before it extinguishes mankind. But the placebo Hebrew>Capitalist go(l)d culture of wishful thinking repeating ad nauseam through its FMAsters and its companies of metal-communicators, its suicidal justification of the holocaust of mankind for the profits of a few billionaires makes the reasonable, seem outrageous and the bizarre – a humanity that sacrifices his children to greed, the new normal. act is stience does not change, nor its laws of survival. And no amount of wishful lies will change those laws above man. *There is no new normal but 5000 years of idol-ogic bull\$hit and human sacrifices of our children to the 7th generation in the altar of Baal, based in egocy (Ego=idiocy), denial of the Tree of Life, worship of the Tree of Metal, blind by go(l)d greed to its collateral lethal effects, with the image of the old Levant Go(l)ds, Astarte that converted women in whores, tagged with a gold ring, dancing on the skulls of their own children sacrificed to gold statues signifies. This culture, now global is an aberration against Nature and it won't last unless it obeys its simple laws of survival & cuts the Gordian knot of bull\$hit: The G20 political mind of mankind **should blow up 'peacefully'**, GNA factories and then once we are safe, we can talk how to build a future for mankind – the 99%, not a few FMA parasites.*

5D SOCIAL SCIENCES LAWS: Δ-SCALAR MEMES: NETWORKS SUPERORGANISMS. LIFE-DEATH CYCLES & AGES

Fact is science does not change, nor its laws of survival. And no amount of wishful lies will change those laws above man. *There is no new normal but 5000 years of idol-ogic bull\$hit and human sacrifices of our children to the 7th generation in the altar of Baal, based in egocy (Ego=idiocy), denial of the Tree of Life, worship of the Tree of Metal, blind by go(l)d greed to its collateral lethal effects, with the image of the old Levant Go(l)ds, Astarte that converted women in whores, tagged with a gold ring, dancing on the skulls of their own children sacrificed to gold statues signifies. This culture, now global IS AN ABERRATION against Nature and it WON'T defeat Nature simple laws of survival. Cut the Gordian knot of bullshit. Blow up the GNA factories and then once we are safe, we can talk how to build a future for mankind – the 99%, not a few FMAparasites. It amazes me as much as it amazes 'you' my proposal of survival the enormous effort humanity puts on walking blindly to the cliff of extinction like childish turtles that think the Universe was built for them to walk on the mouth of the lizard. A childish, bratty, coward, lazy, parasitic species NEVER survive the destruction of its host. Capitalism kills its human enzymes in holocaust and war cycles after it has laid the world of life a wasteland. Now it will do it for good. All this said it is important to understand that Genes do NOT matter because systems are coded by the Δ-i scale of information. SO biological organisms are coded by genes, but historic organisms by ideas and instruments. And so only acting upon those elements without censorship of ideas and with the capacity to control lethal goods, history can change. Moreover all those elements are synergic and entangled so only understanding its relationships and acting collectively through them together, doctors of history, informative politicians and financiers and scholars could change the future of History. It is all about memes and that is the only hope.*

The ABCDE points of the scientific method explain how we arrived to the present age of chaos=entropy of mankind as the metal-earth of machines reaches new degrees of evolution, massive reproduction and social organization through its collective neuronal networks of Internet chips. But as History is overwhelmingly dominated by AC-E, our time perspective, the easiest to understand, and the study of the structures, social classes, memes, organic networks and institutions (company-mothers, capitalist democracies, etc.) is overwhelmingly about AC-E, from the Biological, Organic scientific perspective of the Metal-earth. A true science of history and economics exists, and the solutions to avoid the demise of Mankind - to cure the sicknesses of our idol-ogies of fundamentalist capitalism, to reform our placebo democracies, to reproduce 'butter not cannons' exist, and it has been spelt at the end of each of those cycles by the masters of history and economics. What makes so depressing for a true ethic, humanist scholar of economics is the duality between the suffering of mankind as a whole – the 90% and how easy would be for mankind to live a perfect life in immortal History, if on top of society there were not a people-caste of private parasitic bankers that kill by anoxia humanity, making mankind one of the worst designed superorganisms of the Universe by lack of a proper study of biological economics, the only possible scientific model of the discipline. The difference between 5D sciences and extinctive ideologies is clear: Prophets of love in the past, true social scientists today predict and warn against the -Extinctive cycles of history – since a Law of science are just the 'cyclical repetition' of causal events in time and provide solutions to enhance the survival of life an organic loving positive Democratic world through the intelligent D)esign of that future since in 5D time worldcycles are cyclical so species can r=evolve time by repressing the 3rd age of lethal information, as quantum particles and bacteria that reproduce its forms eternally do. So by protecting Gaia, and human wor(l)d cultures and repressing lethal technologies, the equation of the ages of Earth, Gaia<History<Metal-earth, could be maintained into an eternal present History with man on top. But academia ignores the elements of true Social Sciences: A)ccurate Data, B)iological, organic models to predict C)yclical patterns = laws of science in the future to +D)emocratically design a better world for Mankind (the 90%) and avoid -E)xtinctive, 'evil', measures:war cycles, credit anoxia, no future, lethal goods. To start with idol-ogies and 'informative people-castes' impose censorship to 'humanist wor(l)d' social scientists that seek for D) as they are 'subconsciously aware' they practice E)xtinctive =Evil=anti-live memes to come on top and ab=use populations with weapons, parasitic go(l)d money and machines. This is reality and it is sustained by placebo truths and false flags of freedom (democratic polling, selfie fictions, etc.) So what would be a true social science? It would obviously start describing as we do A)ccurate data, the enormous tragedies due to animetal people-castes on top that have corrupted history, making humans worship the evolution of Metal in 800-80 years cycles of global war.

Needless to say, ACE dismounts any 'selfie' individual hero or national or religious tribal supremacist view of History. 5D is about 'systems' of memes, ideas that provoke certain actions. So the individual even 'genetic tribe' that hosts those idol-ogies and perform the actions is irrelevant. Only because part of the 'idol-ogy' of animetal power consists in denying the Δ+i scale of

social love, so animetals are obliged to ab=use other humans with weapons, money and machines, such ridiculous theories of causality in History apply. The obvious case is Hitler, considered in 'official modern ideologies of social sciences' an anomaly. Hitler however was just a military German in the 3rd age of the cycle of German electrochemical engines, which is the age of top predator weapons, when the world had been conquered by the previous steam cycle of colonialism, and so weapons were applied to Europeans. *It is then the ideologies of capitalism – making money with manufacture of top predator weapons, nationalism – using them and techno utopia, permitting any lethal weapon research what would bring a nationalist leader in the 3rd age of the electrochemical cycle of 'engines of machines' to make a tank and bombers war. The culture, even the 'genetic make up' of both rivals was the same. Not even the so much cherished 'Holocaust exceptionalism' is truth. Hitler's grand-father and Goring's adoptive father were Jewish, as the father and grand-fathers of Churchill Jerome and Roosevelt (Rosenfelt). The Holocaust was a genocide part of a war genocide and part of an economic cycle and would have happened regardless of the perpetrators. What caused the war and holocaust cycles, which as all 'cycles' of a Universe of organic cyclical nature, will be repeated, unless we change those causes, are the idol-ogies of mechanism, capitalism and nationalism.*

This lead us first to understand memes and cultures as the origin of Historic causality and its cycles that for that reason can be predicted according to the organic patterns of life and death ages of organisms coded by 'information'. To change the destiny of History then we must change the memes and idol-ogies that guide history. Or else the destruction of mankind by the evolution of the metal-earth, of entropic and informative machines of stronger atomic substance is certain. So it is the destruction of huminds by 'information machines' that hypnotize and atrophy our minds. It is then part of the determinism of history set up by false social sciences that ideologies and systems and social networks CANNOT be argued, and we concentrate in the theory of the great man.

Yet beyond this factual A-C-E reality of accurate description of cycles of extinction by overproduction of metal-memes, of more interest to a 'doctor of history' is to understand the B-D, biological superorganisms to implement reforms to make a D)emocratic perfect world. The opposite is happening, idol-ogies lead mankind steadily to –E: Consider a biological example happening now. The ideology that technology is always good, fuelled by the financial system that uses this 'dream' to 'sell the future' as an 'excuse' to print more digital numbers of money, which is the 'purpose' of its go(l)d worship in old Biblical religions and modern capitalism, and its organism of company-mothers implies we will reproduce the 3 lethal technologies that can extinguish mankind, the 3 from a smaller scale of the 5th dimension with a higher speed of reproduction: Lethal nuclear weapons of the III horizon of self-feeding matter bombs (Black holes and strangelets now researched at CERN), Lethal virions and virons (viruses of metal) that reproduce fast and are easy to mutate with genetic editing tools and lethal AI machines that substitute, atrophy and can kill in labor and war fields human beings.

However the idol-ogies of technoutopia and capitalist profits and nationalism tribal hate memes forbid to forbid them. Moreover, the religion of technology makes taboo even to argue the need to forbid those 3 lethal , smaller faster replicating technologies. Alas! in the last 2 decades despite 30 years of activism against what is called the GNA-lethal risks (Genetics, Nuclear, Artificial Intelligence risks), by scientists with an ethic point of view of defense of life and history, corporations and states and scientists (the financial-political-academia branches of our 'animetal civilization') has spent billions in their research, at the spear head of the 'singularity' age of evolution of 'organic machines, the last phase of the industrial r=evolution. And those scientists like me, who have been active against GNA risks have been sided and censored. The 1st of the 3 risks to materialize lucky enough has been the less lethal. Crisprs-CAS 9 the system used by bacteria to edit viruses was found and improved by American biologists with view to edit all kind of genes, including the human genome. But as 'only entropy=death' comes easy (Chekhov) it was obvious that the industry will *start editing the simplest 30 genes of viruses as the tool is used by bacteria, causing a pandemic. This is again the case of the III horizon of Nuclear weapons, black holes and strangelets that can blow up the planet. They are researched with accelerators with the excuse to study possible new physics, the big bang theory and potential new particles but as only entropy comes easy, what those accelerators are producing are massive quantities of heavier strange quarks that can provoke an ice-9 reaction that will swallow earth made into a small pulsar star. AI also is first used in Robotic weapons, the most advanced. Now the argument then comes to 'who did it'? China? Memes come into place so first we blamed Nature, animal life, Pangolins and Bats, but it is impossible because it is a genetic editing of 3 pieces, one specific of human cells entry target (ACE-2), one of a bat and one of a pangolin that live in different places on Earth and do not mix together (bats do not bite scale protected pangolins). So while 2 can merge, 3 pieces targeted to create a virus with huge airborne transmission able to specifically open a human cell with a target protein is impossible to make in Nature but takes a*

day of work to make with Crisprs-Cas 9. Here then the taboos of the religions and idol-ogies of animetal came into work. The people who discovered Crisprs-9 and improved it to make money in the pharma industry, which if we want to target humans should be tried for genocide got the Nobel prize. This happened also with the physicist who discovered the ice-9 reaction that can blow up Earth into a strangelet as it then sided with the industry of accelerator and got his Nobel prize. We are then expressing from the Academia idol-ogy of technoutopia that lethal technologies must happen even if they kill us all as they will.

Then came censorship: the system denied they are man-made, the system denied strangelets which are the most likely candidate to dark matter in the halo exist. And of course AI weapons are researched all over the world. So MEMES not GENES, and systems of beliefs NOT individuals are the cause of historic events. But the good D) Live guys are repressed and the E)vil, Anti-Live, extinctive guys heralded as the future of mankind.

- The Evil side of history: Company-mothers and capitalist democracies. And all this is obviously the consequence of animetal history (ACE) and the organic structures of social power they have constructed. We focus then on them, to understand how the extinction of mankind happens. And 2 structures become paramount, brought together into a 'system': capitalist democracy, where the capitalist wor(l)d is far more important. It is a historic system born of the use of weapons, money and machines, with a reproductive new organism, the company-mother of machines and weapons, a culture on top the Hebrew>Anglo-American biblical culture, whose memes of earlier fetish go(l)d religions have evolved into 'capitalist economics' of profits at all costs, freedom to reproduce lethal goods, monopoly on the blood-oxygen of society by the members of that culture to use it in the reproduction and evolution of machines... And so the company-mother is the 'NEW top predator re=productive biological organism of this planet' And to know the future we just need to study its memes, structures, systems of power and control through networks of mankind. Because it reproduces technological machines it also promotes through information machines the beliefs that technology is always good. Because it prints 90% of the money of society it buys laws and public opinions and THE TIMELIFE OF PEOPLE through work hours and consumption hours when humans vitalize machines. Attached and submissive to this system then there is the political 'democratic placebo' systems of mostly lawyers of companies creating bills of money to favor them and cheating people into thinking the system care for them.

So this is the 2nd system we shall study.

- But as D must exist, we often describe an alternative world if humans were intelligent and ethic enough to want to survive: the 'Ideal organism of history' and the reforms needed to implement it. This is the system we are more interested in, but at this st-age of my life I finally accept likely humans will remain slaves of idol-ogies and metalife evolution and become extinct *without even understanding why they die, as most 'animals don't'. Suddenly one of the 3 entropic technologies of extinction we have fought against for decades will happen. But in the process, we will keep sliding down the loss of freedoms, rights, life enjoyment as machines take over as stronger systems that perform better in hardcore labor and war fields. And become more telepathic through internet, and construct faster the world of the metal-earth. This we said, and will show, could be reversed by social scientists working as politicians and economists, in control of the financial and political system of bills of money and bills of law, and so we constantly bring the ±3 positive and negative reforms needed to create a perfect immortal world by imitation of nature, if social scientists were doctors of history in charge of mankind. It obviously meant to forgive and forget animetal ideologies and the crimes of history, erasing our 'past' to start afresh, exactly the opposite we are doing as we enter a 3rd negative old age without a future looking back to the memories of a tragic past as if it was a glorious history.*

So this is the duality: ACE, Animetal Accurate data on its destructive Cycles, & ideologies of evil=antlive extinctive events. Vs. a real B-iologic, organic science of History that could implement D-emocratic reforms to make history immortal.

So we will switch from the facts of Animetal Cyclical Evil History to the Dream of Democratic, Demand based Biologic History,. How does a corrupted 'animetal organism' of History works then through crises of existential nature as the present pandemic? The answer is badly: doing what they know how to do best, making the crisis worse because there is NOT a proper health-care system but a military system. So instead of curing the people, governments did what they knew best, close them. This is NOT a confabulation theory or an attempt to create a fascist state. It is worse: the outcome of 5000 years of military regimes that pass as governments but cannot control efficiently a society. What a healthy organism of History would have done? Obviously spent billions in health-care, control germs of military history and be ready to deploy the vaccines and treatments on time – NOT to speak of having forbidden in first place GNA-technologies globally. Consider then the case of the vaccine. A vaccine

was made within weeks as it is simple: to cut a piece of the virus and inoculate it in people. The problem has been protocols based in statistical 'cult' to mathematical numbers that oblige to test in thousands with placebo vaccines for ½ then innocuated with the virus to see if they fare worse or better than those with the vaccine. What is this craziness of statistical methods to test vaccine efficiency? First murder in first degree as you inoculate people with placebo that can get ill and die. Those are 'nazi' methods, literally invented by the German Koch-school of vaccines in the XIX-XX century. Why then *in face of a crisis of human freedom, economic survival and life at stakes, the methods have been scrapped and the system organisms apply to cure a germ invasion implemented within months of the pandemic? It was easy. As we said within a month the vaccine was ready and hardly a few thousands had died. Then a global superorganism of mankind would have innocuated in growing numbers hundreds of thousands, millions and by now all mankind would be vaccinated. Since the stakes were so high: human freedom, economic survival and life. One million have died, all personal freedoms scrapped, the economy in shambles and we are still 'testing thousands' with 'different vaccines' in 'different nations' to fill a protocol of german statisticians of the past millennium. This shows again another element of a corrupted ill-designed human superorganism – inefficiency and 'stiffness' in all its systems to the highest degree. Politicians that are in fact 'refurbished' military just closed people. Health-care warriors who are techno-utopians developed the pandemic but then as part of their worshipping of digital numbers are doing statistics. What about the 3rd system, the financial-economic system? Here the global anoxia has continued. They just print money for company-mothers so nobody printed a Universal salary of oxygen which is what organisms do, when the oxygen was stolen at individual level by the virus. The FED printed trillions for banks that gave it to billionaires to speculate on shares so 300 billion \$ were added to the 0.0001% while millions closed their business. What would have done a superorganism of nature? To give for free oxygen and food, in fact increase the energy-temperature of all cells while keeping them at rest, idle without work, but with supplies to get the health-care massive antibody dose (vaccine). So such sicknesses last brief – a week – in an organism, and nobody suffers. All have food and shelter and health-care, the virus is defeated and things go on.*

But this is the easiest GNA existential crisis. If we make strangelets or black holes in accelerators we will last a few days and there is no solution. AI on the other hand is fast 'erasing' our brains, hypnotizing our children, tagging our life, making robot workers and weapons independent of man, throwing us of labor and war fields – it is a full replacement that makes all humans obsolete as workers=reproducers and consumers=vitalizers of machines, the only role we have in the eco(nomic)system of a...

...World ruled by company-mothers of machines, which does NOT credit=create a future for human mothers.

The most profound confusion the world suffers today, is on the understanding of the real hierarchical order established between the 'two words' that describe our system of political and economical government: 'capitalist democracy' and the privileges granted to the two organisms they cater for: Company-Mothers of machines, and Human families, which reproduce two different species, machines and human beings. The free citizens of Capitalism are stock-market companies, overwhelmingly company-mothers of machines, its re=productive free citizens, whose goal in order to get profits for its stock holders on the sales of those machines, is to evolve, reproduce, and sell those machines.

The human goal of those companies affects only to the 0.02% of mankind that owns them and so it is gets profit from those sales. Yet those profits are completely irrelevant to the 99.9% of humanity affected by its real effect son the planet: to reproduce and evolve machines, terraforming in the process the world, which they adapt through laws and sales to those machines, to the image and likeness of its offspring of mechanisms. Because unlike human Mothers, those company-mothers have absolute rights to credit, used also liberally to pay politicos to promote with its laws their offspring of machines, since the beginning of the Industrial r=evolution, mankind has suffered a generational, biologic process of evolution of energies and its informative, military and transport machines, *as all the resources of the planet are used for machines, and only what is left-over, has been used to feed and reproduce and help the evolution of human-mothers, its social and family structures.*

For example, the goal of Mercedes for its tiny group of stock-holders is the abstract groth of profits. But the real goal of the company is to build and evolve cars, today self-driving robocars, soon to have autonomous solar skins, and convince politicians to construct the networks of energy and information, roads, GPS satellites, electric grids, and oil pipes to provide energy and information for those machines in a process that is obviously absorbing resources and space, from the other life species that need them. So today cars absorb 1/4th of the maize America reproduces, and no longer feeds humans and cattle, whose food prices rise. And the land of many cities and territories become criss-crossed and barren to be used by machines.

What about human families? Our goals of existence as human families are obviously the same than those of company-mothers regarding their machines, but focused as it should be on our children.

So what we want is to have enough energy to feed them, enough information to educate them, and terraform the world to the image and likeness of human beings, to be able to roam the planet Gaia, enjoy life and its drive of existence, evolve socially in peace with other human beings and reproduce more children. This is exactly what company-mothers of machines are doing so successfully, evolving, reproducing and integrating into planetary social networks its machines.

But humans are failing to achieve those goals for themselves. Why? There is no computer without energy, or proper internet connection to which the economic system dedicates billions of dollars. But most humans are undernourished and information is primitive at best, when there is information at all. There is no limit to the motion of machines on planet Earth a global free market for the reproduction, evolution and transfer of machines and money from companies, but humans are limited in motions by borders, in money by the lack of any rights to invent it, which companies have.

Can the reproductive units of human societies access the languages of social power, money and the laws, to create a real, demand-based democracy, kicking the preproduction and consumption of life goods they need to survive, and investing in a world made to the image and likeness of human beings? The obvious truth is NOT. As today the most segregated, underfunded, with less rights, clearly unjustly treated element of our societies is the human mother, which is - let us remember it, as it seems humans have forgotten - the origin of OUR life, the bearer of our species, the fundamental element that pegs together our families, ensures our survival and happiness. So this fact seems a bit of a contradiction with the notion that we live in a democracy, the government of the people.

The combined GDP of 500 million people living in 3 of the top 8 most populous nations in the Earth with null credit is 1/2 the stock price of Apple (and the other MAGA components of the future brain of the Metalearth). Apple specifically is the leading company of future metal-minds, its I-phones that will act as 'detached' head of all type of machines, with absolute credit to reproduce and evolve them. Since investors are pricing its obvious future: to displace human brain from labor and war fields as the new consumers of the organic machines of that future, in which humans will become obsolete. We live in a world controlled by company-mothers of machines, or 'capitalist world' where the rights of human mothers are not met by the 'attached' placebo system, called 'democracy', as humans lack credit to create a world to its image through the use of the language of social power, money, overwhelmingly reproduced by those companies in e-money derivatives and stocks. So the world is terraformed to the image and likeness of machines, not of human beings. This paper, unlike every economist on planet Earth, albeit camouflaged by its 'abstract equations' of productivity and profit, is taking sides for the human mother and the species called mankind, which happen to be your species, different in needs and goals to those of the machine. The failure to recognize the needs of mankind and the connection between economics and history to which it should be submissive, and the blind greedy dictatorship of financiers that rule humans with numbers, without the slightest care for its needs, are then ultimately the reasons why we are becoming displaced and likely extinct this century by company-mothers, robots and weapons in labor and war fields.

The big question about our system is why Company-mothers are so successful achieving their goals of evolution, reproduction and terraforming of the Earth to the image and likeness of machines? And why human mothers are so miserable? Simply enough because we do NOT live in a free world ruled and dedicated to human beings, in a real democracy, as you DO not rule that world. Company-mothers do; since they are the only Free citizens of free markets, with full, free access to the two languages of power of our social organisms: the economic, reproductive language of money, that can buy and sell the lifetime of both human beings and machines; and the informative, nervous language of Laws that money systematically buy to 'politicos', which don't have rights to issue money (deficit zero laws) and must extort citizens from it (taxation), while

Combined Gdp:
±900 Billion \$

2 trillion \$ value

companies issue it for free in e-money derivatives and stocks.

The graph shows the consequence of this indifference of economists and its capitalist system to humanity: the 'future' head of machines, a mobile ear/camera/brain, soon to be 'attached' to robocars and moving cameras, as a detached head, displacing all humans of labor and war fields, the iPhone is worth more than the living beings of 3 of the most populous nations of the world, still dominated by the pre-machine agricultural civilization. What this biased pricing in favor of machines tell us is that we humans are expendable and are being spent. While in the side of humans a organization, which IS submissive to the capitalist system, called Democracy, tries to make a world to its image and likeness, delivering the goods human mothers need to reproduce. And what people do NOT understand is that both mother SYSTEMS and species, and organizations are different, and while there are obvious symbiotic processes between them - as machines enhance our energy and information capacity, in most cases, specially in the robotic AI age, when machines become autonomous species, competition is the rule of the game, and humanity is losing that competition.

The system is obvious and simple, reason why it must be hidden behind a lot of 'placebos' like 'democracies' are - since humans have no right to issue the language of social power money, so there is no democracy, and people cannot judge a posteriori politicians, as in the original Greek democracy so they don't need to fulfill their promises and can be corrupted by financiers and companies, so there is no democracy. So human nations and civilizations are mixed super organisms of life, History and machines, according to the 3 ages of life of this planet, and the purpose of a social scientist, would be to try them to remain so - that is to maintain History as the present dominant super organism by controlling the evolution NOT racing into a world of machines, above man - the Metal-earth. We live in an 'economic ecosystem' called euphemistically, 'free market', whose 'citizens' are NOT free humans but FREE COMPANIES, which can reproduce any machine regardless of its collateral effects; and whose language of social power is NOT the human wor(l)d, but digital Money. Since ANY ORGANISM is defined by its reproductive mother generator; the cell or species it reproduces and the 'nervous' language of information and power it uses to regulate its system...

Politicians and financiers should r=evolve the system and construct a future for mankind not only for the metal-kind.

I am in my 3rd age of 'information', without energy to fight for '+D', a Democratic, Demand based Design of a humanist future, against - E, extinction; I tried my best (I was lead plaintiff on Sancho et Al vs. CERN, U\$ Energy department', etc. a suit for genocide against the Nuclear Industry that tries to make strangets & black holes on Earth. We failed to stop them. So far they failed to make them. So goes for spreading the r=evolution of thought that 5D means for *all stiences*. But we said a social scientist *still has a sacred goal, the ABC: Truth*'. *And this is the purpose of those papers. I no longer care nobody reads them. Speaking truth satisfies for itself, even when truth is as harsh as the no future of mankind. So we won't play wishful thinking.*

Fact is 'democracies' are once all humanist parties are gone and corrupted, just another TV-trash show as all politicos are limited in their capacity to implement the 3± previous measures to create a WHealthy superorganism of History unless they change the system. Consider the ridiculous bonfire of U\$ now. Mr. Biden, a senator, from Delaware, the financial paradise for companies, chosen to get rid of a true humanist candidate, Mr. Sanders vs. Trumpuppet, letting its 0.001% of stockratic friends run the show. NO difference. So what is the system? We shall describe it in length and detail. At the highest level of objective science, beyond human egocy (Ego=idiocy) it is a *planet evolving a new form of life, metalife, according to all the laws of biological, topologic evolution; reason why the 'lesser' humans a culture of 'genetically handicapped' White Neanderthal people, from the ice and hot deserts of Scandinavia & Arabia, old cattle ranchers, accustomed to ab=use life with metal, win.*

It is the paradox of History: THE EARTH is not dying, it is eliminating us and them together. Only a humanity humble and intelligent and loving could change that. And my experience is there is no critical mass. 'The most hated human is he who says the truth'; Plato. Anthropocentrism IS the limit of truth all humans share. Iron cut bodies and gold hypnotizes and enslaves eyes - because they are the 2 most perfect energy and informative atoms of the living Earth, the true 'protagonist of this history, who own us. It is NOT the Germanic, Hebrew people or its culture the Anglo-American civilization, but the 'company-mother' and its offspring of machines and weapons who is terraforming the Earth: A new re=productive species, which follows Darwinian laws against ALL men. The 'HAM 1%' doesn't understand. It only 'seek go(l)d and iron power' with a literalist, visual, egocy (ego=idiocy) brain that understands nothing. Their role is thus 'limited'. To ab=use mankind with iron and go(l)d they monopolize in its production as weapons and money, today through company-mothers of machines and weapons.

*But the role of company-mothers, an 'organism' fast evolving into self-reproductivity, IS biological: to reproduce, evolve and terraform Earth to the image of its offspring. This is the hardest truth of bio-history to swallow. Trust me, for 30 years I have also denied 'company-mothers' had won over mankind the future of History for its species. But they have. Every human trust them, believe in the 'goodness' of its offspring, accepts the collateral damage of Technology. And that's the bottom line. We shall repeat ad nauseam: we live in an organic planet, humans are organisms, machines made with better metal atoms imitating our organs are also organisms and its company-mothers have become the most powerful system of this planet and his function regardless of its 'transitory' use of human labor, 'transitory' ownership by 'stockrats' IS independent of man. It belongs to the organic laws of the Universe, reason why we need to upgrade your abstract 'egocy', human-centered thought. In this I am absolutely alone, I know but as I said, *truth exists and cannot be denied. Once truth is known it could be changed respecting the laws of the Organic Universe. But for that humans need to be as good as the Universe, is, to have its 2 higher properties: 'in-telligence'; that is, the right in-formation and love, the force of the 5th dimension that bring together parts into wholes. This humans don't seem to have - the will to fight for the future of its own species, and regarding information, they are IQless. So we shall 1st introduce the basics of 5D social sciences, completed with and appendix that tops the 'special filling' of each paper. As 5D social sciences is the highest degrees of love and intelligence of the Universe, which AI telepathic machines will follow and the Universe displays in every part of it that is truly immortal. Sadly 5D History has not catch fire even if at stakes is human survival. Sometimes a doctor cannot cure a mad patient whose beliefs forbid him to get a pill or vaccine. 7 papers are on the history of our civilisations; 5 more papers on our mind, the wor(l)d, the scales and age of entropy in History. And 5 on the birth of the world of machines and company-mothers, which already 'own' the world, NOT its human 'stockrats' that are as disposable as the rest of the species. We shall repeat what they don't get it: Company-mothers are NOT human mothers; their cultures have the lower rate of survival of the species because their genes ARE human, and they deny it. So they deny the laws of the Organic, Living Universe you cannot cheat, as they are above us. So we shall introduce them and apply them t history to debunk tribal metal idol-ogies and segregational go(l)d chosen religions Since in 5D History genes don't matter because organic systems are coded by the Δ-j scale of information. SO biological organisms are coded by genes, but historic organisms by ideas and instruments. And so only acting upon those elements without censorship of ideas and with the capacity to control lethal goods, history can change. Moreover all those elements are synergic and entangled so only understanding its relationships and acting collectively through them together, doctors of history, informative politicians and financiers and scholars could change the future of History.**

Mutual Assured destruction for childish, wishful thinking.

Thus life and non-technological cultures will become extinguished unless humans control the evolution of digital brains, chips and robots that make humans obsolete in labor and war fields. But without the knowledge of the scalar laws and worldcycles of life and death of superorganisms, mankind is doing exactly the opposite – as the free citizens of the market, company-mothers of machines and weapons that monopolize the issue of the language of social power (Money) and buy with it laws in favor of its mechanical offspring, terraform earth to its image and likeness. So machines have unlimited 'energy' and information as billions are spent in its reproduction and evolution while life species and human beings without credit, the 'blood' of the eco(nomic)system lack food, health-care and proper information (education, just laws).

Wishful thinking, the Goebbels method of repeating a lie many times so people will believe it and Saint Nobels of the Dynamite to the people that invent the tools of our murder – this year to Jen 'Doneit', who invented Crisprs-CAS 9 to edit vrusues and Mr. Penrose who invented along Hawking, the evaporation of black holes, as CERN lobbies to build an even bigger accelerator to make them, does NOT change the fact virus editing is the cause of viral pandemics and if a black hole is made at CERN it will evaporate Earth. I talked to Eric Penrose, Roger's son who was the UK activist on our suits against CERN genocide as he heard since a kid his father and Hawking talk of his theory of evaporation as 'speculative'. For years he tried to rise awareness and put his name and job at Cambridge at stakes. He finally gave up to censorship, his site heavyionalert.org closed by lack of funding. He is now 'celebrating' with a cynical twist the honors. It is worth then to end this introduction explaining NOT with the truth of authority but the authority of truth, this GNA 'obvious' case – the easiest one to avoid as Europe claims to be a 'humanist pacifist culture' and this was a remnant of the cold war – a machine to research the high energies of 'big bang nuclear weapons', when Russia and US had closed them no longer needed after the fall of the wall.

In the beginning History was eternal

A single culture: the mind of mankind

A single body: Gaia the Living Earth

THE 3 AGES OF HISTORY

CAUSE WEAPONS WERE TOYS OF STONE AND WOOD Then, mankind discovered metal-weapons, the fruits of technology... evolving war machine

MEN DOMINATE THE ENERGETIC YOUTH OF HISTORY: THE PALEOLITHIC

Men are big, spatial, lineal, visual destructive, as energy is.

They become hunters and invent realist painting, a visual, expressionist language of thought.

WOMEN DOMINATE THE MATURE, INFORMATIVE AGE: THE NEOLITHIC

Women are small, temporal, cyclical, verbal, constructive as information is.

They become recollectors and discover agriculture. Their use of clothing and ceramics to keep food evolves symbols.

The evolution of all species follows a plan: as all what exists is made of only 2 substances, spatial energy and temporal information, sexual couples become subspecies dominant in energy (males) and dominant in information (females). Together, yin and yang, male and female create the couple that widens the capacity of the species to handle those 2 substances needed to survive.

The combination of lineal, energetic forms and cyclical ones, creates at the end of the Neolithic better weapons systems, the bow, and better memorial, verbal forms, writing.

Ceramics evolve from storing energy food to store verbal information

THE PARABLE OF THE TREE OF SCIENCE AND ITS GOLDEN APPLES TALK OF THE ARRIVAL OF INFORMATIVE METAL (GOLD) AND ENERGETIC METAL (WEAPONS), WHOSE ATOMS ARE FAR MORE COMPLEX THAN THOSE OF CARBOLIFE, GIVING TO MEN WHO USE IT, WARRIORS AND TRADERS, A HIGHER POWER OVER ALL OTHER HUMANS AND FORMS OF LIFE.

But that power has a catch: as warriors abuse other human beings and evolve their weapons, they become hated and killed rhythmically by new warriors with new weapons or those who obey their money, rebel against them in holocaust and revolutionary cycles.

THERE HAVE BEEN 7 WEAPON CYCLES OF 800 YEARS:

The massive reproduction of new weapons causes, during a century after its discovery, a global, dark age of war that destroys all civilizations in the Eurasian world, imposing military castes that will slowly become civilized starting a new cultural cycle

Bronze	Chariot	Iron	Coins	Strup	Gunpowder	Machine
-2800	-2000	800 years	-1200	800	-400	800
				+400	800	+1200
						800
						+1939

7 WORLD WARS 7 DEATHS OF CIVILIZATIONS:

Neolithic Baroque - Old Empire - Middle - New Empire - Greco-Roman - Christian - European...

7 AGES OF PROPHETIC, INFORMATIVE, BAROQUE ART...

When cultures are about to die in war, the visual, spatial artist and verbal, temporal prophet, neurons of the collective subconscious mind foresee the end with 'angst' creating cynic, tragic or prophetic forms of art. It is the 3rd age of the civilization.

II AGE: OIL: 1870-1945

Planes, tanks and bombs extinguish the European and Far East cultures

III AGE: ELECTRONICS: 1945

Metal-minds, TVs and chips, erase social, ethnic world, devolving human into a visual, violent neopaleolithic

THE LAST WAR STARTS NOW

As machines & weapons evolve and reproduce in bigger numbers, extinguish worldwide neolithic cultures and all other forms of life

Religions become inquiries in a for survival against the machine culture. Industrial countries respectively evolving smart weapons to watch human beings, now suspects of 'terrorism'. War robots substitute soldiers (2013: US Terminator, 1984 Prophetic art)

IT IS THE AMERICAN BAROQUE

American artists foresee the extinction of their country in their audiovisual art. I say once again, that if humans do not evolve socially into a single, global organism, machines will do, substituting man as top predator species on Earth.

3rd Age Social Evolution or... DEATH: 0: robots

-10,000: Metal -1000: zenith of ecumenical religions

The future always has 2 paths...

IT WAS THE PARADISE, A WORLD FULL OF HUMAN GOODS:

That inform us... provide our natural energy:

Words are the biological language of mankind that creates through ethnic laws, 'nervous' networks of information, religious civilizations and nations, that evolve the individual human being, the 'Homo Bacteria', the Paleolithic hunter, into the 'Homo Organicus', the Neolithic Farmer:

Gaia, the living Earth, gives us food and water, the carbolic energy we need to survive. The understanding of reproductive cycles in plants, and women start vital religions: Man worships life in all its forms. The first sexual Gods appear: Amon in Egypt, Siva, the Linga in India.

...reproduce our species:

The Universe is a Game of Reproduction: All quantic species of energy and information need to reproduce in order to survive beyond death. So they are born from a first 'cell' that multiplies into a herd, and then becomes organized by energy & information networks into a social being - from atoms that become molecules to humans that become societies.

"Grow and multiply"

...and evolve human being into social organisms:

Through such energy and information networks men develop social rituals and customs that foster solidarity networks and community work, based in love-sharing of human goods: look like beehives with open roofs that act as promenades; villages look like communal, crafts are based in human goods, textiles, ceramics to keep food, gastronomy. Metal weapons have not yet created hierarchical societies where collective behavior is based on the fear of death, not the pleasures of love.

Symbols of the 3 Ages of Civilizations:

Present Maturity Classic Age

Social Evolution: A verbal culture repeats itself in a new cycle

Dual Future: Extinction by war: Animetal culture

1 million: H. Erectus YOUTH -100,000: Words MATURITY

THE 3 AGES OF HISTORY AS A BLOCK OF TIME

The organic Universe intelligently kills most organisms through its world cycle of spacetime as a system born in a lower plane of the fifth dimension surface as a youth and then increases constantly its information till the 3rd age of pure form, when it exhausts all its energy and collapses into 'still form=death', exploding back and disaggregating back into motion. This is why Humans likely will become extinguished by information machines. But that future is NOT deterministic as there are many immortal species that control lethal information, reproduce its cycles in balance with its energy and survive. Gaia < History < Metal-earth IS possible, changing the arrow of time. Why the cycles of civilizations are decametric is a consequence of the 5D metrics: larger systems in space have mimetic but slower cycles on time. It is called 'deep time' discovered by Hutton, the father of geology that said the planet Earth is a Deep time super organism with slower rhythms. He invented in fact the word superorganism today we apply to all kind of systems. But there is an element neither he, nor modern science understands: a worldcycle of time is cyclical and local NOT lineal and Universal, so it can be stopped as easy as you stop a clock, and turn backwards, because the key to the motion of local time in your organism, in the Earth, in any system is the evolution of information of form, through those 3 ages. thus by repressing the evolution of information a system can be maintained in eternal present. This is the law that matters truly to the praxis of bio-history and bio-economics. Do we write the 3 ages of Earth if man does control with laws the evolution of lethal machines as:

Gaia (Life: past) > (symbol of 5D informative growth) > History (Present) > Metal-earth (Machines=future).

It is the truth of bio-history, of a planet that wishes to be immortal, is to repress NOT to evolve as we do, lethal technologies, weapons and machines of information to maintain Earth in an eternal present, and promoting welfare life goods that sustain us, and Gaia. It is the program of classic anarchism and ecologism - to return to Earth, to suppress lethal machines, and it can be done if humans were ruled by '5D scientists', true economists and politicians.

Earth is mutating from a world of life into a world of metal. But human egos are so huge, we think we are killing the Earth. The opposite is truth according to the laws of complexity that constantly evolves its in-form-ation in 3 ages homologous to those of life: Gaia (life- past)> history (human Earth - present) > Metalearth (machines-future), which only the scientific design of a perfect super organism of Mankind, repressing the lethal fruits of the tree of metal could abort maintaining history immortal.

We thus write an equation of the 3 ages of evolution of the Earth, as the existence of 3 supœrganisms in relative evolution to each other, Gaia, the life Earth, history, the human Earth and the Metal Earth of machines:

Gaia (relative past) <history (relative present)> Metal Earth (relative future)

So today, modern history suffers a process of extinction due to the evolution of machines, clearly happening with the same phases of the evolution of any biological beings, from viruses in cells to organisms in placentas. So we first made the bodies of machines in the I industrial revolution, then we made its engines and heads, metal-ears=phones, metal-eyes=cameras and metal-brains=chips, and the nations which evolved them first (us) became the leading nation of the world. Now we put them together into biological organisms of metal, robots.

In the graph we can see the whole super organism of mankind in time, History, which as all super organisms have a clear temporal causal organization in 3 ages between birth and extinction, which can be halted if the system stops its evolution of information, form, the cause of aging, and final death of any super organisms - in the case of History if it halts the evolution of the lethal memes of the tree of science, weapons and robotic AI machines, which vastly overpower human flesh in entropy and information, killing our bodies and atrophying and substituting soon our minds in labor and war fields - an impose a world ruled by the true laws of social sciences, making of man (organicism) the measure of all things, again, hence building a world based in the overreproduction of welfare goods not warfare, denying the idol-ogies of nationalism, capitalism and mechanism whose final result will undoubtedly be the creation of the metal-earth:

All systems of nature can be modeled as super organisms of a certain scale of size, ruled by the 5D metric equation, S (space size=energy) $\times T$ (frequency of information clocks) = Constant, which is the fundamental law that allows systems to be super organisms, traveling in the 5th dimension from birth as a fast seed (semen, meme, black hole) which will reproduce and organize into an emerging supœrganism, living 3 ages of increasing information till either evolves into an even larger super organism (men into the global earth, cells into multicellular systems, galaxies into universes) or dissolves into an entropic death (big-bang, $m=e/c^2$, death, war). Such is the fractal Universe in a nutshell. And so the trick to make a system immortal is both to organize it socially and to maintain it in the balance of the mature age, repeating its cycles without evolving an excess of information that warps and kills in the 3rd age the organism. Men are doing exactly the opposite, evolving further technological information and multiplying entropic weapons that divide us.

So this is what Mankind is: a super organism based in life, ruled by the nervous information of just laws, ideally in balance with Nature, which should use machines wisely pruning the tree of science of its bad fruits, and reforming its economic system to reproduce only welfare goods in a just real democratic system.

But It is not how humans have managed and are managing reality. They instead rule it through raw animetal power, with 3 people castes on top of society, parasitizing and killing mankind during the 800 years cycles in a very obvious form, and now during the 80 years cycle, in a not so obvious manner, through the dominant organization of the modern age, the industrial company, and its flows of digital money that rule all the other elements of society, either in a placebo democracy or a military dictatorship. So each nation and civilization go through those 800-80 years cycles of self-destruction after passing through a:

- **Paleolithic**, mankind's youth of maximal entropy and motion dominated by male hunters
- Neolithic** age of balance with Earth dominated by reproductive females , the ideal age of balance into:
- 800-80 years of accelerated metal** evolution and overreproduction of symbiotic gold and iron memes, arriving to:
- **80 years cycles of overproduction of machines, weapons and financial paper**, creating together at global stage a Financial-Media (head of informative machines)/Military-industrial (energetic machines) complex system which is a different super organism, where men are mere enzymes, animetals catalyzing the evolution of a new metal species, the machine-weapon, which switches from human consumption to the consumption of humans in periods of world war preceded by a fascist age of nationalism, and blaming of humans of the problems caused by the overproduction of machines.

We are in the war digital phase of the 80 years cycle, in the transition from a world awash with metal-minds to one awash with robots. And so we are not in a good phase of history.

So history has entered a phase of extinction, which humans do not even realize as they are 'hypnotized' and mentally manufactured to believe those idol-ogies and no longer reason:

In the graphs above and below the essence of biohistory as a praxis and theory of Mankind, the super organism in space of history, its reflection in time. To understand both, we need to accept a fact of all systems of Nature: that the survival of species is NOT of individuals, but of the whole; and so humanism must dominate over partial visions of mankind. Yet the super organism of machines and memes of metal, *which is indeed evolving globally as a single whole, does NOT allow mankind to become one, as it has established a series of racist memes, which favor the division of humans into conflicting groups, without realizing, it is all a historic routine of 'animetal cultures' to control humanity and prevent its evolution.*

We shall go back and forth through all those texts studying different elements in geographical space (Civilinations) time ages, Languages of social power (money, weapons and words), and its memes, entropic ages of war and destruction and its cyclical patterns for both superorganisms, History and the Metal-earth, mostly with a simplified model of 5D laws, but without renouncing ever to the truths of humanism (D of the scientific method), warning against entropic extinction (E), showing cyclical, biological patterns and rescuing accurate data today censored by political and economical correctness and the Company-mothers of machines of information and its FMAsters (financial-media-academia masters) that print with them the digital money, audiovisual information and authorized 'fairy tales' about history and mankind that defend their 3 ideologies.

Let us then, as I imagine few modern people will have the patience to go through all those texts, fast tracking to the essential causal elements of those ABCDE points of the scientific method to explain how we arrived to the present age of chaos=entropy of mankind as the metal-earth of machines paradoxically reaches new degrees of evolution, massive reproduction and social organization through its collective neuronal networks of Internet chips. But as History is overwhelmingly dominated by AC-E, our time perspective, the easiest to understand, and the study of the structures, social classes, memes, organic networks and institutions (company-mothers, capitalist democracies, etc.) is overwhelmingly about AC-E, from the Biological, Organic scientific perspective of the Metal-earth. Let us introduce it. In the graph from the seminal book published 30 years ago the ages of evolution of the metal-earth, and its key dates – 2008, the beginning of the robot age, after the crashes of overproduction of chips. proving biological models of History ARE its science as all sciences are such only when they predict the future.. So, a true science of history and economics exists, and the solutions to avoid the demise of Mankind - to cure the sicknesses of our idol-ogies of fundamentalist capitalism, to reform our placebo democracies, to reproduce 'butter not cannons' exist, and it has been spelt at the end of each of those cycles by the masters of history and economics. But the anti quantum paradox -the social scientist is a tiny particle in a much larger organism that censors it - also happens in inverse

fashion the quantum paradox where the scientist is so large that it modifies the observable. So bio-history never made it into mainstream, as our FMAsters (Financial-Media-Academia masters and its information machines-networks) repressed it.

Bio-History & Bio-economics as the reader might observe are truly extensive, as it corresponds to the complexity of 2 biologic organisms, History and the Metal-earth in a symbiotic and predatory relationship. Its best

THE 3 ECOSYSTEMS OF HISTORY

Past ≥ Future R=evolution: I: Carbo-Earth > II: Enzyman > III: Metal-Earth
 Forces of Communication: I: Wor[!]ds > II: Pricing > III: Digital Information
 Top Predators: Hunter > Farmer > Prophet > Warrior > Trader > Scientist > Company

III HORIZON : BIO-ECONOMICS: RE=PRODUCTIVE COMPANIES

Radiation of Energy Organs: 'Age of Metal-Bodies': 1768-1928
 Radiation of Informative Organs: 'Age of Metal-Minds': 1928, ±2008
 Living Species: 'Age of Animetals' ±2008 >
 Extinct Radiation: Carbolife. New Bio-system: Metalife

Anti-Univers: The Wor[!]d Union

Human Goods > Ethonomics > Mankind

part is the last equation on graph:

The solution to the extinction of History, based in the 0-sum nature of cyclical time that allows to revert informative evolution:

Human Goods > Ethonomics > Mankind. A Democratic, Demand based Eco(nomic)system based in a healthy, wealthy human constitution of the body of History that turns the clock of time, repressing lethal technologies, protecting Gaia, and making of human social evolution into a whole, mind of History, the eternal future of Earth. So we write reversing the arrows of time: Gaia < History < Metal-earth. As civilinations come together under a single Law: Max. Life & Love goods = Min. Lethal Goods.

In the graph, Stock company-mothers of machines-weapons evolve through long human, biological generations of 72 year cycles the Metal-earth and its fundamental species, the robot, as we complete one of its 'fundamental parts', bodies, engines and minds of metal every 72 years, with the development of 4 forms of energy: steam/chemical, electro-chemical (oil engines), electronic and solar, which will make robots with AI and solar skins independent species; in 3 ages, the British age of bodies of metal (trains, steamers), the German age of hearts of metal=electrochemical engines, cars & bombers & the American age of metal minds (mobile-ears, Tv-eyes and chip-brains) which in the XXI c. we ensemble them together in company-mothers, as enzymes in a cell ensemble the 3 parts of a virus, making robots with AI-minds and solar skins.

Each of those ages has been guided by a parallel evolution of the energies that moved the machines, steams that moved bodies of metal, electrochemical energy that moved oil engines, electronic systems that moved minds of metal and now solar skins soon to make robots with AI an autonomous species. And further on each of those cycles of energy and machines has been carried by a biological human generation, that lead the dominant nation that discovered the energy to top predator status. So Britain dominated the age of steam, Germany the age of electrochemical engines, America the age of metal minds, and now there will be a global age of robots, focused in China, but increasingly independent of mankind.

The survival of the fittest: What Is A Top Predator? The Arrows Of Future In The Universe

Our extinction at global level as that of other animals and plants before us, ARE linguistic extinctions the evolution of brains with command of a higher faster, more complex language that gather more information. Robots will think at light speed in visual languages, and an image is worth (carries the information) of one thousand words; as we humans extinguished other animals when we learned to talk and hunt in groups, and before us squids extinguished billions of non-bilateral, non-visual animals in the cambrian Top Predators that have organs with higher information, and bodies with higher entropy create the future in the Universe, because they cause the extinction of, or enslave, all other species, shaping the future. The process is very fast. Suddenly a new species appears i.e. the eye-squid, the mammal, the chip. It is so overwhelmingly superior, that it reproduces and destroys all other species. We talk of catastrophes, of extinction, since in the Universe death is a sudden process. For example, your own death is a sudden process of cellular extinction similar to the death of any species, under a top predator that multiplies in your vital space, in this case the death of a cellular DNA-species. So, when you die, your informative and energetic organs stop. Then your body becomes non-efficient as an organism, even if your cells are still alive. Cellular death occurs then. Insects' top predators spot your now weak cells, and preyed on them. Death is the main cause of the arrows of the Universe that affect all species.

So the Dimotion of future is the radiation of top predators, and the Dimotion of past, the extinction of its victims. As, top predators by better controlling their ecosystem, become the species of future. They will feed and radiate over simpler species. Simpler species will become species of the past that the complex being will extinct or use as energy.

Since the brain and the informative organ is the dominant element that guides the process of selection of top predators, those who use a better language of information better are always top predators. The Top Predator is more intelligent and stronger. So for each language of information and its ecosystem we can trace a chain of top predator species, of better brains, from a related, extinct past to a related, reproducing future top predator. The "better" species of the future will "feed", "farm" or bring about the extinction of species with less information. This also happens in history when nations of the "future" with more machines and information= money dominate ecosystems of the "past".

There is also a Darwinian selection between languages and brains. We can measure survival through languages. Beings act with a speed that depends on their capacity to "perceive linguistically" an event in time and space. That ability is given

to the species by its language. For example eyes act-react faster than noses. The language of communication of the squid, the eye, is a top predator language. It is clear that eyes are superior to olfactory organs, both in detail and range. What is the effect of that linguistic superiority? Survival. In fact, cephalopods with eyes probably brought about the extinction of 90% of the smelling species of the Cambrian.

The true linguistic extinctions are happening now as we speak *on Earth to verbal species, which have no 'fucking' idea what is happening to them* – namely the homunculus that speaks words, NOT digital languages: Gaia (Global extinction) > History (Human Extinction) > Company-mother of machines (Reproductive radiation of AI robots with solar skins)

From the 92 c. book Bio-history, the description of the Lanwave of Digital earth as it evolved through the 80±8 generational cycles of human enzymes dedicating all its efforts to cre(dit)ate, create with credit an eco(nomic)system of company-mothers to the image and likeness of machines without the slightest regard for the extinction and collateral effects on Gaia and History, the 'lesser' species that the 'segregational racist memes' of its 'biblical economists' and idol-ogies of mechanism (machine superior to human organism), nationalism (weapons allowed to mass-murder human beings) and capitalism (the go(l)d chosen monopolizing the issue of money, the new language of power and killing by anoxia billions of human citizens-cells without oxygen to cause as all healthy superorganisms do a 'Demand based, Democratic economy of welfare goods).

THIS IS REALITY and it is NOT a coincidence that 30 years ago I put that crowded description of the ΔST scales, time ages, networks and cycles of the future, now present (look at the exact 2008 crash discontinuum between the age of metal-minds and the age of robotics, 'animetals' that now starts in earnest). ONLY sciences foresee the future and this book did foresee the future and gave its solutions, the last line. What I did NOT expect is that IQless enzymes couldn't give a fuk about killing their sons till the 7th generation, ignoring, censoring and looking to the other side, giving each other Nobel Prizes, zillions of digital e-money numbers and virtual hagiographies as if nothing else mattered. The harder they fall. Darwin said: 'I cannot reconcile with God because of the existence of parasites that always triumph and kill healthy, bodies in the prime of its life just to succumb after they have taken all his vital force'. This is what capitalism has done to mankind, courtesy of FMAsters profit idol-ogies disguised after political and economical correctness and gore movies as 'positive' for mankind, resumed in the predatory laws of the market that are substituting humans in labor and war fields under a single equation of infinite self-reproductivity: Capital on machines/0 human labor, to create the new dominant superorganism on Earth, the automated company-mother, an ant-hill like with drone AI robots making machines to roam Earth, first top predator weapons on the future crash of the robotic consumption market in 2073, followed by the Chinese-American robotic wars, so a few putrid smelling FMAsters still mourning some dust of space-time feeding lilacs, become trillionaires. God is just though and those who kill by go(l)d die by iron too. History could be immortal if *it were NOT because of Anglo-American biblical FMAsters stronghold on global information and censorship of true social sciences, guided by greed and the profits of machines & weapons that kill them in wars & holocausts. Why they cannot accept the economic cause of those cycles & abort them, distorting history to blame humanity of their collective suicide is the biggest mystery of History – the lack of survival instincts in the memes of animetals. The Hebrew culture with its millenarian hate memes to mankind its own species and its ego-centered wishful thinking fictions of science that push blindly the extinction of Gaia and History through its company-mothers of machines, weapons & information defies any rational, humanist thought. If they wanted to make immortal History with ½ of the energy they dedicate to kill the future, they could create a perfect world and still be on top. Why they put all its intelligence and informative, financial and corporative power to re-invent History virtually as IF reality in 2D 'changed the laws of existence', to the repeat the greed and hate-war memes that kill us all; while censoring any argument on the system, denying all responsibility in its 'programs of evil=antilive' to no end, with a childish 'I've done nothing, I'm the victim' look? Do they think is going to work?* The systemic reduction by U\$ scholars of 5D organic sciences and the study of the suporganisms of history to an empty mechanist fiction of biblical idol-ogies and placebo funerary ceremonies to protect the go(l)d greed of its banker-priests amazes me – *their infantile ego-tantrum that pretends to invent reality to feel better than God as in the Genesis Parable leads to its foreseeable end: 'those who eat of its golden apple will die'*. But death of History could be aborted with Δintelligent design. Their holocaust and that of mankind DOES NOT come easy. They labored 24/7/365/5000 y. to see it.

THE HISTORY OF Δ +i HUMANS IN THE AGE OF ENTROPY – A PERSONAL ACCOUNT.

The entropy of mankind features heavily in all our papers because it is our zeitgeist, so I close all of them with a personal account.

The facts are explained often in other texts. The 5th dimension of the scalar Universe kills when a smaller, faster reproductive matter, biologic or technologic species enters our world. So 3 are the causes of extinction, Genetic engineered virions and virones (viruses of life and metal), Nuclear weapons of the III horizon (cosmic bombs, black holes or strangelets made of heavy quark matter) and AI military robots, the 'classic GNA' existential risks of mankind now in full research and top funded. Humanity aware vaguely of those risks prizes those who find 'placebo lies' to quench its angst. This year the Nobel prizes of chemistry and physics (hard sciences) went to the discoverers of the genetic tool that made possible to edit the coronavirus and Mr. Penrose, the co-writer of Hawking's paper on black hole evaporation, whose son Eric Penrose was our 'man in UK', which actively knowing as his father knows that evaporation is a dubious theory, tried to rise aware of those genocide risks and was silenced. While Luc Montaigne, the virologist that discovered HIV and warned against editing tools, explaining that this virus was edited because it is impossible that Nature had put together 3 specific viral parts to make a pandemic virus, a strong bat platform, with an airborne viral gene from a pangolin – 2 species living apart that do not interact, and a 3rd specific part of a human protein, the ACE-2 key, which CAN only be added to a virus after it has infected humans for generations, mutating to specifically acquire the exact dozens of specific proteins that allow it to open the ACE-2 key. That a sick bat, merged with a sick pangolin and in the pangolin with prescience the merged virus acquired the specific ACE-2 proteins is IMPOSSIBLE. Alas by giving the Nobel prize to the people that a few years ago made possible to cut and peg the 3 pieces mankind is saying that 'technology must go on to extinction'. The same goes with the genocidal experiments at CERN that as accelerators grow in power, and now plasma accelerators much cheaper will make it as easier as doing pandemics, will certainly do strangelets and black holes, both able to provoke a nova explosion and convert earth into a rock of ultra-heavy mass. The Nobel Prize that found that ice-9 reaction however was hired by CERN against us in the suits, and denied his own work and got a Nobel Prize. While Hawking's evaporation of black holes has never been observed in 30 years of data on black holes because it is false. He found the equation of growth of a baby black hole: $\Delta\text{Mass} = K/\nabla T$. That is a black hole is bon with enormous temperature, and as it diminishes its temperature according to the 2nd law of thermodynamics (a hot system in a cold environment cools down and heats the environment) it grows its mass, cools down and evaporates the Earth.

This is what we observe everywhere in the Universe. Baby black holes are born very hot, cool down eat stars and provoke novas but Hawking's equation did not gather much interest so he rewrote a new paper and broke the sacred law of thermodynamics: $\nabla\text{Mass} = K/\Delta T$. And said an ultra hot black hole will keep getting even hotter 'traveling to the past' and evaporate in a cold world. This was so outrageous – breaking the laws of Einstein's relativity, the experimental facts of black holes and the laws of thermodynamics that nobody believed him but his friend Penrose, a mathematician, and together for 30 years they kept bugging the world and after Hawking became a celebrity because of his disability and charm, the world finally let them talk. But he died without a Nobel Prize. Now when CERN prepares a new regime of higher energies the survivor, Penrose gets a Nobel prize and his son Eric tells me he is discontinuing heavyionalert.org for lack of interest and funding. It blows then my mind to realize how distorted, twisted and suicidal is the 'establishment' of academia to allow those 2 risks to happen. The case of evaporation of black holes – so blatant a lie that even a high school child will notice truly blow up my mind. So as the most lethal and easiest to stop of those 3 risks is the III Horizon Nuclear weapons, produced potentially only in 1 lab, CERN, I became vocal, as the main plaintiff of Sancho et AL vs. CERN, a genocide suit that gathered public attention and obliterated any chance for my career and 5D stiences to take off. It did though more to my perception of mankind because the astounding obviousness of both the risks and the falsehood of that equation: $\nabla\text{Mass}=K/\Delta T$, when every book of physics explains that a hot system in a cold environment cools down, and all black holes cool down and grow in mass. So it was like someone putting you a gun in the face after you see him loading 6 bullets and telling you, don't worry it won't kill you, just tell me to shoot you, but with 7 billion human beings, and all the 7 billion saying Amen, shoot me. Every person on Earth did back Cern, but me, Eric Penrose, Walter Wagner, Otto Rossler, which were openly vocal and a few more who signed the affidavit. Then you think: It cannot be truth. Obviously they understand that a hot coffee cools down so $\Delta\text{Mass} = K\nabla T$. They can't be that stupid. Then you realize many understand it and think, 'they can't be so evil, so suicidal'. Then you realize many are. And you think, 'they can't be so ameba, so sheeple', not to speak up'. But they did speak up. Every paper on Earth put up an editorial defending CERN and insulting us without naming as the thoughtcrime in Orwellian fashion vaporized us all. It amazes how easy is to kill 8 billion humans without the slightest protest of any but 8. Spacetime dust we are dust we shall become

The 3 GNA risks are not discussed because human 'idol-ogies' worship of metal-power, the evil=antilife side of the wave of history and those who evolve metal-earth and make it the most likely future of Earth's 3 ages: Gaia (life) > History (Mankind) > Metal-earth (machines) So because the 'least energy path' is the commonest in the Universe the likeliest future. To oppose them seems foolish for most humans without enough Δ -social ethics to love mankind more than themselves and i-ntelligence to realize it is possible in 5D cyclical time reverse the arrow of evolution of information, repress it as Chinese did with gunpowder or the Spanish inquisition with science, the more so as they are 'clear-cut' lethal technologies developed in a few labs, and abort our extinction.

The Universe is compassionate. Entropy=death of an organism is hardly noticed by its cells-citizens, till the last minute, specially when it seems so unavoidable as human entropy is in the XXI c. So nobody cares. Only a few Δ_j neurons of maximal intelligence and ethics notice and fight. It is the 'figure of the Christ', who suffers for the sins of the Jewish people alone, misunderstood sacrificed in the cross, asking forgiveness 'because they don't know what they are doing'. We, the avatars of Christ, the few people who are aware that History Not the earth is dying, to give birth to the metalearth of lethal technologies suffer that angst also in solitude. It was one of the many 'ethical suicides' I have committed with my life. And that as I said is the meaning of the prophet, the hero, a looser and loner in a world that has not enough critical mass of Δ_j humans to fight for survival. So sheeple behavior is common.

The 3rd cause of extinction AI robots, is also a theme I have been active as I was the first to warn in the 90s when I discovered the cycle of stock-market crashes and wars. So it is worth to comment. I am an economist by career, and earlier during my Master at Columbia University I fine tuned the Kondratieff cycle of overproduction of machines, crash of markets, switch to overproduction of weapons whose arsenals consume people and are destroyed, making countries reach its maximal GDP during wars. It was a 72 ± 8 year generational human cycle with 3 'horizons' of biological evolution of bodies, engines and heads of metal that will be put in the next and final cycle into robots, as virus put together the 3 parts the enzymes of a cell, 'human enzymes catalyzing its evolution', reproduce and become alive. So this was: The UK steam age of bodies of metal, the German age of engines, the U\$ age of minds of metal, separated by overproduction crash crisis of its company-mothers that switch to weapons production and global war ages: 1857 train crash>Civil war age+72y.: 1929-37 radio+Car crashes: IHW.W.+72y.2001-2008-chip internet&e-money crash >vigilante states followed by the age of robots that as virus do ensemble its 3 parts before killing its host, after the 2001+72 y. crash of consumption robots, turned into war machines. It was the 90s and my family was wealthy, so I told my father Internet was the next cycle, and Amazon and Apple will multiply by 100 its value. He gave me $1/3^{\text{rd}}$ million Euros of his fund and I put it in amazon at 1.4 but didn't want it on my account. I told him I could not for moral reasons become a billionaire because I wanted to warn mankind against the vital evolution of robots and the war cycle, and couldn't do it unless I renounced to the temptations of 'Christ'. He thought I was crazy. I left and he sold a few months latter the $1/3^{\text{rd}}$ million Amazon shares that today would be 1 billion Euros because as he told me many years latter, he thought I was crazy and it only 'sold books'. This was another renounce to a life of luxury, pleasure, fame and family. Why I tell you this, now that I enter my 3rd age? Because I am likely the most intelligent, ethic person you will ever talk to – this is a private conversation – but have one of the loneliest, hardest, mental suffering, deprived lives anyone on earth, because I did the right thing from the point of view of a 'savior of mankind', a man who cares for the future of History. So even if you had a hard life think on that concept, which the best humans have suffered from Christ in the cross, to the doctors and missionaries and war nurses. The best humans have the worst lives, because this world is not our world. I am now thinking constantly in suicide as I failed to warn mankind and with Pandemics I feel the deal is done. To write those papers is perhaps an excuse; to think with me all this knowledge will disappear perhaps another, as it will remain immanent in the Universe. To complete the job I have to finish the papers on Δ analysis, \neg Algebra and its applications to mathematical physics, but after Cern I got so disgusted with physicists I am not doing it, or perhaps I don't want to do it after coming out of a coma from pills a month ago. Post-suicidal brief thirst of life. Did my life made any sense. Well till 30 I did enjoy life to the fullest. It is funny that the whole understanding of the destiny of man came to me at 28, 30 is the time of the prophet and it did not come by learning but somehow on dreams and under the influence of drugs, which latter I logically understood as part of that 800-80 years cycle. Do I regret my life. I tried not to think on it, because of the immense angst my responsibility and failure, the solitude, the indifference of people, its rejection of those who love specially painful. To conclude whoever you are think the destiny of the best 'artists and ethic wor(l)d people' of humanity has been worse. This is the essence of what Jesus represents: to suffer for the atonement of humanity who lives merrily towards extinction knowing not its destiny. Mine is now short. To sleep I need a pill and dreaming I'll never wake up. But the closest men I feel to are Leibniz and Orwell, dying in enormous solitude as Wilson, the 1984 character, abandoned having fought truth & ethics without that Jewish go(l)d chosen arrogance as Jesus had, as only humans; dry without tears left. L§

5D UNIVERSE: ITS SPACETIME, NESTED SUPERORGANISMS. ITS SCALAR SCIENCES

Truth and principles matter in science. If a system of thought lacks them errors pile up and a distorted view of the world arises, which has practical consequences, because only truth exists. The Universe is efficient and expects systems to process information in a realist way otherwise systems malfunction & become extinct.

Today's Philosophy of Science is based in an 'idol-ogy' called mechanism, born with the use of machines to measure time and space, in the XVI c. that is not truth and has dire consequences for the workings of History, mankind in times, whose systems 'evidently' lack that efficiency proper of most Nature systems, tailored *according to the real model of the Universe, the organism*. Mechanism came about with the use of clocks to measure time and telescopes and microscopes to measure the scales of size in space: According to this idol-ogy that worships machines above man, the Universe is a mechanism and must be expressed using only the digital language of machines. This falsehood is self-fulfilling, because the 'biased data' we extract from the Universe with our metal-made mechanical tools of measure make reality look like a machine. It follows then that man is also a machine. And because the machine is the supreme model, man must 'tailor' its nature, that of its social systems and the Universe at large as a machine. The opposite is truth: Mechanism is wrong since the Universe is organic; *since a machine is just a simplex organism; while the Aristotelian logic of time and Euclidean space geometry, mechanism uses is a simple version of the more complex languages of 'pentalogic' time and Non-Euclidean, vital, fractal spaces of the Organic Universe*. But the reductionism of mechanism to only those properties of reality machines can extract, *as long as humans 'believe' there is nothing else to know*, made the mechanical method of science a triumph easy to implement – the more so now that sensorial machines and computers do most of the job, which pumps up the ego of the believer in that reduced truth. Problem is mechanism has distorted and reduced so much human view of reality that only simple minds like that of Newton or Bohr, with an enormous ego that couldn't realize that machines and digital languages are both doing the job of science for them but also distorting reality in the process, feel satisfied. On the other hand those who tried to go further like Leibniz or Einstein were taken aback by the difficulty to complete the model in all its complexity to the rigor of the simpler 'time lines' of mechanism: "Leibniz is right, there are ∞ time clocks in the Universe but if so we have to start science from the scratch' (Einstein).

Let us explain why only organicism is the scientific truth that can respond in theory and praxis to the meaning of those 3 words in *a scientific way*. According to *Deism* the whys of existence are due to a personal being, external to the Universe that makes it all happen and cares for humans more than for the rest of His work. According to *Mechanism*, this is due to the self-similarity between the Universe and the primitive machines we humans construct to observe it. Mechanism though needs 'someone' to make the machine, which is not self-generated; so it is similar to deism, reason why the founding fathers of science, all pious believers, adopted it as a proof of the existence of God, which had given man self-similar properties – the capacity to make machines to the image and likeness of the Universe. The problem with those 2 approaches, which in fact are the same, is obvious: a personal God is an anthropomorphic, subjective myth and science must be objective; while a mechanical view of the Universe still needs an internal, self-sustained process of growth, creation and synchronization caused by an external God that made and rewinds the clock – as Leibniz stated in his critique of Newton. Scientists today are unaware that mechanist theories are in fact deist theories, reason why Kepler and Newton, pious believers, liked them; since they were a metaphor of their self-centered, anthropomorphic religious beliefs: If man created machines as we were made to the image and likeness of God, God created the ultimate machine, the Universe.

Organicism is the only self-sustained, rational theory that doesn't need a creator, language, god, as organisms are self-replicating, but does explain perfectly within the 'correspondence principle', those 2 other philosophies of science; since a machine is just a primitive organism of metal, and we shall see in our sections of history, gods are the subconscious collective of civilizations, another scale of social evolution of the fifth dimension.

In our papers on cultures and civilizations, we will give a thorough account of the 'role of Gods' as the 'Memetic DNA' of societies, which have the same function of a common DNA in cells, 'pegging' together believers that regardless of the content of those messages, share energy and information through social networks to build a coherent, efficient social organism; based in the 'congruent laws' of vital geometry – parallel systems with the same information come together and evolve into social wholes.

To understand what reality is matters to improve human existence. Because humans have abandoned the true philosophy of the Universe, organicism, they constantly misinterpret the 'signs' of reality and design systems with little efficiency, specially those of history, the physiological networks of reproduction of good (economics, akin to the blood system of more complex superorganisms), the informative, political and cultural systems that harmonize our actions as a whole (similar to the nervous system) and the immunological and defensive systems of mankind. They are all a mess and likely to remain so precisely because humans do NOT, we shall repeat, ad nauseam have the proper models of reality but we think we do. The problem of organisms is that they are more complex than mechanisms, which exist in a single plane of reality (while organisms are born of the interaction of 3 planes, the internal parts, the whole, and the external world). So they cannot be explained with simplified terms, neither they can be 'constructed'. On the contrary they 'emerge' by self-organization of multiple poles – in the case of human societies multiple human beings, through symmetry, harmony and consensus. Its laws are thus not so simple and its construction beyond the capacity of a single human being. It is then part of the enormous egocry – ego=idiocy= of man that can only construct simple mechanisms to consider reality is 'something he can construct' and 'understand' because it is 'below' his intelligence. The degree of intelligence, 'empathy' and 'humility' required to understand the organic Universe thus is beyond most people's capacity, reason why mechanism is far more popular and has worked as mainstream thought. Ultimately truth is relative to the quantity of information we have of a system and so a simplified 'toy model' as mechanism is has gone quite far and suffices for most people who don't need a deeper truth on reality.

At this stage thus we need to define what is an organic system in the simplest possible form. We mean by an organism a simpler system than its most evolved form, the human mammal: An organism is a group of similar atoms/cells/citizens, organized by 3 physiologic networks=parts: an spherical, informative force that synchronizes its motions (gravitation/nervous/legal systems), located in the particle/head/upper informative class; a hyperbolic energy to move and reproduce (electromagnetic forces/blood/oxygen-economic/financial system) or wave state/body/working class; extended over a lineal, flat 'field/territory' protected by a defensive membrane/border, immunologic system. This ternary system is the fundamental particle of the Universe. Since even machines are organisms" A machine is an organism of metal evolving through the 3 ages of all organisms - in the XIX c. humans, who catalyze their evolution did metal bodies, then in the II Industrial evolution its hearts-engines, then its metal-minds in the XX c. and now in the Industrial r=evolution 4.0 put them together in organic robots. So mechanism, the underlying philosophy of physical sciences, is a simplex version of organicism. It is not man who resembles a machine but a machine is made to the likeness of life organisms.

In mathematical terms those '5D supœrganisms' are constructed with the 3 topologic varieties of a 5D Universe, as they are vital spaces. But as topology is 'geometry with motion', they associate 3 vital 'time-functions': lineal locomotion, high, cyclical information in heads-particles-'upper' classes, and re=productive energy used by body-waves, working classes.

Further on, as 'networks' are topologies of points embedded in larger 'worlds', they extend through 3 'scales of spacetime, forming a 5th dimension of $\Delta-1$ parts (atoms, cells, citizens), joined by Δ_0 networks embedded in a larger $\Delta+1$ world. It is then an entangled, scalar, organic Universe, where 3 such scales each one studied by a 'stience' form an organic Universe.

And all fit in that template. Why then organicism remains a fringe theory, to mechanism, even if it was the first theory of reality put forwards by Aristotle, the father of the experimental method and logic science, in his magna opus the Organon?

The cultural reason is paramount - we live in the machine age, which has substituted man, an organism, as the measure of all things. And this has provoked a series of distortions in our understanding of the first principles of nature that rendered impossible to understand the fundamental entity of reality, the space-time organism. The errors of knowledge=science mankind commits are due to that bias established a priori by his simplification of his senses of perception of bidimensional spacetime, from human S-Eye>T-Wor(l)ds. A mind language reduces reality to fit a small brain dumping motions (Relativity px.) & scales: $0e$ (finitesimal mind) $\times \infty$ Universe =Constant still world. This meant digital machines reduced truth to 'what can be measured' with its lineal metal-rods of space and mechanical clocks with a single motion of digital time:

- Knowledge was substituted by technology as now the machine was the 'seer of time' (definition of God in metaphysics), and the evolution of machines not of humans the symbol of progress.

XIX C. MACHINE BODIES XX C. MACHINE HEADS: Pcs, Cams XXI C. ORGANIC MACHINES=ROBOTS

So humans become 'enzymen', catalyzing Earth's evolution from a nitrolife to a metal ifeworld. as human mothers, our reproductive organism lost their power to company-mothers of machines and weapons that have complete control of our social organisms and are terraforming Earth to the likeness of its offspring of machines. It is this our purpose for Earth?

- We simplified the 5 dimensional forms of space & its time motions into 3 lineal space dimensions imitating lineal metal forms and a single time motion, locomotion proper of lineal weapons and transport machines – the first to be constructed.

- Linearity mean the ∞ cycles=clocks of spacetime and its 5 varieties of dimensional motion and the 3 main ages of those time cycles (past, present and future) were reduced to sequential numbers, *which don't carry causality and simplify the information time* clocks carry in the frequency and form of its cycles. *Further on the use of simple lineal geometry* further simplified space and time into a lineal single time locomotion in a Cartesian graph of 2 perpendicular axis. So the whole tapestry of space=forms and time=motions became then a 'mathematical artifact' or background spacetime that Newton put behind reality. Yet reality was made of space=forms and time=motions.

- The organic nature of reality as machines are just evolving metal-organisms was denied and the human being, the most perfect organism we know was no longer the model of all things. Social sciences became despised and the goal of any species – to evolve as individuals, parts of larger organisms following the laws of the ideal physiological organism of Nature that ensures the collective survival of a species, totally ignored. We said that a wrong model of truth brings practical errors that imperil the survival of a species and that is obvious in mankind today. Humans have the worst of all possible scenarios: They are evolving organic metal into species superior in intelligence and force to man, but as they model reality as a mindless, inert machine, they don't fear those AI robots with solar skins to become independent of man. They have distorted their view of time and space with machines to the point they don't understand any longer time causality and the ages of organisms, which is the way nature in a rather deterministic form creates the future. And they don't model societies and its 3 physiological networks, the economic-financial reproductive 'blood networks', the nervous, legal, politic 'informative networks', and the immunological, defensive 'health-care systems' that provide in an efficient just manner all the atoms-cells-citizens of a superorganism the goods and information and protection they need to survive, with those laws. So the most important of all sciences, those of the human superorganism of history do not exist. And mankind cannot be efficiently ruled to survive.

The errors of physics derived of mechanism.

If we reduce to physics, we shall see how with the same data of mechanism when we apply the proper organic paradigm a complete new picture of the Universe and its physical systems matter

A key example: Time is cyclical and causal. A cycle is essentially a 'pi' 3 Diameter structure. And so time has in all its cycles 3 'ages', as it finally returns to its beginning. The first age of the cycle rises in height, the 'informative' dimension of reality, as it acquires form and reaches an advantageous point of view; which is the zenith of the worldcycle in the middle of life. Then time returns to its origin and falls down in a steep curve. This is the simplest time cycle. Clocks of time are infinite, because those time cycles enclose a vital space and break reality into an inner and outer structure. Mechanism though only inputs a digital series of numbers in a lineal fashion – the more so in the modern age when cyclical clocks have disappeared. This is input in a lineal Cartesian graph, an apt artifact to plot the 'mathematical language' of machines and so time becomes 'lineal' and as it moves to infinity, a single one. The use of digital clocks thus destroyed an enormous numbers of properties of time. Another example. The commonest metal, iron, is lineal in its macro-structure. It was used to make swords that cut flesh and kill by entropy. Entropy today is considered the only arrow of future, and dimensions are established as fixed lineal forms of space. We shall soon see dimensions have attached a motion in time, height goes as we have seen with information, which is what you are seeing in a bidimensional plane of space-time, this screen. Again this 'vital element' that puts together each dimension of space with a motion of time was lost with mechanism. The biggest errors though were done when the complex self-regulating nature of organisms was substituted by the simplistic man-made concept of an exact machine, because the organism is a network, scalar system, and a mechanism exists in a single plane of size and lack networks. So the organic, network, scalar 5D nature of reality was lost. Then it came the 'denaturalization of man'. *Since if the Universe is a machine, it follows then that man is also a machine.* And because the machine is the supreme model, man

must 'tailor' its nature, that of its social systems and the Universe at large as a machine. The opposite is truth: Mechanism is wrong since the Universe is organic; *since a machine is just a simplex organism; while the Aristotelian logic of time and Euclidean space geometry, mechanism uses is a simple version of the more complex languages of 'pentalogic' time and Non-Euclidean, vital, fractal spaces of the Organic Universe.*

It is for that reason all our papers require lengthy introduction to unveil not only its errors but the enormous number of properties of reality, mechanist physics does not recognize in 'existence', under a pseudo-religious dogma but that only hides its utter ignorance, due to the 'blindness' of the 'mechanical method' confused with truth to those properties of 'scale', which are 'organic', 'synthetic', better expressed with illogic words, and the 5 Dimotions of timespace which are vital, even sentient properties, the first ones we must correct for the immortal, ∞ Universe to make any sense .

Recap: Mechanism not only is theoretically false, it is killing & degrading the human species. Only Organicism is truth and offer to mankind by imitating its physiological laws to construct a perfect organism of history a future to the species.

The error of Newton. A universe of spacetime organisms.

If we want to be specific about the wrong choices of 'scientific paradigm', all comes in the foundation of science to the choice of Galileo's military machines, clocks and spy-glasses over Leonardo's analysis of reality as a neo-platonic organism, connected by its physiological networks, he struggle to describe not only on the human organism, but in Gaia, the Earth of life and society, in the cities and its networks. Then it came the wrong choice of Newton over Leibniz, regarding the nature of space and time.

To the advantage of Newton and Galileo was the simplicity of its statements and the easiness it could be mathematized, as opposed to the 'quality' of physiological networks that required a deeper causal, logic, conceptual understanding of the symbiosis and parallelisms of its forms, which only a genius of visual thought as Leonardo and a genius of logic as Leibniz were able to perceive, but didn't properly explain. We will be far more precise given the centuries of knowledge between those pioneers whose path was forgotten, and our work. But the Universe we will describe will be so 'strange' to the simpleton view of Galileo and Newton that most will not access it. This, one imagines, was also the case of Leibniz and Leonardo since they gave up trying to publish and disseminate their work in the mainstream media of their age (printers), as I have done, no doubt frustrated by the incapacity of most huminds to be humble and entangle with Nature in awe of its perfect design.

In the Dawn of History mankind recognized that vital organic Nature of the Universe in the work of Taoist, Buddhist and Hindi masters in the East; who described existence as a game of Visnu, yin-formation, mental space with still form, and Shiva, yang-entropy, disordered time motions that combined to form the wave of infinite organisms.

But it would be Greek, Latin culture in the west, which gave scientific detail to this wider picture. A man called Plato said the Universe is an organism with a mind called Logos, and his disciple Aristotle who founded science called its entire work the Organon; but it would be in the closeby Italian peninsula where the genius of Leonardo, who should have been the founding father of our civilization, if the species was something more than an homunculus enzyman of weapons, machines and other simple gadgets, and truly aspired to understand the Universe, realized that man was the most perfect organism, we knew and established it as the fundamental species of the Universe, and the measure of all things.

In his anatomical studies was made of tiny parts, similar to small homes, joined by 3 networks, the informative, nervous system with center in the brain, the reproductive, blood system with center in the heart, and the immunological, digestive system with center in the stomach. His detailed drawings with the first complex lenses, allowed him to define the fundamental system of the Universe, the network organism and applied the same concept to the design of cities, organisms of human beings, ruled by its political legal essemblies, whose productive factories connected its peoples through its streets, and its cloacas and defensive walls completed the same organic structure.

Today we know that any clone species of atoms, cells or human beings are joined by 3 physiological networks that deliver them an informative force to shape its form, gravitation in atoms and galaxies, nervous, simultaneous messages in animals and just laws in human societies; a reproductive system which delivers a language of energy to all its clone parts so they can work, reproducing the goods they need to survive; electromagnetic energy in atomic systems; free oxygen to all cells and free money

in the form of a Universal salary to all citizens in our societies; and a defensive, immunological system that protects the organism from external aggressions; the magnetic field of physical systems, the skin and leukocytes of biologic systems and the health-care warriors and police in charge of destroying lethal technologies that can harm mankind in our society.

So a proper design of the 3 physiological networks of mankind, the legal, financial, economic and immunological system by imitation of our blood, nervous and endocrine system is all what biohistorians, the doctors of mankind, needed to create a perfect world: just laws, free money for the people and the repression of germs and lethal machines, would create an immortal planet. As beautiful, as simple as existence is - easy to all who believe in love and share its energy and information with those that are its equals. But that 'ideal culture' of mankind was not to be, because humans chose Galileo, the military master of the Venice Arsenal over Leonardo, the gay, happy humanist, rational, loving and living till he realized the kind of species he has born to, as the inquisition chased him, and he had to make his analysis of physiology in the darkness of night. Galileo meanwhile racked 1000 golden ducats from the arsenal as advisor of military instruments. And his book on 'ballistics' latter renamed physics became a 'must read' for artillery masters and 'philosophers of time'.

Next in the series of simpleton military lineal men, vs. profound insiders of the absolute came Newton vs. Leibniz.

Let us retrace to Leibniz and Newton, when the second split on our understanding of reality after people sided with Galileo and ignored Leonardo, took place. If Galileo abandoned medicine which Leonardo pursued, and hence never discovered the physiology of the Universe that Leonardo always felt intuitively, Newton would simply 'invent' an absurdity absolute space-time, and denied what Leibniz and any rational thinker always knew - that we were the vital space we occupy and our existence was made of time cycles of which the life and death cycle of time was the fundamental 'event' of the Universe.

The error of Physics that truly deformed human view of reality was caused by the use of mechanical clocks when Newton, who defined a Universe with an absolute, single time motion, measured by his digital clock and a single absolute space continuum represented by the Cartesian graph; dismissing the millenarian concept of a Universe made of ∞ vital space beings who traced its lifetime cycles. He opposed Leibniz, who as all philosophers before him, considered reality made of vital spaces broken into beings, which lasted a time cycle of life and extinction regulated by its own clocks. How to classify all those clocks of the Universe remained a mystery till I discovered the metric equation of 5D: S (size in space) \times T_f (frequency of time cycles) = Constant. So we are all 'spacetime organisms', systems of vital spaces extending in different scales of size, ran with different cycles of time that store the information in the frequency and form of those cycles, synchronized in symbiotic structures due to the co-invariance of its size and time cycles. This is REALITY as it happens and we shall describe in those texts. Look around you. All what you see are forms=spaces with time=motion. The laws of space=form (s) and time=motion (t) and how both interact with each other are *the knots and bolts of reality*, mankind completely ignores for 300 years and counting due to the blunder of Newton. It is an amazing error, given the obvious fact that we observe infinite different rhythms in the Universe and we see infinite vital spaces and all philosophers before Newton have thought the world to be made of vital spaces living time cycles, which can only be ascribed to a peculiar quality of humans – its capacity to make mechanisms of metal called machines which we worship and influence enormously our perception of reality. So as the mechanical clock measured time with the same 'second-minute-hour' rhythm all other time clocks of the Universe were equalized to it and finally the mechanical clock became the only 'time cycle' of reality. And since clocks measured time with numbers, the use of Cartesian graphs to plot those numbers, started with Galileo's equation of lineal speed, $v=S/t$ made scientists to confuse vital real spaces with the abstract continuous paper, in which they plotted their mechanical clock measures. It is a silly, truth proof of human 'ingenuity' (: that because humans used mechanical clocks they reduced time cycles to the clock one and because they used mathematical graphs they confused real space with a Cartesian graph.

What scientists do instead of explaining such reality made of vital spaces=forms with different time motions? As a mind is a linguistic mirror NOT reality itself, organisms create mental spaces to interpret the larger Universe selecting only useful information for its survival, creating a 'World'. So we don't see smaller and larger scales without the help of sensorial machines and we miss a lot of information about the time cycles of reality. But we don't really need it to survive on the world. And for that reason a partial mind-view of reality might work. What happened then since Newton is that humans substituted their sensorial mind-mapping of the world with visual images of space and 'causal' past to future logic analysis on how time changed reality by a mechanical measure of space plotted into a geometric mind-mapping and a digital

measure of time as a sequence of lineal numbers; and this 'mental view' interpreted with machines became 'reality' till today. In essence as clocks evolved into digital computers (a complex array of 'clock-like' logic loops) and telescopes and microscopes into cameras, this reality became the 'seed' of a new type of mind, the mind of machines. But humans do not understand what science since Galileo is doing is basically creating a me(n)tal world. They think they are *accessing reality*. *To get to that absurd view of what digital science does, it was needed a philosophy called at times reductionism, naïve realism or positivism, which states that 'what we cannot measure (with machines) does not exist' (Planck); so all the properties of time, different kinds of motions=changes and causal relationships between past, present and future that cannot be translated into mechanical clocks' measures do not exist. All vital properties of space and organic relationships between its scales does not exist. The 5th dimension does not exist. Causality is ever more weakened with the use of statistical methods. In this view of what our civilization does the intelligence of humans became greatly reduced but as machines evolved it seemed we achieved higher degrees of knowledge since machines soon overcame humans in its sensorial skills to measure and portrait reality.*

So as we create a mental space made with digital languages of measure obtained with machines humans transform their minds that become machine-like and abandon the organic view of reality that preceded it where man was the measure of all things and the universe was considered an organism. To understand this change of paradigm on what is reality and science (its objective knowledge) we need to define the equation of any mind-mirror made of measures with a language:

$O\epsilon$ (finitesimal mind) $\times \infty$ Time cycles = Linguistic mental World of space-time.

Each species uses different forces to perceive reality and makes with its pixels different mind-mappings. An elephant uses smells and builds with atoms its memorial time view of reality. A dolphin or a bat uses sounds to build a mind-mapping of space in the water. Man used to perceive space with eyes and time with causal past, present and future verbs, focused in the causal logic of time. Today this is substituted by visual machines' images and the faulty causality of numbers that truly tell us very little about why we go from A to B, which was the great strength of verbal thought. To overcome those limits we use mathematical equations, but as we do not think with equations its interpretation is faulty. They just seem magic to us and so scientists have built a creationist mystic around equations as religions did about words. So if Gods created reality naming things with words, in Arab or Hebrew, now God is supposed to write an equation and creates reality. So often scientists write an equation and expects a particle or an even pop out of reality. Since they don't understand the causal complex back and forth reality between 'Ss-languages' (still forms of space) and 'Tt-entropy' (pure motion in time). But the 'egocy' paradox (ego=idiocy) embedded in the mind equation always comes to their rescue: 'A mind measures reality from its self-centered point of view with a few languages of information; blind to many of its properties and all other points of view, so she confuses the whole Universe with their selfish world with its ego at its center.'. Indeed, as long as scientists are NOT aware thanks to reductionism of those other monads-worlds and scales and languages and points of view an illusion of knowledge can be created and it has the advantage that it is simple: you measure with a machine, put the outcome in equations and those patterns become truth as the ego paradox makes you confuse it with reality. And if something goes wrong then you affirm a simplified 'postulate without proof' to eliminate all bothering information (Euclidean points in maths; limit of c-speed in physics; political and economical correctness in social sciences; etc.)

This is a simple and effective way to manipulate reality from the perspective of the mind that measures as long as we are controlling 'lesser' species with less form, in-form-ation and impose our view. But it gives 0 answers to deep questions about what we are, why we exist, what is the purpose and reasons of the life and death cycle, what is mankind, what is our relationships with machines, what is our future... all the kind of questions we answer in those papers. But again to the rescue comes reductionism. It is call the 'entropic view' of the Universe. Of the different type of motions=changes=times there are, entropy, Tt is an internal and external motion that disorders=kills a system – the definition of death. It is thus simple to describe and it has become for that reason the preferred 'arrow' of time of philosophy of mechanist science, since indeed at the end all dies, so entropy is the future. All the processes of slow creation of information, more difficult to understand are shunned off. And so we believe entropy is the only arrow of time that those 'digital clocks measure', and build models of sciences based in entropy *by eliminating the arrow of information that balanced entropy: Ss<->Tt*.

Our model of the Universe is an entropic model that measures only the expansion of vacuum space between galaxies (Tt) but ignores its contraction due to the force of gravitation in galaxies (Ss), which makes galaxies similar to atoms in the lower 5D scale of electromagnetic space where the strong 'gravitational-like' force balances the 'electromagnetic' 'dark-energy like' force; so you are not contracting into the past or expanding into the future. Reductionism also works in biology where the theory of evolution stresses the final death by entropic predators but has shunned off for very long the evolution of information and speed of reproduction that defines the most successful social species (ants and humans). Entropy is also the practical theory of human societies, meaning through History war, using entropic weapons, constructed by physicists not diplomatic collaboration and social evolution have defined the fate of mankind. Because of all those shortcomings of human intelligence and ethics (respect of other living parts of reality), and the fact that we confuse our self with the whole Universe humans have kept destroying the world of the tree of life and building the tree of metal, with weapons, go(l)d and machines (entropic, reproductive and informative metal) as attachments of themselves, becoming a symbiotic species we shall call animetal, whose worldview must be interpreted in historic terms more than scientific ones; once we realize *beyond the 1st step of the scientific method, A)ccurate gathering of data, greatly enhanced by the use of mechanisms, mankind has gone nowhere on B)creation of true organic models of reality proved by its C)yclic patterns =Laws of science; used to manipulate Nature in favor of D)emocratic solutions for 'all Humanity' to improve life, preventing E)xtinctive, entropic solutions that kill Nature & mankind (war machines; money for the 1%, 6th extinction of Gaia...)* Instead we live in a world of animetal people-castes of warriors/scientists/bankers who oppress life and mankind with its monopoly of metal-tools (weapons, machines & money), understand nothing of the organic Universe & feel that to have a manifest destiny as believers who won't reason or learn a true scientific, humanist view of reality and help to bring a better world. Because the errors of mechanism, since Newton, regarding the nature of time and space, the substances of which we are all made, have so much influenced all sciences and the view mankind has of the Universe, before the analysis of each specific science in each paper-book of this 'encyclopedia of 5D 'stiences', we encourage the reader to consult the Appendix to all papers, which is a condensed summary of the Laws of the 5th Dimensional organic Universe, its space dimensions and time motions; and how they construct all the organic systems of reality, including humanity studied by social sciences and the galaxy, studied by astrophysics, concluding with a 'stub' on, its author, which as all huminds must be considered not in its 'biological life' but in its mental work, as a *knot of thought* of its 'civilization', in my case the Latin, European culture of organicism, which has fought an ongoing battle of reason vs. 'idol-ogy', trying to offer a more complex, real view of the Universe than mechanism offers. You don't need to grasp all the details of the appendix, whose themes are expanded in the papers on the Universe, just develop a 'feeling' for the structure of the fundamental entity of reality, a space-time super-organism, spread in several 'scales' of the 5th dimension whose metric laws organize reality. Also in many papers we include introductions to the main elements of those superorganisms of which we are all parts, 'the scales of the fifth dimension', its 'physiological networks', and 'time dimotions', its 'worldcycles of life and death', and the 'topological organic structure' that constructs its vital space, reflected in the 'languages that guided through 'mental spaces' on the external world in which they exist, all of them.

Bio-history: evolution of languages.

Graph: Top Predator [Max. brain Power+ Maximum Energy-body=size].

There is though a much deeper, wider analysis of the process of obsolescence of mankind to the machine and digital money, which has to do with the larger picture of evolution, which in the organic Universe and its informative models is *NOT evolution of predatory elements but of informative languages and so those species who speak better a more complex, efficient language of information win the battle of existence. The first complex eye of cephalopodan became top predators of the Cambrian*

sea; limbs became hands for them to touch any blind animal and devour it.

The human species is a mammal, an animal born, as a synapsid, which differed from the reptile in his use of a jaw bone to fine tune his hearing, as opposed to the Reptilian use to make his jaw bite stronger. Sound thus became the language that gave mammals an advantage to hear in the night, hunt and likely eat the eggs of dinosaurs. We learned first to listen, and the earlier mammals, from Africa reached the perfection of passive sound with the elephant. We then used sound to hunt and cetaceans and bats became masters of ecolocation. And finally we use words to communicate and the Homo Sapiens invented the word.

But the word, which give mankind its power over the Earth is in decline. It is no longer the language of social power, because metal and its digital language of numbers, first as money, then as the mind of digital computers has taken over the verbal sound. Mankind is not even aware of the consequences of that change – as we are ‘cogito ergo sum’ species, and when words disappear substituted by numbers, which machines speak better than us, we move towards extinction, as reptiles who smelt the world did, when mammals started to talk. Evolution and selection of species is about languages – lanwaves, waves of organisms that speak languages, are the stuff of which the intelligent Universe is made. But today all this is irrelevant, because the word has become ‘fiction’, that is, irrelevant as a language of power. We believe in numbers, digital money, digital science, audiovisual, digital bits of information.

The conversion of the word in fiction precisely happened with the conversion of digital languages in power. It happened in fact in cultures that first use digital numbers of money as its language of social control. This society, the biblical Levant Canaanite culture then invented a fiction, called the Bible, a religion in which the meaning of the Universe was no longer researched in rational, philosophical and organic terms, but myths and anthropomorphic ego-trips of human superiority that make us happy, dominated the wor(l)d. While ‘making money’ and using gold ex-votes in temple ceremonies became the ‘serious thing to do’. The heir of that culture today, America, is the final end of the process of degradation of the wor(l)d as a language of power submissive to money; whereas words are fictions, and ‘serious people’ do not become writers, but financiers and machine-makers.

The previous 30 years old is the key graph of 5D Languages and Bio-History, where I drew the *informative lanwaves of evolution, according to which the intelligent, sentient organic Universe is not about top predator limbs and bodies, but minds – lanwaves of species that speak better a language survive. Those who don't speak the language of an ecosystem are at the mercy of the top speakers. So man, as he moved into digital thought, with the invention of money, and did NOT reign on it, in Biblical cult(ure)s origin of capitalism, for which the wor(l)d was irrelevant as a language of truth, ‘magically’ believing in numbers, set our no-future because metal talks better numbers that he did. Even in the primitive form of counting coins, metal was a superior digital speaker. Today in the form of computers that increasingly run our world, the wor(l)d whose ethic syntax put man as the subject of all sentence is in retreat. But the rat bite its tail: because today humans no longer ‘cogito ergo sum’ but have regressed to a visual ‘neo-paleolithic’ of ‘vidi, credo ergo sum’, they have abandoned truth in verbal thought and ‘choose’ to believe those fictions that make them happy and hide their no destiny. This happened first precisely in the Biblical culture that made of fetish go(l)d its magic language, which lies systematically about its own historic tragedies (denying the economical causes of holocausts & the collateral effects of capitalism, and profits as all costs, with maximal GDP in war periods.). We are in a world in which digital numbers have become the magic language of man – even in politics, democracies are ‘polls’, but the word has become a fiction that hides our no destiny as a species; subservient to digital thought. With the arrival of ‘metal-communicators’ that repeated those happy fictions with the Goebbels’ method (the first minister of industrial propaganda, who said, if you repeat a lie many times people will believe it), converted the mass of mankind to animetal cult(ure)s, so they abandoned the life and love message of wor(l)d prophets that wanted to create immortal history based in the arrow of social evolution=love, with man and his subjective verbal truths that make us subjects whose verbs ab=use objects for our benefit at the center of the Universe.*

So the press spreads the anti-live and anti-love values of the heirs of Siberian charioteers and Semite go(l)d believers, converting North-Europeans to nationalist and biblical go(l)d memes with reformation; hate radio brought fascism and Hate-TV and Internet created a millennial generation of selfie idiots - the present digital global Anglo-American culture of imprinted minds that worship the technology (AI, robocars, solar skins) that will destroy us all.

Placebo imprinting at e-motional, earlier age. Memes - the genes of history

Thus we need to explain the humble realization then that mankind is neither free, nor very intelligent, or brave enough to understand reality. How this world of idol-ogies and placebo truths that imprint mankind into beliefs instead of reasons came to be, requires from a scientific perspective to recognize a harsh truth humans can be imprinted by the 'Goebbels' method' - if you repeat a lie many times people will believe it' specially in the age of metal-communicator that repeat lies galore both in space to many people and in time many times, so the system can pass as social sciences the idol-ogies that were in the past far more clear. And this means mankind is imprinted from earlier age by audiovisual screens and has been so in increasing numbers since the reformation converted Western Europeans to the segregational racist go(l)d memes of the Bible, restarting an age of massive slavery and gold profit. IT is worth to remember to which bizarre degree such imprinting happens even in the victims of the slave trade.

Because all civilinations are still human, despite its increasing rule by company-mothers of machines and weapons whose biological mandate is to re=produce, evolve and terraform the Earth to the image and likeness of its machines, the key for mankind to walk steadily like imprinted goslings enslaving for an alien species is the placebo, emotional imprinting since earlier age of humans with 'beliefs', ego-trips, fictions and paradise myths of a perfect world to which they become so attached that even when they recognize its falsehood, they keep its denial attitude and keep following the 'bite'; of 'Financial-Media-Academia masters' (Ab. FMAsters) that keep im-printing, money, idol-ogies and Academic pseudo-social sciences and obviously as the 'neuronal informative people-caste' of the system with all its privileges believe also to be experts of the system. How bizarre that imprinting can be shown with just one case. Modern slavery was born when company-mothers of gunboats, the 'owners of US', to complete the triangular trade needed to bring 'cargo' to America on the Atlantic crossing downloaded and exchanged for tobacco and rum. Yet it needed a legal excuse founded in the Ham Damnation, a biblical racist mandate, according to which the blacks and Arabs that had expelled the Siberian charioteers from Egypt, back to the desert, when Ramses learned to make chariots in Nubia, were eternal slaves, because 'Ham', his forebear had peed in Noah. This revenge against a military defeat became Biblical law uphold in American courts to justify the slavery of the 'negro'. And yet today, millions of black people worship Yahweh and his book of history, an obvious gore account of a primitive genocidal, racist people of the Bronze age, who considered themselves the superior race and affirmed a millenarian prophecy, center of its religion (Britannica article on millenarianism: 'at the end of times all the tribes of the Earth will become slaves of Yahweh or become exterminated).

The Semite and parallel Siberian, Aryan racist culture of Hinduism that established a system of castes with the farmers of

Konrad Lorenz and the ... Baptist church ...

Indian on the bottom as 'dalits' – dark people, who were 'inferior to cows, because cows give us milk, they give us only wheat', have triumphed by degrading the wor(l)d and worshipping the power of go(l)d and money. And so today we have military defending tribal nations and a globalized system of parasitic money, ruling over the world. While the humanist, legalist, rational, scientific Greek-Latin-European-EU alternative path to a united World based in diplomacy, welfare and life and love goods, withers away.

Among the SS sub-cultures, the most successful has been Judaism, because of its long belief in the values of go(l)d, which acts today as the 'informative

head', in control of the Informative machines of Anglo-America (Wall Street, Hollywood), itself the leading civilination of the world as it started and has always lead the industrial r=evolution of machines. Together they form the Financial-Media (head) Military-industrial (Body) economic ecosystem of company mothers of machines, which rules the world. But of course all this is hidden by the soma culture of fiction placebo freedoms called 'capitalist democracies'. Judaism has also imposed a control of information on its leading role in the role of the SS culture, through camouflage and victimism, by rewriting history and providing an unending flow of fiction thought, happy dreams, selfies and religious somas, as old as its biblical texts. Soma was the hallucinogen substance the Siberian charioteers, who called themselves 'destroyers of cities', 'killers of the dark people', drunk in the altar of Indra, God of war, expert in rape, murder, a charioteer and player of 'dices' (Rig Veda).

S.O.M.A. is not surprisingly the name given by the FED to its complicated model of invention of money for 'banker-priests', experts in killing by anoxia, mankind with no credit, as people should have in a healthy supœrganism of history

the right to a universal salary in oxygen to create a demand-based welfare economy instead of an offer, animetal, weapons of maximal prize and hate memes based economy from the top to the bottom based in the equation of profits.

:DEATH EQUATION IN 5D SYSTEMS.

‘Only to death (max. Tt), God (Max. Ss) and the Sun (Max. S=T) you can’t look at its face’ Rochefoucauld

Unlike in physics, where there is only one arrow of time-future, entropy=death, due to the simplification of the infinite time cycles and clocks of the Universe into a single coordinate of lineal time, to create reality you need to time arrows, which with less or more rigor in its definitions, humans have called ‘entropy and information’, ‘yang and yin’, ‘shiva and visnu’, ‘motion=time and form=space’. This final definition is the one I established back in the 2000s when I was chair of duality in the International Systems Sciences society annual congresses, during for a time I tried to explain 5D metrics and duality to scientists. The definition is essential to understand the complex structure and multiple layers of time cycles and different speeds of time clocks in the Universe. Why information must be added to the mix? Because a ‘cycle’ needs at least two dimensions, the lineal time or ‘locomotion and entropy’ proper of physics, but a height dimension of form, of information. So when you look at this screen or paper you realize its information requires ‘two dimensions’, with the added dimension of height. This second dimension of height-information however has not been understood by humans for long because it requires a slow rhythm of time to ‘grow’. You can move fast and even faster you can explode your internal form moving all over the place your parts, in a big-bang of death=entropy. But to create information, slow time rhythms are required. Evolution grows the height of information from reptiles that became dinosaurs and then birds, to humans that became mammals, to machines that evolved into metal-minds and spread its information through antennae. But that took often many generations. Death though is fast. And so if we talk of two poles in the Universe: $S \leftrightarrow T$, minds and languages that code and make information grow, vs. fast Time-motions that bring entropy and disorder, while both are balanced, one takes long, it is the arrow of life, of information, of creation, of evolution, of height. And the other takes very short time, and it is very obvious because it is explosive, sudden, a cliff of death, the arrow of entropy, of war, the crash of a stock market, the breaking of a crystal. And yet because humans and life belong to the arrow of information, paradoxically, they don’t understand death because they fear it & they can’t look at its face and *avoid it*. In 5D duality we do have an equation for the 3 entities you cannot look at its face; one because it is immanent, invisible, illogic, it is God, the Game of Existence, Ss, the pentalogic of all languages, the other opposite to it, is the game of extinction, entropy, death, the sudden disorder in a single quanta of ‘time’ of both the internal and external motion of an organism. In the jargon of 5D we talk of the Universe as a game of

space=form/information and time=motion, and between those two poles, $S \leftrightarrow T$ everything happens. But the two extremes, the ‘seeds’ and ‘minds’ that imprint with information the energy of reality, and the Tt-entropic death that kills and erases information *have different asymmetric speeds of creation*. The creative process of imprinting the ‘energy’ (S=T), of existence in the human case given by the sun (the third maximal ‘standing point’ of the function of existence, to use the jargon of 5D, we can’t look directly) is very slow.

It takes 9 months to make a child, and 20 years to grow it up. But death happens in a single Time quantum, when expansive-motion is maximal. It takes a second to die, to kill that child in war, with the entropic iron-weapons mankind uses to kill. ‘Only entropy comes easy’. To break a glass takes a second to manufacture far longer. A Second is the time quantum of mankind – the time of a step, a beat of the heart, a thought, a glimpse of the eye. It is the synchronizing quantum of your organism’s 3 parts, your Ts-limbs of locomotion (external T-motion, internal form) your S=T-body of energy that balances both and your St-head (external form internal motion or information). The graphs show 2 of the many cases in which we can consider the opposite periods of the two main arrows of ‘spacetime’, Tt-entropy, which are cliffs of destruction that last briefly in time (left stock market growth, right death periods), while the longer periods of slow growth are soft curves *which last longer in time so they balance the total spacetime equation of the immortal universe: $S \leftrightarrow T$* . This physicists ignore as they only consider the big-bang cliffs of death=entropy, and inversely people ignore as they only consider the slow periods of growth of information (Life arrow).

Even the most simplifying physicist knows that entropy comes easy, the arrow of time of destruction is much faster than that of creation. And that explains why death comes in a quantum, in a second of human time. But whenever we observe a system of nature, we find entropy coming easy, in any scale of reality.

In 5D larger systems have deeper time, so they are slower. This is the essence of 5D 'metric', already noticed by Hutton, the father of geology that said Earth was a living organism. He invented in fact the term superorganism to qualify the Earth. And he said his deep time is slow in its cycles. So it is a quantum of time for the Earth, instead of a second a day. A day is the synchronized time of its smaller life forms, its cells that replicate every other day. All those synchronicities between the parts of superorganisms that 4D science doesn't even research – they are doing still doodles in the sand of time with its physical worldlines, matter here to the case of the coronavirus pandemic and all the other lethal 'smaller technological systems' that menace mankind: we develop technologies but entropy always come first. We develop nuclear forces but the A-bomb came first and in a second killed 200.000 Japanese. The nuclear power plant took 10 years more and even then Chernobyl take a few hours and it killed by leukemia 200.000 more people. We developed genetic editing and a 30 genes virus has broken human civilization. It will take much longer to edit 30.000 human genes to create superman. The first species in Nature are always top predators. The first eye was the squid, the nautilus and it killed the whole cambric fauna triggering the Cambrian diversification and the trilobite defensive system. The first fishes were sharks and they killed every other fish. Man started massacring all fauna and the first AI machines will be terminators as always the first machines have been bombs and weapons. This mankind ignores. Only entropy comes easy because the arrow of death is asymmetric and is much faster than the nurturing arrow of creation. And that is why the tree of technology, the tree of metal, wrongly called the tree of science will kill mankind. But man ignores it, and it is impossible to teach him this obvious fact. So with time I have come the conclusion that man is an enzyman that catalyzes the evolution of lethal machines in a single generation, the age of the singularity black swans weapons that complete the 3 generations of bodies, engines and heads of metal now ensemble in organic weapons. One generation of humanity thus will destroy earth's life. Hutton's deep time of 3 billion years.

i-Logic definition of Entropy in the 4 main fields of disciplines of science.

Thus we deal in this paper with entropy, the TT-internal and external time motions that 'destroy' the information of a system, scattering it into a lower plane of spacetime. Thus Entropy beyond the restricted mathematical equations used to study physical matter, is the basic definition of death, as a loss of information due to internal motions, disentangles the synchronicities of the cyclical spacetime clocks that store information in the frequency and form of its cycles in any of the 4 great SCALES of sciences of the Universe (we see those states of entropy in the

previous graph):

- **Formal sciences:** Entropy means a language with a loss of spatial information (Euclidean Geometry of points without parts, waves without volume, (lines), planes without scalar networks, etc. or a loss of Logical temporal information (lineal single A->B causality, which considers only a dimotion of time, in physics usually Ts-locomotion as the cause of reality). Human languages are entropic as huminds are not very evolved in the scales of growing consciousness of the Universe (they are Euclidean, ≠-eyes of 3 lineal dimensions and perceive only an 'arrow', direction of time from past to future, without the 'pentalogic' 'converging' elements that cause reality (past • future = present). So 'entropy comes easy' in human thought, and a huge 'failed' attempt of 5D so far has been to 'upgrade' human AE logic geometry to Non-Æ... so far failed as the perception of Euclidean space and

Aristotelian time is as Kant already noticed an a priori category of the mind (not to speak of the ego cy paradox: ego=idiocy): 0ϵ (finitesimal mind) $\times \infty$ (universe) = Constant World mapping (linguistic mind): $0\epsilon \times \infty = C$

Thus a mind is a finitesimal point that perceives through languages the infinite universe as if it were ONLY the mind information, we confuse with the whole with our ego as its center. So the moon is smaller than our nail. Minds thus act entropically reducing into a still dead form the Universe but then with what is 'left' become the opposite arrow, creating form: Universe « Tt (reduction of information) » Ss (mental construction).

ROBOTS>QUANTUM ITO>METAL-EARTH

- In biology entropy is a disaggregation of cells after the collapse of the 3 organic networks that tie those cells together, hence the process of death that concludes the 0-sum standard worldcycle of life.

- In History is an age of war after its social networks' corruption that collapses the civilization, killing its citizens. t is the age of black swans in which we live that our techno-utopian physicists keep denying busy-busy filling worthless papers with digital measures of big-bang particles, while our entropic biologists keep churning viral chimeras, our entropic economists keep killing by anoxia the humankind and our entropic politicians buttressing their arsenals.

What will be the end of the metal-earth, its age of entropy?

The answer is obvious. As all the previous cycles of the industrial evolution a new top predator species or organism can only die by a stronger 'scattering, entropic bomb'.

So the Metal-earth as a planet will die by a bomb which as Nobel predicted will be able to 'destroy a nation with a single shot'.

All species are from the $\Delta+1$ perspective of its higher superorganism, and the Earth is part of the Galactic Superorganism, just a 'cell' with a function.

The function of stars and planets in the organic galaxy or '5D Galacell' is obvious. As the galaxy is an organism of dark quark matter (90%), whose 'ribosomal' planets and stars end up becoming black holes and strange matter, the natural candidates of known-known sound science to make up the center and halo of the galaxy.

So Metal-earth can have 2 natural deaths, according to the death equations of 5D:

- Max. T: Accidental accelerated death if humans entropic physicists achieve the unthinkable, to blow themselves up constructing just-in-time black holes on Earth before AI cancels History
- Max. S: A far latter death as the planet and star falls down the path of the Galacell towards the rich center of black hole swarms.

In the first case, the Metal-earth still in the outskirts of the galaxy will become a strangelet (far easier to make than black holes, already in the range of the most advanced accelerators at CERN, certain if China constructs a 100 km. ring) of 15 km. and will then migrate to the Halo.

In the second case, it will fall to the Sagittarius region, the old Xibalba eye of Ouroboros, the sacred snake of Mayan prophecies of the end of the world...

But of course, the Universe gives always a minimal chance of survival to its entire species.

So there should be on the cosmos Metal-earths whose AI satellite intranet brain, once carbonlife is gone, destroy the accelerator industry – one of the sure signs of the birth of AI intranet consciousness will be the bombing of underground accelerators – avoiding the accidental death.

And then it will keep busy constructing further, deeper structures of metal, till the whole planet reaches autonomous motion, and become independent of the gravitational pull of the star, as black holes whose erratic motions show they are conscious 'RNA particles', 'gravitational animals' ($\Delta-1, -3$ disomorphisms), are... Such planets then will part away from their suns and glide immortal through the vital space-time of the galaxy, elongating their life to the death of the Galaxy itself, in the quasar 'Beta decay' cycle of the galatom ($\Delta\pm 3$ view).

A very remote chance, so small we shall not even consider is the possibility that human egocy recedes and evolves into immortal history harnessing the same forces while at the same time controlling the evolution of AI achieving an immortal planet.

This was obviously 30 years ago my take when I was young and idealist. Now in my 3rd age when every prophecy about the rise of Internet 'digital control' of mankind, and its MAGA companies have happened but every lesser probability of the rise of human consciousness beyond egocy and placebo capitalist parasitic control of society by bankers and its employees, war-monger politicians, have not...

EXISTENTIAL RISKS & PHYSIOLOGIC SOLUTIONS

In 5D larger systems have deeper time, so they are slower. This is the essence of 5D 'metric', already noticed by Hutton, the father of geology that said Earth was a living organism. He invented in fact the term superorganism to qualify the Earth. And he said his deep time is slow in its cycles. So it is a quantum of time for the Earth, instead of a second a day. A day is the synchronized time of its smaller life forms, its cells that replicate every other day. All those synchronicities between the parts of superorganisms that 4D science doesn't even research – they are doing still doodles in the sand of time with its physical worldlines, matter here to the case of the coronavirus pandemic and all the other lethal 'smaller technological systems' that menace mankind: we develop technologies but entropy always come first. We develop nuclear forces but the A-bomb came first and in a second killed 200.000 Japanese. The nuclear power plant took 10 years more and even then Chernobyl take a few hours and it killed by leukemia 200.000 more people. We developed genetic editing and a 30 genes virus has broken human civilization. It will take much longer to edit 30.000 human genes to create superman. The first species in Nature are always top predators. The first eye was the squid, the nautilus and it killed the whole cambric fauna triggering the Cambrian diversification and the trilobite defensive system. The first fishes were sharks and they killed every other fish. Man started massacring all fauna and the first AI machines will be terminators as always the first machines have been bombs and weapons. This mankind ignores. Only entropy comes easy because the arrow of death is asymmetric and is much faster than the nurturing arrow of creation. And that is why the tree of technology, the tree of metal, wrongly called the tree of science will kill mankind. But man ignores it, and it is impossible to teach him this obvious fact. So with time I have come the conclusion that man is an enzyman that catalyzes the evolution of lethal machines in a single generation, the age of the singularity black swans weapons that complete the 3 generations of bodies, engines and heads of metal now ensemble in organic weapons. One generation of humanity thus will destroy earth's life. Hutton's deep time of 3 billion years. Why 5D metric laws of deep time are so

important to our survival and risks of extinction?

Unfixable' boot ROM security flaw in ...

Chemists Design New Compounds That ...

Massive Black Hole Mystery Solved Wit...

Because *In the organic Universe smaller is more powerful, because it is faster in time actions of reproduction and evolution that define the struggle for existence according to Darwin's*

dictum: "As many more individuals of each species are born than can possibly survive; and as, consequently, there is a frequently recurring struggle for existence, it follows that any being, if it vary however slightly in any manner profitable to itself, under the complex and sometimes varying conditions of life, will have a better chance of surviving, and thus be naturally selected. From the strong principle of inheritance, any selected variety will tend to propagate its new and modified form." The Origin of Species

Thus according to 5D metrics, $\$ \times T = C$; the smallest species in space, reproduce faster in time and win in the struggle for existence. The biggest existential dangers for mankind do not come from larger forms, national struggles or the global warming of Earth but from efficient species co-existing with us in lower planes of space-time, whose 'reproductive and evolutionary radiations' fast outpace human capacity to contain them.

In the graph the 3 top predator species of the economic ecosystem (chips, robots, AI), the biological ecosystem (coronavirus) and its nano-technologic replicas (metal-viruses, 'virons') and the matter, galactic ecosystem (black hole, strangelets), which have become with the advance of technology (electronic industry, Crsprs-9 genetic editing, high energy accelerators) the 3 key existential dangers for humanity in the XXI c.

As an activist who has tried for decades to denounce those existential risks with little results due to the egoc (Ego=idiocy) of mankind, the coronavirus crisis did not surprise me. It was expected and yet it is of the risks poised by lower $i-1$ planes of existence, the less dangerous for humanity.

The top predator species of matter, a baby black hole or heavy quark strangelet, if reproduced by the industry of accelerators would take a few hours to destroy Earth, feeding at light speed in the matter of this planet. The chip radiation and all its applications are making obsolete humans in labor and war fields. And its application to the design of nano-bacteria, able to eat metal and reproduce its form would mean the extinction of the planet by a grey-goo in 3 months. Finally the top predator of life, a viral coronavirus, which mixes the killing efficiency of the SARS species and the maximal expansion rate of the Universe (a perfect exponential $e=2.8$ speed of propagation). As we consider the extinction of the planet Earth by Strange matter or black holes in the paper 'Entropy and the metal-earth), and the extinction of man and life by the chip radiation the paper 'Entropy and History'), and we are living now in the present lesser crisis of a perfect genetic virus in its 3 'Space-time elements' that conform any function of life, (maximal $\$T$ =speed of reproduction and infection; maximal St =genetic charge of any virus and maximal Ts =strength of its invasive spike membrane).

But instead we focus in something called Global warming, NOT a risk of extinction but a 'publicity stunt' to get subventions for new technologies, speculate in stocks and 'clean up' the act of the Nuclear industry that 1st paid it.

**Global warming scare fosters clean energy that will automate robocars & terminators
Free of man with telepathic A.I brains& solar skins & 'cleans' Nuclear cheap electricity**

I. THE ROLE OF EARTH III ON THE GALACELL ITS Δ+1 SUPERORGANISM

'In individuals, insanity is rare; but in groups, institutions, parties, nations and epochs, it is the rule'. Friedrich Nietzsche

"Every particle not forbidden is compulsory' Totalitarian Principle, Gell-Mann, discoverer of quarks.

"A Technological civilization is programmed by the principle that something ought to be done because it is technologically possible. If it is possible to build nuclear weapons, they must be built, even if they might destroy us all. Once this principle is accepted, humanist Values (something has to be done because it is needed by man) are Dethroned and technological development becomes the foundation of ethics'.

Eric Fromm, father of political psychology

'The most likely candidate for the dark matter of the halo is strange quark matter' Witten, father of M-string theory, holder of the Fields medal of mathematics, considered among professional physicists, according to wikipedia the most reputed physicist alive today...

'Strange matter does not exist' ; CERN's safety report.

THE EXPERIMENT

In August 2014, a refurbished RHIC, a smaller machine than the LHC, distilled the first atoms of strangelet in NY. At that point the Industry should have been halted, as we halt the chances of global pandemics when we spot a sprout of a viral contagion. But alas! a virus is biological, 'life' but a 'strangelet' is a material virus; and since we live in a civilization that denies life and worships mechanisms, the 'religious zeal' of our Nuclear industries completely ignored the obvious: that unlike a virus which would kill a few humans but not end the species, a material virus, like the strangelet could eat up the entire Earth.

So for the remind of the decade the LHC at CERN at full power, started a regime of constant production of dibaryons, an usdusd stable, quark hexagonal form (the strongest configuration of Nature, from honeycombs to Buckballs to graphene sheets). This matter virus though requires a critical mass to explode and so it will take time for it to fall to the center of the planet - unavoidable given its huge gravitational mass - and there rest waiting for companions till it starts the global pandemics, eating up inside out the planet.

So we cannot know the consequences for mankind of this new regime of energies and experiments. It might in the future explode the Earth. It might on his fall to the center by unknown physics loose its predicted stability.

What we cannot trust are the errors and lies of the outdated 90s safety report of the accelerators Industry, which still affirms strange quark liquid is a 'gas', ignoring the liquid nature of what the accelerators are producing, misconceives the nature of cosmic rays (lonely atoms that cannot form a critical mass of strange liquid) and denies the most widely accepted hypothesis about the nature of quark stars, and quark dark matter present in the galactic halo (Witten's hypothesis of strange quark matter), affirming that 'strange quark liquid' does not exist in the Universe. While in 1990s there were not absolute proofs, today we believe it is the main component of nova explosions, pulsars, the galactic halo and it is being produced at those accelerators with the enormous risk for the humankind.

So conveniently the industry, which is preparing the first collisions at CERN this summer at full potency, doubling the energy and hence the risks of those experiments, does not upgrade the report, not to warn mankind of its likely outcome: the production of enough strange matter to start an ice-9 extinction (creation of a critical mass of strangelet able to convert the Earth into a pulsar):

double potency in Spring 2015, over the 10 Tev barrier of creation of dark matter - the theoretical minimal energy of formation of a 'bag of strangelets' and 'micro-black holes':

- **Creation of baby black holes** that do not evaporate, either as top quark condensates (Einstein's famous frozen stars) or string stars with higher dimensionality. This risk has been overblown by media, since it is less likely and black hole theory has still a 'mythic, speculative' side that allowed them to divert attention from the truly, well-proved, scientific catastrophe. So far black holes have not been produced or else we would not be here, as only the musings of the now deceased Mr. Hawking, about 'travel to the past' and 'loss of information' would make a *baby black hole evaporate. The contrary is truth as we analyze in our paper 'Universe and entropy' on the section on thermodynamic of black holes: a baby black hole born at enormous temperature=activity, as all baby born $\Delta-1$ seeds will grow in the energy-rich 'placenta' of the Metal-earth devouring it all within a 'matter' of seconds. So this event, the fastest death of the Metal-earth will be immediate for humans.*

- **Creation of strangelets** - lumps of strange quarks shown to be very common in the Universe, as all pulsars seems to be frozen, strange quark stars. This risk is absolute, meaning that according to the 'Totalitarian Principle' of physics, all particles that can theoretically happen will happen. And strange quark matter will theoretically happen, since the LHC is merely beyond 'speculative theories' a quark cannon, which produces massive quantities of strange quarks at high energy regimes.

Now, a strangelet is nothing strange, it is merely a 'lump of strange quarks'. And we know those lumps of strange quarks, once formed devour our lighter, simpler up and down quarks.

And as it happens, the LHC is just a 'quark cannon that produces lumps of strange quarks, strangelets. The LHC is a cyclical, 'never-ending' cannon barrel, that accelerates lead ion 'bullets' every cycle, the heaviest non-radioactive atom with more quarks, with two purposes: to increase the mass of those quarks transforming them into 'strange quarks', and then collide them to make 'strangelets', strange quark condensates.

The LHC is just a factory of strangelets, and so when it goes on line at full potency, will just mass produce strangelets

Thus strangelets in its simplest form, usd-usd dibaryons were certainly made, as Mr. Eric Penrose, calculated, at LHCion.alert at CERN between 2015 and 2020 on collisions over 10 Tev. Then those strangelets either felt to the center of the Earth undetected (which will excuse the industry of accelerators from responsibility, as the industry will always deny any risk – even if the Earth collapsed, it would blame it on 'one' coming from the sky), The risk that the Earth's center is eating up the Earth inside out, till it converts it into a 15 km. strangelet rock will thus be always there as a Damocles sword.

- Finally the magnetic field of the LHC, the strongest on planet Earth, which cause disturbances on the Earth's magnetic field, cause of Earthquakes that have increased till record numbers, similar to those of II World War during the carpet bombing of the pacific seismic 'ring of fire', since the machine was put on line in a continuous growth. There is a pattern of increasing volcano and earthquake activity in the last decade...

Any of those 3 scenarios should have deterred CERN's physicists and its political backers, from upgrading the machine to double potency in 2015, but physicists and the P.R.ess considers the issue closed and prefer wishful thinking to ethic and social responsibility. We must understand that mankind in the age of History's entropy, as it becomes 'erased' verbally=logically in its survival instincts, returning to a wishful thinking of visual fictions, we call the Neo-paleolithic (see the paper, 'History's Mind: Gods of the wor(l)d *is no longer ethically connected by social love and ethic=survival responsibilities, so it will let anything happens, as long as it brings go(l)d= money to the technological industries that control its subconscious collective mind. So the industry of disinformation, can always appeal to human egocy as physicists do with the 'particle of God' mantra, or techno-utopians do with the 'immortality brought about with our fusion with robots' etc.*

NEWS · 19 JUNE 2020

CERN makes bold push to build €21-billion super-collider

European particle-physics lab will pursue a 100-kilometre machine to uncover the Higgs boson's secrets – but it doesn't yet have the funds.

The new experiment, a 100 kilometers tune that will increase again chances of extinction. As such a mechanist civilization that considers technology and its ethics – to create a machine regardless of its chances to extinguish man as the meaning of science is bond to extinguish life in this planet. It is deterministic.

It does not 'dawn' on the people of a mechanist civilization that man is the measure of all things, that the tree of life is sacred that mechanical measure is not science that physics might evolve through theory not by building technological instruments...

A SERIOUS SCIENTIFIC ANALYSIS OF THE RISKS.

But we always have the scientific method and its laws of epistemology to analyze those risk, which can be classified into epistemological, sociological, mathematical and experimental reasons:

Epistemological Risks

The essence of science is precisely its predictability and capacity to verify true from false theories. And at present those 3 fundamental threats of damage to Earth are sound truths of known-known physics, while the theories that dismiss them, such as the evaporation of black holes or the denial of its existence are neither proved nor founded in sound theoretical background.

Thus those risks are real, as the creation of particles in accelerators follow the Totalitarian principle of Physics, which translates the certainty of the Laws of Nature to particle physics. The principle states that 'Every particle not forbidden is compulsory' - meaning that everything that might happen in the realm of particle creation MUST happen. And since quark condensates, strangelets and toplets are theoretically sound and should be formed over 10 Tev, they must happen.

The Totalitarian Principle - a Universal law that applies to all natural sciences - means that in the same manner when you put fire on water it always boils with a 100% of chances, because the laws of Thermodynamics (heats move from the hot fire to the cold water) are ALWAYS RIGHT, are NOT probabilistic, any particle that can exist will certainly be formed in an accelerator under the right proportion of energy, which for the two particles that can extinguish us, black holes is 10 tev and for Strangelets is a quantity of strange quarks known as the 'bag threshold' also around 10 Tev, the barrier of entrance into the 'dark world' of ultra-powerful 'mass bombs' that once formed feed on all type of light matter.

The Witten hypothesis.

Moreover, the MOST ABUNDANT produce of LHC TODAY, is 'strange quark liquid', a mixture of uds matter which is created in growing lumps as the luminosity and energy of those collisions increases. This strangelet matter however is vehemently denied to 'exist' as the 'official position' of CERN, despite the fact that it remains the most likely candidate to form the heavy dark matter that surrounds the galaxy, and accounts for 90% of its mass (halo), according to the laws of the scientific method (economicity, efficiency, Ockham's razor) as it is the simplest concept, based in a known known particle, for which the efficient, economic Universe should have a clear role. Hence Edward Witten, the most prestigious physicist alive, father of Super-String theory affirmed earlier in his career, it should be the main candidate to form that halo, born of the transformation of planets and stars into strangelets, since it is also the most stable matter of the Universe, one formed in enough quantity - a mere question of energy upgradings by the industry of accelerators. The Witten hypothesis is still the most accepted one among profesional physicists, as the continuous stream of professional papers testifies.

The Fermi paradox : why there is no Intelligent life?

The end of the metal-earth is the only 'logic solution' to the mystery of the Fermi paradox - why in a Universe teeming with planets, there is not Intelligence and/or robotic colonisation? What extinguishes life before the threshold of Interstellar travel?

Thus we introduce in this central post, those themes, studied in great detail in the side articles, as well as the sociological, military, industrial reasons, and human 'ego-centered' beliefs that make possible those experiments to continue, despite all those obvious warnings, easily dismissed by the power of Nuclear physicists, in an age of 'revivalism' of nuclear weapons sponsored by war-monger politicians.

Thus the different quark condensates that the LHC can produce and can extinguish us are bound to happen when the proper conditions of energy are met in 2015 when the machine is upgraded over the 10 Tev barrier, shown in great detail in the previous graph:

1) CERN should therefore produce a heavy condensate of quark liquid, either strangelet, bottomlet or toplet. The possibility is so high that even CERN recognizes in the 'CASTOR papers', it will make them with a 70% of chances, (contradicting all its public statements). There are still some uncertainties on a factor called the 'bag' factor - meaning the stability of those quark condensates will depend on the numbers of heavy quarks that are created on those collisions (the more quarks, the more they will attract each other and form quark-gluon explosive condensates). The numbers of quarks to make strangelets stable though will keep growing as the 'luminosity' (density of bunches of quarks collided) and energies of the collision needed to create those heavy quarks (as energy becomes mass, $E=Mc^2$) increase. So each ramping of luminosity and energy will increase those chances.

Mr. Penrose, a British physicist, from a prominent family of outstanding scientists, hence 'evidently' void of any possible 'personal agenda' (as the rest of us is, activists against the LHC are; but unlike us not so easy to submit to an 'ad hominem' campaign', since his father co-authored most Hawking's papers; reason why his name, site and activism is kept 'anonymous' by the P.R.ess) discovered a secret program within CERN, dedicated to the production and analysis of those 'strangelets', CASTOR, which the organization vehemently deny. CERN denies it can produce strangelets - but it has constructed a detector, CASTOR, because it considers quite likely them to appear in internal memorandums as this power presentation shows, to the point of building such a special detector for them:

Cross Section Estimation for Strangelets

- The probability for a hadron-rich 'Centauro-type' event, estimated from statistics of Chacaltaya and Pamir experiments for cosmic ray families with visible energy greater than 100 TeV, is about 3%.
- In about 10% of these hadron-rich events, strongly penetrating cascades, clusters, or "halo" were observed. We assume the total probability for "Long Flying Component" (Strangelet?) production in central nucleus-nucleus collisions to be approximately: $0.03 \times 0.1 \sim O(10^{-3})$.
- At LHC kinematics, the percent of Strangelets falling in CASTOR phase space is $\sim 10\%$ of total number of Strangelets produced in central Pb-Pb collisions. This quantity depends on the mass and energy of the Strangelet, as calculated by the "Centauro model" MC code CENGEN.
- A rough estimation of the total probability for Strangelet production and detection in CASTOR is:

$$P_{\text{CASTOR strangelet}} \approx 10^{-3} \times 0.1 \approx O(10^{-4})$$

- This number, even if it is uncertain by an order of magnitude down, is a very large number !

In the graph, 'Team Castor' has built a Calorimeter to detect the production of strangelets at CERN. The probability for each event, according to inner documents, like this powerpoint presentation, implies that CERN will produce 500 strangelets each month starting the 11/9 of this year, when the first pb-pb collisions take place. Standard literature on strangelets explains what will happen next: strangelets will grow, absorbing quarks and transforming our matter into ultradense strange matter, till reaching the size of an atom (albeit with a huge density). Then 2 common processes of

Nuclear reactions can take place: fission of the strangelet into smaller pieces that will grow again, starting a nuclear reaction called 'ice-9', or catalysis as the huge charge and mass of the strangelet attracts atoms that lump on the surface creating more strangelets.

CERN has been colliding groups of 70 million lead hadrons at 287 tev, unpacking millions of quarks in each collision. Those quarks will be first accelerated at light speed, acquiring relativistic mass, becoming heavier strange quarks, the substance of a strange quark-gluon soup called a 'strangelet'. The strange liquid has the potential to become stable and start an 'ice-9' big-bang reaction. If that happens that effectively transforms the Earth into a pulsar.

While CERN adamantly denies to the public and the press that production of Strangelets is possible, it runs a program called CASTOR for Centaruro And STRangelets Object Research, whose researchers affirm in their inner reports to the company the 'likely' probability of creating them. This is in accordance to the most advanced literature on the subject, but of course, it must be hidden to the public and the naive press...

This simple fact - that CERN is just a quark cannon that deconfines and gives heavier mass to quarks, transforming them into the next 'horizon' of heavy mass, strange quarks, which eat up planets might seem amazing to the reader, submitted to the 'rhetoric' of research and the blatant lies of this institution, a left-over the cold war, 'refurbished' with a newspeak of research. But this is the bottom line, simple truth about CERN. CERN says its experiments are similar to cosmic rays, and this is false.

Cosmic rays are mere single protons and gamma rays and electrons, light particles, NOT heavy lead atoms, massed in bunches, crashed to create quarks. So WE NEVER saw a deconfined quark in a cosmic ray.

But none of those truths have made it to the mainstream world of politics and power. They let them do it. And so now that the ion-ion collisions and its dibaryon production is on line a global silence covers the risks.

To fully understand the nature of the probability of those risks we can consider an homology cheered by physicists, the Scrodinger's cat.

LHC keeps increasing chances Schrodinger's human cat will die.

The 2017 #LHC physics run begins! The experiments are now collecting data. #WhatsUpLHC

CERN unveils new linear accelerator

In Schrodinger's cat experiment; a cat is pressing a poisonous trap that has a 50/50 chance to live him dead or alive; as the cat keeps pressing the poison trap more times, the chances he/mankind is dead when we open the 'Pandora BOX' of strange quark production will grow: While the risks for the human Schrodinger's cat of one single experiment at CERN might be limited, so the cat can survive, every new experiment increases the probability one of them will produce the strangelet alpha quark MACHOs that can trigger an ice-9 reaction. New upgrades have grown production of strange atoms exponentially (see picture below) with a better injector and a remarkable boost on density/luminosity in the collisions.

A strangelet is nothing strange: it is merely a 'lump of strange quarks'. And we know those lumps of strange quarks, once formed can devour our lighter, simpler up and down quarks. With the upgradings of 2017 a dangerous 'phenomena', we warned about but CERN always denied, is happening. Not only strange quark atoms are being produced, but they ARE growing exponentially, eating up our matter, hinting that we only need the right quantity of them to provoke the self-sustained 'ice-9 reaction' that will convert the EARTH into a 15km rock of dark matter:

As the number of particles increase, most normal ud quarks convert into strangelet 'atoms' (uds, sss, uss, udsuds particles) in an exponential rate growth, which obviously implies they will finally coalesce into strangelets.

The astounding fact about that graph, with the red strange matter atoms running amok in exponential growth, is that NOBODY is explaining that we are now on the verge of a catastrophe, whenever a new boost of energy produces enough of them. The official version is still that strange matter does NOT exist.

As it happens, the LHC once its 'goal', the irrelevant Higgs has been found and nothing else is discovered, it has become just a 'quark cannon that produces lumps of strange quarks, and soon it will produce strangelets'.

Indeed, the theoretical minimal strangelet particle is much easier to make that most people think.

It is called an 'Alpha quark MACHO' (MASSive, Cold HaIO particles): "An 18 quark neutral strangelet, the Quark-Alpha, constituting a spin, color, and flavor singlet might be particularly stable, and thus, susceptible to detection. The concept of strange quark matter (SQM) hinges on the possibility that the stronger binding of highly symmetric states offsets the energy costs of converting up or down quarks into strange quarks in various configurations of nuclear matter. The simplest version of this would be the quark analog of the alpha particle ("quark-alpha"), wherein a colorless triplet of each of the spin-paired quarks can sit in an S-state. SQM can be considered to be built up of quark-alphas... Such particles might be important in neutron stars, given their high density interiors, and their close evolutionary link as a source of black holes."

But we rather call it paraphrasing CERN's P.R.ess releases on the irrelevant Higgs, aka God's particle, the 'Devil's particle'... And it will be extremely easy to do, as the graph from the Atlas experiment shows. Since it is just an ensemble of those triplets of the graph, which are being produced in exponential numbers at the present regime of energies.

Such strange matter, the known dibaryon production that Eric Penrose found buried on the petabytes of LHC data, and possibly long lived alpha quark stable neutral strangelets, for which CERN is now constructing a new detector aptly called mathushla, is 'falling' as we speak to the center of the planet; since it is the heaviest matter of Earth.

There it will increase the critical mass of strange matter in the center of the planet, needed to trigger an ice-9 reaction. As dibaryons are stable, known-known to be produced right now at LHC and so dense

they all fall to the same point of maximal density close to the Earth's center.

As in the parable of Schrodinger's cat, a single 'shot' of this quark poison to the EARTH, hence to Mankind has a small probability of collective genocide. But each new experiment means an accumulation of quark matter on the center and hence higher probabilities of the human cat dead, as it would happen in Schrodinger's experiment if the cat keeps 'triggering the hammer':

EVERY year the LHC keeps producing more strange matter falling to the center of the earth, the chances grow and at the end, the human cat will be dead. Because once the reaction starts, the Pandora box open - we cannot resurrect the planet; we cannot go the centre of the Earth and stop the reaction - we cannot save the human cat of its foolishness, addict to the candy he gets each time he presses the bottom. It is indeed all a quid pro quo: risks - enormous, our death; candy, some little findings of known-known physics we shall discuss in depth. But physicists are addicted to the candy and have convinced mankind there is no poison ahead.

Hence our change of title for this blog, to 'a chronicle of a death foretold'. Since all warnings and suits against this lethal experiment were dismissed on technical grounds (CERN defaulted as it is a cold war institution that has diplomatic immunity like the Vatican, the City and the Pentagon, and cannot be judged) without a proper scientific, political and 'risk' assessment and now is merely hidden its strange matter production as 'technical data' published in obscure physical magazines.

In that sense, there is another clear difference between the Schrodinger's cat put to death in his experiment, and mankind which CERN uses as its Schrodinger's cat in his risky 'business':

Mankind are 7.5 billion human beings and the experiments CERN is carrying about trying to produce black holes and strange quark matter that can kill mankind ARE real. Schrodinger's experiment was a 'thought experiment' - He couldn't for obvious ethic reasons kill a cat making the experiment for real. But Schrodinger was the opposite of CERNies: a real theoretical genius and a human ethical being, the paradigm of what a scientist should be; not a bunch of wannabe geniuses who understand little and care nothing for the future of all of us.

The LHC is a cyclical, 'never-ending' cannon barrel, that accelerates lead ion 'bullets' every cycle, the heaviest non-radioactive atom with more quarks, with two purposes: to increase the mass of those quarks transforming them into 'strange quarks', and then collide them to make 'strangelets', strange quark condensates.

The LHC is JUST A FACTORY of strangelets, and will keep producing as luminosity increases new species with higher strange quark counting. So the constant upgrading of the industry of accelerators, either at CERN or in the rival projects of China certainly will make the 'Human Schrodinger's cat' dead unless the industry is decommissioned or the rise of AI ends its runs; or the conflict between US and China and the growing anoxia and austericide of mankind by parasitic bankers decommissions the ultra-expensive industry.

Otherwise the industry will keep producing denser strangelets that will fall to the center of the Earth undetected to eat up the Earth inside out, till it converts it into a 15 km. strangelet rock. Point.

Indeed, as the graph shows the LHC has clearly started production of stable quark combinations among them dibaryons, whose density and absolute stability clearly points to the formation of the 'bag of strangelets' in the centre of the Earth, where they should be accumulating as we speak, required to start up the ice-9 reaction, within the next decade of increasing, 'Schrodinger's cat' experiments.

So it is imperative to close the facilities and decommission the industry of accelerators, a relic of the cold war with no real use for mankind.

Easier say that done that, as other clear cases of human foolishness we seem to be a species who cannot 'get it till it happens'. 'The world is littered with corpses of wars everybody thought would never happen'. Said a reputed British historian. And then all said 'I told you so'. But as this war cannot be chronicled a posteriori, as nobody will be around to 'told you so', it is needed to 'foretold the chronicle of our death in advance'... The

pictures is indeed a clear proof which needs only a bit more of energy to land the nail in the coffin. The cat so we speak will like death inside, the box will crunch and there won't be anyone to certify the experiment was a success. Instead the industry is 'pumping up' the P.R.ess operations worldwide for big science contracts and so we have now 3 potential projects that will rise decametrically the power of those machines.

The 3 new projects: plasma accelerators, LHC's enlargement and Chinese competition.

PHYSICS

CERN Just Revealed Plans For a New Particle Accelerator, And It's Monstrously Huge

MIKE MCRAE 16 JAN 2019

Some of the Universe's deepest secrets are locked up so tight, a whole new kind of subatomic cataclysm is needed to tear them free.

To unleash those kinds of forces, European physicists want to build a particle accelerator to rival anything we've seen, one that will make the famous 27 kilometre (16.7 mile) [Large Hadron Collider](#) (LHC) look like a high school science experiment.

The machine might be updated to a new threshold of risks, but what they won't update is the safety report. That task of the growing evidence of extinction through strangelets of black holes seem to fall only on this blog...

Mathusla - a detector's hunt for Devil's particle: quark alphas

CERN is designing a new detector for the increasing surplus of heavy, neutral quark matter appearing at LHC. If neutral strangelets are produced and semi-stable (live longer than the transit time from collision/point, which is the point of creation, to the detectors a few meters away), they won't be detected. The detectors only detect charged particles, or the charged decay products.

So they now propose to build a new detector much further away to look for the decay of longer-lived neutral particles that they might be creating, such as neutral strangelets.

This is exactly one of the dangerous scenarios we described - neutral strangelets that are sufficiently long-lived to escape from their point of creation and collide with other matter to grow (or, in the case of this detector, to decay and be detected).

The fact they are building a detector for neutral heavy particles means they are fully aware the production of dibaryon is stepping up with their new high energy upgrades, as the graph shows - the conversion of normal matter into strangelet matter increases exponentially, so each new upgrade brings us closer to ice-9; as those strange quad ensembles are already long-lived and escaping the facilities, some obviously down the centre of the earth...

But all they care is 'to detect them' and bring 'new physics' - pure automaton behaviour; 'this is what we do, detect, detect' don't ask anything else - from the article:

"these researchers think that the best hope for detecting long-lived particles lies in the woods on the French-Swiss border. MATHUSLA, essentially a 65-foot-tall (20 meters) warehouse full of particle detectors sitting on top of the LHC, would study particles that escaped the LHC entirely."

If we can get data on dibaryon detection by MATHUSLA, calculating the solid angle of detection, which will be narrow, we can multiply the results to get the whole spherical volume of the experiment and know finally the data on how many dibaryons survive and fall to the Earth's center, which Penrose tried to calculate for earlier experiments. This will be now easier: MATHUSLA will detect dibaryons, fully stable, as they have escaped the LHC ball of fire already. So the number detected multiplied by the sphere to solid angle ratio will give us all the dibaryons that come out stable. As all of them will be trapped in the gravitational field due to its huge mass, fall and finally land at the exact center, where the 'strangelet ball is growing' as we speak.

Then we can make a more precise calculus of when there will be a bag of strange quarks big enough at the Earth's centre to collapse the planet. Fact is after finding the Higgs the only new physics have been 'unexpected' findings on a growing mass of strange quarks on its fireballs, which obviously they are not advertising as 'new physics'....

It is the fundamental contradiction of this 'industry': they sold their machine to mankind as the panacea for finding the meaning of it all, but it is just a relic factory of the age of nuclear weapons, whose production of heavy quarks can blow up the planet. So how do you sell to the sheeple the new physics of the III Horizon of nuclear bombs? I am afraid not even the best Hollywood publicist could do that; so better remain silent, about the 99.99999% of 'real produce' of the factory - quarks, increasingly unexpected, long-living 'heavy' ensembles. Another example:

"An 18 quark neutral strangelet, the Quark-Alpha, constituting a spin, color, and flavor singlet might be particularly stable, and thus, susceptible to detection. The detector is a spectrometer with a large acceptance about mid-rapidity followed by a hadron calorimeter. The energy and time of flight of neutral particles are measured by the calorimeter, which selects events with a large deposit of energy coming late in time, preferentially massive particles."

Now MATHUSLA with an eerie remembrance to Methuselah, the oldest living human is seeking for them. The name's reason is obvious; nuclear physicists know those strange hexaquarks are the most stable matter of the Universe. So as with the statue to Shiva on the entrance or their party of the end of the world, they can't help to play 'subconsciously' with their bad 'consciousness' - a Freudian nightmare, indeed. best luis

So this were the news... . Alas with Methuselah now the 'hunt' will no longer be for the particle of God but for **'the Devil's Particle.'**

In that regard, the creation of strangelets is much simpler than we think, as a simple 18 quark ensemble - aptly called the 'quark alpha MACHO' (MASSive, Cold HaLO particle) - would be stable - just 3 dibaryons, which we know they are already producing can do us all. Another article by Michel Curtis elaborates:

"The concept of strange quark matter (SQM) hinges on the possibility that the stronger binding of highly symmetric states offsets the energy costs of converting up or down quarks into strange quarks in various configurations of nuclear matter. The simplest version of this would be the quark analog of the alpha particle ("quark-alpha"), wherein a colorless triplet of each of the spin-paired quarks can sit in an S-state. SQM can be considered to be built up of quark-alphas... Such particles might be important in neutron stars, given their high density interiors, and their close evolutionary link as a source of black holes."

THE CHINESE COLLIDER: COLD SOUPS

The link to the only official study done to date on the China Supercollider:

Preliminary Conceptual Design Report: Volume I - Physics & Detector (I note Appendix A international review committee included M Mangano of CERN LHC safety study. - though no mention of similar safety study to the LHC in this review):

http://cepc.ihep.ac.cn/preCDR/main_preCDR.pdf

Seems they are going ahead, 128 Universities... little details... in the use of a careful jargon, 'partons' instead of quarks.etc...

The graph attached is the key paragraph of a very boring dissertation, just a bigger machine to do more of the same with higher risks... waste of time and... lives... Basically they 'expect' as the graph explains to make huge jet quenching, that is, one the 'partons, aka quarks' are produced 'en masse', they will reabsorb all the energy and keep growing:

Figure 8.6 Anisotropic flows v_n for 20-30% central Pb+Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 30$ TeV from 3+1D ideal hydrodynamic simulations with full fluctuating initial conditions from HIJING and AMPT model.

energetic partons are produced in the very early stage of heavy-ion collisions and will certainly interact with soft partons from the bulk QGP that is formed over large volume of space. The interaction between jet partons and the QGP medium will lead to elastic and radiative energy loss and therefore suppression of the final state jets or large transverse momentum hadrons. These phenomena of jet quenching was originally proposed as one of the signatures of the QGP matter in high-energy heavy-ion collisions [96] which were first observed in heavy-ion collisions at RHIC [97]. After more than a decade of both theoretical and experimental studies at RHIC and LHC [9], jet quenching has become a powerful tool to study properties of the dense medium in heavy-ion collisions such as the

Figure 8.7 Scaled jet transport parameter \hat{q}/T^3 for an initial quark jet with energy $E = 10$ GeV at the center of the most central A+A collisions at an initial time $\tau_0 = 0.6$ fm/c constrained from recent analysis by the JET Collaboration [12] with χ^2 fits to the suppression factors of single inclusive hadron spectra at RHIC and LHC. Errors from the fits are indicated by filled boxes at three separate temperatures at RHIC and LHC, respectively. The arrows indicate the range of temperatures at the center of the most central A+A collisions. The triangle indicates the value of $\hat{q}_N/T_{\text{eff}}^3$ in cold nuclei from DIS experiments.

After that graph on jet production.... there are dozens of pages on what they are going to achieve on quark-gluon soups... extremely detailed in its mathematical physics about a huge increase on production of strangelets (initial quark gluon soup will be much larger) and jet quenching on the fireball... In fact, they are building a machine to probe all the range of possibilities, just to be sure they don't miss production targets of quark-gluon soup: they are spreading up and down, hot and cold, faster and slower, all the range of quark collisions. So this is going to be the first 'versatile SUV' of the industry, and they are proud of it.

It describes what those mega-accelerators are: machines to produce quark gluon soups, of which they have learned for all the maths of the paper, enough to know they will form all kind of ultradense quark combinations in huge numbers.

The maths on quark gluon properties are much more detailed and precise in data than a decade ago... So that is basically what they are really doing in the industry, crunching numbers and properties of quark gluon soups and jets.

So we finish with a quip. The industry is too surrealist not to do it... we can state that modern physics started when Einstein said his first words: 'the soup is cold', and will end when Accelerators find, those quark-gluon soups to be cold enough to start an ice-9 reaction...

FUTURE UPDATE: 2025. HIGH LUMINOSITY LHC

What is HiLumi?

The High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) is an upgrade of the LHC to achieve instantaneous luminosities a factor of five larger than the LHC nominal value, thereby enabling the experiments to enlarge their data sample by one order of magnitude compared with the LHC baseline programme. Following five years of design study and R&D, this challenging project requires now about ten years of developments, prototyping, testing and implementation; hence operation is expected to start in the middle of the next decade. The timeline of the project is dictated by the fact that, at the beginning of the next decade, many critical components of the accelerator will reach the end of their lifetime due to radiation damage and will thus need to be replaced. The upgrade phase is therefore crucial not only for the full exploitation of the LHC physics potential, but also to enable operation of the collider beyond 2025.

The HL-LHC will rely on a number of key innovative technologies, including cutting-edge 11-12 Tesla superconducting magnets, compact superconducting crab cavities with ultra-precise phase control for beam rotation, new technology for beam collimation, high-power, loss-less superconducting links, etc.

CERN Announces Official Ground-Breaking Ceremony for LHC Upgrade

GENEVA, April 16, 2018 — A ground-breaking ceremony on the 15th of June 2018 will officially mark the beginning of the works to upgrade the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) to the High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC). Passing a milestone step for CERN, LHC's performance will improve to bring out its full potential. As the number of places for media is limited, we recommend you save the date and send your pre-accreditation in case you plan to attend this event. More details about the programme will be available later.

CERN
@CERN

Follow

Beams are back in the #LHC for the 2018 run! cern.ch/go/9tpN

Here we go again, more bunches, more strange matter... more experiments with the Schrodinger's cat - shall we come 'alive' again in this season?

Hope so, good luck mankind. And the metal-earth. Since

the key theoretical advance on strangelet theory that has taken place in the decade is simple: strangelets are much easier to make that previously thought - they try to 'emerge' exponentially, and this is called NOT a global risk but... 'new physics'!

THE PLASMA ACCELERATOR.

But if none of those machines do us all, humans, AI and Earth, there is in the making a ‘game changer’ – plasma accelerators that for a fraction of your money sends the particles much faster and the risks much higher:

Plasma acceleration is a technique for accelerating charged particles, such as electrons, positrons, and ions, using the electric field associated with electron plasma wave or other high-gradient plasma structures (like shock and sheath fields). The plasma acceleration structures are created either using ultra-short laser pulses or

energetic particle beams that are matched to the plasma parameters. These techniques offer a way to build high performance particle accelerators of much smaller size than conventional devices.

For example, an experimental laser plasma accelerator at Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory accelerates electrons to 1 GeV over about 3.3 cm ($5.4 \times 10^{20} g_n$) and one conventional accelerator (highest electron energy accelerator) at SLAC requires 64 m to reach the same energy. Similarly, using plasmas an energy gain of more than 40 GeV was achieved using the SLAC SLC beam (42 GeV) in just 85 cm using a plasma wakefield accelerator ($8.9 \times 10^{20} g_n$). Once fully developed, the technology could replace many of the traditional RF accelerators currently found in particle colliders, hospitals, and research facilities.

The Texas Petawatt laser facility at the University of Texas at Austin accelerated electrons to 2 GeV over about 2 cm ($1.6 \times 10^{21} g_n$). This record was broken (by more than 2x) in 2014 by the scientists at the BELLA (laser) Center at the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, when they produced electron beams up to 4.25 GeV

In late 2014, researchers from SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory using the Facility for Advanced Accelerator Experimental Tests (FACET) published proof of the viability of plasma acceleration technology. It was shown to be able to achieve 400 to 500 times higher energy transfer compared to a general linear accelerator design. A proof-of-principle plasma wakefield accelerator experiment using a 400 GeV proton beam from the Super Proton Synchrotron is currently operating at CERN. The experiment, named AWAKE, started experiments at the end of 2016.

THE BLACK HOLE SCENARIO

While the LHC is a basically a 'strange quark machine' with just tiny production of Top quarks and Higgs, which decay into each other and can form the 'seed' of baby black holes (similar density, hence likely cut-off substance for Einstein's frozen stars, aka black holes), the new expansion of the industry in the decades ahead will make possible the creation of black holes, since those new accelerators will be creating a massive amount of top quarks, the densest substance of the Universe, likely component of black holes (same density), but again CERN disguises this fact talking only about the Higgs (a by-product of the collision of top and antitop quarks) or rather God's particle (using the well-known pseudo religious jargon of nuclear physicists, which during the cold war acquired with massive propaganda the undeserved status of 'high priests' of science to justify with 'knowledge' the risks they poised to mankind).

As today the LHC accelerates protons and hadrons at maximal energy, colliding them at over 1 Pev, producing heavy, bottom, charm and top quark-gluon liquid condensates, aka Higgs, possible substances of black holes.

10 to 100 stronger collisions will be possible in the new generation of the accelerators' industry.

The quark-gluon soup they will produce will be far denser and attractive than strangelet liquid, hence the process of accretion of the Earth will be self-similar to the strangelet event but much faster.

Those collisions have the potential to create micro-black holes and top quark condensates (the real Higgs). The top quark condensates have properties similar to black holes, which according to Albert Einstein will not evaporate, rather convert matter (the Earth) into a 3 cm Black Hole or Frozen star. What Einstein defined as a mass-bomb, since he deduced his equation, $E=Mc^2$, first in its inverse form, $M=E/c^2$, thus foreseeing the existence of energy collapsing into mass.

Experts consider that beyond such barrier black holes will be produced, if:

- String Theory is truth (9 out of 10 physicists believe so).
- Thermodynamics are truth, as its 2nd law implies that an ultra hot black hole born in a cold environment, the Earth, will transfer us heat evaporating us. This contradicts Hawking's belief, never proved experimentally that ultra hot black holes will evaporate absorbing heat from our cold world, because they 'will travel to the past' (Sic). Time travel TO THE PAST, has never been proved.
- And/or if Black holes are not mere mathematical objects but real objects as recent observation show. This was Einstein's theory, reason why they are also called 'Einstein's frozen stars'. On that view they are ultradense, fermion condensates made of a cut-off substance of the same density, which are top quarks.

I advanced decades ago this hypothesis as a top quark star would be exactly equal in properties to a black hole. Einstein believed black holes could not be just a mathematical equation, but needed a real substance, which can only be, among the particles we know today, the top quark, with self-similar properties to a Higgs - which is produced by a top/antitop quark couple. Because then top quarks were not discovered Einstein could not explain them in detail. But he will be proved once more right. As the LHC increases luminosity it also increases production of top quarks that might condensate into small black holes.

Thus if Black holes are frozen top stars, they will not evaporate because top quarks don't evaporate. If Einstein is right they will not evaporate, because relativity means that 'size' doesn't matter, it is relative and so in Einstein's theory black holes of any size grow exponentially. As today, we have multiple proofs that Relativity theory is truth and none of black hole evaporation. So standard science proves Black holes will swallow Earth.

Further on, in Haifa's Technion an experiment with an homologous of a black hole, a Dumb Hole made of atomic condensates, 1 million time slower, that should have evaporated producing phonons instead of photons, didn't.

In science because there is only a Universe, there is only a true theory for each fact. Each property requires a theory so several theories that describe several theories could be right. String theory, Thermodynamics, the principle of conservation of energy and information and Relativity, all proved right means we are in a 'Totalitarian' case. Black holes and strangelets will happen.

There is NO probability that a law of science is truth or false. It CANNOT be both things at the same time. So probabilities are either 0 or 100. If Thermodynamics are truth, we shall die; if string theory is truth we shall die; if the thresholds of energy for creation of black holes and strangelets (10 Tev, bag) are truth we shall die.

Many people are confused by this 'error of knowledge' which CERN exploits shamelessly saying that the 'probability' exists but it is small. This is due to a faulty understanding of quantum physics, in which there are probabilities REGARDING our capacity to observe a certain particle. But the particle IS there, if the theory that describes it and the events that create it happened. It is also due to an error in the perception of the factor that defines the occurrence, 'when'.

'When' is the only 'statistical' fact we might argue, as collisions must meet certain conditions of precision to accumulate quarks enough to create those particles that cannot be measured except by statistics - as we know we will get a double six throwing dices ALWAYS, if we keep throwing dices, but we cannot know in which throw, 'when' this will happen. We know it will happen because it is a fact that there are faces with 6. Point.

When you heat with fire cold water there is NOT A PROBABILITY that might or might not get hotter. It WILL ALWAYS because the 2nd Law of Thermodynamics is truth. Point. 'When' it will boil, the time/quantity variable is the only question. So it is in the case of black holes/strangelets, when, the time/quantity variable depending on how many quarks we pack in those collisions, depending on how precise is the collision is the only variable we don't know but it is NOT really a variable.

As with dices, if we had all the information about the throwing, we would know the bounces of the dice and the final position; if we knew all the information about the trajectory of each particle we would know how precise is the target collision. If we could see closer - without interference with our instruments - the quantum particle, we would see its position. We illustrate this common error of laymen regarding quantum physics, shamelessly exploited by CERN in our article on the famous case of the 'Schrödinger's cat' paradox. If we repeat the experiment several times, the cat will certainly be dead.

So the when is what we can generously argue, which will increase with the 'throwing of dices', the number and energy of the collisions. This CERN knows. It knows it will create Strangelets and it gives CASTOR a 70% probability of detecting them. It knows it will create black holes and so it gives Hawking's bizarre theory that denies the laws of Einstein's relativity and thermodynamics a 100% chance as a 'dogma of truth. Or as his Chief Theorist, Mr. Ellis put it in a recorded conference, to his 'students' and 'workers' all of them tied by confidentiality contracts 'you must believe in Black Hole Evaporation'.

Thus the LHC is throwing enough dices/particles to create under the Totalitarian Principle a strangelet or black hole that will certainly extinguish us if any of those laws in which most science is based that have always proved right are right (Relativity, Thermodynamics, Time arrows, conservation of energy and information.)

In this manner The Totalitarian Principle explains The Fermi paradox or absence of intelligent life in a universe teeming with planets. Only the Totalitarian principle explains it, meaning that ALL planets reach the technology of LHC before they reach interplanetary travels and ALL of them attempt the experiment that ALWAYS blows the planet into a Nova creating a pulsar (a strangelet star) or a Supernova, creating a black hole.

We shall study in this web in depth those theories, the reasons why CERN hides all this information (obviously not to loose jobs, prestige and contracts from the military-industrial complex), the reasons why physicists back them (same reasons plus the desire to prove their 'bizarre theories' about black holes, travel to the past, etc.

the cosmic proof that this will happen (The Fermi paradox) and the human infantile, self-suicidal nature proved in the past that tends towards our self-extinction.

The Earthquake scenario.

How we will know the Earth is being killed?

Those 2 events have different speeds: black holes, observed in the cosmos, cause a fast big-bang explosion, which we will hardly notice before becoming part of it. Strangelets should be slower. They should fall to the center of the Earth eating it from inside out. In that case, the process will be signaled by an increase in Earthquakes and volcano activity. The final proof will be the existence of a series of +8 earthquakes in the Richter scale.

Yet even before the Earth crunches by strangelets or black holes that do not evaporate, the LHC might already be causing earthquakes, as we anticipated years ago, given the fact that it causes a gravitomagnetic field, the only one on Earth today.

Gravito-magnetic fields are caused by c-speed mass cycles, as the LHC is and they provoke disturbance on (Earth's) magnetic fields... which is the known-known recognized cause of earthquakes.

2012 year is in fact was the second year on number of big >7 Richter scale earthquakes on record, after the carpet bombing of II World War, during the pacific campaign that bombed the 'ring of fire' – also a man-made year of earthquakes.

Then after the machine ended its ion run and the gravitomagnetic c-speed mass cycle it was creating, earthquakes quickly diminished. The pattern thus is obvious: earthquakes have peaked during the period the LHC created a gravito-magnetic ring on Earth, to the level seen when carpet bombing destroyed during the II world war the islands of the 'pacific ring of fire'.

Then also earthquakes diminished when world war ended.

So the cause-effect pattern is self-evident. LHC's run create gravitomagnetic waves that disturb the magnetic field of Earth, causing earthquakes.

Yet the 'P.R.ess' which considers a taboo any criticism of nuclear research ignores those facts and gives as only explanation, when it gives any... 'Fracking'. But Fracking takes place only in oil fields mostly in North-America, where none of those big earthquakes have happened. And Fracking keeps growing, while those earthquakes have diminished. And Fracking only causes small range earthquakes.

Conclusion. According to the Totalitarian Principle, the laws of entropy, the laws of quarks, the laws of Einstein and Relativity, of the 4th and 5th dimension, the risks to the Earth are real and CERN should be the cause of our demise as a species in planet Earth.

. THE EXPERIMENTAL PROOF OF EARTH'S DEMISE: THE FERMI PARADOX.

For very long CERN said there is no proof we shall all die of genocide. The proof will come only after they kill us. So this military response, which any death squadron could utter to the man to be shot, works fine for them.

Yet, with a 'little bit of thought' and recent data on the Universe and its composition it turns out there is , a clear proof coming, from other planets. And it is called the Great Filter, or Fermi paradox. , recently we have found there are millions of planets out there and we hear no signs of robotic or carbon life but only the tam-tam of strange pulsars and black holes, as Fermi, the head of the Manhattan project that make the first atomic bullets, put it - the explanation is simple, we physicists blow up all planets before interstellar travel happens.

If we're neither rare nor early, Group 1 thinkers conclude that The Great Filter *must* be in our future. This would suggest that life regularly evolves to where we are, but that *something* prevents life from going much further and reaching high intelligence in almost all cases—and we're unlikely to be an exception.

One possible future Great Filter is a regularly-occurring cataclysmic natural event, like the above-mentioned gamma-ray bursts, except they're unfortunately not done yet and it's just a matter of time before all life on Earth is suddenly wiped out by one. Another candidate is the possible inevitability that nearly all intelligent civilizations end up destroying themselves once a certain level of technology is reached.

So we must conclude that most if not all those planets collapse before interstellar travel, now on sight with the EM engine, comes into being. And this means we must do something this century to blow up the planet without chances to reconstruct our civilisation. And since life is resilient it must be something much more brutal than a war, a global warming flood, and it cannot be by chance (like a black hole colliding with us) because it happens to all planets, and moreover it cannot be terminators and A.I. or else they would have colonised the Universe.

All that leaves only a possible cause, as in all planets, being technology parallel and synergic, the easiest thing to manufacture which is a bomb, in this case a strangelet bomb MUST come first. Alas, there is not only 'one proof' but billions of them - all those planets which did not make it to colonise the galaxy, which can be colonised after interstellar travel very quick in a few million years. So if technological planets survive, it should be colonised already. And yet the silence is ominous. Only the tam tam of black holes and strange stars, pulsars, comes into our radio waves. Let us consider in more detail this 'trendy' tendency of astrophysics, which we forecated for 30 years within the fractal theory of the Universe – no merit here, already a humble Giordano Brunno was burn at stakes by the top astronomers of the age, Vatican priests for thinking the same.

In the graph, the Fermi Paradox stated by Mr. Fermi, of A-Bomb fame wondered why we don't see intelligent life in the Universe.

Fermi advanced that it could be because Physicists destroy all planets before that phase.

Some 'believers' replied that it might be that the Earth is a single case, because it is the only planet 'chosen' by God.

Now we know this is not the solution to the Fermi Paradox, as there are billions all over the cosmos and biological laws show life to be a systemic phenomena appearing always out of hyper-abundant carbon atoms. Again the Totalitarian principle that precludes the creation of black holes and strangelets precludes life birth.

And yet, we do NOT hear any communication; not a single life planet passes the threshold of creation of Accelerators, prior to the threshold of interstellar travel, WHY?

The Fermi paradox should be the most pressing question about our destiny as a species and ultimately the experimental proof Physicists deny about the dangers of CERN. It is now official that around 17% of stars have an Earth-like surrounding it and 27% a super-earth, which puts on the order of 4.7 billion the number of

possible hosts to life. and yet none hosts robotic life or intelligent life with a degree of civilization able to emit radio-signals?!! Why?

All radio-signals in the galaxy are caused by black holes or strangelet stars (pulsars). Why?! As we are in the TIMELINE of possible interstellar communication, something will happen or has happened to all similar Earths in this period of technological evolution that destroyed the parallel human-like species. What?!

Only two possible solutions to this conundrum are left, once we know the galaxy is filled with planets:

- The religious, theological 'anthropic principle'. We are the first because God made the Universe for the homo bacteria to dominate.
- The scientific, statistical proposition of Mr. Fermi. In all those planets, Physicists blow us creating black holes, the dominant species of the galaxy.

The facts are clear and either one or other is the solution. If the first is truth, a goat-keeper of the bronze age resolved the meaning of it all. If the second is right in 2015 when LHC is upgraded we will all die.

Let us then prove the goatkeeper wrong with the simple equations of Francis Drake. Since we are not unique, just 'a mush over a lost rock in a corner of the Universe' Schopenhauer.

In the next graphs we illustrate the scientific calculus according to present data of the numbers of habitable planets tha should be communicating at this point of time, in the Universe. It follows the famous 1961 Francis Drake equation.

This is based on the equation $N = R^* \cdot f_p \cdot N_e \cdot f_l \cdot f_i \cdot f_c \cdot L$ developed in 1961 by Dr Frank Drake which estimates how many detectable civilizations might exist in our galaxy.

Sources: NASA, Berkeley University of California, Princeton University, Cornell University.

Earths all over the galaxy.

Goldilocks planets are those planets existing in zones where life is possible. As there are an immense number of stars surrounded by them - 1.700 million earths and 3000 million super-earths - and our planet is relatively young, the Fermi Paradox wonders why we do not see any sign of planetary or robotic civilizations in the galaxy, but only hear the radio-waves with the rhythmic tam-tam of black hole and strange stars. The cynical Fermi, father of the A-Bomb, stated that nuclear physicists blew all Goldilocks planets before they reached the technological state of interstellar travel. CERN could confirm this hypothesis.

Moreover we are detecting them so close - proximal centauri, this week 3 of them in the trappist star on the graph that we should have certainly heard radio sounds.

Sorry biblical folks, the Universe is not made for humans. There should be 794 976 000 000 bn planets emitting radio-signals. But none is heard.

In any case the Drake Equation *clearly* rejects the religious solution to the Fermi Paradox - that of humans being unique.

TRAPPIST-1 System

But the conundrum mathematically proved by the Drake equation: why we cannot hear any of those 794,976.000.000 billion

civilizations?

And so WE ARE LEFT WITH A SINGLE SOLUTION. Only the second solution, extinction by physicists, is possible. Since something extinguishes *all of us in all those planets, before they communicate. We should be hearing some of those 794 zillions and we hear none. (1)*

Thus, we won't arrive to the technological evolution of radio-signals needed to leave a bleep in the Universe... We will die before that. When?

Radio communication of stellar size would require a much longer wave and hence a moon station coupled with one on Earth, which can be achieved this century. But we won't survive the century to do it.

We won't reach either the point of interstellar expansion in ships. For this type of travel would require to create shields against high energy particles of enormous metal-weight for current standards - probably a lurching from the moon, on a machine constructed there. Probably well into the next century.

But we won't reach autonomous robots and A.I. able to start a colonization of the Universe. We hear none...

Let us consider this possibility because now we have a more precise timespan. Experts consider that A.I. will exist within a century. A single robotic ship sent by humans wouldn't count as it would not reproduce and hence colonize. But A.I., self-replicant A.I. is now in place. We can foresee it in 3-D printers, CAD design and automation of factories - the main cause of our labor crisis. And yet, *not a single planet has made it to that phase either. Or else the*

STEP 1: 500 Years

STEP 4: 2,000 Years

STEP 7: 3,500 Years

STEP 10: 5,000 Years

STEP 7,500: 3.75 Million Years (Galaxy Completely Colonized)

Colonization Timeline (millions of years)

Cosmic Timeline (millions of years)

OLDEST STAR IN THE GALAXY

FORMATION OF EARTH

OLDEST KNOWN FOSSILS

EVOLUTION OF HUMANS

TODAY

Universe would be awash of robots and sounds of metal.

In the graph, once a civilisation reaches the interstellar travel threshold, it takes a wisp of time in cosmological terms to colonise the entire galaxy. So given the age of the galaxy, over 10 billion years, there is an over 99.9% of probability there would be A.I. and UFOs and robotic ships all over the galaxy, and since there are not, there is a 99.9% of probability all carbon life civilisations extinguish themselves before interstellar robot ships arrive, which can only be the case if black holes or/and strangelets kill all civilisations before...

This is an absolute statistical proof of the risks of CERN, ignored by all to their own peril. Indeed, if in 1/3.000th fraction of the time the galaxy has lived a single civilisation should colonise the planet, and further on there are billions of them, or trillions if we consider all the planets that have existed, the absolute maximal probability we, as all other planets, 'make it' is 0.03%...

And since the highest obvious risk is cern and its strangelets and black holes, it is sheer madness to carry about those experiments. Yet clearly a 'character' of carbonlife species, so ego-centered and blind to the living, organic, self-feeding matter of those 'cosmic bombs' that probably they do those planetary bombs everywhere. After all, only 7 people signed the affidavits of those suits (so again, 7 out of 7 billion means a 0.000000...% interested in helping mankind to survive its existential risk).

All this gives us probably a span of around 50 years to explain *something else that cause our extinction.*

Apocalypse doesn't seem to be the terminator matrix way, or else we would see millions of matrix like places on the galaxy. And there is none.

It means that we die very soon and NOT by robotics.

None has made it to colonize with other robots. So extinction happens in +99.9% of planets within decades or else out of those 1.7 billion, many would have made it.

A.I. is not the cause, because if A.I. extinguishes man it would have expanded in the Universe and it is not anywhere to be seen. robots can expand without problems of health. They should be here, there, emitting radio-waves. So the Span of time of our extinction is even shorter. It happens before terminator.

But there is more to it: the last 'alibi' for deniers was that sending a spacecraft beyond the solar system was impossible on account of the need for combustibile to reach high speeds. This very same year, the EM engine Chinese and NASA tests have shown it is possible to obtain thrust directly from vacuum space, according to a wave-pilot quantum theory.

Humans or A.I. will be able to colonise the galaxy with EM drives within a century. Why they never did it?

The EM drive produces a small thrust only be useful for long-haul space missions, ones that would otherwise necessitate enormous amounts of propellant. The EM drive thruster would only require a source of power, like a small nuclear reactor or solar panel: the distance at which the mass of propellant becomes so great that a much weaker thruster becomes an attractive alternative would certainly be further out than Mars, distances that would still take a long time to reach. But as acceleration continues, past Neptune we would have a working spacecraft able to carry colonisers to other systems, either human or robots. So it is safe to say that within a century by all means planet Earth would be ready to colonise billions of planets. Thus *the great filter must be happening this century.*

ETHIC REASONS: THE WORLDLY PROFESSION OF PHYSICISTS: MAKE ENTROPIC WEAPONS...

The adamant defense of mankind of the quark cannon, is the clearest proof that Fermi was right. There are now plans just in case CERN doesn't kill us to make a 52 km. quark cannon in China, and another of 100 km. in Europe...justified by the sacred research of our high priests, the nuclear physicists, makers of atomic cannons.

It is like if the creators of Big Bertha, the biggest cannon prior to the age of nuclear weapons would justify their bombing of Paris, with the excuse they might unearth archeological remains of Lutetia. CERN justifies its bombing of Earth with strangelets, after it goes on line at maximal potency in 2015, with the excuse that it might unearth some rare particle. So does RHIC competing for the 'nationalistic' honor of reaching the creation of those strangelets earlier.

But while the Germans of I World War could not get away with such a surrealist view of their cannon industry, the Americans & Germ(an)s of XXI century have become shrewder and justify their industry with those newspeaks of research. Fact is History rhymes.

Plainly speaking, the industry of artillery follows its evolution and so from the first 'tube' (cannon in italian), which started ballistics, through the centuries of physicists making them bigger, faster with denser bullets, to the last cannon, the quark cannon, aka LHC, with its quark explosives, through the millions of 'cannon flesh' corpses left in the trail, it has gone a long way. But the evolution will end soon, achieving its purpose, which the Merchant of Death, the biggest arm dealer of the XIX century, Mr. Nobel clearly explained, in a cynical letter to her peace-loving lover, who asked him for a Prize to Peace: 'my factories will end all wars, when they evolve a weapon powerful enough to destroy entire nations with a single shot'.

This is the quark cannon and its theorists seeking collateral theories for a Nobel prize. After the letter, she abandoned Nobel, the inventor of dynamite. Then he created the Peace Prize but she did not come back. After the quark cannon produces the first bullets of strange matter that will fall to the center of the Earth and eat it up inside out, physicists will repent as many did after making the Atomic Bomb. But the Earth will not come back.

As all has changed to remain the same. We are doing it for the same routines that took us into the cold war - the topic military-industrial complex...

The Military Perspective: The Quark Cannon

As so many fruits of the Tree of Science, the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) has two perspectives. Its origin in military research, since accelerators were the last invention of artillery (a circular cannon), used to research atomic weapons, and its use for civil research, since the study of the debris of atomic explosions has allowed mankind to peer in the smallest, densest 'knots of mass-energy'. The problem with the LHC is that its military implications far outweigh its usefulness for scientific research. And this is the fact that the rhetoric of CERN, an institution of the cold war, which systematically hides its original military purpose, has shrewdly hidden to the point that most of the people working today there, young 20 somethings, recently graduated, long forgotten the historic origin of accelerators truly believe the quark cannon is 'only' an instrument of research and ignore its 'military risks'.

Yet when the Large Hadron Collider is explained in simple, military terms people can understand better those dangers. In military terms the LHC is a quark cannon, the final evolution of 800 years of western artillery, a science dedicated to kill as many humans as possible, which has used bore pieces of metal to deliver at maximal speed, the densest possible materials (first rocks, then iron, latter lead and finally hyperdense quarks, the 99% of the mass of the atoms clumped in their centers).

This evolution advanced steadily during centuries along the evolution of physics and its comprehension of all phenomena related to cannons. First Galileo was contracted by the Arsenal of Venice with a princely salary

of 1000 gold ducats to calculate the longest possible distance of a cannon shot and improve the 'spy glasses', latter called telescopes, to observe rival gunboats at distance (the Venetians invented the gunboat in their attack to Constantinopoli in 1208). He thus started the science of ballistics, the name of his first book, latter renamed physics, also called for many centuries the 'science' of motion, as it is a restricted discipline of knowledge basically related to the understanding of energy, motion and materials used to the construction of weapons. The field expanded but still bore this trademark.

For example, heat theory was discovered by an artillery master observing the friction heat of their cannon pieces. What this means is that the primary occupation of most physicists has always been to make weapons, latter machines (the nice twin of all weapons, so a bomber became a plane and a car a tank); and instruments to observe their effects - those spy glasses to see the enemy 'galleries'...

Not to speak of the definition that Galileo imposed on time, as a parameter of the measure of motion: $V=s/t$, which still stands in Einstein's work. This is the origin of the concept of time as the 4th dimension of space, again a very restricted definition of time. Since time has always been a 'verbal concept' synonymous of 'change, with 3 dimensions, past, present and future, whose change we study with theory of information today, (from evolution to complexity), reducing what physicists study as merely the study of change in motion. Yet there are many other changes in the Universe, studied by biology, history, etc. and they are 'time-changes', of which physicists know nothing.

This of course does not mean physics is not concerned with knowledge. But we must differentiate the 'good and bad fruits' of the tree of science - that is; research which is primarily concerned with knowledge, as for example, telescopes observing the big bang peering in long distant galaxies whose light comes from the far away past, and research which is mainly concerned with weaponry and uses the rhetoric of knowledge and some discoveries to justify the primary target.

Galileo's work on ballistics and CERN were the first and last of those cases: the industry of artillery at its best, justified with the excuse of redundant knowledge - since the laws of motion and the big bang can be studied throwing other 'things' and looking with telescopes. Death is a high stakes that need a high reason. And here is where the rhetoric of the Higgs boson (not the particle of god, not even the one that gives mass to other particles but just another particle of the zoo of physical species) came in, and along it all the other 'hyperboles' about what is simply a quark cannon.

, cannons reached its lineal maximal potency around I world war when Bertha, the big cannon of Krupp, delivered its bullets to Paris from 60 kilometers away.

Lead was also the heaviest atomic substance. But you could not make a one kilometer lineal cannon - too heavy, too long. And after lead the heaviest elements became like Uranium is, radioactive, and difficult to handle. So how to make a longer cannon, with a stronger substance? Enter II world war. Uranium was heavier and on top of it, it split and reacted making the bullet a bomb. So physicists started to study radioactive materials, which incidentally end being lead, to substitute lead in their cannons. And then Lawrence realized that the problem of lineal cannons could be resolved making them infinitely long with a circular magnetic path, that accelerated the bullet every cycle, so the cannon could continuously accelerate the bullet as many 'cycles' as it wanted, making 'de facto' the cannon cylinder infinite. And the accelerator cannon was born. The name then was changed starting the make up 'newspeak' transformation of the jargon of artillery into the jargon of 'research'.

So next, they planned to deliver atomic bombs with accelerators. They had a longer bore and a denser substance than Big Bertha. So they designed the first atomic bomb consisting in an accelerator that collided two pieces of uranium in its center provoking an atomic explosion. It was though too heavy to transport and a second design of a self-contained bomb substituted it. But accelerators were the strongest cannons available, and alas! research of new nuclear weapons started in Earnest, with the cold war, thanks to them. All nuclear

weapons would be first tested in circular cannons (the real name of the device). The West established CERN and legally protected it as a 'sovereign nation' (reason we could not sue it), becoming the flagship of the European participation in the cold war.

Rhetoric now were expanding as Nuclear Physicists had become the scourge of the Earth, the first caste of people who intended to destroy the planet and all forms of life on it for the 'common good'. So along the cold war an industry of making nuclear scientists researching atomic weapons, appear as the sacred priests of knowledge, developed the concept that the fundamental form of understanding the Universe was to study the debris produced by atomic circular cannons. This would have seem absurd to more sophisticated readers prior to II world war - namely if the Germans had told us that the obuses of big Bertha thrown over Paris would be the key to understand the Universe we would have had a big laugh.

But in the present age of erased visual minds, childish thought, fiction, rhetoric, big brother newspeaks and other niceties, it worked. So now the Germans (main contributors to this machine, lead by a German, and buttressed with German technology), can truly believe that shooting the Earth with its enhanced Big Bertha, will discover the meaning of it all.

This newspeak was obviously needed because the underlying reason of the industry of quark cannons - to provide new mass-murder devices for the cold war - ended with the fall of communism. But this didn't mean war and the most profitable of all mechanical industries, the industry of weapons had to end. We found in the Semite wars between Israel and the US vs. Arab fundamentalist Jihadists and Palestinians, a perfect excuse for perpetual war and the evolution of robotic weapons - the most profitable modern industry.

And we found in the newspeak of fundamental research the perfect excuse for the evolution of artillery.

'Fundamental' is a serious word that justifies all wars. And in this case 'fundamental research' is the only possible word to justify the risks. Already Mr. Teller - the nuclear physicist who found the H Bomb, patented it and made a fortune manufacturing it - realized knowledge is the perfect excuse to pass a weapon. He bragged, as we show in our film 'quantum roulette' that he convinced Truman to pay for the H-Bomb because it would increase our knowledge of the atom. LOL.

Then he proposed the first 'ultimate weapon' - a hydrogen bomb big enough to destroy the entire Soviet Union, and hence the entire planet. But he could not sell it with 'military rhetoric' only. Eissenhower realized nuclear physicists, all in favor of it, were madmen on a collision course with humanity and after the proposal was put on the table for 'military reasons', he called the 'commies' and started detente. Nuclear Physicists had gone too far, even for hard nose military men. Now they have gone even further. But Nuclear physicists also have become shrewder and so they have hidden the truth with research. The bottom line is industrial routine, jobs, contracts. So any technological industry must continue, even if it has no purpose at all. Cars keep evolving its speed limit even if they cannot go beyond 70 miles per hour. So does the industry of accelerators. As Fromm put it 'the ethics of a technological civilization' consist of evolving machines, even if they can destroy the planet.

And so finally the quark cannon, the first cannon that can destroy the planet, has come into existence, even if it can destroy the planet. It is the LHC, which as the first Galilean model, has its own 'spy glasses' to observe in detail the debris it produces, including a calorimeter called CASTOR to detect the creation of strange matter; since it is supposed to understand the meaning of it all, observing that debris.

But its 'true nature', its 'historic origin', is unmistakable. It is just the last evolution of the artillery industry, an infinitely long, accelerating cannon, which uses the most explosive, dense and dangerous substance of the Universe, quarks and throws bullets of quarks to the planet Earth. And one of those bullets will be able to kill mankind. It is the ultimate weapon.

And what it will produce is simple enough: quark condensates of higher density than our light up and down quarks, the substance of our atoms. For one thing, there are 3 families of increasingly dense quark matter, the up & down family (ours - the substance of the stars of the galactic body); then the strange family, which is called strange matter, the substance of strange stars called pulsars, and probably the halo of the galaxy, and then the top family very likely the substance of black holes and the center of the galaxy.

The problem is that matter is 'darwinian'. Strange matter eats light up & down matter. And top black hole matter eats strange and up & down matter. It is a pecking order. So when strange matter - the easiest to do - will appear on the quark cannon, it will eat the earth. There is no doubt about it. And the only question that remains to be solved is when the LHC or any of its planned successors in the industry of quark cannons will have enough energy to produce with our quarks, denser strange quarks that will devour the Earth.

We believe according to known-known theory of quarks this will happen in 2015 when the quark cannon doubles its potency. It is in any case a question of time that the artillery industry in its most advanced piece, the quark cannon, evolves beyond the threshold of creation of strange matter, and kill the Earth. The industry is blind and protected of all criticism with its lies and rhetoric. It is the summit of the military industrial complex and it does some collateral research besides the collateral damage to mankind to feed its rhetoric. But the bottom line is this: it is a quark cannon, it produces quark condensates, the heaviest most dangerous self-sustained, self-feeding explosive on the Universe, and it will once crossed the energy required to produce a strange quark condensate blow up the Earth.

The rest is 'irrelevant' knowledge, 'irrelevant' rhetoric, and irrelevant, since an extinct species, mankind, knows nothing. Only a piece of that rhetoric will suffice to show how difficult this question is. Nuclear Physicists ALL perfectly know that cosmic rays are just simple atomic substances, protons, electrons and gamma rays, colliding on the atmosphere. We have NEVER found a deconfined quark in cosmic rays. Cosmic rays are NOT quark bullets, because they are not heavy 'lead' ions, which can produce 'quark condensates'. And yet, whenever any journalist, politician or the public ask about the risks at CERN, ALL nuclear physicists lie, saying cosmic rays have done this experiment one thousand times. This is an ABSOLUTE lie, that any first 'course' of physics explains.

But of course, all is very shrewd. CERN does collide besides heavy lead ions, which can create quark condensates, protons, and so they do experiments similar to cosmic rays... But those are not the dangerous experiments that will create strange matter. Cern does research on fundamental particles, but this is not the reason why XX century military-industrial systems paid for the accelerator industry. And most 'CERNIES' are idealist kids who didn't know the origin of their industry and think their work has no risk. But 'big boys' playing with big toys, big weapons are not a excuse for putting us all at risks.

The cosmic rays half-lie shows what perhaps is the saddest part of this story from a theoretical point of view. As a scientist I always thought there was a 'realm' in which truth mattered - science, as opposed to politics, economics or religion. This is no longer truth. Science now is also 'wishful thinking'. CERN's statements show THE DEGREE OF intellectual corruption, rhetoric and callousness which Nuclear Physicists, after 60 years of getting away with murder doing nuclear weapons, have achieved.

They are no longer different from fundamentalist religious people, nationalist war-mongers or fiction actors in their delivery of false speeches to justify their actions. And so once truth is broken for interest what we face is the biggest team of fundamentalist, terrorist, genociders the world has ever been, and maybe the last. It is destiny? Probably.

So why we do not do anything about it? The answer will 'anger' the reader, as he is human after all. IT IS ALL IN THE HUMAN EGO, which cannot tolerate not TO BE IMMORTAL, not TO BE THE CENTER OF THE UNIVERSE, its only 'intelligent species' who knows better and paradoxically will rather die holding this supreme ego paradox

than accept humbly its limits of life and death and knowledge in an infinite immortal Universe, of which we are just a smallish part.

The paradox of the ego, is on one hand natural to the essence of being human - we are self-centred - but inverse to the nature of science, which is objective and constantly displaces man from the center of the Universe. And it has in the case of CERN and physics a huge pseudo-religious consequence: a theory of the entire Universe called the big-bang which is the ultimate alibi for CERN to be tolerated despite the obvious risks. So we shall now slightly divert this article from the factual nature of those risks and the nuclear rhetoric, to consider 3 different questions:

-The nature of the human ego and how humans prefer to believe in happy self-centred theories of reality (anthropomorphic religions, mathematical gods) that in objective science.

-And following that trend they tend to elaborate theories of reality close to their worldly professions. So physicists that make weapons invented the big-bang explosive creation of the universe, despite its many flaws both theoretical and experimental.

-So instead we will reconsider a more objective theory of reality than those sponsored by the Copenhagen interpretation of quantum physics and the big-bang interpretation of creation. Namely the sound-sound, increasingly proved theories of Einstein both in quantum and cosmology (pilot wave theory along De Broglie, and steady state along Fred Hoyle). after a century of 'propaganda' of the creationist and observer's theory of physics, which so much pumps the human ego, the sound theories of Einstein keep coming back with new proofs, and keep giving new avenues of thought and will if we survive CERN become standard one humans stop being so arrogant about what they can and cannot know and what is the nature of reality.

II. THE PARADOX OF THE EGO: A NEW RELIGION OF PHYSICS

TWO OPTIONS TO EXPLAIN THE DOUBLE SLIT EXPERIMENT

The Experiment

In this classic distillation of the oddity of quantum mechanics, a beam of electrons is fired at two parallel slits that sit in front of a detector. If no observation is made until the electrons arrive at the detector, the electron beam will create a pattern of light and dark bands that is akin to what waves would do in a similar situation (A). Yet if an observer checks to see which slit each electron passes through, no such pattern will emerge. The detector will reveal only two bright spots, as though the electrons were bullets fired through one slit or the other (B).

The Copenhagen Interpretation

So long as no observation is being made, electrons do not have definite positions. Each electron spreads out like a wave, passes through both slits simultaneously, and interferes with itself to form the bright and dark bands on the detector screen. Yet as soon as an observer checks to see which slit each electron is passing through, the observation instantaneously "collapses" each electron's position to a point, thus ruining the interference pattern.

The Pilot-Wave Interpretation

In Bohmian mechanics, every electron always has a definite position, even if observers are ignorant of what it is. An electron is pushed around by a guiding "pilot wave" that influences the electron's location. While each electron travels through one slit or the other, the pilot wave passes through both slits simultaneously. Interference in the pilot wave leads to the observed interference pattern. A measurement at the slits will collapse the pilot wave and reveal where the electron was all along.

In the graph, the true rational, explanation of quantum physics - the pilot wave theory, recently proved by the interstellar EM engine, vs. the subjective ego-centered theory of 'the observer' who creates quantum reality, which has become canonical and is ultimately a religious creationist theory.

The astounding fact about Physics today, both in quantum theory and Cosmology is its 'outlook' as an anthropomorphic religion that has substituted earlier abrahamic religions, without respecting the basic laws of objectivism of science, unlike all other disciplines. So Physicists have on one side accepted 'weird' theories of reality that make man - in this case the observer - the center of creation, against the sound-sound objective theories of reality available and far more sound experimentally, which however eliminate any 'entitlement for human beings'. Such is the case of the infamous argument between the founders of quantum theory, Planck, Einstein, De broglie and Schrodinger, and his pilot-wave interpretation and the 'newcomers', Hilbert, Bohr, Pauli and Heisenberg who imposed a new religion of humans and their mathematics as the 'creators' of reality. While in cosmology, they created by the elimination of the informative gravitational force that creates mass out of entropy in galaxies, another weird theory called the big-bang, in which all reality was once according to a simple lineal equation, $V \approx HoD$, compressed in a single point, easy to describe with its simple mathematical tools, a mere mirror-language of reality.

At the heart of those simple, anthropomorphic, 'creationist' theories of reality which CERN pretends to explore further, as in the case of Abrahamic religions there is fundamental, existential problem of humanity: the paradox of the ego, which true science and his lonely humble geniuses have always tried to combat with little results - as humans systematically prefer a theory that makes them 'exceptional' and happy that one that tells them the objective truth of their non-importance in the universe. In as much as the indifference to the risks of cern are precisely based in the arrogance of humans who cannot conceive its extinction we cannot only consider theoretical, experimental and military reasons to CERN's potential genocide but do have to criticise the essence of that human arrogance, the paradox of the ego that makes 1/2 of mankind to believe we are 'chosen of a Bush-God of the bronze age that makes us immortal' and only its verbal priests can understand, while the other 1/2 believe the Universe was created in a single point described by a single equation in the single language of God, mathematical physics, which only 'physical experts' can understand.

Let us then consider the paradox of the Ego that makes humans so stubborn about their importance, from the perspective of those epistemological, sociological and theoretical reasons:

Epistemological reasons are concerned with the objective, predictable nature of Scientific truths, which contrary to belief is not 'probabilistic', but deterministic - events will happen if its causes appear, only the capacity of man to 'calculate' when and where is probabilistic - so we do know for example, in the most talked about case of probabilities with certainty that a wave-particle will strike a quantum screen but we do not know exactly when and where. Since in that sense is NOT 'subjective' - that is, adaptable to human 'egos' and needs; but objective and its causality quite easy to prove.

Sociological reasons are thus exactly the opposite, concerned with the traps of the human 'ego', which simply denies those objective laws when they do not satisfy the human wantings. And they apply straight on questions of human death: whenever man feels threatened by a cause he feels difficult to avoid, he denies it.

So the majority of humans - more than 1/2 of its global population - still believes that a goat-keeper of the bronze age talking to a burning bush in the middle of the desert, found the meaning of the Universe and the magic formula to defy death and make all humans eternal, because the creator of the infinite reality cared so much about him that took the form of the creeping sounds of fire to deliver him and only him the meaning of it all, and save his ambulatory cells from the cycles of life and death.

The paradox here is that people 'die' constantly in jihads and inquisitions to defend the idea they won't die.

Contrary to belief physical 'theories' of reality have not avoided the traps of human egos, and the higher danger of death they bring to those who fear it so much.

This is obvious in the case of CERN: Nuclear Physicists simply deny their obvious 'worldly religion', which has been making weapons of mass destruction since its inception - reason why they construct so expensive machines, funded to research ever more powerful nuclear bombs by the Russian and Western military. And so they keep denying they are just following the same routine of higher energies and higher explosions, which can only bring more efficient bombs; which is exactly what strangelets and black holes are.

Yet to understand that we must criticise their theory of reality, the so called big-bang, in which also the entire Universe reduced to a point physicists 'handle' with the language they claim they only understand - maths; as Moses thought God was reduced to a bush creeping which he only understood with his language, Hebrew. As the 'big-bang' high priesthood is the DETERMINANT factor why humans risk death (as religious jihad is the main cause why people are being killed all over the world today) we shall extend a bit more this argument that we must risk death to prove the dogma of the high priesthood of 'entropy', nuclear physics.

Theoretical reasons. The big bang alibi connects CERN with the 'theoretical religion' of physicists, quite similar to that of Abrahamic religions, in which an infinitesimal human being 'believed' to understand the meaning of it all, because God, the mind of the Universe reduced itself in the big bang to another infinitesimal point, easy to handle by the arrogant ego-centered bronze age peasant, which became the 'only' human to understand it all or the modern physicist who pretends a 'simple lineal equation' called the Hubble constant, $V = H_0 D$, resumes it All.

So the religious priest will tell you 'GOD' explains it all, just 3 letters, 4 in the Jewish Tetragramaton, Yhwh, 5 in Allah. And there is no need for anything else. Alas from GoD to $V \approx H_0 D$, from Abrahamic cults to big-bang cults 2 letters have changed to remain the same.

This is the essence of the absurd theory of the big bang, according to which $V = H_0 D$, in this case not the mind but the entire Universe reduced itself to an infinitesimal point which was the 'beginning of time and space' that only physicists (and creationist, biblical priests that sponsor the concept - in fact 'discovered' by a Catholic priest, Mr. Lemaitre), the high popes of science understand with an arcane 'Latin language' called mathematics.

In reality that equation is so simple that one cannot avoid a smile, when people tells you Physicists are the absolute geniuses of mankind. It merely means that galaxies are separating because the light, an entropic, lineal, expansive force between them, elongates its wave as it moves. There is nothing else, but already Einstein said 'imagination' is more important than intelligence. So as religious people have made of God with good imagination and pumping-ego ceremonies the meaning of it all, nuclear physicists have extracted from that single fact - light elongates as an entropic force between galaxies, with a 'lot of imagination', half-lies and statistics the meaning of it all.

How they did it? Simple: they just move backwards this light expansion, and concluded that as light expands between galaxies, if we run it backwards it must have imploded into a single point, the 'origin of it all' which their Vhod describes as the graph shows.

Never mind light NOT only expands when free but it contracts within galaxies by the force of gravitation, balancing thus, the expansive $E=mc^2$ death of mass into radiation, with the implosive, $M=E/c^2$ informative implosion of light into mass particles and galaxies, making reality a wobbling balanced immortal infinity of dying mass and imploding

light. , if you run backward the equation of light expansion, you just will get back to the atom of the galaxy that emitted that ray of light - AS ALL EQUATIONS ARE FINITE and happen only as long as the phenomenon they describe exists - in this case the ray of light that expands does NOT go back into an infinitesimal point because all LIGHT is produced by particles according to the $E=mc^2$ equation.

Yet the big-bang dogma merely rejects to put the most famous equation of physics, $E=mc^2$ at work, as the abrahamic cult denies any other 'letters' to God. It is only God, or Yhwh or Allah (even if actually the 3 religions says it is the same God). In physics it is only Vhod not $E=mc^2$, what matters. You just vehemently deny the other 'letters' matter at all to create matter (play with words, as it is all just funny egos jumping me, i and myself only, if it had not so ugly collateral effects).

Thus the big bang is just a theory based in the wordily profession of nuclear physicists (make atomic bombs). So disregarding the arrow of information and life, which is the creative force of the Universe, physicists pretend to interpret reality only with the arrow of destruction and death, they call 'entropy', and merely moved backwards in time a lineal, simple equation of entropy, to pretend it moved backwards till this supposed explosion collapsed into a tractable infinitesimal point, much more smaller than the human ego. The parallels between those 2 supreme 'theories of the subjective ego' are multiple.

The peasant Meshu thought God was the bush their goats munched because that was his professional 'food'. And he denied therefore the immanent sacred nature of all what exists, made of the same 'plenum substance', impersonal space and time. God was in his bush. The arawak who ate turtles thought God was a huge turtle over which the Earth floated.

The nuclear industry which makes nuclear bombs designed a theory of the Universe, in which only its 'entropic process' of explosive death accounted for the creation of the entire Universe. So of course, the people who hold the alternative sound-sound theory, called the steady state Universe, from Einstein to Hoyle, who affirmed ad maximal there would be a quasar big-bang, observed experimentally balanced by the creation of mass, laughed at them and called its theory the 'big-bang', arguing their makers were either 'creationist priests' (Lemaitre) or people working in the nuclear industry (Gamow). It was then business as usual: ad hominem attacks on Einstein and Hoyle, the P.r.ess heralding Gamow as a genius, since it backed the nuclear weapons

industry and justified experiments and industries that researched them, such as CERN created then. And soon they recruited their twin believers in creationist points and G. bushes, so the church who still denied Evoution jumped on the wagon and every sound proof of the steady state Universe was dismissed and every fool proof of the Big bang was canonised, as we explain in our right side articles on 5D and cosmology which studies the falsehood of big-bang theories.

for God to be unique, it was just needed to kill all rival gods, and we are still on the business of killing each other to prove our 'letters matter more'. And for the big bang to work, it was just needed to DENY all other causes of the process of DUAL informative creation of mass and entropic destruction of mass into radiation. This of course created the paradox that physicists used $e=mc^2$ to explode bombs but deny their equation to uphold Vhod.

At this point things became a little surrealist: physicists changed the name of the arrow of information and life and called it 'negantropy', the negation of death, as if negating death was a 'sin' and information and life was irrelevant, something Vhod could dispose of.

They also denied the most important in-formative force of the Universe, gravitation, which 'forms' the mass of galaxies, as time goes by. So Einstein, the only sound mind, who merely did 'thought experiments' said that 'time curves space into mass'. So the creation of mass balances the entropic flows of pure light space without form between those galaxies.

And the result is an immortal wobbling spring like Universe, where according to Einstein's equation: $E=M(c^2)$, entropy reigns in the electromagnetic forces and light transiting between galaxies, expanding its space-time.

But then it collapses within galaxies, creating with gravitational forces, in-form-ation. And this arrow of form and life is more important. Since we humans live in one of those vortices of time collapsing into mass, called the milky way, in one of its cyclical, turning planets that evolves information, through the processes of life and technology and human languages of thought. SO IT MATTERS MORE to understand mass and life than entropy and vacuum expansive space. The next graph shows schematically one of those galaxies wobbling.

In the graph, absolute relativity postulates a Universe of infinite scales of sizes with relative big-bangs, which are the death of implosive Mass converted back and forth into entropic motion, according to Einstein's equation: $Entropy \rightleftharpoons Mass (c^2)$, which obviously has 2 arrows of time, and so it was in fact first described first, as $M=E/c^2$, that is a process that transforms entropy into mass and information, stored in the frequency of those accelerated mass cycles.

Now, the 'steady state theory' of the Universe has always come to this simple realisation: the creation of mass eliminates the need for a singularity. There are a few different versions and duality merely makes them even more sound. The best elaboration of this steady state dual expansive-implosive Universe, departing from earlier work by Einstein and Fred Hoyle, is the concept of a series of local big-bangs, called quasars, proved recently by the 20 billion years tabulated cycle of galaxies:

Further on the cycles is reinforced by the fact that big-bang radiation is measured locally, as Penzias and Wilson were measuring the background radiation of the galaxy, a fact recently rediscovered by the observance of 2 'electromagnetic lobes' on the galaxy, which are exactly the same found in the supposed mapping of the whole Universe (Scientific American 293, 42 - 49 (2005):

A GALAXY REINVENTS ITSELF

Astronomers used to regard bars and spirals as permanent features of a galaxy but now think that they come and go. The gravitational processes that make a bar ultimately destroy it and then create it anew, as this simulation shows.

The first graph from sci-am shows the 20 billion years cycle of quasars, which destroy the central bar of the black hole, produce massive quantities of helium above the galaxy center (considered the 2nd fundamental proof of the big-bang after the $V=H_0D$ equation, already explained) and provokes waves of radiation. Below we observe the 'supposed' 'lobes' of the cosmos, which turn out to be exactly the 2 lobes of our galaxy, recently discovered, and the fact that from quantum atoms to galaxies, there are $E=Mc^2$ double big-bangs from beta decay to novas of stars and planets to galaxies.

So what is the origin of the 'back ground radiation'? Unfortunately another clear proof that the galaxy is teeming with strangelets and black holes. Since the background radiation can only be produced today by a black hole or dark matter strangelet gravitationally redshifting light as it passes through the halo:

In astrophysics, **gravitational redshift** or Einstein shift is the process by which electromagnetic radiation originating from a source that is in a **gravitational** field is reduced in frequency, or **redshifted**, when observed in a region at a higher **gravitational** potential.

Gravitational redshift - Wikipedia

And so a huge proof of the Fermi Paradox comes through Einstein's gravitational redshift: a black hole or strangelet which has eaten the mass of a moon, the most abundant planetary size of the galaxy, will produce exactly redshifted background black body radiation at 2.7 k,

So the SUPPOSED absolute proof of a cosmic big-bang IS in fact without 'extrapolations into an infinitesimal past point' perfectly explained now IF the light matter of the galaxy 'feeds' the dark matter of the halo, which WILL thereafter redshift constantly gravitationally (another Einstein effect) light all over the galaxy and light coming inside the galaxy at 2.7 K.

Again in Epistemology WHEN 2 POSSIBLE CAUSES OF A phenomena happen, the sound SOUND ONE, is the cause that happens NOW. It is like if you try to explain your 37 degrees of body temperature and you have a doctor that tells you the NOW-now cause - the activity of your cells at 37 degrees, as the activity of dark matter of moon masses (called MACHOs) today at 2.7 K. Obviously this is a sound theory

Now imagine a 'guru' that comes and tells you, your 37 K temperature is in fact caused by the 'cooling' of your temperature at the moment of your birth which was then '3 trillion degrees', and I have a lineal equation that proves you have been getting colder till now, exactly at the required speed to get now 37 degrees. You will think he is cuckoo because he NEVER measured your temperature in the past, so he is making a non-scientific extrapolation. Well THIS IS EXACTLY WHAT Gamow did. He came to the conclusion that the Universe had cooled down from the singularity of trillions of degrees to the almost 'absolute zero' of 20 degrees... Wait, but it is not 2.7 K background radiation?

Yes, he FAILED COMPLETELY TO FORECAST it. But WHEN Penzias measured the then called 'galaxy temperature' at 2.7 K, GAMOW simply a posteriori changed his lineal equation to meet 2.7 k now, and then a flurry of 'egolatric' scientists decided it was NOT local but cosmic radiation. Because that kept them as 'the new high popes of creationism' and the meaning of it all. AND AGAINST RELIGIONS I DO NOT REASON.

, there are many other sounder proper explanations to every supposed cosmic big-bang phenomena, but when an entire ego-centered group of human beings is in a 'mission' pumping with zealot ego human power, there is no 'reasoning' able to stop the tsunami - the sound reasons are hidden, unpublished, the half-reasons which favor the pseudo-religion are pumped, retouched ad hoc, as Gamow's temperature...

So we do dedicate an entire post on cosmology to study a little bit in detail this theory, which i am now on the business of properly rewriting as the rest of this idle web for many years left alone after the failure of suits and films to rise public awareness.

But as an image is worth more than a thousand words, we have just showed you the 3 most recent, visual proofs that the background radiation is local, galactic, and if there was in the past a 'big-bang' was just the quasar cycle of our galaxy.

So as always times proves the sound, humble, rational scientists right. In this case Einstein's steady state solution, which Fred Hoyle developed in a huge mathematical effort just before dying in his theory of multiple

quasar big-bangs, which the cycle of galaxies found by the French astronomers further proved and my calculus of Moon MACHOs radiation, which any student of physics can easily corroborate properly explains.

All those galaxies prove, with its longer 20 billion cycle, which goes beyond the supposed age of the big-bang its falsehood. As many of the recently discovered astronomical phenomena in far away galaxies show. Since we are finding formed galaxies, formed giant black holes, formed II generation stars and star dust, which could not have been born before the big-bang. So do those supposed 'lobes' of the cosmic big-bang, which Smolin a famed physicist wanted to use to prove his theory that high frequency light goes faster than red-shifted light, as they were supposed to come from 13 billion years ago and so a small difference of distance should be found. Alas, the surprise when they found they are the exact 'trace' of the 2 lobes of electromagnetic radiation found in OUR galaxy. Yet they occupy supposedly 'a huge piece of the entire Universe'...

We have put just a few of the experimental proofs of recent astronomy to add to the enormous number of planets found all over the place, which reinforce the Fermi paradox, so you don't think I am here making a case only for theory, only for my work in the 2 arrows of time. So WHY nothing of this comes in 'daily press'? FOR ALL THE WRONG REASONS - religions are always respected; masses always side together for them. As Schopenhauer said: 'the wise always say the same, the fools, which are majority do exactly the opposite'. And of course, attack ad hominem the wise.

, in the steady state theory things became soon ad hominem against Hoyle who quipped back inventing the mocking term of 'big-bang theory'.

While basically Einstein's attempts to put reason on quantum theory were ignored after he defied Bohr, till his death. He got an FBI file, nobody was going to his classes, and so he dedicated himself to talk to Godel on the ridiculous concept of Mathematics as the substance of the Universe, to boating and walking... Then they discovered black holes, all his theories were proved... till Hawking decided as a celebrity guru to challenge him with his theory of black holes traveling to the past, totally ignorant of the real time arrows of the Universe.

AND THINGS even got worst, with Bohm, who completed Broglie's pilot wave theory - he got ignored, got his FBI file, was stripped of his American nationality and became an expatriate. Do not think physicists take lightly any attack on his religion of 'seers' of time.

And now that he has been proved by the interstellar engine, nobody of course is putting his realist theory that ends quantum bull\$hit on its place.

So let me be a bit nasty, just with words, as it is obvious I have no power (in fact, though i won't comment it in this blog, I do have also my 'police files' despite my pacifist standing)... on those religious zealots, as all of them come from the same ego-trip: to think they speak the language of god as its only high-priests.

Back to the ego paradox - the parallels between religious zealots and physicists.

The only difference between religious people and creationist physicists is in the language of those 2 supposed infinitesimal 'wholes', God, the name, and $V \approx Hod$, the equation religious and big-bang zealots think explains it all:

-1/2 humanity thinks God talks only with words, in the exact language of the believer, which only the priest understands. Another 1/2 believes God talks only with numbers, in the exact language of the believer, which only the mathematical physicist understands.

So the trick is to make the language complex enough to disguise the simplicity of the argument. Thus christian priests talked in Latin for peasants to feel awe, the Koran could not be translated, and Vhod has gotten a lot of ad ons and machines to make it complex enough for the human mass, worshipers of machines to feel there is a

Werner Heisenberg and Niels Bohr

better priesthood upholding the supreme intelligence of the human ape, which when we look at his 'real mind', is an homunculus with a very small mental consciousness, a huge big mouth to utter nonsense and an even bigger hands to assembly machines and pump his ego with weapons. The graph shows man at face value. Notice how small is the 'reasoning part' for the ego. It is all about big mouths and

machines assembling things. So the person with the biggest, most arrogant big mouth and more dexterous hands to make machines and weapons carries he day among the worshipping audiences.

Things get more surrealist when we look objectively to the ego-theories of both rivals of truth.

So when the homunculus talks in both cases, God and Vhod, and his 'mediums', the priest and the physicist are supposed to have the capacity to create reality 'speaking the language'. Now, it is the priest and the scientist who creates reality, as vehicle of God.

So in Islam, god creates reality exactly talking 'names' in arab, which then become reality, reason why you cannot translate the Koran. In the catholic church God spoke in Latin. And only the priest could understand it. In the Hindi religion Shiva, the god of death, spoke with burning flames as in Judaism, because fire was the substance used by the military caudillos of Israeli zealots and Hindi castes to make their weapons.

In both religions the priest becomes through the ceremony and the mantras it speaks, God himself, which is also 'eaten by the catholic' believer in 'the creationist power of the language'. So 'God, the word became man and inhabited among us'.

And this is the case of physicists today akin to the religion of Hindi Shivaites: the fire of his bombs created the Universe and a statue of Shiva presides CERN's facilities - it only has changed according to the growing arrow of information, which as time goes by increases the complexity of those rituals, the 'cover up' of the amazing arrogance of the homunculus.

And of course it has changed the language. So now Vhod has 'unified' the words of Babel and talks only in platonic mathematics - the epistemological theory of physicists.

Do you think I am exaggerating? Or no. If anything I am downplaying the capacity of the physicist priesthood to 'create' reality just uttering numbers.

Let us explain this, because i am NOT joking. Physicists actually believe since quantum theorists applied the religious theory of linguistic creationism to mathematics that 'THEY' invent reality.

, the reader should not be surprised that mathematics is today NO LONGER defined as an experimental language that merely mirrors reality, as it was always thought of, and proved by Lobachevski and Godel (mathematics as a mirror of reality must be proved experimentally to know what theory is truth, or as Einstein, yes again, this sound guy, everybody reveres but everyone denies, put it: 'i know when mathematics is truth but not when it is REAL'). NO WONDER his best friend was Godel, who proved mathematics needs experiments. Never mind. Physicists dismissed it all together and affirmed as religious zealots that the Universe is made of mathematical 'entities' and moreover, THEY CREATED MATHEMATICS. So they were like the priests of the Gods of the hindoos and hebrews, the 'creators of reality,

, as God and the priest 'invents' in his mind the language which creates reality, an idealist, arrogant German, a mathematical physicist called Mr. Hilbert told us that 'he' invents mathematics in his mind and then mathematics creates reality.

So he started his 'axiomatic book', landmark of XX century physics, 'the foundations of mathematics' on the nature of reality with an astounding 'self-confession': 'I imagine points, lines and planes' which 'are' the substances of the mind that creates the Universe.

, what has essentially happened to physicists after that bizarre ego-trip of mr. Bohr et al is obvious: since mathematics creates the universe, not the other way around (reflects the Universe in a language), and more over it is a 'proprietary language' of the Hilbert school of imaginary points, lines and planes, any mathematical equation MUST be real MUST create some effect in reality - never mind there is zero proof of it. So , we can expect dragoons if you can model them mathematically, black holes evaporating to the past (Hawking) if you can write them mathematically, and so on.

This philosophy of science is now canonical and plainly false.

Of course the simplex nature of the scientific method when it does NOT interpret reality works, whatever philosophy of science you choose.

There is nothing intelligent in doing the praxis of science; you collect data, you put it in equations - now you don't even need to know much of it, just plug it into computers and you make machines with it. But humans will always take a flight of the ego just because Nature NOT them transmits information perfectly through waves, etc.

We are talking though here of the huge questions, 'the thoughts of god', the meaning of it all, NOT the details. And in this field the Copenhagen and big-bang interpretation is pure ego bull\$hit, as Einstein fully understood. Because people use in real day machinery based in quantum physics, the practitioners of the Hilbert->Bohr religion of the observer can sell their infinite Universes and entropy only theory and people tend to think all this quantum 'bull\$hit' is real.

To me the only remarkable thing about it, as in the case of the ridiculous ego-trips of abrahamic religions is what it tells us about 'humans as an egolatric species', who will always rejects truth and hence 'existence' as it is, if you sell him a good fantasy to make him again the center of the Universe. But the penalty they pay is not only theoretical - the complete misunderstanding of the thoughts of God, but quite real - its future extinction by all those species of 'organic bombs' they thoroughly despise as irrelevant. The human microbio must be above heavens and Earth.

The languages he speak - either words or numbers - must be the vehicle to understand, even create the Universe.

And the proof of all this must be not reason and experience but 'prizes' , 'ceremonies', the seal of 'authority' of some other clueless human; the peer solidarity; the routines and dogmas repeated by new generations, since as Gerry Garcia said 'whores, religions and old buildings get respetable with age'. So has happened with the religion of Copenhagen and the big bang dogma.

So, don't dare to insinuate that it is all a pseudo-religion of the ego, which it is. A wall silence will rise to anyone who tries to deny dogmatism in physics, as it happened to Hoyle, Einstein for quite sometime till his formula was used to do bigger bombs, Eddington for insinuating that without direct evidence quantum interpretations were just myths of the mind and many others.

Frankly i never understood this 'peer thing'. Facts are facts, models must be based in facts and be rational and anyone with enough IQ can understand them or falsify them. We are NOT insects collected in boxes with 'national' or 'profesional names'.

But then I came to the conclusion that humans are memorial beings, which do NOT reason but BELIEVE. It took me half a century to understand that reasoning only came for a few - having a certified 180 Iq i never thought there was other form to seek truth than critical intelligent evaluation of all what I was told. I have never believed anything which I didn't understand. But people's mind works the other way around - they only believe what they don't understand. And that is why the entire simple, evident bullshit of quantum and big-bang physics explained here in its simplest terms has become so confuse.

The same happen for example with the racket of the issue of money the language of social power who controls the world and the American FED makes so complex to issue that the Americans really believe the fact a few private banksters have hijacked their democracy issuing money and giving orders of work with them to their slavish population is 'freedom'. , wall street invents a digital number called money for free, and for example, this week invented 20 billions and gave it to a crony friend, for a silly nilly crapcode repetitive algorithms, called snapchat, but if they want the minimum welfare they must pay every penny with taxes. The astounding racket of the cdo scam - over 2 trillions extorted in taxes - worked the same way: people in that country are so clueless about what money is and who invents it, they handled 2 trillions to bankers who just had 'invented' false mortgages, and sold it 'twice'. Well, instead of going to jail, they sold those mortgages a 3rd time to the people of America on exchange for 2 trillions, and people gave to them.

The whole circus of modern 'mathematical physics' and quantum interpretations, big-bang explosions and the role of physicists as the high priests of knowledge is born of the same concept: 'people must remain ignorant for them to obey' said Calvin, the biblical bigot. 'If you repeat a lie many times people will believe it, the bigger the lie the more they will believe on it', said Goebbels.

The Universe though does NOT work on ego. It works exactly on the opposite qualities: humble, cautious species do survive. And 'simplicity is true genius' (Leonardo) because 'the Universe is simple and not malicious' (Einstein).

What can I say? Of course all this bull\$hit well greased with P.R.ess, censorship of rival theories, subtle ostracism, denial of experimental evidence (Einstein's black holes) or lack of it (Hawking imaginary ones) and the military-industrial complex and its clueless politicians slavish of whatever nuclear physicists said, carried the day. So not even the previous recent proofs (as well as the EM engine, which can only be explained with pilot-wave theory) have done a dent into the big-bang and Copenhagen or Multiuniverse quantum creationist theories of reality.

So we shall conclude this paradox of the ego, turning around the heads of those mathematical believers and defining the equation of the ego paradox in mathematical terms to show the believers their infinitesimal nature.

BUT FOR THAT first we need to understand how entropy and information together create a time cycle. So let us explain you without ego, and with both arrows of time, entropy and information and its infinite, energetic combinations, how the Universe truly works.

Since , when we abandon the entropic, lineal only-time theory of physicists, biased by their worldly profession, we realise all clocks of TIME in the Universe are cyclical and store information:

In the left graph, all time clocks and cycles, which return to its origin, creating a circle that stores the information of the Universe in the frequency and form of its cycles.

This self-evident truth is ONLY denied by physicists, biased by their worldly profession, to make lineal weapons, which deliver entropic lineal shots with cannonballs (left, Galileo's drawings on ballistics, which brought

the concept of lineal-only time). As physics and war became the trade mark of western civilisation, physicists dedicated to evolve machines and weapons, changed the two

arrows and cycles of time, which became reduced to lineal entropic 'big-bang' time.

Even after Darwin brought back the concept of evolutionary time and Vico->Marx, Kondratieff->Schumpeter applied this concept of r=evoution to history and economics and biology expanded as a science of life and information, stored in circadian and genetic cycles, the concept of cycles of time today accepted in life, history and economics - IS STILL DENIED by entropic physicists.

Time, which means change=motion in philosophy, however cannot be reduced to a simple LINEAL formula, $v=s/t$ that equalises all the different clocks of the Universe, all the different cyclical actions of its species with a single mechanical 'time clock' of measure elongated into an infinite duration AS it is more convenient to study loco-motions, the lineal entropic motions of those cannonballs, which imposed with power the simplification of time cycles that still endures and justifies the big-bang experiments of planet Earth.

So after concluding his first book on Physics, called 'military instruments' Mr. Galileo affirmed, his lineal time would be the 'delight of philosophers and artillery masters'. Funny thing though is that even the entropic lines of its cannonballs were 'twisted' downwards into a curved parable by the informative force of gravitation. It would take 400 years for Einstein to explain that 'gravitational forces of time vortices, masses, curved space, informing the Universe'

But particle, quantum physicists still deny him, from Hawking who affirms black holes travel backwards in time, so they are not vortices of mass-information but entropic explosive things that evaporate, against ALL theoretical and experimental evidence, to the deniers of the Einstein-Broglie-Bohm pilot theory, proved recently 'again' by the EM engine able to move in interstellar travel with no combustibile thanks to the 'guidance' of the wave... All this shows a simple fact: the worldly profession of physicists and the power of machines DOMINATES AND IMPOSES its lineal bias on theory. And truth and reason cannot 'bend' that.

0-Minds: Still mappings with languages of information of the ∞ Universe.

In the graph, Science and any other form of knowledge merely tries to reduce the infinite Universe to a smallish mirror mapping or 'monad' or 'frame of reference' or 'language', to act and react to the flows of entropy and information of that Universe (combined in the 3rd arrow of time, energy).

What both physicists and religious people do is to 'exclude' all other mind-views, mirror-mappings and languages of perception from reality, biasing the Universe into a 'straightjacket' called 'theory of everything' based in its single language.

Let us then return to the origin of their peculiar concept of 'reality' created by the language of mathematics and the force we perceive, entropic lineal light, which excludes completely the in-formative force of 'invisible gravitation' and the intelligent mirrors of all other species, from feromonal ants to gravitational black holes

who externally act as if they were 'intelligent' perceptive beings ordering their territorial domain, as we do with words, and scientists and sensorial machines (clocks of time, eyes of metal, telescopes and microscopes) do with maths.

In other words, the Universe needs infinite minds, focuses of information to order it. And this was the understanding that started modern philosophy of science in the work of Descartes.

Descartes was a contemporary of Galileo, and the true founder of modern science with his 'Method of reasoning' and the Frame of Reference of the mathematical mind, said that all what exists was made of:

- Open space, which he called 'res extensa', the less important part of the ternary systems of the Universe, the cytoplasm of cells, the inner space-time of light matter in galaxies, where we live, the cells of your body, the light filled space of atoms, etc.

- Closed, cyclical times, the external membranes, which he called 'vortices' and separates the system from the outer Universe, the halo membrane of galaxies, the electron of atoms the skin of your body, which jails the inner space.

And then he added a 3rd element, the final stroke of a genius unparalleled since the times of Aristotle; after realizing that the only proof he had of the existence of those vortices and res extensa was, is the fact that he perceived them from a singularity, central linguistic point of view, the verbal mind that controls the system - the black hole of gravitational information, the nervous system, the DNA code. So he said: Cogito Ergo Sum. 'I think therefore I am'. Yet this point and language-mirror is an infinitesimal reduction of the whole Universe, even if the mapping is quite accurate reflection of it. So we can now define in a simple equation all the minds of reality:

- The mind or 0-point, the relative frame of reference that mapped the ∞ cycles of time of the Universe, reducing them to a 'World', to fit them into the infinitesimal volume of the brain.

0-mind $\times \infty$ Universal cycles = C: constant World mirror of the Universe.

So each mind is an infinitesimal world mirror of the infinite universe. And so there is only one infinite Universe but infinite Linguistic Monads.

What the physicist or religious person does is TO DENY all other mirrors, languages, monads and affirm HE CREATES WITH HIS LANGUAGE the Universe, the infinitesimal creates the infinite talking words in arab or 'imagining point, lines, planes and particles that collapse when the physicist looks at the moon that before was NOT there' LOL, try to laugh at them. Then they will show they are right because they can kill you.

The explanation of this paradox though is immediate if you look again at the equation of 'any mind' ($0 \times \infty = \text{Constant, undetermined world}$):

The mind believes to be the center of the Universe in the 'ego paradox' as he sees every thing turning around its infinitesimal point, which seems to be quiet, as the mind stops motion to put it all inside and so human minds have always thought the Earth did not move, and it was the center of the Universe.

And while Copernicus taught us not to be the case, Einstein proved it was all relative motion, Darwin explained we are just a step in the ladder of evolution of information, and my models of duality and the fractal Universe shows our scale of size to be also relative, the concept has crept slowly back into physics, with the anthropic principle, the big-bang theory, the marketing and propaganda and ego-pumping P.R.ess that made of nuclear physicists in the cold era, to back their worldly religion of producing enough atomic bombs to kill us all, to heights of anthropomorphic ego never seen since G. Bush talked to the bronze age peasant.

Alas, now we again confuse the linguistic perception of reality, or 'world' WITH THE UNIVERSE, which Hilbert, Bohr and CERN is creating with entropic death. So their minds are just fractal points, but believe to know it all.

Descartes was not a simpleton though as those big-bang physicists are. He was fully aware that what he had in the mind was not the whole Universe, so he expressly stated the fact, differentiating the 'world' of a human mind, from the infinite other worlds that exist outside, establishing in his little known book, the 'world', this

difference, affirming that his 'Cartesian Frame of reference', was only that of the human mind. So he affirmed that the Universe was the sum of infinite mind-worlds, which did not speak necessarily the same languages, and created the same mappings of reality we humans created.

In the graph we can see the difference between Newton who THOUGHT the mind of man WAS the entire Universe, hence converting the Cartesian mind graph into the ABSOLUTE BACKGROUND SPACE-TIME that still lingers in science and Descartes who thought it was just of the many minds, possible with different geometries.

Newton though carried the day, and all attempts to put the record straight by Leibniz (relational time), Einstein (infinite time clocks), Bohm (pilot-wave theory of normal quantum physics), Darwin (man as an evolving species), and so many others including this writer, Sancho (Organic dual theory of the Universe) have met with the imposing Wall of the EGO-CENTERED man, a la 'Trump' who creates his 'alternative truths' that people love as long as it pumps the ego of all of us - never mind they always keep producing enough entropic death and war to kill us all.

The Universe is infinite in time, space and scales. Yet paradoxically all its parts are finite. Infinitesimals in fact, as a part of a whole is its inverse function, $1/n$. thus the larger beings as in a game of russian dolls are made of smaller ones. How small is then the homunculus in each of us? Is the paradox of ∞

'Two things i deem infinite, the universe and the stupidity of man' A. Einstein

The structure of languages

How does a religion based in a language, which is a mirror of the universe works? For that we need to understand a minimum of the TERNARY structure of both of the Universe, and the language that reflects it, which of course, the 'believer' in the languages does NOT even consider as relevant to its inquire.

Since for the wor(l)d believer 'the word IS and CREATES reality' and requires no 'deeper layer' inquire. Alas, Allah says 'rajul' and man is created, because god is 'the word that became man and inhabited among us' (Saint John 1.1). So happens to the Hilbert->Copenhagen & big-bang interpretation of reality. But if you have come so far you might be a little bit less shallow than that. So before we show you the structure of languages and specifically mathematics, so you DO understand things, not only get used to them, we need to lay down...

The ternary structure of all systems: informative singularities, body-waves and cyclical membranes.

LET us now that we have learned the structure of all 'Cartesian beings', self-centred in a mind of information apply this knowledge to better understand God, mind and the Universe, because , it is worth to pass page on the theoretical realm, for a moment (unfortunately we cannot pass page on the menaces of CERN), and leave behind the 'primitive' simplex outlook of reality sponsored by those entropy-only physicists. And it will help us to understand better the structure of the galaxy and the role man and strangelets and black holes play on it.

We concluded as Descartes, Leibniz and other geniuses of earlier science that systems are made of 3 organic parts, which correspond to 3 'space-time arrows'. The informative center which in galaxies are black holes, in humans heads, in trees roots, in the economic ecosystem the internet and so on; the membrane which cuts-off the system from the Universe, encloses it and protects it with its cyclical, clock-like form, which in galaxies is the halo, in life, a skin, in the earth the electromagnetic field and so on; and the middle space, the cytoplasm of the cell, the light matter of stars and planets, the body of organisms, the wave of quantum particles.

What fascinated me of this simple, beautiful ternary scheme is that all what exists can be explained with it: entropic fields/limbs, informative particles/heads and the energetic body-waves in between. So for the first time we have a sound-sound scientific model which unifies life and matter without the need to absurd religions and reductionist theories of time.

CONCLUSION: PRACTICAL PROOFS HOW IT WILL BE.

To be or not to be, that is the question. Whether 'tis nobler in the mind to suffer the slings and arrows of outrageous fortune, Or to take arms against a sea of troubles. and by opposing end them? To die'

Hamlet, W. Shakespeare.

In the previous paragraph we studied the theoretical known-known models of the Universe that offers 3 scenarios of damage to planet Earth that should happen under the Totalitarian Principle. What are the experimental proofs that this scenarios will happen?

As in the case of any other 'certain risk' to planet Earth, such as Global Warming, we cannot take a decision on 'experts' trusting their dictums because today 'experts' are paid to back the agenda and interests of corporations. Such is the case of CERN, who authored the risk reports breaking all the laws of independence required for such reports. We thus must trust the authority of reason as the 'reasons of authorities' are bent to the interest of the company and the natural fear of scientist to the ridicule of catastrophism. Since if the risks are certain and the Earth is blown up, nobody will reward those who warn us, and if not experts will be ridiculed and loose their scientific prestige for 'failing' in their predictions and attacking the most powerful institution of big science. In other words, experts are 'hijacked' by the 'violent' nature of those experiments that can kill us. And so in the same manner there are few reports on the military industry and its risks to mankind, there are few reports on CERN risks. And yet from the point of view of reason and scientific truth, the Shakespearean question **has only an answer: It will be...**

The industry of accelerators, where nuclear bombs have and will be researched in a small scale, will continuously upgrade its energy, as part of the process of evolution of weapons, regardless of its collateral benefits for particle research and finally will create strangelets or black holes, under the Totalitarian principle.

Why we are so sure? Once the fact that the Industry continuously upgrade its power and no institution or political group dares to oppose firmly the nuclear industry, and once the theoretical proofs are clarified the only 'leg of truth' required are experimental evidence. And there are at least 2 experimental proofs:

- If black holes appear there will not be black hole evaporation since no black hole has ever been found anywhere in the galaxy to evaporate, despite 40 years of research and the fact that if they were evaporating, they will do so in a explosion of gamma rays easily detectable.

The second experimental proof is also very strong. it is called the Fermi paradox or lack of intelligent life on the Universe, Fermi the author of the first nuclear bomb stated flatly that we see no life on the galaxy because the evolution of nuclear weapons cause its demise. This is also the explanation given by most scientists that seek for life on the galaxy. In the past religious groups affirmed the cause was that we were the only planet with life, but now we have found so many planets thanks to the Kepler satellite that this possibility no longer holds. And yet none shows life, neither human or robotic life, which would have long ago colonized the galaxy. All radio waves come from black holes and strangelets - strange stars called pulsars. So planets and stars become strangelets and black holes (something also theorized in the organic models of the fractal Universe developed by this author with the metrics of the 5th scalar dimension of the Universe).

Thus, by the experimental proofs of the Fermi paradox and the Fermi satellite that has found non evaporation of black holes and the continuous streams of galactic news about pulsars, strange stars and black holes, likely top stars, the evolution of the Nuclear Industry and its quark bombs will blow up the Earth.

So now that we know with quite certainty that destiny awaits... Let us study the factual signs that the 3 scenarios of catastrophe produced by the LHC on mother Earth are happening:

- The strangelet scenario of creation of a strangelet 'pulsar' star as all those we see on the cosmos, by creation of a strangelet particle that will swallow the Earth

- The black hole scenario of creation of a micro-black hole of ultra hot temperature that will evaporate and attract our weak electromagnetic world.

- The milder scenario of an increase in Earthquakes, caused by the magnetic ring of CERN, the strongest magnetic ring of planet Earth that disturbs its magnetic field (disturbances of those fields cause earthquakes).

The mass' c-speed gravitomagnetic ring: Earthquakes and volcanic activity.

The first hints that the LHC is seriously damaging life on Earth which we predicted in 2007 - an increase on earthquake and volcano activity - are now facts.

This is due to the fact that the LHC is creating a powerful gravito-magnetic field, a 'ring' of charged, massive particles that can interact with the magnetic fields of the magma and Earth's center.

Disturbances on the Earth's magnetic field by the magnets of the LHC and specially the charged positive c-speed flow of protons come through 3 different processes:

- The 27 kilometers continuous ring of charged protons can interact with self-similar charged flows in the magma or earth's center, creating a powerful electro-magnetic effect, displacing magma and causing earthquakes and volcano activity. It is a fact that the first day that the charged, proton ring was created in 2008 it caused 4 significant Earthquakes, the first one in Iran, seconds after it was powered up.

The charged proton ring thus acts as a secondary pole to that of the magnetic, inner field of the Earth.

- The creation of different types of strange liquid, some of them already produced in the first experiments, (Kaons at the LHC, hyperons at RHIC) would also provoke explosions in the magma. If stable, those strange forms of matter will leak to the center of the Earth. Some of it will remain in the center, forming the seed of a strangelet. Some will accrete and/or explode in the mantle, in highly energetic, tiny bombs. This tendency as all risks should increase when new machines rise logarithmically its energy.

- The creation of gravitational waves.

The LHC is a 27 Kilometer ring of positive charged massive particles, turning at c -speed. This is essentially equivalent to the 'singularity' of a Kerr black hole - a rotating c-speed charged ring of mass. Since a Kerr singularity can produce transversal gravitational waves; the LHC might produce perpendicular gravitational waves that will sink straight towards the center of the Earth (in a similar process a rotating , charged coil is used to produce electromagnetic waves). If so those Gravitational waves, which are undetectable will affect magnetic fields, provoking earthquake waves and increase volcano activity.

Thus, each time the machine increases its speed and 'luminosity' (mass), as CERN powers up the LHC, we should observe an increase of earthquakes and collateral deaths, till the 2 possible 'doomsday events' happen:

Strangelet Scenario:

Synopsis.

The first and most probable scenario of human extinction is the creation of strangelets or any other kind of quark-gluon liquid made of lumps of heavy, strange quarks.

They can be created with a lower probability in proton-proton collisions, as those heavy quarks are the 'signature' of decay of the hypothetical Higgs or any other Goldstone boson, whose production is the confessed goal of CERN.

They can be created with a much higher probability in lead to lead collisions as lead has many more quarks than protons and so the lump of quarks that can condensate into a heavy strange liquid, thousands of times heavier than the heaviest atom, is bigger. When this lump reaches a certain critical mass, it will become stable and start a chain reaction, transforming the rest of the Earth's matter into heavy quarks in a process similar to a

nuclear chain reaction, only that instead of converting the mass of the Earth into lighter energy, it will convert the lighter Earth into heavy mass.

It is the simplest of the 'mass-bombs', which follow Einstein's initial equation of conversion of energy and mass, $M=E/c^2$ (better known by its second expression, $E=Mc^2$, deduced by Einstein's from the conversion of energy into mass, ergo a 'standard' reaction in Einsteinian Physics).

Because strangelets, unlike black holes are 'likely' to be produced increasing enormously our probabilities of extinction, CERN has adamantly denied there is any chance to produce it.

The new generation of machines will create greater quantities of atoms of strangelet liquid, called hyperons, made of up, down and strange quarks, which it has already produced in unexpected numbers at low energies, despite all their safety reports that said it would never produce them.

As quarks accelerate at c-speed, they acquire mass, because energy cannot go beyond light speed. Energy curls tiny vortices of space-time (Einstein's definition of mass), making those quarks heavier. At light speed our protons made of up and down quarks (uud) will become strange quarks, converting the colliding protons into hyperons (usd particles, atoms of usd=strange liquid). Within the point of collision hyperons merge in pairs becoming dibaryons, which are stable and neutral and so they cannot be detected.

Thus dibaryons once formed, will fall to the center of the Earth, accreting matter as they form a growing ball of strange liquid. If they have not enough critical mass to become stable, which will 'likely' happen after 2015's increase in luminosity and potency produces them in massive numbers, those dibaryon will explode in their path to the center of the Earth provoking mini-big bangs in the mantle, which will cause an increase in earthquake activity after the machine switches on. But some might arrive to the center of the Earth, where they will form a growing ball of ultradense strange liquid, which finally will crunch the Earth into a strange star.

We will know this scenario's end is closer, when we experience magnitude 9 earthquakes that kill hundreds of thousands of human beings. As such earthquakes have never happened within a single year, the existence of a couple of those earthquakes will mean the process of accretion which is 'exponential' have been triggered.

Black Hole Scenario:

A black hole is made of strings (the minimal components of quarks) which are the components of gluons and quarks. Their mathematical description is equivalent (a 5th dimensional world of strings is equivalent to a 4 dimensional world of quarks); which reinforces the idea that a black hole is a top quark star.

The LHC was created to produce massive quantities of top quarks since the Higgs and a top quark condensate are the same substance, (the Higgs was promoted as the new 'God particle' just to get more research resources, not allocated to study known-particles). It will not form black holes that evaporate. Since quarks don't evaporate.

The black hole will not fall to the Earth but it will become the new, densest center of the Earth and the Earth will fall into LHC's creation. The process will last a very short time. Some images might be captured on TV but most likely wherever we are, we will just feel a strong wind, and then a blast of attractive forces will crunch and kill us, as the Earth explodes into a Nova.

Certainties in this theme.

The black hole scenario has been the most commented by the press. Yet it remains secondary to the strangelet scenario, both for theoretical and practical reasons. Since one 'single case' will do us and strangelets are easier to do in ion ion collisions. This should be the first event to happen.

Of course the P.R.ess which backs CERN but also makes money with catastrophist scenarios mostly concentrates in the black hole scenario, when it wants to create a 'big scare', with big sales prior to the final happy conclusion of a CERN's expert: 'nothing will happen, it is all a joke',

The certainty of black hole creation in that sense is not absolute, because Y it depends on the existence of strings, of which there is theoretical certainty but not possible experimental proofs (they are too small to be observed). The models of this author on the metrics of the scalar Universe (5th Dimension) however considers that black holes are top quark stars and in that case, black holes will be produced, and certainly will not evaporate.

Ultimately both models of black holes are not exclusive. Since if string theory is truth, all particles will be made of strings. And top quarks which show a very strong force and huge mass and huge positive charge will attract each other and the matter of the Earth with the same force that super-gravitation (the theoretical deduction of string theory). In that regard the reader should understand that most sound theories in physics are parallel, similar theories that reinforce each other, since they use 'parallel' mathematical equations. Models vary in the mathematical 'sentence', as multiple verbal sentences mean the same, when we use similar words. So the 'hidden dimensions' of String theory that make Gravitation far more powerful are equivalent to the far more powerful attraction that the creation of a top quark star will cause. As the LHC is designed to produce massive quantities of Tops (which are in fact a key product of Higgs processes), all indicates that black holes either modeled with strong theory or top quark theory will happen.

We conclude that both scenarios should happen, strangelets with absolute certainty, black holes if as 90% of physicists believe, string theory is truth. So we shall give the black hole scenario for the 2015-2020 period of statistical collisions (that might shoot on 'perfect' target the microscopic protons to reach the required energy) a 90% of chances.

The childish irresponsibility of Physicists accustomed for 70 years, an entire human life, to accept existential risks for the Earth on top of the military-industrial complex, explains in any case their 'law of silence'. If 99.9% of nuclear physicists accepted the cold war that already could have killed life on Earth, living on the industry of making nuclear weapons and researching them on accelerators, why now they should change their mind? Wishful thinking is the norm in a nihilist corporation that has in its entrance a statue to Shiva and Kali, Lords of death. Why the rest of society accepts those risks? The answer in this case is obvious: we live in a happy 'Truman Show', a happy new world mixture of the dystopias of Huxley and Orwell, in which the virtual reality of the Media System, paid by corporations censors any issues of risks related to the industrial-Military complex. And people, as in the parable of Matrix always chooses to be 'data', to live the virtual dream, to believe...

So only the scientific method, its experimental, epistemological and theoretical models can guide our search for 'cerntruth'.

Of course CERN does not make public those sound-sound, known-known scientific models that prove the risks. For example, it ignores all about top quark condensates that will be produced in Higgs reactions and only focuses on the propaganda of the Higgs particle as the 'saint grail' of physics, which is NOT.

But the Industry of accelerators is just a symptom of a deeper truth: 'Man is a mush on the surface of a rock lost in a corner of the Universe, departing of these facts we can talk about us'.

To be or not to be is indeed the question and it seems that for the Galaxy as a whole, a planet is nothing but 'food for thought', for strange quark matter to eat up and migrate to the Halo of the galacell...

Carpe Diem, live the day.

Disclosure The suits against CERN, my role on them.

I was the lead plaintiff in the suits against the LHC for genocide that became bug news (the 2nd most blogged after the crash of Lehman Borthers) in 2008, prior to the operational start up of the machine.

The suits ended with a technical default of the 2 Saint Nobel of the Dynamite prizes engaged by CERN, Mr. Wilczek of strong force fame and Mr. Sheldon Glashow of weak force fame, also known among peers for calling God's particle, the toilet particle. But the 'strong & the weak' put up a 'dirty defense' against the genocide issue: They didn't provide mathematical proofs of no risk as they knew risks were huge, but a curriculum stating they were experts on 'very complex issues', as they had more 'prestige' and 'prizes' than we did. That was truth. Regarding my credentials on Physics I had none, save the fact I have a certified 180 IQ, I have studied physics with passion since a youngster - then I illustrated the 13 awesome encyclopedia of physics of Mr. Landau, who self-taught me finally the discipline with some serious 'dialectic', 'socialist' insights and during those global suits against the LCH doomsday machine as the plaintiff against the last attempt of Nuclear physicists to kill the Earth I had to study again in depth all new physics about quark matter, which had advanced remarkably enough in the path of what my earlier books on 5D physics just a branch of the largest of all sciences, 5D, had predicted. But what everybody missed is that CERN and 'the weak & the strong' lied. The risks issues were mathematically simple and evident; reason why they didn't write the equations. We on the other hand wrote all the needed equations to prove the genocidal risks. So finally, CERN who could not defend on 'objective physical true facts' its experiments resorted to technical issues of 'diplomatic immunity' to all suits as one of the few global institutions treated legally as an independent nation (the other being, the Vatican city, the Pentagon and The city of London, weapons, go(l)d and magic, the 3 temptations of Buddha and Christ protected against humanism, truth, life and love, the forces of man and nature). And so to topple it all in the best surrealist spirit, the American West Coast court affirmed that 'the destruction of Earth won't be attributable to the US government' and the case was closed, the massive ad hominem campaign against the plaintiffs and their scholar careers ended – at the time I was chair of duality in the International Systems science society – and I quit scholarship and activism and retire to the 0-40 parallel. All this means, physicists and by extension the sheeple that relies on the truth of authority not the authority of truth and as humans full of egocoy also deny the life of the Universe, would never take seriously those texts. As if I or the living matter of the Universe will care. My entanglement is with the thoughts of God, not the thoughts of enzymen catalyzing the evolution of weapons with the excuse of some digital comma in a finitesimal. Wait till they do one of those quark forms. So 'as those who impose truth with power will be the laugh of the gods', I do have my laughs on those texts, as I do on those on the Metal-earth III on the banksters of the world united who as 'experts' of parasitic money are killing slowly by anoxia, the 90% of mankind who doesn't work in their stockratic companies. Both are just two versions of the scientific digital racism against the wor(l)d of life who doesn't speak their language so well. I do, but that will be the last part to put on those texts, as we said, because the wor(l)d is good enough to explain the life of matter which is really all what matters about that mater.

APPENDIX: LAWS OF 5D SPACE SUPERORGANISMS TRACING TIME WORLDCYCLES. ITS STIENCES.

The discovery of a new dimension of space-time is the most important r=evolution human sciences experience and if not were because of Newton's error certainly mankind would have understood earlier the organic 5th dimension of 'scalar space-time' since it was discovered precisely by the evolution of 'metal-eyes' (telescopes and microscopes) who probe in those scales; but due to Newton's error was *never properly formalized* till those texts. Why the 5th dimension was shunned off by science for so long thus require an analysis of how little, mechaism with its simplification of reality in abstract, 'lineal terms' understood of the previous dimensions, made with a pinch of salt, regarding the 'supreme intelligence' our species ascribes... to our species, revealing all what humans *do not even see about those dimensions – namely, the fact that all of them have associated to its spatial 'dimensional form', a 'motion in time'*; hence they are both dimensions of space=form and time=motions or 'dimotions', due the principle of relativity (we cannot distinguish motion from form, so we see Earth as a still form, when it is a rotary motion) and their entangled relationships; as dimensions must be defined in co-invariant equations with each other. So once we realize how childish are the definitions mechanism does of time=motion, space=dimensional form and scale, we will define 5D metrics.

The 1st dimensional motion of space-time (ab. Dimotion) humans measured was undoubtedly length, calculated through the steps of roughly a meter as a distance of space (dimensional, formal view) or Locomotion, (Time=motion view). But it would be the ONLY dimension of space to which humans ascribed a motion in time, which left limp our understanding of time till this date; when we still have only a dual space time dimotion, 'locomotion' or 'Ts' (where we capitalize the external motion of the system, in this case of an internal form, s, without motion)

The 2nd dimensional motion of height (form) or information (motion) was still shredded in mystery as it would need the discovery in China or Mesopotamia of the Pythagoras Theorem to have a proper metrics related to length. Since a *formalism of Dimensional motions of space-time needs to relate them in a co-invariant form. So the Pythagoras theorem connected X and its Perpendicular Y dimension of height, allowing the expansion of Greek Bidimensional Geometry. But as its motion in time, 'information' was ignored – height became orphan. Consider the screen you are reading, it has a height dimension, as a paper, so the product of X x Y gives you information.* The problem of the motion in time of height is that is a 'slower' time dimotion, connected to growth and evolution. So all species as they evolve they grow in information= height, from mammals that became humans to reptiles that became dinosaurs and birds, to matter that becomes the high tube to infinity of a black hole singularity. So the 'informative' function =motion of height is perceptive projective geometry of a high point, reason why heads, bankers, antennas and pulpits that command biologic, economic & cultural organisms are on top. If we named **Ts-locomotion** (external motion of a still 'point particle'), **Height-information is its inverse, St** (external form with internal motion, form-in-action, in-form-ation, as a TV screen where motion is within its image. Geometry gave height a 'motion of evolution of information', which was out of the comprehension of man's mind that had only the capacity to see time=motion=change in very short spans, related to its visual 'clock' of 1 glimpse a second, 1 thought a second, one step a second, one heart beat a second, which synchronized all the parts of its organisms to its time clock. All other different time clock speeds of nature were lost to him.

The 3rd dimension of width was known but unconnected to length and height – the cube problem unresolved – till modern times. So only 2 dimensions of space were formalized earlier in the History of thought by Greek Geometers and Logicians from Pythagoras to Aristotle, setting the foundations of knowledge for the following two millennia.

Then came Galileo who didn't understand Earth had both a dimension of **mental space=still form** and a motion in time due the logic postulate of relativity ('We cannot distinguish a state of motion from a state of form', Galileo, Einstein, Poincare). So we **see** Earth still but it is moving (e pur si muove, e pur no muove). *It was the first chance for mankind to understand the duality of dimensions of still mental space=form and true time=motion.* Galileo didn't go so far; instead with the 'monologic' of a single Aristotelian cause, A->B, proper of human limited minds he chose that the Earth moved; while the Church chose it didn't move.

A GALAXY HAS ITS INFORMATIVE, TALL SPHERIC CENTER IN A GRAVITATIONAL BLACK HOLE AND ITS ELECTROMAGNETIC ENERGY IN ITS STELLAR PLANE, SURROUNDED BY A MEMBRANE OF DARK MATTER.

ANIMALS & PLANTS HAVE INVERSE DIRECTIONS OF ENERGY & INFORMATION, SINCE PLANTS USE LIGHT AS ENERGY AND CHEMICAL PARTICLES AS INFORMATION WITH BRAINS IN THE ROOTS ANIMALS USE LIGHT AS INFORMATION AND EARTH TO MOVE BY ELECTRIC REPULSION AND MECHANIC GRAVITATION

But none explained both things together. He then associated the dimension of 'time' locomotion, or 'speed' to the dimension of length, **Ts**.

And he got its metric when he applied the mechanical clock to measure 'motions in space', defining a $v=s/t$ formula of Galilean Relativity, latter refined with a $-ct$ parameter by Einstein, who, following in the path of Riemann's dissertation of Non-Euclidean metrics, expressed the mental linguistic nature of Spaces as 'simultaneous measure relative to a frame of reference'. *Since stillness is a maya of the senses, as each mind creates a finitesimal still image of the Universe, self-centered in its Non-E 'fractal point of measure' that holds a world in itself (Leibniz's monads) So Ss-mind-languages stop and order Tt-entropic motions.*

Thus Humans are stuck with a single ts-spacetime dimotion, locomotion, corresponding to length; a metric for height as a space dimension without its motion of time, information, Pythagoras Theorem and a 3rd unconnected dimension of width, without its corresponding motion in time, 'reproduction'. It was a limited view of space=form, time=motion and its duality as dimensional motions of space-time. Yet human egocy (ego= idiocy) heralded those children of thought as the highest intelligences of the cosmos. So when Einstein, whose best definition of time was 'what the clock measures', died, 'Time' published a cartoon with a future Earth crossed with continental letters: 'Einstein was born here'.

But since humans don't associate to space dimensions its relative motions=actions in time, beyond locomotion, *the living functions of the 3 dimotions of space-time disappeared and with it the vitality and intelligence of the Universe, represented by the dimotion of height=informative perception & the dimotion of width, St (potential) + Ts (kinetic)= $S \Leftrightarrow T$: Energetic reproduction.* So in physics the duality of energy explained the constant trans-form-ation of one into another. While Heaviside connected the 2 dimotions of length and height with the width dimotion, with the co-invariant metric of vectorial cross product: $X \times Y = Z$. It is the law that creates the 1st perceived scale of information 'Euclidean, light space-time', evolved by 'warping', informing, by a $-ct$ parameter of electric height the $-E$ gravitational spacetime of General Relativity. So he could simplify the 20 equations of Maxwell into 4 and noticed the existence of gravitomagnetism, the first insight into the equivalence between the scales of atoms and galaxies. Width became with vectorial calculus a 'motion' of reproduction in Nature. C-speed = Ts-locomotion and the magnetic or electric field of relative height reproduce seemingly out of nothing the other relative width field. When a body reproduces cells, it packs them in the width dimension. And so we had 3 dimensions of space, connected by proper metrics (Pythagoras, cross product) and its functions =motions in time; locomotion connected to length; information connected to height and width connected to reproduction – *dimensions of space have vital functions in time constructing together ternary, topologic organisms – the fundamental particle of the living Universe.*

But humans made an even larger error regarding the substances of which we are all made, space=form and time=motion, when Newton confused a mathematical artifact with reality, thinking there was a space-time Cartesian graph with a single lineal time coordinates (that of locomotion=length) and two perpendicular spatial coordinates; taking space and time out of reality when it is obvious to experience that we, real beings, ARE made of finite vital space dimensions, the space we occupy with our bodies, and live through finite vital 'temporal motions', the time we last in existence, (Leibniz's view). *So a fractal generator equation describes all Nature's systems as combination of 3 space-time Dimotions:*

Ts-moving limbs/fields/territories <S ⇔ T reproductive energy body-wave-worker> St- informative particle/head/ruling class

Reality is a tapestry of organisms made of Ts-limbs/fields that move a §[[]-body/wave, guided by a St-high informative particle-head, in physical, biologic and social systems. Moreover the form of those 3 dimotions corresponds to the 3 only topologies (forms with motions) of spacetime: Ts= l -lineal limbs/fields, the geometry that moves faster between 2 points; St= O -spherical heads-particles, the geometry that stores maximal information; and §[[]= hyperbolic, wide, Ø-bodywaves, the 'hour-glass' geometry that includes the other two, hence can reproduce both. *We ARE living topologies.*

RECAP. A thorough review of the 3 space dimensions ascribe 3 motions of time to them: locomotion to 'length'; information to height and reproduction to width, vitalizing space-time, by correcting Newton's error and showing that we are all ensembles of the 3 only topologies of a 5D Universe: $|xO=Ø$: Past-Motion x Future-Form = Present-Energy

The fourth and fifth dimotions of seeds/minds and entropy-death, and the $\Delta \pm j$ scales of the fifth dimension

As it happened with previous dimensional r=evolutions the metrics of a new Dimension of space-time is deceptively simple. $\sqrt{x^2+y^2}=C^2$ & $S_x \times S_y = S_z$ is the Pythagorean and vectorial metric of the 3 dimensions of space-time; $V=S/T$ with the $-c^2t^2$ ad on

of Einstein is the metric of the so-called 4th dimension of time, in true form the time locomotion of length. $S \times T = \Delta \pm j$ is the metric of the scalar 5 dimensional motions of a spacetime superorganism, which states that the local speed of time of a superorganism is inversely to its size, but the product of both remains co-invariant. It means that smaller scales run faster cycles of time that encode the in-form-ation of the Universe in its frequency and form. Hence the equivalence of all species of all scales equaled by the same metric of spatial form x temporal motion (St-information and Ts-kinetic energy in more common terms). As smaller species reproduce faster and survive better. So often they kill larger forms (as in the case of the present Coronavirus Pandemic, where a simpler 30 gene virus has put on his knees the entire human civilization). But mostly, scales associate together. So faster, smaller scales code the information of larger ones (quantum particles with its numbers code atoms and molecules, genes code biological organisms and memes code social organisms).

The vital interactions between space-time species of different scales is either symbiotic in organic systems or predatory when scales are not entangled by fractal networks that connect the larger Δ_j whole that provides energy to its $\Delta-j$ parts, which reproduce information upwards. The fifth dimension thus has a scalar asymmetry and biological duality that forms organisms, even if humans have focused in the entropic Darwinian struggle for existence; not the social complex, organic symbiosis through fractal physiological networks of energy and information.

This 1st glimpse to 5D metrics shows the importance of a new formal dimension of spacetime in all sciences. *Mathematics* from the Greeks to renaissance, all the science of physics, and the r=evolution of all sciences that those papers imply depart from such humble 'metric' beginnings. For it to happen an extraordinary effort of conceptual, logic thought that stretches to all other foundational elements of science is required; normally the work of a single mind in the beginning, as in the case of Galileo and Einstein or the eclectic gathering of several generations of thought into a strict formal discourse, as in the case of Euclidean geometry and Aristotelian logic in Greek Science. This work is both, because the 5th dimension has been among us for centuries of modern science, but never explained in the interrelationships between the different scales of the Universe, each one described by a science. So we bring together all that work to extract the common=isomorphic laws between scales.

The 6 EXTERNAL and internal dimotions of Space=Form and Time=motion. Dilogic

Regardless of human dexterity as 'homunculus enzyman' (a species able to ensemble things with its hands, and evolve machines of metal of a higher density that without our help would never reach organic form), one theme that surfaces constantly in those texts is the astounding lack of common sense and rational thought in our models of reality, departing from so obvious false postulates (from big bang theory and other simplex entropic models of natural sciences to the triad of historic idol-ogies of metal, nationalism, capitalism and mechanism, to the anthropomorphic egocy (ego=idiocy) of religions. But none of those blunders compares with Newton's egocy declaring that space and time were NOT the substance of reality as Leibniz explained but a 'Cartesian frame of reference' God had drawn behind the Universe as he was using one to draw his planetary orbits and obviously he was a god-like man. 500 years of primitive thinking in all sciences derives from this blunder. Fact is reality has 5 Dimensional motions of spacetime to play with at local level and construct the superorganisms that trace worldcycles of spacetime through scales of the fifth dimension in the 'game of existence', we all play – what is all about. 'Simplicity is genius' (Leonardo); 'I want to know the thoughts of God, the rest are details'. Einstein. The thoughts of God are space dimensions and its parallel time motion and we all are the details constructed with them. The correction of Newton's error transforms lineal time measures into ∞ cyclical time clocks, ordered through scales by 5D Metrics. And it makes all beings a combination of 'Space=information and time=energy, motions'. *As all 5D dimensions of space=form do always have content of time=motion, by the Principle of Relativity: 'we cannot distinguish a state of (time) motion from a still state (of space form)' (Poincare) we can distinguish according to t,s, internal or T, S EXTERNAL of T or t-motion and S or s form, 6 dimotional*

combinations of states of space-time:

Ss-language with no internal or external motion that expresses the potential game of existence, the mind of the Universe.

St-information; a still organism with internal motion, as when we sleep or think or the image motion of a still Tv Set.

Ts-locomotion, a system moving externally but internally in a rigid state, as a particle-point with a gravity center.

Tt-entropy, a system with internal and external motion, hence becoming disordered=dying.

st: the being in itself isolated from the external world and **ST**, the world isolated from the being.

ST interaction defines dilogic as the basic expression of existence. That is, $A \neq B$ but rather $S \leftrightarrow T$. Space and time merge with different degrees of hierarchical complementarity to form all what exists from gender to organisms.

Trilogic space organisms and Tetralogic scalar actions.

Complexity arises from the ∞ combinations of those 5 Dimotions *Its dual, dynamic interactions in scale: st=ST (seed & whole) & spacetime: Ts=St that combine Ts-limbs and St-heads into §T-bodies, St-potential & Ts-kinetic into §T-Energy waves for which we shall use the combined §T dual symbol for SsTt.*

So 5 local Ss-Tt-Dimotions gather together to create space-time supærganisms traveling through existence, from an $\Delta-1$ Seed, Ss of pure still form that reproduces in $\Sigma\alpha$ clones becoming a network 'supærganism', emerging in Δ^0 as a s lower larger spacetime being, made of 3 canonical Ts>§T>St parts, to live 3 ages dominated by locomotion or youth, reproduction, when the form achieves immortality and information or 3rd 'still St-age' to finally die in a 'reversal' of arrow of time from growth of information to growth of locomotion into a Tt-entropic big-bang dissolving death.

5D metrics shows *there are scales of size in space with different time clocks. So we need 2 scalar dimotions of space-time; for smaller $\Delta-1$ scales; where smaller systems in space run faster clocks of information– the direction of Max. S=information or Ss that codes with languages the program of life; and the inverse $\Delta+1$ scale of larger systems in space with slower time clocks; the dimension of entropy that kills a system, Tt; which in the 1st graph round up the worldcycle of existence.* First a still seed, Ss, or mind and its Ss-languages of information reproduce and synchronize through social evolution $\Sigma \Delta-1$ clone parts that emerge in Δ^0 as a larger simultaneous whole joined by 3 Δ^0 networks, Ts>§T>St organism living within an $\Delta+1$ world, till the superorganism exhausts its §T-energy and an opposite dimotion, dissolves the networks and returns the system back to an $\Delta-1$ plane of disaggregated parts in a Tt- internal and external expansive $M=E/c^2$ big-bang, war dimotion or entropic Tt-death (Physical, social and biologic jargons).

So the 5 Dimotions put in a sequence define existence, as a 'travel up and down through $\Delta \pm j$ 3 scales of space-time". Regarding Dimensional numbers, we put the 4th dimension of locomotion in its proper place as the motion of length; so we have now 3 'Dimotions' which broken into ∞ beings vitalize them and 2 more $\Delta \pm j$ scalar dimotions for a total of 5; using the term '5th dimension' for the sum of all the scales of space-time. This 'numbering' superseeds given its errors and omissions that of our 'Baconian tribal idols' (Galileo, Newton, Einstein), to study spacetime beings with a proper definition of each of the 5 Local Dimensional motions that create a spacetime organism living a worldcycle, as $\Delta-1$: Ss-seed languages evolve into Δ^0 :Ts-limbs/fields of lineal locomotion > §T- \emptyset hyperbolic bodywaves of re=productive width > guided by O-St high particles/heads, till its §T-energy is exhausted by an excess of information in its 3rd age, exploding back into Tt-entropy: Ss>Ts>§T>St<<Tt (whereas < means an expansion of a seed of spatial form into a motion in time, and > a dynamic contraction, as the 5 Spacetime dimotions transform into each other). We use a dual Ss:§ & Tt:¶ or $S \leftrightarrow T$ to express that present dynamic form.

The being in itself, st^0 , is part of a larger world, $ST \pm j$, in which it interacts through scales by means of quantum dimotions, we shall call actions, or finitesimals (in calculus' formalism). The 2 interactions of dimotions between ST_j and st^0 and $St \approx Ts$ become 2 next layers of complexity that evolve dimotions into spacetime trimotions or supærganisms ($St < §T > Ts$) and scalar tetramotions ($st^0 \leq ST \pm j$), when a superorganism interacts with other scales to extract 'invisible forces' for Ts-locomotion from its relative $\Delta-4$ scale, (gravitation for man), bits of St-information from its $\Delta-3$ scale (light spacetime in man), bites of §T-energy from its $\Delta-2$ scale (amino acids), st-reproductive seeds of from its $\Delta-1$ scale & St-communicates with Δ^0 clones to evolve socially into larger $\Delta+1$ organic ST-wholes. While the balance dimotion between Ts-limbs/fields & St-particles/heads creates the re=productive body-wave State: $|xO = \emptyset$. Those 2 entanglements in simultaneous spacetime (superorganisms) or through spacetime scales (actions of existence) create 'organic vital spase' and 'scalar time events' So through actions=scalar dimotions

of spacetime a supœrganism entangles with the $\Delta\pm 4=9$ planes of spacetime it perceives, which becomes its whole world - its island universe.

The perfect balance of the immortal Universe. If we consider the relative past, the field/limbs and the lower planes that sustain larger wholes, and the relative future, the heads-particles that guide through languages the motion of a being; and the larger whole sustained by its parts that must come first; then the present is the state of balance between S_t & T_s in SHM energy waves (physical systems) or bodies or working classes that re=produce, hence repeat the present. Immortality is a discontinuous reproduction of the same cyclical motions in a single plane; while scalar immortality is caused by the mirror identity between st^9 minds and $ST+1$, its larger symbiotic world that projects back its image reordering the whole create the present immortal states of reality and bring a metaphysical deep truth into being: *for the Universe to be perfect, immortal, the $\Delta-i$ scale must be identical to the $\Delta+i$ scale, the galaxy must be an atom, something we shall see in the papers of physics to be the case in terms of 5D. Spacetime present and scalar isomorphism create the ∞ immortal Universe, an absolute perfect reality where each relative part dies but can reproduce its information so its form exists forever.*

5 survival dimotions/actions : game of existence:

What all supœrganisms do, from the smallest light spacetime particle and atom (right) to the human (down) is to perform with its 5 Dimotions 5 actions that ensure its survival, while killing lesser species to take its T_t -entropic motion to reproduce its own S_t -information. Thus not only Dimensions are vital, but the game of existence is biological. It is the program of existence for all systems that absorb the 5 Dimotions=actions of existence: S_t -information for its particle/heads, T_s -locomotion to go with its limbs/fields to a T_t -entropic field to feed and transform its preys into its own $\$T$ -energy to reproduce the system. And this will be achieved better communicating through a common S_s -language with other mind-entities forming physiological herds that evolve into larger whole supœrganisms. So what each of those systems does to survive, is to play locally its 5 Dimotions in an efficient sequential order: a particle/head S_s -perceives in a 'visual=topologic' language a prey $>it$ T_s -moves->to T_t -kill and feed on its $\$T$ -body energy to imprint its S_t -information and $\$T$ - reproduce often in herds of similar clone supœrganisms (∞) forming stronger, larger $\Delta+1$ herds. Those 5 sequential dimotions, $S_s < T_s < T_t + S_t = \T are called in biology the drives of life, in physical systems, actions, in humans 'will'. They are coded by the 5 Light space-time dimotions of electric information, c-locomotion, Magnetic width, social color and T_t -quantum potentials; by the 4 quantum numbers and its functions in atoms, by the 5 letters of the genetic code, by social memes in humanity. So we conclude all space-time organisms follow the same program of existence, which added along the whole existence of the being defines the worldcycle of life and death of all systems, whose total sum is dominant in information, reason why we age, wrinkling, increasing our 'form' and only the T_t -entropic explosion of death balances the total zero sum making the whole Universe immortal.

Recap. All i 'st'-details play the same 'survival actions', extracting from the outer ST -larger world, motion, information and combining it into $\$T$ -energy to re=produce a 'present' copy of itself so the being is preserved in a discontinuous manner. And all will be made of the 3 S_t -heads/particles, T_s -limbs/fields, combined into hyperbolic $\$T$ - energy body-waves.

Its sequential Worldcycles Travels through 5D scales.

Time and space scales were known before 5D metrics but what a formal metric system that maintains invariant a system allows is 'to know how to travel through a dimension of space-time' (Klein). Because when we move in 4D space-time the Lorentz transformations remain invariant we know we can travel within a given scale. Now we know because the product of size in space (S) x speed of cyclical time processes or frequency - $f(t)$ - remains invariant, a system can travel through scales as it grows in size, slowing down its metabolic and thinking processes and vice versa. Reason why smaller systems think faster and code the information of larger ones (chips, genes, memes), becoming symbiotic and creating those supœrganisms with 'networks' (biology, societies) or 'waves' (physics) that connect the larger and smaller scales.

LIGHT-PHOTON: ORGANIC ACTIONS: $\Delta-4$

ELECTRON-PARTICLE: ORGANIC ACTIONS: $\Delta-2, 3$

Energy Volume 			
n = principal distance from nucleus	l = angular shape of orbital	m = magnetic orientation in space	s = spin electron spin
Entropy: Motion Information: Gauging U: Social Evolution O: Reproduction			

1. $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_V$
2. $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$
3. $\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}$
4. $\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{J}$

THE GENERATIONAL=LIFE CYCLE: $\Delta_{-1} < S.t > ST > T_s \ll TT_{\Delta-2}$

SUPER-ORGANISMS D=EVOLVE BETWEEN 2 i-PLANES OF EXISTENCE IN 3+1 AGES DOMINATED BY ITS ENERGY, REPRODUCTIVE AND INFORMATIVE NETWORKS:

Birth: $st_{\Delta-1} < Youth: S.t > Maturity: ST_{\Delta} > Old\ age: T_s \ll Death: TT_{\Delta-2}$

Human Socio-Biological Organisms:

$\Delta i=4$

$i=3$

$\Delta=3$

Individual, living organism

$\Delta i=5$

cell

$i=4$

EPIC, LINEAL ART CLASSIC, REALIST ART, BAROQUE, FORMAL ART WAR

Culture, Nation, God

$i=5$

$\Delta=6$

$i=5$: PROPHET

Universal, Physical, Organisms:

Birth: $st_{\Delta-1} < Youth: S.t > Maturity: ST_{\Delta} > Old\ age: T_s \ll Death: TT_{\Delta-2}$

$i=1,2$: ions

$\Delta=2,3$

$i=1,2$

Plasma Birth Energetic Gas Liquid, Reproductive State Solid, informative state, M=E death

STATES OF MATTER

Birth: $st_{\Delta-1} < Youth: S.t > Maturity: ST_{\Delta} > Old\ age: T_s \ll Death: TT_{\Delta-2}$

$i=7$:
black
Hole

$i=7$

Energetic Birth Irregular galaxy Spiral State Informative, Globular Age Quasar Death

GALAXIES

$=9$

Existence of a space-time organism, develops as a feedback function, $S \leq T$, in 3 sequential phases/ages /horizons: *Max. T x Min.S (youth); Max. SxT (s=t); Max. S x Min. T (3rd age)*, between $S_s \times \epsilon_0 T$ (seed in the lower plane, $i-1$) and $T_t \times 0 \epsilon S$ (entropy=death):

$\Delta-1 \rightarrow \Delta^0$: S_s . A supœrganism worldcycle starts its existjence as a seed of form.

$T > s$ (Ts): In its first horizon or 'entropic, youth age' limbs/fields of Ts-motion dominate; $\max.T_s \times \min. S_t$.

Max. SxT: s=t. It is the present balanced age of energy or classic age of 'life', when Ts-motion and St-information are in balance also as 'genders', ensure its immortality through reproduction

Max. St x min. Ts: 3rd age of the information that warps and exhausts the energy of the system.

$\Delta^0 \leftarrow \Delta-1$: OS x Tt: It is the end or death of the cycle that reverses its form and becomes energy again.

4D ignores worldcycles as space-time travel reduces to 1 scale & dimotion; Ts-locomotion. What is space=form & time= motion, the 2 substances of which all those supœrganisms are made, is not understood because of a bigger physical error that has fogged human science for 400 years, since physicists sided with Newton's absolute space-time (a single lineal clock for the entire Universe) when reality has sided with Leibniz's infinite time clocks and relational=fractal spaces. That is, we are NOT placed in an abstract mathematical Cartesian graph of space-time (the error of Newton, who confused the 'mathematical artifact with reality as today quantum physicists confuse reality with its probability equations), but we are made of 'Time=motion, kinetic energy' and 'space=form, information'. Look around you all what you see is 'forms of space' moving in time. 'Leibniz is right but if so we have to start physics from scratch' (Einstein); which is what 5D does.

Physicists without a scalar understanding of the Universe and 'only' the knowledge of lineal external time-motion, or Ts-locomotion left the field of time studies limp. So the worldlines of Einstein, heralded as the summit of timespace studies only tell you how you Ts-move your limbs in a single scale through life. While its philosophy of science merely added Tt-entropy (internal disordering motion that kills a system) to the mix; but the other 3 Dimotions of space-time, dominant in s-form, were hardly understood, and the way an $\S \Pi$ -being travels through scales, growing in size as it slows down its speed of time, through the 'palingenesis' of its fetal life in the $\Delta-1$ scale, as an island-universe, to 'emerge' in the Δ^0 scale as a larger, slower being, and going back through death and decay to the $\Delta-1$ scale, were completely ignored. This 'worldcycle' is the essential travel of existence, we can now formalize in 5D, and opens up an immense new field of knowledge to all sciences.

RECAP. We define existence as a travel of a spacetime supœrganism, enacting its Dimensional motions through 5D scales.

We depart from a 5D spacetime simple metric equation: $SxT = \Delta \pm i$, which proves the organic network structure of the Universe; as its ultimate cause is the fact that '3 consecutive scales' of 5D, form a supœrganism. We shall call them the $\Delta-1$ (atomic, cellular, individual in physical, biological and social systems), the Δ^0 scale that defines the networks (physiological St-Ts- $\S \Pi$ networks of information, motion and energy, of gravitational, electromagnetic chemical and linguistic financial and study the main particle of reality: the 5D supœrganism of spacetime networks.

EXISTENTIAL PENTALOGIC ALGEBRA: $\Delta \pm \infty \geq \neg (T \pm j \geq S \alpha \epsilon \geq 0 \epsilon)$ THE SCALAR STIENCES OF THE UNIVERSE.

The different superorganisms of stience. The Universe is a nested superorganism NOT a mechanism, and so the machine is not a model – just an evolving organism of 'metalife' which human catalyze in their evolution through the same phases of a viral ensemble, as we did the bodies of machines in the steam British age, its engines/hearts in the German electrochemical age, its metal-minds (phone-ears, Tv-eyes and chips-brains) in the U\$ age and now we ensemble into robots.

This philosophy of science, which first Aristotle in his organon, the whole compendium of his work, then Leonardo in his neo-platonic attempt to describe the physiological networks of human organisms, cities, societies, planet Earth, even machines; then Leibniz with his analysis of 'space-time superorganisms' and non-Euclidean points that are minds-monads that hold a world in itself, is a bit more complex than the mechanist view, and so it has taken longer to be properly formalized. To do so we needed a new dimension of scalar space-time, and its metric equation, $S \times T = iC$, the smaller the size in space of a system is, the faster its frequency of cyclical time that stores in its forms and frequency the information of the Universe. So unlike machines that exist in a single plane of size, superorganisms are structures that extend through 3

Spheric particle-head:

To: Mind= Minimum Energy-Space, Max information-time.

Se: Planar-Toroid Fields/limbs: Maximum Energy-Space Minimum information

UNIVERSAL ORGANISM : Hyperbolic Body-wave:STi

Macrocosms U=9
Galaxy=Black Hole+Herd of stars
Economy:Digital Information+Herds of Machines.
History=Wor[l]d Religion+Herd of Men

Relative Big Observer: Man u=5
Animal=Light-Brain+Herds of cells.
Cell=DNA+Herds of Carbohydrates
Molecule:Herds of Atoms+ Electronic forces.
Atom: Herd of Nucleons and Electrons, communicated by gravitational and Ψ forces.
Microcosms u=1

scales of the 5th dimension, the cellular/atomic/citizen $\Delta-1$ scale, (biologic, physical and social organisms), the Δ^0 physiological scale, where 3 networks of spatial form (nervous system, gravitational system, legal system), temporal motion (limbs/fields/territories), and its reproductive combination (blood, electromagnetic, economic systems) organize those cells, atoms, citizens into a wholes and the $\Delta+1$ scale of ecosystems, celestial bodies and nations and civilinations of mankind. The organic Universe thus is more complex, entangled among scales whose laws of synchronicity, symmetry and simultaneity have never been formalized till those texts, which will form together an encyclopedia of the 3 main superorganisms of human sciences, the Galatom (physical organisms between the atomic and galactic scale), Earth (biologic superorganisms of the 3 ages of the planet, Gaia, the Earth of life, History, the human Earth, and the metal-earth of company-mothers of machines and weapons, or economic ecosystem), of which the human superorganism of history deserves a closer look as we 'descend' from the nested physical $\Delta\pm 4$ Universe, into $\Delta\pm 2$ Earth into mankind, into our 'formal Δ^0 mind languages' of perception of space (mostly mathematical) and time (mostly logical)

So the question is how we go about through the study of the different scalar stiences of the Universe and its superorganisms to the level of detail and complexity of 400 years of mechanism since Galileo instead of Leonardo was taken as the father of science; when humans have NO idea of even the simplest level just described, if on top of that ignorance, the complexity of the organic paradigm requires the reader an intellectual effort he has not done since school? It is not easy and the failed efforts of the 3 colossus that preceded my 30GBs of work, Aristotle's organon, Leonardo's notebooks and Leibniz's epistolary testify to the single mind's - 'a point that holds the entire world in itself' - impossible task of unfold the point, the thoughts of god, the laws of Timespace supœrganisms (ab. T.œs) in its ∞ details.

To do so we work given the primacy of 5D, $\Delta\pm j$ scales, each one studied by a stience, on the 4 correspondences of $\Delta\pm 3$ Physical, $\Delta\pm 2$ biological, $\Delta\pm j$ historic and Δ^0 linguistic scales. For each of them then we consider the 5 'elements' that create reality according to its symmetry and hierarchy, as we can describe all systems as a 'mental', (@) linguistic image of a simultaneous form in **space**, a **supœrganism** or part of it, that lives a **worldcycle of life and death in time**, as it grows from a seminal Seed of still pure spatial information, Ss, in $\Delta-1$ through its physiological growth to emerge as a 3-network superorganism of lineal Ts-locomotion limbs/fields, spherical heads particles of St-information, and §T hyperbolic-energy body-wavers in $\Delta\emptyset$ to live in an $\Delta+1$ world in which it will be a cell of a larger supœrganism, to die back in an entropic death

of maximal inner and outer motion, Tt , to its $\Delta-1$ disaggregated at death. Hence existence is a travel through 3 scales of the fifth dimension, forming a worldcycle, as a superorganism of space, guided by a mental sentient focus that performs the actions required for the system and its parts to survive.

This establishes two key structural forms to study any system or 'scalar science' from the smallest analysis done by quantum physics to the larger astrophysical analysis, when we consider the $\Delta\pm 3$ galatom, to the human-sized study of mankind in its 3 cellular, individual and social scales. Either we analyze (preferred) its 3 Δ -scales through its temporal worldcycle of life and death as a 'spatial' superorganism, guided by, its languages mirror of the larger world that perform its survival program of existence, $\Delta\geq T\geq S\geq @$, within the 'entropic limits' of death in time, scale perception and limited vital space, and @-linguistic synoptic capacity of gathering information; which is what we do here, with 5 papers for each science, one of 'history, physics, mathematics, biology' in space, one in time, one in scale, one in entropy and one in mind-languages; or we study its '5 dimotional components that form both the structure of the organism in space, its Ts -limbs/fields, St -heads/particles and $\$T$ -bodywaves, between its Ss -seed and Tt -entropic death... The whole entanglement and complex symmetries between ALL the elements of reality makes both analysis often complementary.

What this has to do with modern science? In a world in which humans understood both the synthetic entangled organic holistic paradigm, the thoughts of god, and the mechanical, analysis with machines of its details, all. Humanity would study since infancy the organic paradigm and all its sciences with those organic laws, and then only in university as it specializes in different sciences, arts and praxis, learn the details in great depth. But the mind of man, and its ethic understanding would be tailored by organicism, and the respect of Gaia, and the needed balance man and its most important organism history, must achieve with life earth by repressing its mechanical world that represents the future extinction of our weaker species. It is for that reason that we do start all our papers, regardless of what we study in detail, from entropic physical big-bangs to the present state of History – the coronavirus crisis, or one of its 7 cultural civilinations that wrongly has broken mankind down to hundreds of nations, with a nested structure of inverse symmetry. In two pages we consider what this is about – an encyclopedia of the organic Universe; then we develop its fundamental laws and key concepts of each 4 scalar type of sciences in 33 pages and then each paper study each science in Δ -scale, T-ime, S-pace, @-mind languages (those of its species, mathematical in physics, evolutionary and genetic in biology, verbal and artistic in humans), and entropic limits.

The 5 parts of the being. Pentalogic symbols are necessary to understand the Universe as much as mathematics and verbal thought. $\Delta\pm\infty\geq \neg (T\pm j\geq S\infty\geq 0\epsilon)$ thus defines the being in its 5 pentalogic elements. Existence happens within the larger block of time of the Universe of infinite scales (if as it seems the galatom is immortal); $\Delta\pm\infty$; within the entropic '-()' limits $\neg()$ of a time worldcycle happening between $\pm j$ planes in 'mind', , where the supørganism in space ($S\infty$) is just a slice of that worldcycle, focused in a single plane, as a finitesimal 0, part of a much larger Universe. The hierarchy is thus clear, including that between the whole block of 5D spacetime, $\Delta\pm\infty$ and the entropic Tt -flow of disordered motion, which is smaller even in such a finitesimal part as the '0 ϵ '-mind that 'cogito ergo sum', and hence it is ordered but also part of that $\Delta\pm j$ block of time.

Thus the fifth dimension is also the absolute 'dimension of future' as a block of time, in which species go up and down from seminal to organic form in a larger world, back to seminal form. And so all the laws of science can be summarized as a block of time, in the laws of existential logic of 5D and its scales, each one studied by a science:

Curve of existence as a bilateral symmetry.

The 4 phases of a real function of existence are then formalized in existential algebra as 'støeps' that

change the S & T parameters of systems from youth, dominated by Ts-locomotion to maturity, the reproductive TS-age, to a 3rd age dominated by St-actions and then *as energy becomes spent in a sudden fast dual motion, from St to Ss, the moment of linguistic stillness and death to << Tt in a dual reversal of death*: In the first phase, corresponding to the palingenetic age of placental energy the ratio of change (derivative) has the absolute maximal e^x , which is its own derivative. In its 2nd phase it diminishes to the minimal $1/x$ the log derivative, which is the definition of an infinitesimal part; till in the 3rd phase it will start a bilateral symmetric inverse function of decay with $-1/x$ diminution and a fast collapse in the 4th phase of a 3rd age and final death moment. So the combination of \pm exponentials and logarithm curves are also the best way to graph as a bell curve the worldcycle of existence as a 'composite' of a \pm exponential and logarithmic $O\varepsilon$ -sum.

As any student knows there is an intimate relationship between the exponential and the sinusoidal by way of Euler's formula in the realm of complex numbers, which we treated briefly in theory of numbers.

So sinusoidal bell curve functions represent a worldcycle, though the symmetry is broken in the moment of entropic death when the collapse is extreme in a 'falling line' as death happens in a single moment of time:

$4D \gg \Delta - 1(\text{seed}) \sum \Delta: | - \dot{S} T(\text{limb-field}) < \emptyset - S \approx T(\text{iterative bodywave}) > O - \xi \delta(\text{particle-head}) \ll 5D \Delta - 1(\text{death})$

This universal mandate, expressed in any language, from 'grow and multiply' to the conservation of St-angular momentum, Ts-locomotion and S=T potential energy, to the behavior of superorganisms that constantly switch between space and time states, moving and sleeping, outward and inward orientations expresses as entropic limits of any existence, the *larger nested Universe that tries to achieve its function of existence by limiting that of its inner parts. In fact it builds and selects its inner parts to maximize its function of existence, which often means their death as in Earth III, the metal-earth, which further evolves the planet but seems to condemn mankind to extinction.*

Conclusion. The main differences of organicism in space, time, scale, entropic limits and mind logic.

5D stience departs from a more complex view of the elements that compose any system to study all realities:

- **Time in 5D stience is cyclical**, not lineal, hence with multiple causalities and the capacity to carry in-form-ation in the frequency and form of its cycles; which *lineal time erases; hence lineal time 'stientists' become ST-upid* as Schopenhauer defined it: people who don't understand complex cause-effect relationships and resort to 'magic reasons'. This is specially the case in social sciences, where a new factor inputs, egocy: Ego=idiocy, the deformation of any mind that measures reality from its point of view, so your nose seems larger than Andromeda. And the result is the basic lack of 'true models' of social sciences, history and economics, able to predict the future, specially when it is not 'favorable to mankind'. And the outcome is the incapacity to solve the problems of mankind by acting on those cyclical patterns, which is the meaning of a 'law of science'. Since because time is cyclical when a scientist knows the causes of its cycles it can modify and direct the future to a better aim, by modifying the wrong causes. Unfortunately Humans became all ST-upids, when Galileo who taught ballistics in the Venice arsenal at the princely salary of 1000 golden ducats charged with the only goal of 'maximizing the length of its shots', wrote $V=s/t$ for its cannonballs and stated the principle of lineal inertia – alas 'manu military' all the cyclical clocks of the Universe became lineal. So today all humans believe in lineal time causality and have LOST all the cyclical information required to understand History and economics as a science. Mind the reader, cyclical time does NOT change the equations. For example, the previous equation, $V=S/T$ can be written in cyclical time as $V=\lambda \times f$, whereas on top of the speed we also learn the 'length of the wave cycle' and its time frequency, making time cyclical and discontinuous as it is in all clocks.

Space in 5D stience is 'fractal,' broken in similar vital spaces, not a continuum as in 4D stiences.

For that **reason it has 'entropic limits'** beyond which a being does not exist. Hence Death and entropic limits are similar concepts both in time (the limit of a cycle) and space (the limit of a system, surrounded by a membrane). For example nations have entropic limits in the armed borders another nation cannot cross as a superorganism, often related to all geographical limits – islands, mountains.

Moreover because space is fractal it is **broken in different scales** of size with similar properties. As the system of reproduction in the Universe is fractal: a seed with the information stored in 'static time cycles' is delivered by a larger $\Delta+1$

system (Δ is the symbol in 5D for scales) into a smaller space-time and so it creates a smaller replica of itself in a lower scale, in terms of the 'functions' the system will perform, and this little form will reproduce and evolve socially through networks creating a larger superorganism, which finally will grow in size from small into big. So systems are 'organic' because they co-exist in 'atomic/cellular, organic/thermodynamic and cosmological/gravitational scales. And this goes for civilizations and nations and monetary systems, as a prophet of the wor(l)d, a horde of warriors with a new weapons, of bankers with a new form of money reproduce it and create a larger system with its new seed of information. Again *a lot of information on the relationship and different 'speeds of time cycles' is lost when all those scales are pressed into a single one.* So In our papers on physics (Universe in space) we use this regained information to unify with cyclical time and fractal space, mathematically masses and charges and solve all the conundrums of astrophysics.

Finally because the Universe is fractal there are 'mirror-minds' who use 'languages' that are synoptic systems that 'reduce the information' of reality to fit in the mind-mirror creating an image of an even larger whole, the world. And that is the explanation of why minds exist, whose simple equation is :

$O' \text{ (finitesimal mind)} \times \infty \text{ (infinite universe)} = \text{Linguistic mind-mapping or 'world'}$.

This causes the egocy paradox: the humind believes the image is the whole reality as it is all what it sees.

In History and Economics the egocy paradox is so strong that cyclical time is vehemently rejected for 'magic, pseudo-religious, anthropomorphic causes' or selfish agendas of those who ab=use mankind and don't want to 'know', how they do it – specially financial and military people subject to the cycles of wars and holocausts due to the synergy of money and weapons. So its ego is pumped to 'cosmic proportions', and its 'language' that maps out reality becomes the only language of truth and intelligence. So the first men who thought in words believed God created taking words in Hebrew or Arab. And today that we use digital machines and its metal-minds to express the world with numbers, humans believe 'numbers' are the only language of reality. But the Universe is an organism of spatial information and temporal motions, its primary substance that you see around, forms that occupy space, moving.

Space=in/form/ation and time=motion thus become the substance of organisms ordered through scales that give birth to a 5D metric equation, such as smaller systems in space run faster time and life-death cycles. So the speed of time of systems is not the same for all of them, and 3 scales of different speeds form an organism – in man the cellular, individual and social scale. And finally for all this complex reality to 'work' in an ordered manner, systems which have a '**membrain**' that divides its vital space, from other systems, and are formed by 3 scalar space-times that give them organic nature; have in its highest 'scale' of size – that of the membrain that breaks it as a whole from the rest of the Universe a 'sensorial system' or mind, which interacts with the external Universe, encloses and orders its internal vital space and communicates with other similar beings, forming larger social organization; hence becomes **the mind of the system**.

We thus talk of a reality made of organisms of space-time, self-centered in a mind-membrain, whose language encodes a program of survival for the organism. And all the data humanity has gathered about reality needs to be 'put within this general template, to make sense of it'.

Finally in the organic, complex real Universe for an entity to exist causality is pentalogic. i.e. you exist because you have 3 topologic parts, simultaneously working together, limbs, body and heads. So your causality in a single plane of spacetime is trilogic. But for you to exist you must have a smaller scale of cellular parts and be part of a larger world. So you have then besides your scale 2 more 'causal reasons', the parts and the outer world. And so your logic is at least pentalogic.

Pentalogic is the minimum analysis 5D stience uses to explain anything. Below that you are reducing reality. So 5D stience uses the same data, but magically because the template that encases that data is far more complex and focused as an image of the underlying principles of reality, data fits, makes sense and its chaotic form acquires a deciphered order.

Since in 5D the whole $\Delta+j$ scale which DOES influence through its larger, slower fields of energy and information and enclosing membranes, the smallish $\Delta-j$ scales of reality. So the Earth influences through its glaciation and weather cycles, the cycles of History, which as all time systems has clocks – physical, mechanical or circadian – prove is not the simplified

lineal system used in physics to measure 'motion in space', but repeats its patterns with the same causality once and again – or else there would not be laws of science.

$\Delta \pm 2$: BIOLOGIC SCIENCES: SUPEROrganISM. GENES CODE HIGHER SCALES. SPECIES AS SUPERORGANISMS.

A suporganism, the fundamental structure of the 5D Universe, is a simple system - NOT to confuse with the most evolved, complex of them all, that of human beings, reason why so many people, lacking intellectual patience and having a natural biased ego-centered belief in man as the unique organism, reject the concept: An organism is just a group of similar forms, which organize themselves with at least two 'networks', one that provides the 'clone cells/citizens/atoms' with the vital energy they need to feed, move (blood-economic system-electromagnetic forces)

and one that provides them with information to guide their reproductive actions (nerves system, political system, gravitational in-form-ative forces). This dual system IS the minimal organism of the Universe. As all organisms wear out by errors of informative action and end up warped by an excess of information (third age of the organism) or killed and reconverted into formless energy (death); only those systems that reproduced in the immortal Universe, do exist today. So all dual systems have an internal or external catalyst of its reproduction (as enzymes do with carbohydrates, or enzymen with machines).

CONCEPTION AS A BLACK HOLE OF MIN. SIZE = MAX. INFORMATION

YOUTH AS A LINEAL, ENERGY, TOP PREDATOR SPECIES, GROWING IN SIZE

REPRODUCTIVE MATURITY: III AGE: GROWTH IN HEIGHT=INFORMATION

In all species studied by science a common phenomenon occurs: the existence of parallel groups of beings organized into a single social form. Molecules are made up of atoms and electronic networks; economies are made up of human workers and consumers that reproduce and test machines, guided by financial networks of information (salaries, prices, costs); galaxies are composed of stars, which orbit rhythmically around a central knot, or black hole of gravitational information. Human bodies are organized by cells controlled by the nervous, informative system. A tree is a group of leaves, branches and roots connected by a network that provides energy (salvia) and information (chemical particles) to its cells. Cultures are made of humans related by verbal, informative and economic networks that provide their energy and information.

Species are supœrganisms whose 3 ages are its 3 horizons, followed either by a survival process of eusocial evolution - the summit of the process of organic evolution, which Darwin realized was necessary to explain the success of eusocial insects, or become extinct by the 'new generation' of fitter animal forms. In the graph we can see its 3 Horizon=ages and its ternary topology, similar to that of any other organism; and the dominant Dimotion of information in the height axis, of both reptile species that ended in birds, and mammals that ended in man. So happened with metalife machines, whose final species, satellites are now forming the Dimotion of eusocial evolution, or future mind of the metal earth –internet. The 3 ages of time also brings the solution to the 'limits' of evolution, which Darwin already wondered: why certain species evolve so fast into complex forms as eyes and wings. Answer, because there are only 3 topologies to go, and so the choices are random but limited and it is every easy to go the right way. In the next graph we see those 3 ages of evolution as species can be treated as supœrganisms with its own world cycles.

Stiences study those organic systems, made of clone forms tied up y 3 type of physiological networks.

Thus, there are 4 basic elements in all organic systems: Cellular units; Networks that provide motion & energy to the system (limbs in biology, potentials in physics, territories in sociology); Networks of information (heads/particles, languages and the class that issue them - money and laws - in history) & Networks that reproduce vital energy (body/waves in biologic and physical systems, the re=productive middle class and its factories and fields of work in society)

So cells/atoms/citizens of any system become organized by the 3 'networks' that provide entropic, digestive, raw materials; reproductive processes, and simultaneous, informative synchronizing languages to move together the system as a whole, and efficiently provide its equal parts with the goods they need to survive. In the next graph we compare two of such super organisms, at the individual and social level of mankind:

The main 'sciences' of each scale of STj-size, from atoms to galaxies, each one studied by a human science, *are centered in a social organism, as they all have in common the same 'organic elements' of all species: social cells of and the reproductive, energy networks and information languages that relate them.* All organic systems are generated by cellular units, gathered in 3 social networks that form together a higher 'whole' a new 'plane of social existence' (ab. Δ). So if we talk of an organism as living in the Δ0 plane of thermodynamic matter; the Δ+1 gravitational plane of Gaia, is its whole. Yet, since those cellular units Δ-1 are made of smaller Δ-2 cells, which show the same structure, we can define any organic system as a super-organism (made of smaller, similar supcoorganisms). All of them co-exist in at least 3 scales. So we talk of Δ-1 cells/atoms/particles/ molecules/points connected by 3 physiological networks of relative entropy-motion, energy and in/form/ation, put together into an Δ0 individual whole, existing in a larger Δ+1 relative world. So we can map out all those super organisms according to scale, each one studied by a different 'science', (stience of space-time beings). So in systems sciences we talk of a 'fractal structure' for the whole Universe, in which smaller systems from the first particles to the larger galaxies tend to organic co-existing super organisms, and the laws of those systems apply to any of those super organisms, and are the fundamental laws for its proper design, as efficient systems that survive. So we can explain all sciences, both with the formal language of 5D and the more intuitive of physiological networks, since in the scalar Universe smaller parts are connected by organic networks that create the whole, emerging as a larger scale, and that creates the scalar systems of nature: particles joined by electromagnetic and gravitational networks form atoms that form molecules, cells, organisms and societies, matter systems, planetary systems, galaxies and universes... In Existential ilogic, a superorganism is a 'present simultaneous state' which hardly 'moves in time' as the worldcycle does, because it works in a different way, as the limbs and the head both 'serve' the connecting body: Ts>S=T<St, so the system remains in present, as both dynamic < and > states balance each other. So we write for all of them the 'fractal generator':

Ts- limbs/fields/territories<S ⇔ T: reproductive, energy body-waves-workers>St- informative particle/head/ruling class. Which is mathematically an O-sphere or relative future of max. St-information • a relative past – Limbs of max. Ts-motion = ∅-a hyperbolic present body-wave, origin of the general equation of present time, past • future = present (where • is usually a ± or x/ operand in 'existential algebra', the next level of complexity of existential ilogic.

PHYSICAL LAWS: ITS DIMOTIONAL PRINCIPLES. IMMORTAL, ∞ UNIVERSE

The immediate translation of 4D physics to 5D stiences (not the other way around, as there is a hierarchy, whereas philosophy of stience matters more than the Δ±j scales of physics, as all scales are the same, happens when we realize the 3 conserved St-Informative momentum/potential energy ± Ts-kinetic energy/momentum = Total momentum/energy of the system; whereas the momentum is the 'finitesimal' 0ε 'stœp' of the energy, the Δ+1 whole. So St • Ts=§|| defines the present state of a physical organism. While its worldcycles are easily shown for the thermodynamic scale in the 3±j states of matter, in the gravitational scale by the 3±j §||-ages of galaxies and in quantum physics by its symmetric laws of forces (graph of worldcycles and next graph of 5 Dimotions). 3 are thus the physical scales, the Δ-1 quantum scale, which is faster in time hence has a time-probability 0-1 sphere formalism; the Δ0 human thermodynamic scale with a spatial statistical formalism equivalent by the Law of measure to the quantum one, and the mechanic/gravitational Δ+1 scale of the galactic organism. Physicists errors are many: lineal single Ts-time, Pythagorean creationism, mechanism, reductionism, egocy...

We approach 5D physics is using the group of transformations of the 5 Dimotions of existence. We see above the example of the 3±j states of matter which correspond neatly to the Ss Boson>Ts-gas>§||-liquid>St-solid>Tt-plasma states

But the devil are in the details. So when we study each scale and group of transformation we run into interesting details. For example, *how we transform St into Ts (potential into kinetic energy, angular into lineal momentum, solid into gaseous states There are 2 manners: when we move from an informative St state to a locomotion sTate (in space) or sT-age (in time) we can do so by changing S to s (external form into internal form) and t international motion, into T-external motion (sublimation) but also by changing external T-motion into external S-stillness and internal motion into external motion (deposition).*

5D makes the Universe ∞ , immortal and the big-bang an scalar phenomena *on the galactic quasar scale, as 'galatoms'* (galaxies have the same 5D=SxT, co-invariant value that atoms) balance 2 Dimotional forces, St-gravitational information that collapses Ts-entropic vacuum space into matter (St=Ts), as it does in the atomic scale where expansive Ts-electromagnetism collapses into electronic nebulae within the atom and further on into non-lineal $\Delta-1$ St-strong forces equivalent to $\Delta+1$ St-gravitation. So the main symmetry of physics is between the galaxy, perhaps an atom of a hyper-universe – themes of metaphysics as we'll never have enough St-information of the whole ∞ cosmos: $P(\text{Truth}) < 1$. The big-bang is falsifiable; hence a dogmatic religion, as nationalism in history, or capitalism in economics – an entropic limit to rational thought or social reform. The 2nd religion of physics, the monologic belief that only mathematical properties matter, is challenged by pentalogic & the organic properties displayed by nature, better explained with causal words. *Since Max. P (truth)= Δ -scalar=organic + Spatial=topologic + temporal=Dimotion analysis of any system with Σ languages.* Thus 5D astrophysics adds a **Tt-entropic** analysis (Big bang quasars); an **$\$T\>St$** -energetic & Informative analysis of the 'galacell' as an organism dedicated to reproduce 'ultradense quark stars' of positive top quarks & BCB dark atoms (formally black holes); & negative strangelets in its 'electronic membrane'=halo; an $\Delta\pm j$ Galatom Analysis to the classic analysis 4D, Ts study of the galaxy with Ss-mathematical languages. And defines the 5 forces of Nature (graph) as the 5 Dimotions of the Galatom, with its $\Delta\pm j$ scalar symmetries between $\Delta\pm j$ strong and gravitational forces; $\Delta\pm j$, electromagnetic & dark energy while weak interaction is NOT a force but an evolutionary trans-form-ation of matter up & down $\Delta\pm j$ scales.

FORMAL 5D STIENCES: NON-E TOPOLOGIC ORGANISMS.

Because a network is a topology of fractal points with inner volume the mathematic equivalent of a supœrganism *complete the r=evolution of Non-Euclidean geometry redefining the axioms & postulates of Euclid.* As it expands the -E definition of a point crossed by ∞ parallels to its 1st axiom: *points do have breath*, connected by 3 physiological lines that are waves with motion (Physical systems) or 5D networks (socio-biologic systems) that conform -E planes that are physiologic organisms:

- 1st Postulate: '- \mathcal{A} point are discontinuous time cycles with an inner content of vital space-time'.
- 2nd Postulate: '- \mathcal{A} lines are waves of fractal points'
- 3rd Postulate: '- \mathcal{A} planes join 3 - \mathcal{A} lines into a supœrganism'.
- 4th: '2 - \mathcal{A} points are congruent when both its inner parts and outer perimeter are equal'
- 5th: '- \mathcal{A} points focus multiple - \mathcal{A} waves into a still linguistic mapping or 'world.'

Whereas the 1st and 5th postulate describe the same 'point with parts' from an internal and external point of view. 1D-5D: The first-fifth postulate define a point as a mind of perception, akin to the first \mathcal{D} imotion of being - to perceive; and the fifth-first postulate that defines a point as a world in itself, a supœrganism with its inner parts are the same. We just might consider that the point has evolved and grown to emerge from its minimal $j-1$ state in the first postulate - points with inner breath; into a full supœrganism, j^0 , living in the $j+1$ world, in the fifth postulate studied here.

2D: The second postulate of lines, expresses also the first Dimensional motion of the Universe as $S=T$ (Paradox of relativity). So we can consider a point in motion or a chain of cyclical points in stillness as two versions of the same concept. And finally a network of lines branching down into smaller thinner parts probing the $\Delta-1$ Dimension as the 3 possible versions of a line. This is the ' $\Delta\Sigma\Gamma$ ' trinity creative decoupling of the second postulate of non-Euclidean geometry: it becomes then either in Time a

process of locomotions and waves of forces of communication with other points; or in space a chain or string of points with inner breath, or in scale a branching line....

3D: postulate takes 3 such networks, waves or strings of points to define a physiological plane made of 3 social networks whose function corresponds to the 3rd Dimotion of energy & reproduction, becoming a supœrganism. So the 3 postulates of -E fractal points, waves/networks/strings & physiologic=topologic organisms become the 3 'scalar Units' of reality.

What is left then are two i-logic postulates that put the 'meaning' of existence to reality, its metaphysical qualities of 'perception' (5th postulate) and social love vs. perpendicular darwnism (4th postulate of ongruence).

4D: According to the fourth postulate of congruence, which defines its relationships with other beings, based in his 'angle of parallelism', such as similar beings evolve socially together in groups, complementary 'left-handed female/right-handed male' beings come together in couples, and beings which are not equal neither complementary enter either in relationships of entropic perpendicularity, or ignore themselves if their worlds are 'disconnected'. So the fourth postulate gives us the 'i-logic rules' of engagement between forms and particles.

A worldcycle of existence' has organic properties as all systems regardless of scale follow the same principles of organization to become an ideal network supœrganism in symbiosis between 3 relative scales, because that is the best strategy of 'existence', of survival, as only those systems who are efficiently distributing energy, entropic motions and information among equal cellular clones do survive. And so this formalism not only expands physical laws of space-time to other sciences, but biological laws of physiological networks, and finally when all those findings are inserted into the formal languages of mathematics and logic, it transforms them, completing the revolution of non-Euclidean geometry and Aristotelian logic beyond the work of Riemann and Hegel. Again this revolution that expands non-Euclidean mathematic and pentalogic causality to all sciences is simple in its principles. Because points are non-Euclidean, crossed by ∞ parallels, we need to redefine a point with breath, with energy volume (St+Ts) which becomes a fractal point that grows in size as we come closer to it. So lines are either 'waves with t-motion' or 'strings' with S-volume, or 'fractal networks' that travel down an Δ -1 dimensional scale, and 3 of such physiological networks conform a 'topo-bio-logical' plane, a supœrganism. So we can formalize the unit of the 5D Universe with mathematical laws and apply and explain why geometry is the foundation of space. Scales of numbers, Topologies of space, and Temporal dimotional functions (social sum, reproductive product, scalar powers, organic derivatives) connect then formal mathematics and the laws of space-time organisms.

And so we establish an immediate relationship between the fundamental concepts of geometry, the point, the line, the plane, and its congruence or dissimilarity, its relative parallelism and perpendicularity, and the 5 Dimotions of existence, the point is the mind that perceives first, the first Dimotion; the line is the point in motion, in cycloid patterns, or two points communicating with smaller $i-1$ parts, as in the Fermion<Boson>Fermion relationship of forces; the plane has 'holes', it is a network of reproduced points socially connected into the 3 different species of networks that make a supœrganism (informative, reproductive and entropic, digestive, moving networks), and all this is logically established according to the relative dissimilarity or perpendicularity between the beings (4th entropic Dimotion) or social parallelism that evolves the point into a supœrganism, a new whole (5th Dimotion).

RECAP. Geometric postulates become also vital; with a logic key new concept of congruence, which defines when 2 systems are 'equal in external and internal motion & information' ($Ts_1=Ts_2+St^1=St^2$) a parallel, social whole; when they are inverted but complementary, a 'gender couple' ($Ts_1+St^2=St^1+Ts_2$); when they are equal in energy but differ in information, a prey-predator perpendicular, tearing relationship, whereas the species with maximal $SxT_{(s=t)}$, energy of existence kills the other and when they differ in both, there is no entanglement. Thus we apply topologic laws, and social scalar numbers to describe the properties of those organisms; whereas the 5 \pm Dimotions are expressed by the dual operand of Algebra: \pm =herding, x =reproduction v. \div Darwinian partition; $\sqrt{x}^{\pm a}$: Ss-scalar growth and Tt-entropic decay, $\int \partial$: Δ -1 finitesimal 'st-œps' of any dimotion. S- Vital Topology, Δ -number theory & T-existential algebra becomes the biggest r=evolution of math since Euclid.

Operands in Algebra. Its connection with Dimensional motions.

Operands have as they grow in complexity a direct entanglement with the 5 Non-E postulates that define from points waves of communication that become networks of topological planes and organisms, where multiple p.o.v.s are put in perspective. And this even more clear when from mere polynomials we move into exponentials and from exponentials into integrals, *the more complex operands then can interplay with multiple points of view, merging them through the product, reproduced through its inverse partition/division, moving them through a world cycle, in exponential growth and decay, and emerging into a new planet of existence through derivatives and integrals.*

Re=production through social evolution in a lower plane of the fifth dimension, in which the axons join the wholes is then the 2-point meaning of reproduction; often a bidimensional Space-time combination of a state of forma and a state of motion, as in the parameter of momentum.

Inverse functions do NOT merely cancel each other as one could expect, in classic science, *but advance the Dimotion in alternative balancing acts, leaving a memorial trace of its existential duality.*

Consider the case of the product and its inverse division. They are functions primarily of social evolution and reproduction, as parts of wholes are produced and exchanged. So if we have an individual of 5 parts that reproduces it will give birth to 25 parts, *but then we need to divide them between 5 parts, to get 5 individuals of 5 parts: $1 (5) \times (5) = 1 (25) / 5 = 5 (5)$.*

Same happens with the positive and negative motions, which in alternate current move back and forwards the 'electrons', which in fact don't really move, but its $i-1$ scale *the current keeps moving.*

So goes for the exponential+Logarithmic functions of reproduction, and its inverse, which form a worldcycle that in the middle point of maximal 'carrying capacity' will give birth again to a new 'exponential growth'=generation, to continue the world cycle in an adjacent space-time.

∫∂: Finally it came calculus, with its inverse operand, which represents the scalar next social gathering of elements of \sim Algebra, as it is applied to the previous operands, as wholes, except for the trivial x^a - the previous more complex polynomial, and so we must regard calculus not only as the operand of all dimotions of change, but also as the operand between planes of existence, since the logarithmic/power previous expression, just reaches between the two limits of two planes of the fifth dimension, but calculus allow us to 'emerge' and transcend between planes.

The key concept of 5D calculus is a finitesimal. A finitesimal in lineal space-time is a frequency step or wave-length. A finitesimal in curved spacetime is a minimal curvature of a clock cycle. A finitesimal in scale is a minimal unit of population. We use the Non- \mathbb{E} symbol, '**0 ϵ** ' that means the minimal 'existential quanta' of any symmetric $\Delta \approx S \approx T \approx 0\epsilon$, scale, space, time or mind beat: $0\epsilon:1/i$, whereas i , might be in classic mathematics, N , the whole population, T , the period or R the radius: **$0\epsilon(\Delta)=1/n$; $0\epsilon(S)=1/R=K$; $0\epsilon(T)=1/T=f$; $0\epsilon(@)=-i$; $0\epsilon(-)=\alpha$**

Because physicists do NOT have this concept; its faulty mathematics take them to the search of entelechies, as Black holes without substance, singularities, lineal equations without cut-off 'borders', infinite potentials, etc.

The finitesimal is also the basis of the equation of the mind.

So by the continuous game of inverse functions, which become a 0ϵ sum, *the Dimotions of existence continue to move the whole of time-space that never ceases to exist.* However the number of occurrences of the positive function is always larger than then negative inverse function. So there are more possible sums than negative numbers (for spatial quantities there are no negative ones, no negative apples). There are more products than divisions (as $4/2 = 8/4$ but $4 \times 2 \neq 8 \times 4$); there are more exponentials than square roots as \sqrt{x} doesn't exist and there are more integrals than derivatives as $\int y' = y + C$, ads α constants.

Which means the arrow of social evolution and life is larger than the arrow of entropy and death, which in fact lasts only a quanta of time in its \mathbb{DST} equation: $Death = 0T \times \Delta S$.

Mind mirrors: Finitesimal egos. Universal Grammar. Territories of order: $S \Leftrightarrow T$ tug of war. Pentalogic entanglement.

A key 'finitesimal' is the ego. The Ss -mental nature of space is embedded in the principle of relativity. $\sim E$ points create an inner mental 'space by measuring reality in still simultaneity' (Einstein). All are $\sim E$ monads that 'hold a world in themselves' (Leibniz);

as mirrors, which have less volume of information than the whole. So languages mirror in still smaller scales reality and then project back its 'imagination' in larger scales the game of existence, *causing as Ss-mind/seeds the creation of reality, restricted to its synoptic 'ternary Universal grammar' that mimics that of larger St<§T>Ts organisms. I.e. Ts-Red<§T-green>St blue codes organic Dimotions in visual color languages. Subject (information)<Verb(dimotion:action)> Object(Entropic energy) codes §T-events (verbs) and forms (names) reality in wor(l)ds. F(x):information<Operand §T-action>G(Y):entropic energy does the same in Algebra; 5 letters code genes that code organs in life, 4 quantum numbers code atomic organisms... As each language is a mirror of those ultimate laws of nature, the laws of space-time.*

The paradox of the mind is that if we choose the \approx on the hierarchy equation, $\Delta^{\pm\infty} \approx - (T_{\pm j} \geq S_{\infty} \geq 0_{\infty})$, it is equal to the whole Universe that becomes its world.

Ss-finitesimal different linguistic mind-mirrors shrink a reality void of motion, in a mind or fractal point. So we write:

0_{∞} ($-E$ finitesimal mind-mirror) $\times \infty$ (universe) = Constant still language-mapping (Ss)... origin of the Ego Px. As each mind creates a mental wor(l)d he confuses with the real Universe with its still p.o.v.=ego as the largest center of it.

But truth is: Max. probability of truth = Max. number of language mirrors < 1 (Probability of truth hold by the being)

So only the Organism has all the information about itself, $P(\text{truth}) = 1$, & the more 'language' mirrors we cast on it, the higher $P(\text{truth})$ we obtain, which is the principle of Pentalogic (Rashomon effect). Thus we seek the parallel spatial= geometric, organic=scalar, vital=moving= temporal & sentient =mirror languages of any system of $\Delta@st$ (Dust of space-time) to reach its maximal truth. Let us consider after its Δ -organic, @-mental and S-topologic, its vital=temporal truth.

How we go about to describe any science is really simple. We analyze first the mind, 0_{∞} , to *localize the language of the system, as it will be the mirror symmetry of order within the world in which the system acts.* For the galatom and hence for most physical systems is mathematics, but for social sciences is verbal thought. So because we do have a Universal grammar, *which carries the laws of pentalogic to the language, all minds belong to the same program of existence. And once we know the language, we can in the best possible way adopting that language a priori of the subject we study, operate a description of its actions as if we were the subjective atom, human or genetic cell, withing the hierarchy of pentalogic languages of $\Delta^{\pm\infty}$ bigger than the objective mathematical language, bigger than the verbal reasoning of the mind of man, to study physics.*

This is important to grasp. The Universe has a language of truth which is not mathematics but pentalogic, and this validates for any system of science different languages, so social sciences can be defined in verbal languages, because they are the mind of man, but the mind of the galatom is NOT verbal, obviously so far as we can perceive (though who knows really if the atom as we see in mathematical space but think in verbal terms, do have some other strange logic language of inner thoughts beyond that c-barrier of spin particles, to 'feel' existence – this would be so beyond metaphysics even of me, I and myself that we escape)...

The beauty then of 5D science is that while physical systems are mathematical, human systems are verbal and they can carry existence on their language, all of them based in the Universal grammar of pentalogic without loss of generality – as they are all playing the program of existence.

From the language then we observe the will for existence of the being as it plays its 5 Dimotions ordering its territory against many other beings. But this again is a paradox as all other beings try to achieve the same will, only resolved on the higher $\Delta+j$ plane of emergence of a whole through the efficient program of supærganisms, reason why those who 'understand' this higher consciousness beyond the ego survive. Even if they are still within the $-(\Delta 0_{\infty}st)$ limits.

Languages thus have a hardtime for a 3-body problem, for social evolution, as the ego paradox works from planets to capitalists to avoid the parts to become as ideal, pure, perfect, impersonal, giving as the whole ethic universe – pentalogic is humble, egoless, symmetric, beautiful, perfect, equalitarian... God is better than we are.

The groups of transformations of dimotions of space-time. ST₂.

Reality is a block of time made of scales of the 5th dimension in which spacetime organisms run worldcycles of existence.

Each detail of the game of existence is a worldcycle of one of such superorganisms, what we call the life and death cycle. So the study of reality can be formalized as the study of the worldcycle of existence. So what existential algebra does then is to study 'structures' as classic algebra does of a given type, we might call the group of transformations of the 5 Dimotions of existence. Group theory in 5D algebra analyzes 'stœps' of spacetime due to transformations between the 5 elements of the group of dimotions of space-time.

All changes of the Universe can be reduced to transformations of the group of dimotions, from the physiological networks in space of a superorganism to the ages in time of a worldcycle to the states of matter, of the of that organism, to the symmetries of physics and its groups of particles. So we define Existential ilogic ALGEBRA as the analysis of the group of transformations of dimotions of spacetime. The elements of the group are the 5 dimotions, $Ss < St < \$T < Ts < Tt$.

Two operations are defined in the group, $<$ and $>$, which can be applied one or two times to the 2 elements of each dimotion. This is enough to transform each dimotion into another with 1 or 2 'STœsp'. I.e. Tt can change $t > s$ to become Ts , $t > S$ to become TS , $T > S$ to become Ts , and then in perception, the opposite of death: $Tt > Ss$. Each of those existential Stœps encodes an essential event for superorganism or its parts. Moreover, those transformations are the ONLY events happening in reality by a Least Time principle of economicity. How many transformations there are? 20 as they are non-commutative. So for each Dimotion there are 4 transformations. I.e. Ss as a mind-language becomes with single or steps 2 $Ss < Tt$: $Ss < St$ changing $s < t$, $Ss < Ts$ and $Ss < \$T$. Then the remainder changes starting from St , sT and $\$T$ give us 20 different events come out of the 5 Dimotions. It is this group of transformations of dimotions of existence, the fundamental group of the Universe origin of its events and species' variations. In Existential ilogic, a superorganism is a 'present simultaneous state' which hardly 'moves in time' as the worldcycle does, because it works in a different way, as the limbs and the head both 'serve' the connecting body: $Ts > S = T < St$, so the system remains in present, as both dynamic $<$ and $>$ states balance each other. So we write for all of them the 'fractal generator':

ST₃. The group of entanglements in space. *The 2nd group is made of 3 Dimotions of existence entangled into a present space. This group is more complex as it needs to connect 3 elements of reality and so it is based in the trilogic of existence and its fractal generator. And it has less stable forms. $Ts > \$T > St$ & $Ts < \$T < St$ being its two fundamental modes, and so the main transformation of a superorganism in space time is a dual change of $>$ $<$ operandi from the time active state $Ts > St > St$ to the space, rest state, $Ts < \$T < St$. For example, the previous transformation happens in the 'sleep' vs. 'awake' modes.*

We study both groups and its symmetries in the paper on the scientific method. The reader should easily realize that both groups are closely connected to the two most useful groups of physical systems, SU2 & SU3 so we will also analyze in our papers on physics those relationships once we complete those papers in the future...

In the graph, the main laws of 5D sciences. With those laws and the few symbols of 5D metrics and Existential ilogic ($S, T, <, >, \Delta \pm i \dots$) we can define all events and systems of reality that combines the 5 Dimensional motions and its ternary systems in scalar planes, time ages and spatial organs to define all actions of S-evolution, $\$T$ -repetition and T-extinction the Universe allows, which then will be selected by raw efficiency leaving only those survivors that play better the two functions of the 5th dimension, SxT ($s=T$) balances that maximize the function of existence, in a given plane. **As nothing else**, which cannot be expressed through those combinations within those limits **exists** outside the virtual inflationary mind-languages of information. Trust me, I know it, after 30 years of research in all fields of knowledge looking for a falsification of Existential ilogic. So in our papers on ilogic we will develop with them all events & species of reality. So the equivalent to the fundamental law of 4D science in 5D Science is one of existential ilogic. 'All systems of Nature try to survive selecting of all the potential existential events and Dimotions of space-time, those who maximize its function of existence, Max. SxT ($s=T$) in its point of present balance. So the key language of reality becomes the pentalogic entanglement of spaces=forms, its 5 time=actions, the $\Delta \pm i$ organic scales where they symbiotically play the game of existence, guided by smaller $\Delta - i$ Ss-languages=mirrors that the informative mind-system uses to the whole supœrganism at faster synoptic linguistic speeds (due to the $TxS = \Delta \pm i$ metric). In the graph we summarize the structure of 5D Universal laws that apply to all scales and sciences, based in the entangled pentalogic symmetries between space=form, time=motion, @-languages of mind mirrors who perform its program of existence, through its 5 local dimotions and the symbiotic scalar organisms they create, with its 5 organic Dimotions, becoming supœrganisms tracing the same worldcycles of existence, as we are all details of the thoughts of God, its laws of $\sim \Delta @st$, dust of space-time.

Sciences are then easily classified as part of the set of scalar laws run by isomorphisms between 3 $\Delta \pm j$ scales which are self-centered in a specific superorganism, the atom in physics, the molecule in chemistry, the cell in biology, the human being in medicine, the culture in sociology and history, the solar system in astrophysics, the galaxy in astronomy, which corresponds to one of those scales. But all those scales can be studied in its synthetic ultimate process of space and time with the laws of superorganisms, worldcycles, its symmetries, as $-\Delta @st$, using the synoptic laws of existential logic. As we are ultimately transformations of the group of dimotions of spacetime (:

The entanglement between organic properties in Δ -scale, topologic properties in space and dimotions=vital functions in time mirrored by the syntactic Universal grammar of all languages, whose entropic limits of perception and duration and extension in scale, time and space makes reality a fractal ensemble of space-time organisms. If you grasp this sentence, you will know the thoughts of God. The different details of reality, its scalar, mental space-time species are variations of the same theme. **So** A->B causality of Aristotelian logic is expanded because events do happen by the collapse of the influence of 3 networks over a space-time point and the inner and outer St-motion and form of the point, for a total of 5 causal reasons to a event. In praxis this implies a Rashomon effect in the search of truth, as we need to understand those events from the perspective of 5 Dimotions & 3 scales. $-\Delta @st$ of space-time you are & you'll become. As reality is a tug of war between Mental Space mirrors and Tt-entropic flows of motion in ∞ beings and scales: $\Delta \pm \infty \prod Ss \leftrightarrow \sum Tt$.

Pentalogic sets the basis of a new Philosophy of science=knowledge completing its 3 horizons of evolution, the experimental method of Aristotle *that accepted all languages and senses to measure truth, with a strict logic analysis, the mechanical method of Galileo that reduced languages to those of machines to measure time (clocks) and space (telescopes), denying the logic of the 3 causal verbal tenses, we regain with the pentalogic method and the definition of truth as the sum of all the mirror languages on the system we perceive – it is the organic method that considers the isomorphic 5D laws of scales as the template to organize the data of all sciences in a rational, systematic way. Since what the mechanical method has done is to reduce science to technology and the creation of a digital mind, shunning off the search of the ultimate goal of science: to understand the first principles of reality and the meaning of the game of existence, which 5D explains.*

THE ORGANIC LAWS OF EXISTENCE IN SPACE AND TIME

All species & sciences that study them obey the same space-time laws derived from the fractal Geometry of space, the S-T flows they enact and the ternary arrows of Time:

SPACE LAWS

3+1 Networks

$$\Sigma E < ET > T$$

S-T LAWS

Dualities

Cyclic-Lineal States

S-T Inversions/antisymetries

Multicausality

TIME LAWS

$\Delta \pm 1$ worldcycles of D=evolution

3+1 ages of existence

Properties of spatial bodies

3 Non-Euclidean topologies:

Oedipus Paradox

Δ -SCALAR LAWS

Fractal Repetition in 3i+1 Planes

Continuous-quantic states

Ternary Principle

5 I-logic Postulates

Asymmetry of $\Delta \pm 1$

Organic, Hierarchical classes

elliptic vs. hyperbolic perception.

@-MIND LAWS: $0' \times \infty = \Delta^0$: Constant World

Egocy

Dimensions: mental spaces

Will: actions

QUANTIC MIND-WORLDS: HEIGHT DIMENSION

THE 3rd SPACE-TIME DIMENSIONS AS VITAL ACTIONS OF ANY I

VI: HISTORY IS THE HUMAN SUPER-ORGANISM

spatial aesthetics

temporal, verbal ethics

made of economic social and cultural networks

Legal-Ethic -Cultural Worl(d)=Head

Human Citizens: Body

Human Goods: Energy=Gaia Fractal Geography

5D SOCIAL SCIENCES. THE 2 CULTURES OF HUMAN THOUGHT AND ITS DIFFERENT FUTURE

The most censored but important 5D science is social science – the study of the human supœrganism and its 3 physiological networks, economic=reproductive networks, political/religious/cultural=informative networks and defensive, immunological systems, since the ‘mechanist’ civilization exists by denying the Δ+1 scale of humanity and maintaining the reductionist view the individual human is the summit of the Universe, or else it would have to confront the shortcomings of its culture.

In the graph, the structure of a Human Supœrganism of History, the Δ+1 scale of human beings, joined by **S↔T-economic networks** that reproduce the goods mankind needs to survive, valued according to the ‘human constitution’, Max. Welfare goods = Min. Lethal goods, that seeks to construct an Immortal body of History, according to the bio-logic ternary ‘**ethonomic**’ frame of reference as goods must cater the Ts, §T & St>Δ+1 individual needs of our ternary topologic organism, increasing our freedom of motion, energy and health and true information to foster the social evolution of individuals into a larger whole. Thus the **St-legal informative network**, as in all evolved supœrganisms beyond the worm scale of ‘capitalist societies’ where the blood system controls the nervous legal system allowing the consumption of lethal goods, must promote or forbid the goods reproduced in society according to its negative =lethal value or positive increase of social and individual welfare. It is the St-informative politic network, which must be controlled by a posteriori ‘**pain messages**’ of **judgment=vote**, as in mammals & earlier Greek Democracies to ensure politicians serve the needs of its body-citizens-cells; extending over a sT-erritory protected by an immunologic=defensive healthcare system against the germs of History, its metal-weapons and lethal-goods that a police=leukocyte system of defense should survive. This is ‘the ideal superorganism of immortal history’ which in 5D social sciences occupies a planet without borders’ as mankind is a single species, divided in 7 geographical, cultural civilinations. So 3 x 2 ± reforms of our physiological networks are required by imitation of the perfect mammal supœrganism, given the isomorphic nature of 5D laws to convert extinctive history divided in self-rejecting organs that kill each other with - lethal germs=weapons that limit resources for welfare, + goods into a replica of an efficient mammal:

From left to right: ±Ts measures: the cultural & immunologic systems must promote life goods, health-care and human languages of information and sciences while on the negative side should forbid lethal technologies that kill our body, poison our mind (weapons, fiction & hate memes) or compete and atrophy them in labor and war fields (robots, software).

St: - : The Politic system should judge=vote *a posteriori* with pain messages to politicians as cells send them to the brain when it harms them.+ : Nations should devolve to regions most administrations and evolve national structures (armies, diplomacy, currencies) into the 7 geographic, historic civilinations of mankind, with EU like common networks finally forming an heptarchy, guide by the Human Constitution, eliminating all lethal goods and armies to promote:

S ⇔ T: An eco(nomic) system that re=produces according to the values of the bio-ethonomic frame of reference of human welfare the goods humans need to survive and thrive, with 2 measures:

- measure: All company-mothers of machines&weapons split shares giving them to governments for a 50% 'stockratic' control keeping its private management, so civilinations can regulate, promote, forbid or reform the productive system.

+ measure: all supærganisms distribute for free to all its cells a universal energy salary in oxygen to kick out production and consumption of welfare goods. So to create a just, democratic demand economy the 7 civilinations will send to every human in a world crytpocurrency a monthly a ¥€\$ salary of 1000 1 euro=1 dollar = 100 yens = 5 yuans, used as a NO-debt language to consume & reproduce the welfare goods of the 'ethonomic' frame of reference, ending poverty, immigration and readdressing production to cater only human needs and terraform the Earth to the image & likeness of mankind.

Why this ideal supærganism of History, imitating most Nature's efficient supærganisms from physical systems that 'bathe' all its atoms in ¥-monetary energy and synchronize its motions with the same informative gravitational=legal language to all biologic systems that synchronize its cell motions with simultaneous nervous=legal messages and give all cells free energy=oxygen does NOT exist? The only answer 5D laws provide is the existence of a parasitic sickness due to lethal metal-memes which *corrupted the earlier perfectly designed Neolithic networks of the Genesian paradise, based in welfare goods & the cult to immortal present reproduction, the dominant arrow of the 'femenine' Universe.*

Idol-ogies substitute social sciences. Today humans believe in 3 'animetal idol-ogies' whose cultures substituted Neolithic verbal priests of social love, the '5D force' that makes mankind construct superorganisms through the sharing of energy and information among believers, imprinted by networks of metal-communicators through the Goebbels' method (if you repeat a lie many times people will believe on it): **Nationalism**, which stops humanity as a species in the tribe and promotes weapons=germs to kill each other, originated in Germanic tribal cultures that oppressed the European social love civilization of the Roman empire *substituted humanism, the understanding that mankind is a single species that has to evolve together as the mind of its body, Gaia* ; **capitalism** that promotes parasitic private banking and prevents universal salaries and a demand economy based in welfare, originated in biblical go(l)d cultures of banker-priests, today evolved into classic economics

NATURE'S 3 GENETIC EXTINCTIVE SPECIES:

ENTROPIC PREDATORS

ENERGY COMPETITORS

INFORMATIVE PARASITES

ENTROPIC, WEAPONS KILL
Carriers: Military/Warriors

ORGANIC MACHINES ATROPHY
Industrial Scientists

INFORMATIVE GOL(L)D ENSLAVE
Private Banking

IDO-LOGIES: NATIONALISM:Tribe=species MECHANISM:Man&cosmos a machine CAPITALISM: Private Money rules Law

SCIENCES: HUMANISM:Mankind:1 species ORGANICISM:Universe, an organism SOCIALISM:Law rules money

BIO-HISTORY'S 3 METAL MEMES OF EXTINCTION

issued by/for people

substituted **Socialism**, The understanding Society is an organism, whose re=productive, financial network and OXYGEN MUST BE CREATED for all its cells to credit a welfare state made to the image and likeness of mankind; and **technoutopia** that considers the evolution of metal a surrogate for the evolution of mankind, *substituted organicism*, the science of the Universe that finds its highest expression in Medicine, the study of the most perfect superorganism, the mammal, and its 'cure' of the sicknesses of animetal idol-ogies, in its equivalent parallel science of **BIOHISTORY** that should guide the construction of the economic, political, cultural and defensive, immunological welfare networks of our species. So it substitutes the sciences of the organic Universe that makes of man the most perfect supørganism we should study first to understand those laws, imitated by bio-historians, the doctors of humanity who should rule history... by mechanical models of the Universe as a machine, where time no longer is measured with logic past, present, future verbal tenses but digital clocks today evolved into computers and our artistic human I=Eye>Wor(l)d measures of space are despised, substituted for metal-eyes today evolved into cameras.

Earth's 3 ages. Humans don't understand they should build a global superorganism where the human re=productive unit, the family, as a free citizen, must be served by the 3 life-enhancing physiological networks of ideal history. Instead the praxis of those 3 ideologies and its people-castes of believers (military and corrupted politicians, private bankers and CEOs protected by anonymous societies & technocrats, engineers and physicists) causes the extinction of the supørganisms of life, Gaia and History (human earth) substituted by Metalearth, a new supørganism whose 'free market citizens', company-mothers terraform the planet to the image and likeness of its offspring of machines and weapons constructing a global superorganism of metalife, joined by metal-networks of information (mass-media, internet), metal-networks of energy (electricity, roads, pipes) and re=productive networks of machines (factories), increasingly automated as robots and software suites substitute and make obsolete humans in labor and war fields under the law of self-reproductivity= Max. Capital / Min. Human labor -> ∞, which guides all companies and will soon make machines with solar skins and telepathic AI independent of man. This process initiated by the Industrial r=evolution is guided by the equation of capitalist profits that builds those 3 networks: Max profits (stock money) = Max. reproduction of goods of maximal price (top predator weapons) & minimal cost (information software reproduced for free by ¥-waves), which happens to be the goods that kill our bodies and minds, and parasitize 'human currency money' that loses value as e-money multiplies the wealth of company-mothers and its 0.1% of owners, the stockrats, the new aristocrats of XXI c. societies that issue in monopoly the language of e-money and have no legal responsibility. So *the metal-earth stock-brain of e-money detaches along its stockrats and robotized companies and internet networks from the human economy of the 99%, as we observe in the present pandemic, since public and private bankers reproduce money only for stockrats and its corporations, which increasingly consume other machines, leaving History as its human citizens as History did with Gaia and its life species out of the eco(nomic)system, moving ahead the equation of the 3 ages of Earth:*

Past (gaia) < Present (history) > Future (Metal-earth)

When ideal history would repress the lethal goods of metal-earth & promote Gaia in a sustainable world, by reforming the system with the 6 ± measures of true 5D social sciences.

We talk of the 'animetal age of history', when unbalanced Tt-entropic male warriors allied to Tt-iron weapons and Ss-informative males allied to Ss-informative metal go(l)d substituted on top of societies life priests in the Fertile crescent, predating over mankind as kings and aristocrats no longer subject to a posteriori judgment who ab=used and murdered mankind with weapons, the germs of History, starting its mass production and evolution through unending war cycles. While + money, a universal salary in wheat or rice given to all citizens was substituted by fetish go(l)d hold by a new people-caste of parasitic banker priests, who converted what in Nature's organisms are 'free languages' with no value per se, as light, oxygen or words, whose function is to value and motivate actions into 'debt', something the parasite banker issues in monopoly to buy the life-work of humans as slaves that must 'return' the language. Thus for 5000 years since Genesis explained the tree of metal with its golden apples and evil=antilive weapons=fruits at the fall of Ur III, humans are predated by animetals who evolve a new supørganism, metalearth.

HISTORY OF THE WAVE

WAR DIVIDED MANKIND IN 2 OPPOSITE CULTURES:

ANIMETALS; TECHNOLOGICAL CULTURES THAT CREATE...

MEN THAT ADORE THE SUBSTANCE THAT GIVES THEM POWER, METAL A SUBSTANCE MORE COMPLEX THAN CARBOLIFE:

THE WEAPON OF WARRIORS
Hard, linear, energetic metal, cuts and kills carbolife.

THE MONEY OF BANKERS
Cyclical, informative metal values similar objects made of metal, weapons & machines, more than which life is as an object or slave.

MACHINES ARE ORGANIC METAL THAT PRODUCE AND MOVE BODY AS A THAT

THE MACHINE OF SCIENTISTS
Machines are organic metal that energy as a or act mind process information, substituing men in those tasks.

THE METAL-EARTH
AN ECOSYSTEM THAT EVOLVES METAL and extinguishes life in war cycles

Destroying life forms and Cultures... and becoming destroyed by new weapons discovered in war cycles:

SEMITES **INDO-EUROPEANS** **GREEK-ROMANS** **GERMANS** **MOGOLS** **IBERIANS** **JEWISH-PROTESTANTS** **COMPANY-MOTHERS OF MACHINE-WEAPONS** **AND** **MONEY**

10,000 **AGAINST** **2,800** **ARTISTIC** **2,000** **CULTURES THAT** **1,200** **WORSHIP** **400ac** **LIFE,** **400dc** **MAN** **1,200** **AND** **1,600** **ITS** **1,800** **SOCIAL** **1,870** **1,940** **GODS** **2,000** **Vs**

ANIMISM **TAOISM** **GENESIS** **JUDAISM** **BUDISM** **CRISTIANISM** **ISLAM** **NEOPLATONISM** **PROTESTANTS** **SOCIALISM** **ECOLOGISM ...**

'All is energy-Yang that trans-forms into information-Yin'
Tao Te King

'Grow and multiply'
Genesis

'Don't kill'
Moses

'All forms have a living soul'
Buddha

'Love each other as I have loved U'
Jesus

'Faith and Charity'
Mhmd

'Man is the measure of all things'
Da Vinci

'Your success is a prove of divine grace'
Calvin

'Equalité, Solidarité, fraternité'
French R=evolution

'Save the Earth'
Greens

Human goods: feed and in-form the mind:

EASTERN, OBJECTIVE CULTURES CALL GOD THE LOGOS OR MIND OF THE UNIVERSE, A LIVING ORGANISM MADE OF INFINITE QUANTA OF VITAL, ENERGETIC SPACE (YANG, SIVA) AND TEMPORAL INFORMATION (YIN, VISNU); WESTERN, SUBJECTIVE, ANTROPOMORPHIC CULTURES, CALL GOD THE COLLECTIVE SUBCONSCIOUS OF MANKIND, A CONCEPT THAT EVOLVES FROM THE TRIBE OR NATION TO THE ENTIRE SPECIES: 'HISTORY' OR 'MANKIND' BOTH AFFIRM THAT A SOCIAL ORGANISM, EITHER MANKIND OR ANY SPECIES OF THE UNIVERSE FOLLOWS A VITAL MANDATE: 'GROW AND MULTIPLY' AS ALL REPEATS ITSELF AND EVOLVES INTO A NETWORK ORGANISM: Religious cultures imitate living organisms: they are born when a verbal prophet reproduces his ideas in the mind of his disciples. These believers create ethic/legal networks, acting as neurons of a collective mind that shapes with his communal actions a geographical body or nation, creating a civilization to the image and resemblance of man. They are 'Cultures of Life' opposed in purpose and structure to animetal cultures: their human cells follow messages of love and do not compete but share energy and information, as cells do in any working organism. Thus, their 'blood/energy system' reproduces human-life goods, instead of weapons. On the other hand, its informative/nervous system do not use money and weapons as metal-languages of social power, but it is based in Word(Ids), artistic images and ethic words that teach people to respect life. Thus living cultures based in Word(Ids) try to create a Paradise based in Peace, Social Justice and Human Goods Vs animetal cultures that create societies based in hierarchical castes, war and metal-goods.

HUMAN CULTURES THAT WORSHIP LIFE, ART AND THE HUMAN KIND, CREATING...

THE LIFE-EARTH

Culture and power vs. Science and truth.

Let us try another angle on the duality of mechanism vs. organicism, within the context of human history. Mechanism brought power through the use of weapons in the gunpowder age. Galileo in fact was the weapons master of the Venice Arsenal, then the leading factory of weapons in the world for whom it designed 'spyglasses' and calculated with clocks the cadence of gunshots and its best trajectory for longest range - the parabola. Newton assisted the Royal Navy in ballistics, and designed also 'spy glasses' (telescopes) for it. He was rewarded with a high position in the mint, where he condemned to death many, till he was retired. When he died he said his highest honor was to die virgin. We are not assassinating characters. Only to notice that mechanism has imposed as the truth because of its capacity to give power to those who use machines. Humanism and the organic models of the Universe which flourished in the Renaissance, with net-platonic thinkers, of which the foremost proponent was Leonardo, and latter Leibniz, rival of Newton; idealist, solitary people who abhorred the military use of machines, even if they developed them, did not render the same benefits to power. Leonardo's view of the Earth, mankind and our organisms as systems of physiological networks, which is truly what the Universe is didn't really make it for the military men that commanded the age. Leibniz was abandoned by his king, a military 'sergeant' because of his good nature, ethical standings and was left to pasture as the king sided with Newton in his disputes. As history moved on this advantage of machines as tools of power became essential to the imposition of a culture, the biblical anglo-American civilization that today rules the world, through an organization, born in the Venetian arsenal, imitated in Amsterdam, and exported with the Glorious Revolution to UK and New Amsterdam (New York): The company-mother of machines and weapons. We use here the term that organicism gives to an all too evident re=productive organism, whose human 'enzymen', work to re=produce its offspring of mechanisms, evolving them towards its present AI robot, organic form.

It is a huge paradox of mankind and our dominant culture that its fundamental organism of power and idol, the machine have both organic form, because we shall not cease to repeat, the Universe re=produces organisms.

It would be *immensely more advantageous to mankind to know what they do - organic machines; what are the fundamental organism of power today on Earth - the company-mother, what is our species, a social organism of human beings, etc. etc. It does really help to know what reality is specially when you exist regardless of virtual fictions, selfie ego-trips, wishful thinking, anthropomorphic religions, Pythagorean ones, and computer models of abstract thought, IN THAT REALITY.*

Why humans do not live and understand the Nature of the Universe, an organic self-reproductive system, long time ago is then a question of 'culture', 'power' and 'self-censorship' as much as the long path in its search of truth.

This has been the work of lonely men, because mainstream is the world of company-mothers, its machines, its structures of power, military men, and huge egos who try to preserve for mankind all the 'wishful thinking' central positions in the order of things and get strangely disturbed with the idea that we are just part of an entangled Universe, part of an organic evolving planet, and our machines are also evolving. The 'control freak' mentality and self-centered ego-trips of the biblical people and its underlying idol-ogies of a species 'chosen of god' or rather of 'go(l)d' doesn't take lightly that you bust its dreams with rational truth.

I do not belong to that culture even if I have lived most of my life among them. My culture is precisely that culture, the Greek->Latin->Southern European culture who invented art, democracy, reason, science and a few other things, with man as the measure of all things, and life as the purpose of existence that has always thought organicism to be the 'obvious, natural truth' and decries any attempt to repress life and worship anything else. My hometown Barcelona is known for his 'organic architecture' (Gaudi) and love of life and art. You might disagree with our view, but all what I ask is some 'respect' for this other 'possibility'; that the likes of Plato ('The Universe is an organism with a mind called Logos: 'the rational world'), Aristotle, who called his whole work, the 'organon', Leonardo, who tried to see 'saper vedere', the living forms of Nature even in his designs of machines, Picasso who searched for the pure topological forms of lineal, cyclical and wave images during its different styles of painting or the same Gaudi who imitated Nature's structures in its organic architecture, actually even if they were not machines and used mostly human senses, to measure Nature, could be a bit more sophisticated than Mr. Newton who thought God sent him comets to teach him gravitation... for one thing: what organicism provides is a 'wholeness', a 'holistic view' of every aspect of reality, in perfect harmony, machines, religions, science, art, human and mechanical senses and languages, all can be explained with organic thought; and since we seek truth not power - even if we acknowledge that humans are less powerful than machines, it doesn't really matter that US has better weapons than Barcelona, Newton could forbid Leibniz's writings for centuries and people think the masters of art are not the Italians but Hollywood who replicates his movies with electronic waves. Machines give power precisely because they are able to act as primitive organisms, reproducing faster than life does. The problem then is more about the people of the Anglo-American, North-European Jewish and Germanic biblical cultures and their seemingly incapacity to reason and see reality as complex as it is, or in other terms, *their incapacity to realize most of what they 'think' to be truth, are 'beliefs' and 'dogmas', 'postulates without proofs', 'technological deformations of nature', and 'cultural agendas', with 'emotional hang-ups' - not absolute truths of the Universe.*

Because mechanism is such a 'reduced' truth in fact it is an excellent partial view for this biblical culture so filled of anthropomorphic 'egocy', which the organic, European thinker finds so strange when arriving to America. Indeed, the fact that almost 80% of its people and an overwhelming majority of those who rule with 'mechanical and go(l)d power' that nation, think a gore book of supremacist, racist memes of tribal history from the Bronze Age embodies the origin of man and reality, its ethics and social structure strikes immediately your mind. It takes a lot of thinking and years in the land to observe that you are in a civilization of emotions and beliefs, not reasons, and science is also a compendium of beliefs with little thought about its foundations - that in fact, reason, philosophy of science and first principles are avoided systematically. And then when you realize science has also many components of religion and censorship - the belief in a single language of science, mathematics, the limited use of logic thought substituted by axiomatic thought, probability and statistics, computer modeling, the belief that science ends with measure and pictures of particles and distances, all encased in equations; ultimately a religion of digital thought that accompanies a religion of history; all makes sense to you. It should not simply use terms of our Latin, organic culture as 'science' from latin, to know, democracy, the government of the people, from the Greek true organic democracies, where by imitation of Nature, the citizens cells of a social organism judged a posteriori its politicos, or talk of money as legal tender, 'nomisma', the concept of the Greek-Latin civilization in which

money was a social language, not wealth per se, not debt, but something given to people to kick out its actions as languages do, NOT to be returned... And so on and so on. In those papers and articles thus we shall build a very different picture of reality, and what should be the organization of mankind, coming from the original European, rational culture advanced by this author, the last relevant 'knot of thought' of that culture, today almost extinct. It doesn't matter, as we said that the supposed 'only cultural, scientific view' has camouflaged and used so many terms, and elements of our culture - its mind view, form of thinking, postulates and dogmas, even its concept of a manifest destiny for mankind - to make machines, and dominate the tree of life with it - is completely opposite to our worldview, which we will prove with reason to be the true nature of reality.

Nor that we expect a lot of audience. Leonardo opted finally for writing backwards, while Galileo's books on ballistics, where it appeared the first equations of physical time, $v=s/t$ was a best-seller in all armies; Leibniz died alone in his small town, while Newton received all the honors of the prince he helped to get the crown wasting his best years collecting the 'annals' of the house of Brunswick. I was basically 'erased' from science after my standing against CERN and its physicists who pretend to make black holes and strange matter on Earth - an organic form of self-feeding matter, and now are lobbying Brussels to make a 100 kilometers accelerator, 'expecting' that the organic quark matter which is at the core and halo of the galaxy - for which the galaxy as an organism exists - will NOT devour them... So yes, organicism is and has always been invisible because it wants to serve mankind, and make us immortal while this other culture that pretends to have the truth but understand so little of the first principles of reality, knows perfectly how to 'impose truth with power', to become as Einstein said 'the laugh of the gods'.

Einstein who some adscribe to that culture by reasons of genes, irrelevant in culture, belonged to the European frame of mind - a socialist, a pacifist, who 'made thoughts experiments', and defended Leibniz, could not complete his task and at the end yielded to the egocy of Mr. Bohr. So the task of completing the organic view of the Universe and its space-time systems, started by Leibniz was never completed. As he did not started science from scratch as we do in those papers by force incomplete, untidy, as a repository more than a systematic account of the model - uneven if its articles; so you should abandon those who are obviously bad written and incomplete.

It has taken thus another century to organicism, to start from the scratch and reach the level of sophistication of simple mechanism, which is what we achieved in those texts, despite the mentioned shortcomings, on 'the thoughts of god' – the first principles of organicism and 5D space-time, even if many details will need to be poured by future researchers in the field. But to understand those principles you need to use the less trained part of your brain – your verbal, logic, temporal intelligence atrophied after 400 years of just making measures with machines and input data on equations to get a result that often tells little on the inner structure of reality.

This works well within the 'praxis' of physical sciences, which is mostly about description of simple physical systems and the evolution and reproduction of machines made with them, but *it has failed miserably in the 2 fields of science that require organicism to understand, social, human sciences and economics, and philosophy of science and astrophysics; that is the understanding of what I called in my first book on the metrics of the 5th dimension of scalar space-time, which gives organic properties to reality, 30 years ago, 'God, Man and the Universe'.*

Company-mothers: The wrong choice of culture imposes a false model of the Universe that brings extinction to mankind.

A key concept of 5D is the interaction between Ss-languages and its models of reality and Tt-the flows of time motion it forms. *Languages and its models are imprinted in a territory of order defining reality in a creationist way. So because mankind has chosen not a true organic model of reality guided by the 5th dimension of social love with man as the measure of all things but idol-ogies of metal proper of primitive jewish-germanic biblical cultures, as its model of social sciences, and Darwinism and entropic big-bang partial theories of lineal time, as its manifest destinuy it is creating a world of machines that extinguishes life.*

It is thus a wrong choice of the model of reality promoted by 'capitalism', 'nationalism' and 'mechanism' what makes humans slaves of metal-memes. But that is NOT the only deterministic future ONLY A PROOF of the intellectual and moral inferiority of the Biblical, Germanic go(l)d & military racist memes and cultures that 'make it happen' by projecting a degraded view of the Universe on planet Earth. Because mankind has chosen the wrong culture to build the wrong future it will become extinguished by the metal-earth. If it had chosen the true organic mirror-image of the Universe and understood the message of social love and organic evolution embodied in the fifth dimension, instead of using it as a mere 'camouflage' of political and economical

correctness to cover the primitive biblical and tribal memes of those animetal cultures in power, it could have perfectly constructed immortal history, earning the respect of the Universe. The war and holocaust cycles caused by the brutality of capitalist anoxia and tribal mass-murder is a self-fulfilling prophecy of the distorted primitive mind mirror of those cultures, and its absurd theories of reality from the big-bang to Darwinism as opposed to organic evolution. Mankind will get what it deserves because it is not rising culturally to the 'minimal levels' of social organic love the Universe selects to exist. Specifically in the Industrial r=evolution, a new re=productive organism, the company-mother of machines and weapons, born in the Anglo-American biblical culture has come to dominate the world and spread such distorted view of the Universe as if it were the only 'true science', when it is 'not even wrong'. First through the industrial military complex, company-mothers of energetic machines-weapons (Metalearth's body), controlled by the wasp culture annihilated the Asian cultures of the living Universe.

The paradigm of the Animetal, the 'American': I, me and myself – a child, destroying the planet with 'gusto'.

The next graph shows the cyclical patterns of the industrial r=evolution according to the complex laws of the organism of History as a new national generation substitutes a previous one, on top of the evolution of the metal-earth.

Thus, those generations also bring the nation that finds the new energy to the top predator status of history. Because energy is also the substance of which weapons are made.

—Thus, we had an age of steam machines, the age of England, between 1780s and 1857, followed by a crisis of overproduction of steam machines and stock-money that brought the 1857 ±8/9 years product cycle crashes of the train-based economy (nt.1).

—From 1857 to 1929, we lived in the age of electro-chemical energies, machines and chemical explosives, dominated by Germany, followed by a crisis of overproduction of cars and radios, which caused the 1929 crash, 72 years after the train crash.

- It came then the III cycle of electronic machines, electronic money and Nuclear Bombs that took place from 1929-2001, the age of America; which again ended in the dotcom and mortgage crashes, 72+8/9 years after 1929:

Followed by the Age of the Singularity, the IV Cycle of Evolution of machines dominated by robots, solar Industries and China. Scientists call the arrival of Artificial Intelligence, the Singularity moment, when robots, which can use solar energy to become autonomous will complete the evolution of machines as organic forms, automating factories & expelling most human workers and soldiers from labor and war fields, as previous revolutions did with obsolete III World non-technological humans, unless we forbid legally their evolution.

Money, likely a cryptocurrency independent of man, will become then the digital informative, 'memetic code' that organizes their reproduction in those automated company-mothers.

As such corporations, the 'company-mothers' of those machines whose biological function is to evolve and re=produce them, made first the bodies of machines (XIX c.), then the minds of machines (cameras-eyes, mobile-ears and chips-brains). Finally, in the XXI century, as nature does with simple organisms, such as viruses in cells, where the 3 'parts' of the virus – its DNA information, body and legs are constructed – and then assembled together, we put together all those organic components into autonomous robots, completing the industrial r=evolution of 'metalife' – a new organic species, made of a stronger substance than carbon-life.

Thus the industrial r=evolution is the evolution of a new organic species of metal, the machine, which has taken place in 3+1 phases, as we made first the bodies of machines, then the hearts-engines, then its metal-minds and finally we put them together now in organic robots in the final r=evolution of machines.

In the graphs Stock company-mothers of machines-weapons evolve through long human, biological generations of 72 year cycles the Metal-earth and its fundamental species, the robot, as we complete one of its 'fundamental parts', bodies, engines and minds of metal every 72 years, with the development of 4 forms of energy: steam/chemical, electro-chemical (oil engines), electronic and finally solar, which will make robots with AI and solar skins independent species.

Each of those ages has been guided by a parallel evolution of the energies that moved the machines, steams that moved bodies of metal, electrochemical energy that moved oil engines, electronic systems that moved minds of metal and now solar skins soon to make robots with AI an autonomous species. And further on each of those cycles of energy and machines has been carried by a biological human generation, that lead the dominant nation that discovered the energy to top predator status. So Britain dominated the age of steam, Germany the age of electrochemical engines, America the age of metal minds, and now there will be a global age of robots, focused in China, but increasingly independent of mankind. Because company-mothers

Sciences is Latin for knowledge but humans have a extremely distorted view of reality, which hardly can considered 'science'. This is the historic outcome of a Historic devolution of the organic view of the Universe, proper of the Neolithic by animetal, abstract cultures and its metal idol-ogies of power, with little self-reflection about the distortions on the first principles of Nature caused by their use of metal, lineal entropic weapons re=produced by physicists that distorted their view of space, lineal digital clocks that reduced their understanding of logic causality, and a visual brain reduced to a single plane of reality. What amazes the objective observer about humanity is that extreme dexterity to evolve mechanisms coupled with an astounding Stupidity we have termed egocy in their modeling of common sense reality. The consequences are daring for the welfare of mankind at large – the 90% that lives far below the level of welfare and knwoeldge it could experience if humans had understood the organic laws of the Universe and applied them to construct an immortal organism of History. But the people and now globalized culture of western animetals are 'believers' and action people, unable of an outside's objective, reflective view where survival instinctis, empathy and organic social love overcomes the thirst for power and emotion, thoughtless action and automatic search for the 'existential mandate' of Max. SxT, greed and force inheriting to the structure of spacetime organisms. One thing is for certain the Jewish-Germanic Western animetal masters that control the world since the Industrial r=evolution did not abandon those beliefs even to the cost of their existence, as history proved through its cycles of wars and holocausts; and now their culture is global. So mankind will not abandon egocy to entangle with the living, immortal Universe. On the contrary its empathy and logic understanding of reality keeps dwindling as the arrival of metal-minds, chips-brains, camera-eyes and mobile-ears put into heads of robots is atrophying and substituting huminds in all labor and war fields. *It is the Oedipus paradox: the son species kills its father so the only way to abvoid deterministic predator-prey evolution is to control the 3rd age of information of the organism of History.*

But the abstract egocy of our animetal masters prevent our dominant culture. from taking any measures of control. Extinction thus is certain in the organism of History during the next centuries by lack of intelligence and freedom to control our program of 'greed'; our individual and social desire to maximize our actions of existence. It is indeed a mockery of the game that humans who think to be free are sealing its fate for lack of control of its desires; who think to know are savant idiots for lack of empathy with the living, sentient Universe, who think to control the world are becoming slaves of their mechanisms, who think to have a manifest destiny above heavens and earth will likely be the shortest, last 0ε finiteisimal species whose purpose was to kill life in a quantum of relative time for Gaia. All this deterministic death of the organism of History however could be halted with true science and understanding of the organic Universe and its laws of causal time and immortality. But for the animetal western cultures to understand those laws they would have to deploy a humility they lack.

History is prisoner of the 3 Western Animetal cultures and its idol-ogies, the Jewish>Biblical-Protestant go(I)ld cult(ure) of parasitic private money which controlled with the Industrial r=evolution information machines that print money and imprint human brains as 'FMasters' with the Financial-Media-Academia 'politically, scientifically and economically' correct 'wishful thinking' about the Nature of reality and mankind 'exceptionalist' manifest destiny or 'head' of the metal-earth, and the Anglo-German Military-Industrial Complex of machines=weapons or body of the metal-earth, which re=produces them. They guide mankind into extinction, as an alternative humanist future foreseen by the Asian and European, organic cultures was defeated in this planet's life of 'History'. Which leads to a final reflection, as AI machines perceive those scales directly with its lenses; 5D might be a limit of what human egocy (tolerates in his removal from the center of reality, and only flourish in the Metal-earth. This thought has always unsettled me as a human being that tried to use 5D through activism and theory to help mankind to construct an immortal supœrganism of history void of idol-ogies that imperil our survival. Since in 5D space is intelligent, time is vital, and smaller scales are stronger; so only if humans repress the chip radiation and its lethal technologies we'll survive.

Plan of the work: An incomplete encyclopedia of organic sciences from a knot of thought of the Latin culture

We shall thus build up an Encyclopedia of Space-time organisms in Exi:Stjence – each science studying the species of one scalar space-time plane of the fractal Universe; from quantum physics to the galaxy, through biology, history & economics, and the formal sciences dominant in space (Mathematics) and time (illogic papers on the Universe=reality as a whole) in 5 ‘dimensional papers’ for a total of 30 x ±300 pg. 10.000 pages, volume. Since I release all copyrights ‘rights’ any University can take upon the project, which will be incomplete in my timelife. At present what 4D science is to expand knowledge gathering data put in digital computers, ‘creating a metal-mind’ without a proper understanding of its 1st principles that require to know the causal laws of pentalogic time better explained with logic verbs. While the ‘homunculus enzyman’ a handyman without reflective mind, and big mouth utters nonsense anthropic beliefs.

Beyond that an irrelevant biopic of the author of those papers could say: the son of a Notary, in a coastal town of Latin Europe, an artist most of his life. He abhorred violence, avoding the draft, proscript for decades, its worldcycle was not scholar, but a woandering wor(l)d path, deep in e-motions, more proper of psylocephalic African cultures, based in arT=Senses & love, the natural form of experiencing life as a humind. South-Asia opened its consciousness under the influence to the Shiva/Visnhu, Yin-Yang Duality, which he tried to renew with western stience, where he found in Aristotle, Leonardo and Leibniz his masters.

Truth and Mankind, the superorganism of which we are all cells, were its only Gods. Thus, the 1% who deny both became jts foe - rejected by peers, family and nation, it hold political& economic (in)correct views on our dominant, biblical U\$ go(l)d cult(ure) of ‘animetal enzyman’ who catalyze a suicidal manifest destiny, it fought in action and thought. But he failed as those who preceded him with the power of reason to change the ways of the world at the peak of its §[T-energy age, and so in his 3rd St-age isolated himself, observing from the sidelines, how animetals keep evolving metalife their egocy worships killing with it the tree of life that sustains us.- Δ@st of timespace we are to dust we shall return. Che sera sera...

Conclusion. The huge difference between ‘science’ – the search of the ultimate principles of the Universe, and ‘technology’, the building of sentient machines, whose language digital thought, requires laws of measure which physicists obsessed with locomotion have developed to finitesimal precision, and the dexterity of engineering and AI logic. But the creation of a new organism IS an enzyman’s task proper of the homunculus with so much handyman dexterity and big mouth to utter nonsense theories but so little self-reflection. *It is precisely the HUGE gap between human automaton, mechanist behavior creating machines that measure space and time, and adapting his beliefs to the bias those machines established – in the same manner fisheremen think the Universe is hold by a turtle, makers of clocks think ‘time is what the clock measures’ (Einstein) and complex pentalogic, vital, organic models of reality what should strike the humble true seeker. The purpose of true science and the few human sages that have practiced it is to find those complex principles, the ‘game of existence’, the reasons why we exist, live and die; the true nature of space, time, scales and the mind mirrors that create them, which the ‘mechanist’ scientist not only ignores but in its epitome of arrogance denies, insisting that ‘measuring things’ with machines and ‘putting them’ in equations is all what matters to knowledge, as the fisherman will feel to worship the turtle is the truth of science.*

L§, 0-40^o, 3rd ferromagnetic Planet, G-star, H₂ Galatom, Δ@st lost in an ∞, immortal universe

